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**NEMUNO, LIELUPĒS, VENTOS IR DAUGUVOS UPIŲ BASEINŲ
RAJONŲ VALDYMO PLANŲ, PRIEMONIŲ PROGRAMŲ IR KITŲ
REIKIAMŲ DOKUMENTŲ VANDENSAUGOS TIKSLAMS
NUSTATYTI
PARENGIMAS IR ATNAUJINIMAS**

GALUTINĖ ATASKAITA

**SWAT modelio duomenų ir parametrų atnaujinimas,
kalibravimas ir validavimas, modeliavimo rezultatai**

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I. SWAT MODELIO DUOMENŲ IR PARAMERTŲ ATNAUJINIMAS (3.1 VEIKLA)

Abstract

The report describes the renewal of water quality modeling system of Lithuania and its extension for Belarus. The spatial division of the model is enhanced to comply with division of Lithuania into river water bodies and account for slope classes on the detailed digital terrain map. The renewal, preprocessing and update of particular data blocks include soil data, meteorology, land use and crop fertilization data, pollution point sources and water extraction data, drainage data, riverbed data and further minor data updates.

The automated system of scripts is developed and employed for building the SWAT modeling system from the preprocessed data units. The result of employments of these scripts is a hierarchical modeling system of water quality of Lithuania.

The water quality modeling system is extended to the part of Belarus in catchments of Nemunas and Neris. Public data is used for setting this part of model. Modeling system of Lithuania can be employed with either measured or modeled inflow data at the border nodes on Nemunas and Neris.

Report is written in English, it contains 140 pages, 30 figures, 37 tables, 15 references and 2 annexes.

1. Introduction

This is the interim report describing renewal of the SWAT model data and parameters, used by the Environmental Protection Agency according to p.3.1 Terms of Reference (further ToR) of the project “*Renewal of a River Basin Districts Management Plans and Programmes of Measures*”, ID 141278.

The modeling system referred to is the one described in PAIC&ELLE (2012).

The manual describes the steps of renewal the parameters and data of this modelling system. For each data block we proceed with

- a. identification, evaluation and assessment of data,
- b. selection of methods for data preprocessing,
- c. data preprocessing itself
- d. development of tools (if relevant) for automated data transfer to modelling system
- e. documentation of these tools
- f. transfer of data to the modelling system and documentation

The Chapters of this User manual describes:

1. The thematic data blocks are considered in the sections of Chapter 2 according to ToR:
 - a. The used data and their general assessment
 - b. The methods and results of data preprocessing
 - c. The reference to the tools used in processing of the data
 - d. The results of the data processing
2. The renewal of the SWAT modelling system is described in Chapter 3.
 - a. Section 3.1 provides the general principles of the renewal of the SWAT modeling system.

- b. Sections 3.2-3.3 provide the step-by-step generation of the SWAT model system for, respectively,
 - i. the geospatial data (Section 3.2),
 - ii. filling information in the SWAT setups (Section 3.3).
- c. Section 3.4 describes the file and folder system of the model system, data and tools used in the generation of the modeling system.

The file and folder system is described in Section 3.4.1

- i. The configuration of the automated system for model system generation is described in Section 3.4.2. The system variables used in model generation is given in Annex 2.
3. The list and short description of the tools (Python scripts) used in the data processing and automated generation of the modeling system are given in Chapter 4.

The electronic deliverables accompanying the report are listed in Annex 1 providing the references to the respective Sections of the report.

2. Data renewal

2.1. Spatial division of model (3.1.9)

Spatial division of the modeling system in Lithuania PAIC&ELLE (2012) was reconsidered to reach the spatial resolution of River/Lake water bodies (defined in geodatabases *RiverWBlatest.gdb* and *LakeWBlatest.gdb*) which is necessary for further development of River basin management plans. Such an approach is not requested by ToR of the project but is dictated by the logics of the further work.

The spatial division was performed in 3 steps:

1. Creation of dense river network, see Section 2.1.1.
2. Delineation of the subcatchments for the dense river network of point (1), see Section 2.1.2.
3. Aggregation of the dense river network and its subcatchments into SWAT model subbasins and associated stretches, see Section 2.1.3.

2.1.1. River network of Lithuania

Rivers with a length longer than 3 km, has to be designated into a separate river hydrological network using a geo-spatial dataset of 1:10 000 scale for the territory of Lithuania and GIS data of the rivers, lakes and ponds cadastre of the territory of the Republic of Lithuania *UETK_DB.gdb* (further referred as UETK) according to pp. 3.1.9.1-3.1.9.2 of ToR.

The following data provided by the Client were used in this task:

- 1) Polyline feature class *Upes_l* from *UETK_DB.gdb* was used as a source for river geometry generation and field "*Kadastroid*" was used to determine the value of the field "*River*" in output file *EDGES*.
- 2) Polygone feature class *Ezerai_Tvenkiniai* from *UETK_DB.gdb* was used to determine the intersections with river lines for river segments inside the lake

polygons. The field "*Kadastrid*" was used to determine the value of the field "*Lake*" in output file *EDGES*.

- 3) *Rivers.shp* of type *polyline* was used for visual network connectivity inspection.
- 4) Layer *RWseg* of type *polyline* from *Export_Output.shp* of geodatabase *RiverWBlatest.gdb* was used for: (1) intersection with river lines to obtain division in segments related to river waterbodies, (2) the field "*RWb_cd*" was used to determine the value of the field "*WLine*" in output file *EDGES*.
- 5) Layer *LWseg* of type *polygon* from *Export_Output_2.shp* of geodatabase *LakeWBlatest.gdb* was used for: (1) intersection with river lines to obtain segments inside lake waterbodies, (2) the field "*LWb_cd*" was used to determine the value of the field "*WPolygon*" in output file *EDGES*.
- 6) DEM2x2 - digital terrain map SEŽP_0,5LT or 2x2 m raster cell.

The following steps were taken and problems encountered and solved for the generation of the river network:

Step 1: Generation of river segment lines from polylines of *Upes_l*. The following problems were encountered and solution provided:

Fig.1. Illustration of quality problem in Upes_l. The red line follows the original (incorrect) sequence of the nodes which define the multipart line segments in Upes_l.

- 1) *Upes_l* consists of multipart shape objects (polylines) whose parts are not connected, and the directions (sequence of nodes defining polyline) of polylines are

not consistent (Fig.1). The multipart shape objects were connected and the node sequence along the river flow was prescribed.

- 2) *Upes_l* contains not connected river segments in one polyline. The solution adapted included
 - a. Removal of isolated points after visual inspection. The isolated points in Fig. 2 belong to remote polyline. They are removed.
 - b. Treating the distant multipart shape objects as separate river segments after visual inspection. Fig. 3 illustrates that distant river segments (connected with a straight line) are included in the same polyline. Such polyline fragments are separated.

*Fig. 2. Illustration of quality problem in *Upes_l*. Removal of isolated points within red polygon.*

Fig. 3. Illustration of quality problems in *Upes_1*. Multipart shape objects contain distant fragments (connected with straight line. Such river segments are separated.

- 3) River segments connected according to *rivers.shp* are not connected in *Upes_1*. We added additional river segments to ensure connection. An example of the added river segment is shown in red in Fig. 4.
- 4) *Upes_1* contains double points in one shape object part and incorrectly placed points at the polyline ends. We removed double and faulty nodes. An example of deleted node is shown in red rectangle in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Illustration of quality problems in *Upes_1*. Missing river connections. The river segments in red are added to the polyline.

Fig. 5. Illustration of quality problems in Upes_1. Incorrectly placed point near the polyline end (in red rectangle) is removed.

Step 2: Finding intersections of river segments of Step 1 with objects from *Ezerai_Tvenkiniai ezeri.shp*, *Export_Output.shp* and *Export_Output_2.shp*, and assigning attributes to the river segments. During this step we encountered quality problem that river body lines do not match UETK riverlines (Fig. 6) The closest match for the middle point of the river body line to the UETK river segment was found if possible.

Step 3: Finding river flow directions and placing vertices (notes) at the river segment connections. The data quality problem in this step was an ambiguity in the river flow direction. Ambiguity was resolved using digital terrain 2x2 m for assigning the flow direction of the river segment according to the terrain elevation difference between the end nodes of the segment.

Fig. 6. Illustration of quality problems. Differences between Upes_1 and river body lines RiverWBlatest.gdb.

The river vectors were prepared in shape format, adding the attribute data with the following information according to p.3.1.9.3 of ToR: segment code; point code from which segment starts; the point code where segment ends, catchment code, to which segment belongs; catchment code into which segment flows; code connecting with UETK database objects. The prepared electronic deliverables are:

1. *Vertices.shp* (VERTICES) of type *point* contains the river network vertex coordinates with the following attributes:
 - "ID"- unique identification number.
 - "Internal" - Boolean, true if the vertex is in closed internal water catchment (according to p.3.1.9.1.4 of ToR the river network segments, which are not connected to the overall network of rivers must be separated).
 - "IsSink" - Boolean, true if vertex is a network sink.
 - "IsFork" - Boolean, true if vertex has more than one outgoing river segments
2. *Edges.shp* (EDGES) of type *polyline* contains the coordinates of river network edges (river segments) with the following attributes:
 - "ID"- unique identification number.
 - "River" -id from *Upes_l.*
 - "Lake" - id from *Ezerai_Tvenkiniai.*
 - "WLine"- id from *Export_Output.shp* of *RiverWBlatest.gdb.*
 - "WPoligon"- id from *Export_Output_2.shp* of *RiverWBlatest.gdb.*
 - "Begin"- vertex id at segment start, according to flow direction.
 - "End" – vertex id at segment end, according to flow direction.
 - "FlowTo" - river segment id to which a segment flows to. Due to ambiguity if there is more than one alternative, then one is chosen randomly. "FlowTo" = "-1" for if the end vertex is a network sink.
 - "Internal" – Boolean, true if the network edge belongs to closed internal water catchment (according to p.3.1.9.1.4 of ToR the river network segments, which are not connected to the overall network of rivers must be separated).
 - "Patch" – Boolean, true if segment is manually created.
3. *Network.gdb* is a geographic database of the geometric river network structure which is prepared for the river network according to p.3.1.9.5 of ToR.

2.1.2. Catchment delineation for the river network of Lithuania

According to p.3.1.9.6 of ToR the catchments should be designated for each of river segments of Section 2.1.2 using the SEŽP_0,5LT height data or transformed form of these data, which is not less accurate than the 2-meter raster cell.

The delineation of the catchments were done by PAIC's in-house software MyDEM which reads the DEM files, does the depression filling, associates the drainage direction for each raster point, reads the river network from a text file, builds catchment area for each segment of the river network, and creates a text file where the shape and properties of each catchment are written.

The software is written with freeware Lazarus 1.0.14 based on Free Pascal 2.6.2 and compiled for 64bit Windows environment. It uses external resources

- GDAL utilities from freeware OSGEO4W64. It is required to be able to read DEMs stored in different formats (e.g. ArcMap, TIF, etc).
- Lazarus AvgLvlTree unit which is available in general Lazarus package is used for fast sorting of large one-dimensional arrays, where the elements are frequently added and popped out.
- Lazarus Contnrs unit is used for building a queues: Last In First Out (LIFO) or First In First Out (FIFO).

The modified versions of effective DEM processing algorithms presented in two papers by Barnes et al. (2014a, b) is used for the catchment delineation.

In Barnes et al. (2014a) the effective algorithm for depression filling is given which is most time consuming part of the catchment delineation. The basic idea is to start from the perimeter of the input DEM and move inwards from the position of currently lowest elevation. If it meets even lower elevation inside the input DEM, the particular location (depression) is filled, i.e., elevation is increased to the current lowest value of the perimeter queue and location is put to Pit queue which is processed with highest priority. As the perimeter array needs to be sorted frequently to get the element with the lowest elevation, then fast AvgLvlTree unit is used for that purpose. Depression filling creates a number of flat areas that need to be appropriately addressed. The next paper Barnes et al. (2014b) is used for that purpose.

After depression filling the flow directions are assigned for each raster cell. D8 approach is used for that purpose, where 8 possible directions exist that marks one of the 8 neighbours with the lowest elevation. If there are several neighbours with the same but lower elevation then priority is given to horizontal/vertical directions instead of diagonal one. This will minimise possibility to form complex shaped catchment areas, where the area is connected only by diagonal neighbours at some locations. However, after depression filling there are many flat areas where the direction cannot be assigned directly. Therefore, two queues are built: LowEdges and HighEdges. LowEdges are cells which have a flow direction and has no label yet but it has neighbour at the same elevation with no flow direction. Starting from cells marked LowEdges we collect all the unlabeled neighbour cells continuously with the same elevation and label them with current label. All cells with the same label correspond to one flat. HighEdges are cells from these which do not have a flow direction but has a neighbour at a higher elevation. Because it is assumed that flat cells at the perimeter of the input DEM has a direction out of the input DEM (DEM drains itself) then all elements of LowEdges queue has corresponding element in HighEdges queue with the same label and viceversa. Unlike the Barnes et al. (2014b) paper, our algorithm processes flat by flat instead of all DEM at the same time. It allows to minimise required operational memory size. A FlatMask (named „lab”) attribute is put for all cells of the flat. First we start from the HighEdges and look to neighbours of the same flat until we reach the LowEdges. A FlatMask attribute is assigned to for all cells of the flat depending on the distance from HighEdges. Then the direction is reversed: from LowEdges to HighEdges, and similar procedure is made. FlatMask attribute in the last case is made twice more sensitive to the distance from LowEdges. FlatMask attribute allows to obtain the flow direction for each cell of the flat likely at was made with elevation and taking to account priority of horizontal/vertical directions over diagonal ones as above.

Information from river network could also be used in the delineation, see, e.g. Turcotte et al (2001). Consider the cells which coincides with the cells from the river network and has no flow direction after primary flow direction assignment from digital elevation (that is cells belonging to a flat). The flow direction for them is obtained from the river network and assigned to that cell if river segment has an assigned flow direction. This also reduces the size of flats and thus increases the speed of the program.

Catchment assignment. To assign the catchment we need to specify the point for which catchment should be drawn. Two possibilities exist: (1) manually and (2) from segments of the river network.

In both cases we start from the given cell or cells (in the second case) and collect all the neighbouring cells which has a flow direction pointing to the given cells. The process is continued until no more cells exist that has a flow direction pointing to the previous ones. A label is assigned for each cell of the catchment. A RGB colour of the catchment is assigned as function from the label. The starting cell(s) may not be positioned precisely on the river or other cell where the water would flow. Therefore, the starting point is searched some small distance in pixels apart from the starting point specified by parameter „dist”. This is done by going (down) according to the specified flow direction for each cell „dist” times unless border of the input DEM is reached. In the second case all the cells in the path towards starting cells are also assigned to the catchment. There, however, the path can go only in perpendicular to the river direction in order to exclude cells which would rather belong to other river segment.

It is possible to artificially enlarge the catchments of the river segments at the raster boundary to include all the interesting raster region, e.g., Lithuania. To do so, we move around the border of the region and if there is unlabeled pixel within the border then draw a catchment from this point. If the catchment touches another catchment from a river segment then it is added to the catchment of this river segment. Otherwise the new catchment is ignored.

Peculiarities for catchment assignment for segments of the river network. In this case the catchment of the downstream part of the river would normally include also the upstream part of the river. However, we want to assign the catchment for each segment of the river that is not included in some other catchment for some river segment upstream.

Therefore the following procedure is made:

- 1) Read all the river segments one by one and include all the cells which coincides with the path of the river network in the catchment start-up and add a corresponding label with minus sign to the cells of this catchment. The cells „dist” pixels apart are also added the same way as described above.
- 2) Read again all river segments one by one and look for the catchment for the corresponding catchment start-up. All unlabeled cells meeting criteria are added to the catchment as described above and positive label is assigned to each cell. The catchment, thus, cannot path the minus labeled cells (that is cells belonging to other river segments) or already labelled cells from other catchment.

If there is no sorting of the river segments then there could arise a problem that if we start from the downstream segment of the river then the catchment of the river segment would be that of all the river and catchments from upstream part of the river has left no space to form. Therefore, all river segments in the interested area are sorted by their lowest elevation,

and catchment assignment starts from river segments of higher minimal elevation. Quick sorting is made by AvgLvlTree type of the general Lazarus package, the same as used for depression filling.

Examples and illustrations of the algorithm application are given in the following Figures: (1) initial DEM and DEM after depression filling is shown in Fig. 7, (2) D8 directions are visualized in Fig. 8, (3) manually assigned catchments are shown in Fig. 9, (delineated catchments for LT are shown in Figs. 10-11.

Fig. 7. Initial DEM and DEM after depression filling is shown in Fig.7.

Fig. 8. D8 directions.

Fig. 9. Manually assigned catchments (by mouse clicks).

Fig. 10. Automatically assigned catchments for the segments of the river network.

Fig. 11. Automatically assigned catchments for the segments of the river network (zoom).

The catchment data were prepared in shape format according to p.3.1.9.7 of ToR, adding the attribute data with the following information: a unique catchments code, code for the water body, river basin codes to which designated catchments belongs; river basin district identifier.

The prepared electronic deliverable is *polygons.shp* (POLYGONS) of type polygon. It contains catchment polygon coordinates corresponding to river network edges (river segments) and the following attributes:

"ID"- unique identification number (as in *edges.shp*)

"River" -id from *Upes_l*.

"Lake" - id from *Ezerai_Tvenkiniai*.

"WLine"- id from *Export_Output.shp* of *RiverWBlatest.gdb*.

"WPoligon"- id from *Export_Output_2.shp* of *RiverWBlatest.gdb*.

"Begin"- vertex id at corresponding river segment start, according to flow direction.

"End" – vertex id at corresponding river segment end, according to flow direction.

"FlowTo" - river segment id to witch a corresponding river segment flows to.

Due to ambiguity if there is more than one alternative, then one is chosen randomly. "FlowTo" = "-1" if the end vertex is a network sink.

"Internal" – Boolean, true if the network edge belongs to closed internal water catchment.

"Patch" – Boolean, true if the corresponding river segment is manually created.

2.1.3 Aggregation of catchments

The elementary catchments (Section 2.1.2) and the corresponding river segments (Section 2.1.1) were aggregated (joined) for use in SWAT model as model subbasins in Chapter 4. The aggregation level corresponds to the division of territory of Lithuania into water bodies. Note that the division of Lithuania into subbasins is original because it is based on the catchment delineation within the present project.

The input data for the aggregation are shape files *vertices.shp*, *edges.shp* and *polygons.shp*.

The result of aggregation is shape filew *vertices.shp*, *segments_edges.shp* and *aggregated_simplified.shp*. The aggregated catchments are shown in Fig.12.

Fig.12. Aggregated catchments of river bodies corresponding to SWAT subbasins.

The connectivity of the river network and the subbasins is established in the geodatabase *catchmentData.gdb* which contains the following information:

- a. Table containing rivers and their IDs (**catchmentData.gdb/rivers**) for connecting the river names to river segments.
- b. Table containing the definition of watersheds, their name and ID (**catchmentData.gdb/Watersheds**).

- c. Table containing the connection between catchments and Watersheds including all catchments and the ID of the corresponding Watershed (**catchmentData.gdb/CatchmentbyWatersheds**).
- d. Table containing all the outlets of the river segments that flow out of the modelling system. Table includes a unique identifier corresponding to the FlowTo field in the river segment file (**catchmentData.gdb/Outlets**).
- e. Table containing all the inlets into the system from transboundary sources containing an ID of the inlet as well as the ID of the river segment it flows into (**catchmentData.gdb/Inlets**).
- f. Table containing all the catchments which have part of their territory outside of Lithuania containing the ID of the catchments and area outside of the Lithuanian territory (**catchmentData.gdb/Transboundary**).

Table containing all special water transfer points. Such points include, for example, Sanžile canal, Merkys-Voke water diversion, as well as Gilijos channel (Matrosovka) explicitly requested in TOR 3.1.16.5. The table contains (1) the outletID from which the water is transferred, (2) the river segment to which the water is added as well as (3) a coefficient by which the amount of water transferred must be multiplied.

2.2. Soil data (3.1.1)

Update of soil data according to p.3.1.1.1 of ToR included preparation of the unified soil polygons for the territory of Lithuania from various sources, soil lookup table and table of soil properties required for SWAT model.

The following input data was used:

1. **Soil data from database DIRV_DR10LT**, polygon feature class *konturas_LKS94* was used. Field *SNS_KOMI_T*, representing systematic soil type code, soil granulometric content and texture codes (further referred as *SoilCode*) was used. Field *PAVKOMPI* shows soil code. If the soil code is missing then symbol 'M' in this field means forest, 'SV' urban territories, while 'W' is water. The database file was preprocessed by removing unnecessary columns and placed in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/dirv*.
2. **Forest cadaster data**. We used forest cadaster geospatial data as provided in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Forests\Forest_data\SKL_Atdb.shp*. It contains polygonal feature classes. Field *augaviete* is required to determine the soil type in the forest. File was preprocessed by dissolving polygons using *augaviete* field. It is placed in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/forest*.
3. **Quaternary geology data** represented by polygon feature class as provided in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Geology\QuaternaryGeology\Quaternary Geology\quaternary_geology.shp*. Fields *INDEKSAS* representing geological index and *LITOLOGIJA* representing name of the soil lithology were used. We preprocessed the file by adding column *LITOINDEX* representing an index of soil lithology. It was done using forest soil lookup table (see below p.5). The intermediate file is placed in *Data/soil/geology/quaternary_geology*.

4. **Soil maps** on scale 1:300000 as provided in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Soil\Soil1_300000\soil.shp*. Field *SNS* representing systematic soil type code was used from these maps.
5. **Forest soil lookup table** as provided by soil expert, original name of the file containing lookup table was *miskai_new_2.dbf*. We placed it in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/forestsoillookup*. Field *Aug_G_gr1* were used representing composite index: “forest soil + geological index + lithological index”. It provides a link between the forest *augaviete* field combined with geological and lithological indices and *SoilCode* represented by field *Dirv_gran*.
6. **Lookup table for soil aggregation** relating *SoilCode* and aggregated soil code (further referred to as *SWATSoilCode*) was provided by soil expert. File *usersoil_lithuania.xls* contains all soil properties. In this file *SoilCode* is represented by field *SNS_KOM1_T*, while *SWATSoilCode* by field *SNAM*.
7. **Soil properties’ table** for soil types of SWAT model was provided soil expert as a file *usersoil_Lithuania_agregat_svertinis.xls*. In this file *SWATSoilCode* is in field *AGR_SNAM*.

Fig. 13. Illustration of soil raster in the central part of Lithuania (river Neris).

We used the following preprocessing steps with above input data:

1. Geospatial union of various data sources: soil data polygons (*DIRV_DR10LT*), forest cadaster polygons, quaternary geology polygons and reduced scale soil polygons. Result of this union is a polygon feature class placed in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/union*.

2. Assigning *SoilCode* field for the resulting unified set of polygons as follows (applying the below steps in decreasing priority):
 - a. If field *SNS_KOMI_T* is not empty, then *SoilCode* = *SNS_KOMI_T* (data from *DIRV_DR1OLT*).
 - b. Assign composite key combining “forest soil + geological index + lithological index” (fields: *augaviete*, *INDEKSAS*, *LITOINDEX*) to the polygons. If the composite key is present in the forest soil lookup table then *SoilCode* = *Dirv_gran*.
 - c. If a systematic soil type code is present in the soil maps on scale 1:300000 (field *SNS* is not empty) then *SoilCode* = *SNS*.

An illustration of the soil polygons is shown in Fig. 13.

Lookup table between *SoilCode* and aggregated soil code *SWATSoilCode* is additionally supplemented by systematic soil type codes from soil maps of scale 1:300000. Resulting lookup table is placed in *Data/soil/soil.gdb/globallookup*.

2.3. Meteorological data (3.1.2)

Data. ToR (3.1.2.1) requests that the existing meteorological data must be updated with the data from years 2011 and 2012. This is done by updating the meteorological data database of PAIC&ELLE (2012) adding the data provided by the Client.

Different methods of preprocessing for different meteorological parameters were used:

1. Temperature (T, degrees C), precipitation (P, mm/day), wind speed (W10, m/s), relative humidity (RHUM, %) and solar radiation (SLR, MJ/day/m²), where added to the database without preprocessing using the observed daily time series provided.
2. Minimal daily temperature (Tmin, degrees C), was calculated from hourly observed temperature by taking the minimal observed value for each day.
3. Maximal daily temperature (Tmax, degrees C), was calculated from hourly observed temperature by taking the maximal observed value for each day.

The datafiles from PAIC&ELLE (2012) were used as meteorological data base, namely:

- Table containing the weather stations for the model including the coordinates (LKS94) and names of the stations *WeatherData.sta*.
- File containing meteorological observations *WeatherData.txt*.

ToR (3.1.2.2) requests that if technical possibilities allow, then precipitation .pcp data files of the Model should be updated based on the precipitation radar data that are collected by Lithuanian Hydrometeorological Service under the Ministry of Environment. The consultation with the Client revealed that currently such a calibrated radar product is not available for the past time periods.

ToR (3.1.2.3) requests that SWAT Model .wgn files are updated based on statistical evaluations of weather data. Specifications of .wgn files and required statistical evaluations for the model are described in TWRI (2012), Chapter 12. Data prepared previously according to ToR (3.1.2.1) were used for calculations.

WGNmaker software (Excel Macros) was used for calculation of required statistical evaluations. This software (WGN Excel Macro) and its manual can be found on SWAT homepage (SWAT, Links to Related Software).

Maximum half-hour rainfall measurements are unavailable for all stations. Furthermore, the solar radiation measurements are unavailable for 16 out of 18 stations. These data are required for .wgn file preparation and therefore were acquired as follows:

1. Maximum half-hour rainfall was calculated using daily precipitation according to method described in SWAT Theoretical Documentation ARS (2005), p.66 eq. 1:3.2.3.
2. Solar radiation measurements for stations with no measurements were taken from the geographically closest station where the solar radiation is measured.

ToR (3.1.15.3) requests that meteorological data for the territory of Belarus must be extracted from the global meteorological database for the SWAT model, Global Weather Data for SWAT. Time series of daily average values for temperature, precipitation, wind, relative humidity and solar radiation for years from 1994 to 2010 was extracted in 64 grid points of Belarus. The weather generator is used for extending the time series of meteorological data of Belarus for Years 2011-2012.

Further processing of data to create the necessary .wgn files was carried out using the same methodology as for meteorological data for Lithuania, as described above and in TWRI (2012), chapter 12. Locations of grid points for Belarus are shown in Fig.14.

1. WGNmaker software (Excel Macros) was used for calculation of required statistical evaluations. This software (WGN Excel Macro) and its manual can be found on SWAT homepage (SWAT, Links to Related Software).
2. Maximum half-hour measurements are unavailable for all grid points. This data is required for .wgn file preparation and was acquired by using daily precipitation according to method described in SWAT Theoretical Documentation ARS (2005), p.66, eq. 1:3.2.3.

Fig.14. Location of grid points for meteorological data in the territory of Belarus.

The preparation of weather scenarios (.cst files) for iterative model runs using weather generator data is requested in TOR 3.1.2.4 (for Lithuania) and 3.1.15.6 (for Belarus). We defined the forecast regions coinciding with the meteorological observation stations. The weather scenario .cst files were added to the setups and filled with the weather generator data during the automated creation of the respective (Lithuania or Belarus) water quality modeling system, see also Chapter 3.

2.4. Elevation data (3.1.3)

Data. TOR (3.1.3.1-3.1.3.2) requests that digital land surface laser scanning point data (SEŽP_0,5LT) products with spatial resolution of no less than 5 m must be used for updating the elevation data.

Digital elevation model (DEM) *visas.aux* provided by the Client with spatial resolution 2x2 meters was used for this task. See the coverage of Lithuania by this product in Fig.15.

Fig. 15. DEM *visas.aux*, coverage of Lithuanian territory.

During the data preprocessing stage a 5x5 meter resolution raster (*dem_5m.aux*) was created by expanding the 2x2 m given DEM:

1. *visas.aux* was projected to a 5x5 meter grid using ArcMap method “resample nearest neighbour”.
2. The grid area was extended to cover the whole territory of Lithuania using a 10x10 meter grid provided by the Client (*dem_10m.aux*).

The synthesised *dem_5m.aux* DEM is shown in Fig. 16.

The updated elevation data was further used for establishing slope classes according to p.3.1.3.3 of ToR.

The slope distribution in Lithuania was calculated (see Fig. 17), and two slope classes (Table 1) were established assigning ~75% of the territory to the flatter class. An example of the soil slope raster is illustrated in Fig. 18.

Fig. 16. DEM dem_5m.aux used for creating slope classes.

Table. 1. Slope classes for SWAT model.

Slope class	Terrain slope, %
1	0-4
2	4-100

Fig. 17. Cumulative probability of terrain slope from DEM dem_5m.aux.

Fig. 18. Illustration of the slope raster in the central part of Lithuania (river Neris).

2.5. Land use data (3.1.4, 3.1.12)

Update of land use data of PAIC & ELLE (2012) where performed according to p.3.1.4 (but for urban land also to p.3.1.12) of ToR. It included preparation of the unified land use polygons and codes.

The following input data was used:

1. **Declared crops data.** We used declared crops for year 2012 as provided by the Client in folder *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Crops\2012\2012*. Particular files were *2012_dkl_1.shp*, *2012_dkl_2.shp*, *2012_dkl_3.shp*, *2012_dkl_4.shp*, *2012_dkl_5.shp*, *2012_dkl_6.shp*, *2012_dkl_7.shp*. They contain polygonal feature classes, field *DKL_PASEL* contains declared field code. Files were merged into one for further processing to one feature class stored in *Data/landuse.gdb/crops*.
2. **Forest cadaster data.** We used forest cadaster geospatial data as provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Forests\Forest_data\SKL_Atdb.shp*. It contains polygonal feature classes. We used field *naudmena* representing land use type of forest cadaster lands and *vyr_medz_r* representing dominant tree species. File was preprocessed by removing unnecessary columns and placed in *Data/landuse.gdb/forest*.
3. **Abandoned land data.** We used polygonal feature class as provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\AZ_DR10LT\AZ_DR10LT.gdb\apleistos_zemes_LKS94*. No fields for this data source were used. File was copied to *Data/landuse.gdb/abandoned*.
4. **GDR geospatial data** from “*Lietuvos Respublikos teritorijos M1:10000 georeferencinių erdviųjų duomenų rinkinio (GDR10LT)*” provided by the Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GDR10LT\GDR10LT.gdb* was used in addition to the sources directly mentioned in the terms of reference. We used polygonal feature class *PLOTAI*, field *GKODAS* represents classification of the geospatial polygons. This feature class was preprocessed by removing unnecessary fields and copied to *Data/landuse.gdb/gdr*.
5. The high-resolution (HR) Imperviousness Layer from **Geoland2** was used as provided by Client in *SWAT_DATABASE\GIS_DATABASE\Urban\PAN_P-EL-03_2009* (3.1.12 of ToR). Raster datasets in size 100x100 km of 20x20 m resolution were provided covering all Europe. We used 12 rasters covering territory of Lithuania:

100KME50n35_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME50n36_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME50n37_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME51n35_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME51n36_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME51n37_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME52n35_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME52n36_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME52n37_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,

100KME53n35_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME53n36_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img,
100KME53n37_P-EL-03_Imperviousness_Degrees_1v0.img.

These rasters were combined into single raster in *Data\LandUse\Geoland\Combined\geoland*. Values of the raster represent, respectively:

0 - *Non-built up areas, water bodies inland,*
1-100 – degree of soil sealing,
254 - *Unclassifiable Area (clouds, shadow, etc.),*
255 *Outside area (no thematic information)*

We preprocessed the raster setting values 254 and 255 to 0. The preprocessed raster was placed in *Data/LandUse/Geoland/impervious*.

We used the following preprocessing steps with above input data:

1. Spatial union of the declared crops layer, forest cadaster layer, abandoned land layer, and *GDR10LT* layer. Union of above information is a polygonal feature class representing geometric intersection of the input features with all features written. It is located in *Data/landuse.gdb/union* and contains the fields listed in Table 2.

Table 2. List of fields in unified land use polygons Data/landuse.gdb/union.

Field	Contents and exceptions
FID_crops	<i>ObjectID</i> of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/crops</i> , -1 if crop is not declared for this polygon
DKL_PASEL	<i>DKL_PASEL</i> field of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/crops</i> representing declared crop code
FID_abandoned	<i>ObjectID</i> of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/abandoned</i> , -1 if abandoned land is present in this polygon
FID_gdr	<i>ObjectID</i> in <i>Data/landuse.gdb/gdr</i> , -1 if polygon is outside <i>GDR10LT</i>
GKODAS	<i>GKODAS</i> field of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/gdr</i> representing polygon class according to <i>GDR10LT PLOTAI</i> feature class
FID_forest	<i>ObjectID</i> in <i>Data/landuse.gdb/forest</i> , -1 if polygon is outside forest cadaster data
naudmena	<i>Naudmena</i> field of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing land use type of forest cadaster lands
vyr_medz_r	<i>vyr_medz_r</i> field of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing dominant tree species
augaviete	<i>augaviete</i> field of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing soil type of forest lands
Amzius	<i>amzius</i> field of <i>Data/landuse.gdb/forest</i> representing average age of the trees in years
Shape_Length	Perimeter of polygon in m
Shape_Area	Area of polygon in m ²
LUCODE	Generalised land use code for a polygon (see below)

2. For the crop types in the declared crops data that were not possible to relate to crops according to agricultural expert, crop dataset was not used. For those polygons we set *FID_crops* to -1.
3. Average imperviousness for the polygons representing *GDR10LT* classes “Build up areas” and “Industrial areas not less than 1 ha” was prepared.

- a. Polygon to raster conversion was performed for the polygons of *union* feature class where *GKODAS* is “pu0” and “pu3”. The resulting raster containing *FID_gdr* values is *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious_raster*.
- b. Zonal statistics tool was used for calculating average value of *Data/LandUse/Geoland/impervious* raster for each unique value of *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious_raster*. Resulting table of the average degree of soil sealing (imperviousness) for each of the polygons is *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious*, field *MEAN*. The ranges of imperviousness for urban land is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Ranges of imperviousness for urban land use classes.

SWAT urban land use class	Swat name	Degree of soil sealing (imperviousness) from Geoland2
URLD	Residential-Low Density	0% - 18%
URML	Residential-Med/Low Density	18% - 26%
URMD	Residential-Medium Density	26% - 44%
URHD	Residential-High Density	44% - 82%
UIDU	Industrial	82% - 100%

4. Generalized land use code *LUCODE* was assigned to the polygons following the rules below:
 - a. If *FID_crops* ≥ 0 (for declared crops), then *LUCODE* = “C_” + [*DKL_PASEL*].
 - b. Else if *FID_forest* ≥ 0 (for forest cadaster data where crops are not declared), *LUCODE* = “F_” + [*naudmena*] + “_” + [*vyr_medz_r*]. If the value of field *augaviete* is in the list of wet forest soil types (Pa, Pan, Pb) then *LUCODE* = “F_” + [*naudmena*] + “_” + [*vyr_medz_r*] + “_” + [*augaviete*].
 - c. Else if *FID_abandoned* ≥ 0 (for abandoned land without crops declared and not in forest cadaster) then *LUCODE* = “A_”.
 - d. Else if *FID_gdr* ≥ 0 and *GKODAS* is neither “pu0” nor “pu3”, then *LUCODE* = “G_” + [*GKODAS*].
 - e. Otherwise if *FID_gdr* ≥ 0 then *LUCODE* = “G_” + [*GKODAS*] + “_” + *URBANCLASS*. Urban class is determined from average degrees of soil sealing represented in table *Data/LandUse/landuse.gdb/gdr_impervious*. The ranges of imperviousness for urban classes are given in Table 3. They are correlated with the values of the range total impervios in Table A-15 of SWAT 2012 I/O manual TWRI (2012).
5. The global lookup table for the connection between the generalized land use code and SWAT code from *crop* or *urban* tables was prepared:
 - a. **Declared crops.** We used a classification (generalisation) provided by the agricultural expert. Table 4 summarizes the respective declared crop classification.

Table 4. Relation of the declared crops classes to SWAT crop classes.

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT crop code	SWAT crop name
C_5AM-1	Aromatiniai, medicininiai ir prieskoniniai augalai (mėtos, kalendros, medetkos, čiobreliai, ramunėlės, mairūnai, šalavijai, pankoliai, bazilikai, melisos, valerijonai ir kt.)	aromatic, medical, spice plants	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5AR-1	Aliejiniai ridikai	cultivated radish	CANP	Spring Canola-Polish
C_5AV-1	Avižos	oat	OATS	Oats
C_5BG-1	Baltosios garstyčios	white mustard	CANP	Spring Canola-Polish
C_5BU-1	Bulvės, skirtos perdirbti į krakmolą	potato	POTA	Potato
C_5BU-2	Bulvės (išskyrus skirtas perdirbti į krakmolą ir pašarui)	potato	POTA	Potato
C_5BU-3	Bulvės pašarui	fodder potato	POTA	Potato
C_5CR-1	Runkeliai (cukriniai)	sugar beet	SGBT	Sugarbeet
C_5DA-1	Daržovės (atviro grunto, be sėklojų ir pasodų) – gūžiniai kopūstai	cabbage	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-10	Daržovės (uždaro grunto) – kitos	other vegetables	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-11	Daržovių sėklojai ir pasodai	seed plants	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-2	Daržovės (atviro grunto, be sėklojų ir pasodų) – žiediniai kopūstai	cauliflower	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-3	Daržovės (atviro grunto, be sėklojų ir pasodų) – kininiai kopūstai	chinese cabbage	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-4	Daržovės (atviro grunto, be sėklojų ir pasodų) – burokėliai	common beet	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-5	Daržovės (atviro grunto, be sėklojų ir pasodų) – morkos	carrot	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-6	Daržovės (atviro grunto, be sėklojų ir pasodų) – svogūnai	onion	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-7	Daržovės (atviro grunto, be sėklojų ir pasodų) – kitos	other vegetables	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-8	Daržovės (uždaro grunto) – agurkai	cucumber	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DA-9	Daržovės (uždaro grunto) – pomidorai	tomato	CRRT	Carrot
C_5DB-1	Dobilai pašarui	clover	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5DG-1	Daugiametės ganyklos (pievos) (5 m. ir daugiau)	perennial pastures	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5DS-1	Daugiametės svidrės	perennial	WPAS	Winter Pasture

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT crop code	SWAT crop name
		ryegrass		
C_5EC-1	Esparcetai	sainfoin	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5FL-1	Facelijos	phacelia	CANP	Spring Canola-Polish
C_5GB-1	Geltonžiedžiai, baltažiedžiai barkūnai	sweet clover	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5GP-1	Ganyklos (pievos) (iki 5 m.)	pastures (under 5 years)	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5GR-1	Grikliai	buckwheat	BWHT	Buckwheat
C_5KD-1	Kiti daugiamečiai augalai (pynimui, audimui ir kt.) (karklai, nendrės, meldai, vikšriai ir kiti)	other perennial plants	WILL	Willow
C_5KJ-1	Kiti varpiniai javai, įskaitant jų mišinius		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5KM-1	Pirmamečiai kmynai	first-year caraway	CELR	Celery
C_5KM-2	Kmynai	caraway	CELR	Celery
C_5KR-1	Kvietrugiai (vasariniai)	triticale (summer)	STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye
C_5KR-2	Kvietrugiai (žieminiai)	triticale (winter)	WTRC	Winter triticale
C_5KT-1	Kiti žemės ūkio augalai	other agricultural plants	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5KV-1	Kviečiai (vasariniai)	summer wheat	SWHT	Spring Wheat
C_5KV-2	Kviečiai (žieminiai)	winter wheat	WWHT	Winter Wheat
C_5KZ-1	Kukurūzai grūdams	corn	CORN	Corn
C_5KZ-2	Kukurūzai silosui, žaliajam pašarui	corn silage	CSIL	Corn Silage
C_5LC-1	Liucernos	alfalfa	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5LE-1	Lęšiai	lenses	GRBN	Green Beans
C_5LI-1	Linai pluoštui	flax	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5LI-2	Sėmeniniai (aliejiniai) linai	flax	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5LI-3	Sėmeniniai (aliejiniai) linai sėklai	flax	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5LU-1	Lubiniai (saldieji)	lupine	LUPN	Lupine
C_5LU-2	Lubiniai pašarui	lupine	LUPN	Lupine
C_5MB-1	Kiti trumpos rotacijos plantaciniai želdiniai	other plants with short rotation	POPL	Poplar
C_5MD-1	Medelynai	arboretum	POPL	Poplar
C_5MI-1	Miežiai (salykliniai)	barley	BARL	Spring Barley

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT crop code	SWAT crop name
C_5MI-2	Miežiai (vasariniai, nesalykliniai)	summer barley	BARL	Spring Barley
C_5MI-3	Miežiai (žieminiai, nesalykliniai)	winter barley	WBAR	Winter Barley
C_5MR-1	Gluosnis, karklas (Salix L)	willow	WILL	Willow
C_5MR-3	Baltalksnis (Alnus incana L, Moench)	alder	POPL	Poplar
C_5ND-1	Nendriniai dryžučiai	reed canarygrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5PD-1	Pūdymas (juodasis)	fallow	BARR	Barren
C_5PD-2	Pūdymas (sideracinis)	fallow	CLVR	Red Clover
C_5PG-1	Paprastieji gargždeniai	Bird's-foot Trefoil	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5PP-1	Pieviniai pašiaušėliai	field meadow foxtail	CANP	Spring Canola- Polish
C_5PP-2	Daugiametės ganyklos (pievos) (5 m. ir daugiau), skirtos prekynei žolinės produkcijos gamybai	perennial pastures for grass production	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5PT-1	Natūralių ir pusiau natūralių pievų tvarkymas		BROS	Smooth Bromegrass
C_5PU-1	Pupos (lauko / pašarinės)	beans	GRBN	Green Beans
C_5PU-2	Pupos (daržo)	kidney bean	GRBN	Green Beans
C_5RA-1	Rapsai (vasariniai)	summer rape	SCAN	Summer rape
C_5RA-2	Rapsai (žieminiai)	winter rape	CANA	Spring Canola- Argentine
C_5RA-3	Rapsukai	colza	SCAN	Summer rape
C_5RG-1	Rudosios, juodosios garstyčios	black mustard	CANP	Spring Canola- Polish
C_5RO-1	Rytiniai ožiarūčiai	professor-weed	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5RU-1	Rugiai	rye	RYE	Rye
C_5RU-2	Rugiai (vasariniai)	rye (summer)	SRYE	Summer Rye
C_5SA-1	Saulėgražos	sunflower	AGRC	Agricultural Land- Close-grown
C_5SD-1	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) obelių sodai	apple tree	ORCD	Orchard
C_5SD-2	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) kriaušių sodai	pear tree	ORCD	Orchard
C_5SD-3	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) slyvų sodai	plum tree	ORCD	Orchard
C_5SD-4	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) vyšnių sodai	cherry tree	ORCD	Orchard
C_5SD-5	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) trešnių sodai	cherry tree	ORCD	Orchard
C_5SD-6	Kiti sodai (vaismedžiai, lazdynai)	other orchards	ORCD	Orchard
C_5SD-7	Pirmamečiai ir antramečiai sodai	first and second- year orchards	ORCD	Orchard

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT crop code	SWAT crop name
C_5SE-1	Pluoštiniai linai sėklai	flax	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5SE-10	Tikrieji eraičinai sėklai	fescue	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-11	Raudonieji eraičinai sėklai	red fescue	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-12	Nendriniai eraičinai sėklai	fescue	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-14	Tarpgentiniai hibridai sėklai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5SE-15	Gausiažiedės svidrės sėklai	Italian ryegrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-16	Daugiametės svidrės sėklai	perennial ryegrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-18	Pašariniai motiejukai sėklai	timothy grass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-2	Ruginiai vikiai sėklai	winter vetch	VTCH	Vetch
C_5SE-20	Pievinės miglės sėklai	Kentucky bluegrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-24	Raudonieji dobilai sėklai	red clover	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5SE-25	Baltieji dobilai sėklai	white clover	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5SE-26	Rausvieji dobilai sėklai	alsike clover	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5SE-3	Sėjami vikiai sėklai	garden vetch	VTCH	Vetch
C_5SE-30	Mėlynžiedės liucernos sėklai	alfalfa	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5SE-33	Sėjami esparcetai sėklai	sainfoin	ALFA	Alfalfa
C_5SE-4	Paprastosios šunažolės sėklai	orchardgrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-5	Paprastosios smilgos sėklai	colonial bentgrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SE-8	Šuninės smilgos sėklai	velvet bentgrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5SJ-1	Sojos	soy	SOYB	Soybean
C_5SL-1	Sujungtas laukas, kuriame auginami V grupės augalai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5SO-1	Sorgas (grūdinis)	sorghum	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5SP-1	Šakniavaisiai (pašariniai) (be sėklojų ir pasodų)	fodder root vegetables	SGBT	Sugarbeet
C_5SP-2	Šakniavaisiai (pašariniai) (sėklojai ir pasodai)	seed plants for root vegetables	SGBT	Sugarbeet
C_5SR-1	Soros	millet	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5SR-2	Seradėlės	common bird's-foot	GRBN	Green Beans
C_5ST-1	Strypinių sėklos (kanarėlių lesalas)	canarygrass	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5SV-1	Svidrės	ryegrass	WPAS	Winter Pasture
C_5TA-1	Techniniai augalai (tabakas, apyniai ir kt.)	technical plants (tobacco, hops)	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_5UG-1	Gėlės ir dekoratyviniai augalai	flowers and	AGRC	Agricultural Land-

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT crop code	SWAT crop name
	(uždaro grunto)	decorative plants		Close-grown
C_5UO-1	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) juodųjų serbentų uogynai	black currant	ORCD	Orchard
C_5UO-2	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) raudonųjų serbentų uogynai	red currant	ORCD	Orchard
C_5UO-3	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) braškių uogynai	strawberry	CRRT	Carrot
C_5UO-4	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) aviečių uogynai	raspberry	ORCD	Orchard
C_5UO-5	Versliniai (intensyviai prižiūrimi) aronijų uogynai	chokeberry	ORCD	Orchard
C_5UO-6	Kiti uogynai	other berries	ORCD	Orchard
C_5UO-7	Pirmamečiai ir antramečiai uogynai	first and second-year berries	ORCD	Orchard
C_5UO-8	Uždaro grunto braškių uogynai	strawberry	CRRT	Carrot
C_5VA-1	Varpinių-baltyminių (kitų nei žirnių, lauko / pašarinių pupų ar saldžiųjų lubinų)-aliejinė augalų mišiniai		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
C_5VA-2	Varpinių-baltyminių (žirnių, lauko / pašarinių pupų ir saldžiųjų lubinų)-aliejinė augalų mišiniai (kuriuose baltyminiai augalai yra vyraujantys)		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
C_5VA-3	Varpinių-baltyminių (žirnių, lauko / pašarinių pupų ir saldžiųjų lubinų)-aliejinė augalų mišiniai (kuriuose baltyminiai augalai nėra vyraujantys)		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
C_5VA-4	Varpinių-ankštinių (išskyrus vikius) javų mišiniai		LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
C_5VI-1	Vikiai ir jų mišiniai	garden vetch	VTCH	Vetch
C_5ZI-1	Žirniai	peas	PEAS	Garden or Canning Peas
C_JSL-1	Sujungtas laukas, kuriame auginami II grupės augalai		AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_RKR-2	Kvietrugiai (žieminiai) ir jų ražienos		STTR	Winter triticale (straw fields)
C_RKV-1	Kviečiai (vasariniai) ir jų ražienos		STWH	Summer wheat (straw fields)
C_RKV-2	Kviečiai (žieminiai) ir jų ražienos		STWW	Winter wheat (straw fields)
C_RMI-2	Miežiai (vasariniai, nesalykliniai)		STBR	Summer barley

LUCODE	Lithuanian crop name (pasėlis)	Crop name	SWAT crop code	SWAT crop name
	ir jų ražienos			(straw fields)
C_RRA-1	Rapsai (vasariniai) ir jų ražienos		STCN	Summer rape (straw fields)
C_RRU-1	Rugiai (žieminiai ir vasariniai) ir jų ražienos		STRY	Rye (straw fields)
C_SKN-1	Sėjamoji kanapė sėklai	Marijuana	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
C_SKN-2	Sėjamoji kanapė pluoštui	Marijuana	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown

Table 5. Lookup table – relation of dominant species data from forest cadaster to SWAT crop classes.

vyr_medz_r	name_Lithuanian	SWATCODE	CROPNAME
P	Pušis	PINE	Pine
Pb	Pušis bankso	PINE	Pine
Pk	Pušis kalninė	PINE	Pine
Pj	Pušis juodoji	PINE	Pine
E	Eglė	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Pc	Pocūgė	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Kn	Kėnis	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
M	Maumedis	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Ks	Kiti spygliuočiai	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
Kk	Kiti kietieji lapuočiai	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
A	Ažuolas	OAK	Oak
Ar	Ažuolas raudonasis	OAK	Oak
U	Uosis	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
K	Klevas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Sb	Skroblas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
G	Guoba	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
S	Skirpstas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
B	Beržas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Bt	Baltalksnis	POPL	Poplar
J	Juodalksnis	POPL	Poplar
D	Drebulė	POPL	Poplar
T	Tuopa	POPL	Poplar
L	Liepa	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Bl	Blindė	WILL	Willow
Gl	Gluosnis	WILL	Willow
Km	Kiti minkštieji lapuočiai	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Kd	Kedras	FRSE	Forest-Evergreen
V	Vinkšna	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous
Bu	Bukas	FRSD	Forest-Deciduous

- b. **Forest lands.** The following rules were used:
- i. If the dominant tree species were defined then we used lookup Table 5 relating these species with the SWAT crop code.
 - ii. If the soil type corresponds to the wet forests (Pa, Pan, Pb), then the SWAT landuse code was set to *WETF*.
 - iii. For other forest lands landuse type was determined using *naudmena* field of forest cadaster data, using lookup Table 6.

Table 6. Lookup table – relation of forest land use classes to SWAT crop/urban classes.

Naudmena	Name_Lithuanian	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
5	Kirtavietė	BARR	Barren
6	Žuvės medynas	BARR	Barren
7	Miško aikštė	BARR	Barren
8	Žemė, skirta miškui įveisti	BARR	Barren
9	Miško žemė, verčiama ne miško	WPAS	Winter Pasture
10	Daigynas	RNGB	Range-Brush
11	Medelynas	RNGB	Range-Brush
12	Sėklinė plantacija	RNGB	Range-Brush
13	Žaliavinė plantacija	WILL	Willow
14	Rekreaciniai želdiniai	WILL	Willow
21	Technologinė linija	WPAS	Winter Pasture
22	Priešgaisrinė juosta	BARR	Barren
23	Griovio trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
24	Elektros trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
25	Ryšių trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
26	Energetikos trasa	WPAS	Winter Pasture
28	Elektros linija	WPAS	Winter Pasture
29	Miško kelias	UTRN	Transportation
30	Priešgaisrinis barjeras	BARR	Barren
31	Medienos sandėlis	BARR	Barren
32	Miško poilsivietė	FRST	Forest-Mixed
33	Pašarų aikštelė	FRST	Forest-Mixed
34	Miško laukymė	WPAS	Winter Pasture
9	Miško žemė, verčiama ne miško	WPAS	Winter Pasture
40	Ariama žemė	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
41	Pieva	WPAS	Winter Pasture
42	Ganykla	WPAS	Winter Pasture
43	Sodas	ORCD	Orchard
45	Krūmai	RNGB	Range-Brush
47	Pelkė	WETL	Wetlands-Mixed
50	Pastatai	URMD	Residential-Medium Density
51	Sodyba	URLD	Residential-Low Density

Naudmena	Name_Lithuanian	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
52	Kiemas	URMD	Residential-Medium Density
53	Paminklinė aikštė	URMD	Residential-Medium Density
54	Geležinkelio pylimas	UTRN	Transportation
60	Ežeras	WATR	Water
62	Kūdra	WATR	Water
63	Tvenkinys	WATR	Water
64	Griovys	WATR	Water
70	Trasa (platesnė nei 10 m.)	WPAS	Winter Pasture
74	Karjeras	BARR	Barren
75	Poilsiavietė	BARR	Barren
76	Paplūdimys	BARR	Barren
77	Kopos	BARR	Barren
78	Skardis	BARR	Barren
79	Akmenynas	BARR	Barren
80	Kapinės	URLD	Residential-Low Density
81	Durpynas	BARR	Barren
82	Smėlynas	BARR	Barren
83	Kitos žemės	RNGB	Range-Brush
84	Parkas	FRST	Forest-Mixed
85	Skveras (aikštė)	FRST	Forest-Mixed
86	Sodas (botan., zool.)	FRST	Forest-Mixed
87	Dekoratyviniis želdynas	ORCD	Orchard
89	Sąvartynas	UIDU	Industrial
91	Žemė, apauganti mišku	FRST	Forest-Mixed

c. For abandoned lands we uses SWAT crop code *RNGB* representing range brush.

d. The classification (relation) of GDR10LT classes according to SWAT crop/urban codes is given in Table 7. For Build-up areas urban class was determined from imperviousness according to Table 3.

The illustrations of the land use raster is given in two different scales in Figures 19 and 20.

The contents of the intermediate electronic deliverable *Data/Landuse/landuse.gdb* – is as follows:

- *crops* – polygon feature class containing declared crop data (2012),
- *forest* – polygon feature class containing forest cadaster data,
- *abandoned* - polygon feature class containing abandoned lands data,
- *gdr* - polygon feature class representing GDR10LT layer *PLOTAI*,
- *gdr_alone* – polygon feature class for those features of layer *gdr* for which there are no crop, forest or abandoned land data,
- *gdr_impervious_raster* – raster data representing values of *OBJECTID* field of *gdr*,
- *gdr_impervious* – table of imperviousness statistics for each of the *gdr_alone* polygons having *GKODAS* pu0 or pu3,

- *union* – layer containing intersections of crop, forest, abandoned lands and GDR10LT data.

Table 7. Connection of GDR10LT landuse classification with SWAT crop/urban classes.

GKODAS	SWATCODE	CROP/URBAN
gt12	UTRN	Transportation
gt14	UTRN	Transportation
gt15	UTRN	Transportation
gt16	UTRN	Transportation
gt18	UTRN	Transportation
gt19	UTRN	Transportation
gt2	UTRN	Transportation
hd1	WATR	Water
hd2	WATR	Water
hd21	WATR	Water
hd22	WATR	Water
hd23	WATR	Water
hd3	WATR	Water
hd4	WATR	Water
hd5	WATR	Water
hd6	WETL	Wetlands-Mixed
hd9	WATR	Water
ms0	FRST	Forest-Mixed
ms4	ORCD	Orchard
pu0	determined by imperviousness	
pu3	determined by imperviousness	
sd11	AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown
sd15	RNGB	Range-Brush
sd2	WPAS	Winter Pasture
sd4	BARR	Barren
sd42	BARR	Barren
sd7	BARR	Barren
va1	URLD	Residential-Low Density
va11	UTRN	Transportation
vk1	URLD	Residential-Low Density
vp1	URLD	Residential-Low Density

Fig. 19. Illustration of land use polygons in central part of Lithuania (river Neris).

Fig. 20. Illustration of the land use polygons. Small scale detailisation.

The following additional electronic data is supplied:

1. *globallookup* – table for connection of *union.LUCODE* with SWAT crop/urban codes
2. *croplookup* – table for connection of *crop.DKL_PASEL* with SWAT crop codes
3. *lucode_statistics* – summary areas of *union* polygons grouped by *LUCODE*
4. *lucode_dissolved* – *union* feature class dissolved by *LUCODE* and with reduced amount of fields
5. *crops_statistics* – summary areas of *crop* polygons grouped by *DKL_PASEL*
6. *forest_statistics* – summary areas of *forest* polygons grouped by *naudmena*, *vyr_medz_r*, *augaviete*
7. *gdr_statistics* – summary areas of *GDR* polygons grouped by *GKODAS*.

One update of the land cover for the time period 2000 – 2012 is suggested by TOR 3.1.4.2. The rather representative data set used in this Section which represents the contemporary land use is not available for any another time period. Therefore CORINE 2000 and CORINE 2006 data sets are used to account for changes in land cover. The following method is used:

1. The land use classes are aggregated in 7 groups as “Agricultural”, “Pastures”, “Forest”, “Urban”, “Wetlands”, “Water” and “Barren”.
2. For each of the catchments (Section 2.1.3) the relative fractions of each of the group of the land use classes are calculated for CORINE 2000 and CORINE 2006.
3. The table containing catchment ID, and 7 numbers – the changes (in %) of the relative fraction of each of the group of land use classes is prepared

The prepared data is further used by the automated system of the generation of the water quality modeling system for creation of *.lup* files of respective SWAT subbasins, see Chapter 3.

2.6. Point source pollution data (3.1.5)

According to p.3.1.5.1 point source water pollution data in the SWAT model PAIC&ELLE (2012) must be appended with the data from 1997-1999., 2011 and 2012 for suspended solids, BOD, dissolved oxygen, organic and mineral nitrogen and phosphorus loads.

The database (*1997-2012 correction updated.xls*) of the annual amounts of point source pollution as well as data (multiple files) of monthly amounts of point source pollution were supplied by the Client. The later dataset is aimed to prepare monthly pollution datasets according to TOR 3.1.5.2.

The database has severe quality problems requiring development of methodology of data processing prior to including the point pollution sources in the model.

The assessment of the yearly database *1997-2012 correction updated.xls* is given in Section 2.6.1. The manual digitizing and analysis of monthly data (multiple files) is described in Section 2.6.2, whilst the largest point sources of Lithuania are analysed in Section 2.6.3. The data preparation for their usage with automated script system for generation of the water quality model is described in Section 2.6.4.

2.6.1. Pre-processing and analysis of database quality and structure

The main issue for use of the database is identification of the unique point sources. Methodology of identification of the individual point sources of water pollution in Lithuania is based on the set of consequent steps:

- 1) primary identification of the potentially different point pollution sources:
 - a. identification of different codes (for example “L191038”) from the field „Ukio subjektas” – 2266 different codes found;
 - b. calculation of the different coordinates (“Platuma” and “Ilguma” values) for each acquired code.

Steps *a&b* showed that there are a large number of codes with the huge variety of coordinates - (“unclear location” of the point) that gives evidence that the code can not be used as an unique identifier of the potential point pollution source; example of different records of coordinates of the same company is shown in Table 8.

- c. to reduce the number of sources with “unclair location” concatenation of database fields has been done: the code (for example “L191038”) from the field „Ukio subjektas” and the value of the field “Isleistuvas”;
 - d. identification of the count of different concatenations acquired by step *c* resulted in 5207 different concatenations found.
- 2) Since the number of different concatenated codes was around five thousand (different potential point pollution sources), the priority of potential sources was analysed. The importance of priority of the codes arises from the fact that concatenation of two fields only partly reduces the diversity of coordinates noticed in point *1b*. The reason of that two changes during years can happen for the unique company:
 - a. the same value of “Isleistuvas” might match very different spatially distant coordinates;
 - b. the same coordinates may match different “Isleistuvas”.

Table 8. Example of variety of coordinates for the same typical “problematic” ID code.

Id („Ukio subjektas”)	Platuma	Ilguma	Count of records in the database
267548080	0.0	0.0	10
267548080	6101715.0	61020.0	4
267548080	6102844.0	61073.5	46
267548080	6102976.3	60750.8	12
267548080	6102976.5	60750.9	4
267548080	6103103.0	61004.9	4
267548080	6103281.0	61004.7	5
267548080	6103810.0	61034.7	5
267548080	6103810.1	61034.8	20
267548080	6096258.0	61250.6	9
267548080	6101849.0	61096.1	4
267548080	6102685.3	61082.8	48
267548080	6102844.5	61073.6	4
267548080	6102850.0	60992.8	8
267548080	6102852.9	61073.0	13
267548080	6025901.0	54832.6	4
267548080	6101812.0	61066.7	12
267548080	6102460.0	61019.1	5
267548080	6102460.5	61019.1	10
267548080	6102850.5	60992.8	4

Id („Ukio subjektas“)	Platuma	Ilguma	Count of records in the database
267548080	6102895.7	60992.9	22
267548080	6026082.0	54810.8	4
267548080	6101601.0	61016.3	5
267548080	6101601.5	61016.3	5
267548080	6101781.0	61051.0	12
267548080	6101812.6	61066.7	44
267548080	6101836.4	61113.3	12
267548080	6101849.1	61096.1	17
267548080	6101639.4	61027.7	17
267548080	6101715.3	61020.1	4
267548080	6102976.0	60750.9	18

The manual analysis for determination of co-ordinates in case of “unclear location” was performed for “major polluters”. The criteria for selection the “major polluters” is described below.

We have done analysis that shows that the large part of codes (point sources) have records only for part of the years from 1997-2012 (see Table 9). Summary of record number in Table 9 gives evidence also that only few pollution agents “*Tersalas*” – like “bendras azotas”, “fosforas” etc. – are measured at each point every year.

To obtain the proportion of “major polluters” input in the total amount of water pollution three years (2000, 2006 and 2012) were selected. The records with the value “*Azotas bendras*” and “*Bendras azotas*” were considered. Sorting of to field “*Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis*” values from the largest to smallest was performed. The sum of records of major pollution sources (with the value of “*Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis*” ≥ 200 , and excluding the largest amount from “*Ignalinos atomine elektrine*”) was calculated to assess its ratio in the total amount of wastewater. Results of this calculation are given in Table 10. Detailed calculation of the sum of records is given in Table 11.

As the result – the part of the database with column “*Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis*” value above 200 000 m³/year (6.3 liters/s) was selected for further manual analysis.

Table 9. The count of records for potential waste water pollution sources in the database (situation is shown for a selected set of the id).

id\year	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
110006173_1	0	0	0	0	3	0	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
110012450_1	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	0	0	0	0	4	4
110012450_2	0	1	0	4	3	3	0	0	0	3	3	4	4	0	4	4
110012450_3	0	0	0	3	3	2	0	0	0	0	3	4	4	0	4	4
110012450_4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
110012450_5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
110012450_6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
110027534_1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	3	3	4	4	4
110038559_2	35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
110044455_1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	7	6
110044455_2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	9	0
110053842_1	11	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
110053842_2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
110068730_1	5	6	6	6	6	6	7	5	6	5	5	4	3	3	3	3
110068730_2	5	6	7	6	6	5	6	6	5	6	5	4	3	3	3	0
110068730_3	5	6	6	6	6	5	6	5	5	0	6	4	3	3	3	3

110070044_1	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	3	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
110080729_1	0	0	0	0	3	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
110083458_1	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	7	5	6	9	6	6	6	4	4
110083458_2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0

Table 10. Identification of the criteria for the major pollution sources.

Year	Total sum of "Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis" (excluding "Ignalinos atomine elektrine")	Sum of records of major pollution sources ("Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis" > = 200, excluding "Ignalinos atomine elektrine")	% of pollution form major pollution sources
2000	256710.9	247042.9	96.23
2006	266219.5	257006.3	96.54
2012	240334.4	228725.7	95.17

Table 11. List of the major pollution sources in year 2012 regarding the amount of "Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis" in 1000 m³ per year.

Ukio subjektas	Isleis-tuvas	Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis
255450080 VI "Ignalinos atomine elektrine"	1	47980
120545849 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "VILNIAUS VANDENYS"	1	25230
132751369 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kauno vandenys"	1	24329
140089260 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPEDOS VANDUO"	1	17162
120545849 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "VILNIAUS VANDENYS"	2	14169
255450080 VI "Ignalinos atomine elektrine"	2	10336
147104754 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "AUKŠTAITIJS VANDENYS"	2	9031
144133366 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Siauliu vandenys"	11	8622
165723594 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "KARPIS"	1	5925
286143880 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Akvilėgija"	1	5633
155480076 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birvetos tvenkiniai"	1	5545
151104226 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Suduvos vandenys"	1	4580
156667399 Akcine bendrove "Achema"	1	4112
183633981 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Utenos vandenys"	1	3587
166486116 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Mazeikiu vandenys"	1	3586
149566841 UAB "Dzukijos vandenys"	1	3257
180153137 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove " Telsiu vandenys "	1	3174
166451720 AB "ORLEN Lietuva"	1	3075
152447391 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "PALANGOS VANDENYS"	1	3028
162496878 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Silo Pavezupis"	1	2865
161186428 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kedainiu vandenys"	1	2427
177059215 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove " Silutes vandenys "	1	2311
180195588 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove " Zemaitijos zuvis "	1	2250
256564350 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Jonavos vandenys"	1	2200
177155847 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kintai"	1	2091
158889861 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Bartzuve"	2	2089
179249836 UAB "Taurages vandenys"	1	2083
187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"	4	1973

Ukio subjektas	Isleis- tuvas	Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis
153622317 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Daugu zuvis"	1	1808
L690350 Zuvininkystes tarnybos prie Lietuvos Respublikos Zemes ukio ministerijos Vidaus vandenu ir akvakulturos skyria	1	1770.1
161634276 UAB "KAPLIU ZUVYS"	1	1750
161110455 Akcine bendrove "LIFOSA"	1	1687
301500997 UAB "Druskininku vandenys"	2	1627.8
267548080 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "ARMOLE"	1	1584
163994426 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kretingos vandenys"	1	1399
173741535 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Rokiskio vandenys"	1	1316.4
169845485 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Plunges vandenys"	1	1296
267548080 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "ARMOLE"	2	1226
110087517 Valstybes imone "VISAGINO ENERGIJA"	1	1208
158889861 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Bartzuve"	1	1199
182743364 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "UKMERMES VANDENYS"	1	1164
158834726 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove " Kasiadoriu vandenys "	1	1145
181613656 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "ELEKTRENU KOMUNALINIS UKIS"	1	1122
275746610 UZDAROJI AKCINE BENDROVE "SVENTJONIS"	1	1120
187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"	1	1104.9
169236961 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Pasvalio vandenys"	20	1061.5
170694265 Akcine bendrove "Islauzo zuvis"	1	1052
154850665 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birzu vandenys"	1	1031.6
187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"	3	1000
158852934 Valstybes imone "Laukystos zuvu veislynas"	1	987
171265176 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Radviliskio vanduo"	1	941
L730360 AB "Vasaknos" Civiliu padalinys Rokiskio r.	2	880
301507301 UAB "Kursenu vandenys"	1	876
172287193 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Raseiniu zuvininkyste"	1	836
253255950 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Akmenes vandenys"	1	811
154138664 UAB "Anyksciu vandenys"	1	788
173057512 Akcine bendrove "ROKISKIO SURIS"	2	780.7
177155847 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kintai"	2	772
185304657 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Vilkaviskio vandenys"	7	726.3
157531950 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Joniskio vandenys"	1	721
153622317 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Daugu zuvis"	2	720
191812820 Lietuvos valstybinio zuvivaisos ir zuvininkystes tyrimu centro Simno filialas	1	715.9
187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"	2	715
141011268 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPEDOS KARTONAS"	1	706
152812840 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birstono vandentiekis"	1	695
302560890 Pravieniskiu pataisos namai-atviroji kolonija	1	670
158275315 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Jurbarko vandenys"	1	657
172380181 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Raseiniu vandenys"	1	610

Ukio subjektas	Isleis- tuvas	Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis
255450080 VI "Ignalinos atominė elektrinė"	3	604
174264880 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Sakiu vandenys"	1	586
164702145 UAB "Kupiskio vandenys"	11	551
L860196 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Pabrade	1	538
286143880 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Akvilegija"	2	525
186107463 Akcinė bendrovė "Vilniaus paukštynas"	1	516
162559136 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Kelmės vanduo"	16	466
L860194 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Svencionėliai	1	444
L850137 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys", Salcininkai	1	438
184626819 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Varenos vandenys"	1	414.3
173820527 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Skuodo vandenys"	1	385
155461670 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Ignalinos vanduo"	1	380.6
186154228 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "ARVYDAI"	1	376
L410857 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Nemencinė	1	346
165695198 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Kazlu Rudos komunalininkas"	1	339.4
110648893 Akcinė bendrovė "Klaipėdos nafta"	1	333
281523640 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "TRAKU VANDENYS"	1	324
152767676 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Neringos vanduo"	2	311.4
176523470 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Silalės vandenys"	6	304
L450302 Lietuvos valstybinis žuvininkystės ir žuvininkystės tyrimų centras Ignalinos fil.	1	300
277160980 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Vilkyskių pieninė"	2	298
178230181 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Sirvintų vandenys"	1	291
L860195 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Svencionys	1	287
187920473 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Zarasų vandenys"	1	278
167922698 UAB "Pakruojo vandentiekis"	1	277
165717011 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Kalvarijos komunalininkas"	3	270
174264880 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Sakiu vandenys"	4	258
172287193 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Raseinių žuvininkystė"	2	250
162496878 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Silo Pavezupis"	2	237
185304657 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Vilkaviskio vandenys"	1	229.8
190464695 Lietuvos jūrų muziejus	1	208
140249252 Akcinė bendrovė "KLAIPĖDOS ENERGIJA"	5	206
171668992 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Rietavo komunalinis ukis"	1	204
Sum (excluding "Ignalinos atominė elektrinė" Isleistuvai 1)		228725.7

2.6.2. Manual digitising and analysis of data

A The monthly data of several (72) point sources were supplied as multiple files of various (pdf, doc, xls, odt) formats. These data was digitized (pdf files) and systematized (the rest) in uniform format.

A manual analysis was done to match the systematized information of monthly discharges from these 72 major Lithuanian water polluters avoiding a duplication of information in the annual database and monthly data.

As it was shown in Table 9 the database does not contain the information about every year and every pollutant “*Tersalas*”. Therefore the monthly data from the 72 major city water suppliers for the period 2006-2012, which includes larger amount of data is a valuable information.

The consequent steps were taken to avoid duplication of information in both data sets (digitized monthly data and the yearly database):

1. The records for the monthly data were manually found in the database (by manual lookup by name of the town, amount of “*Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis*” etc.). In order to avoid over- or underestimation of the amount of pollution in the years for which information was not given in the database, the manual analysis included:
 - 1.1. identification of change of the name/code of the pollution source;
 - 1.2. identification of point sources where concatenation with “*Isleituvas*” field gives multiple id for actually the same pollution source (not spatially distributed branch offices or affiliates of the main company).

Table 12. Example of manual identification of change of the name/code of the point source

Metai	Ukio subjektas	Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis	Atstumas iki ziociu	Platuma	Ilguma	Suggested id
1997	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	827	6	6084839	513577	302560890
1998	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	755	6	6084839	513577	302560890
1999	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	893	6	6084839	513577	302560890
2000	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	714	6	6084839	513577	302560890
2001	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	582	6	6084839	513577	302560890
2002	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	644	6	6084839	513577	302560890
2005	L490665Pravieniskiu 2-osios Sustiprinto rezimo pataisos darbu kolonijos komunalinio ukio tarnyba	496	6	6087164	514056	302560890
2006	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	513	6	6087164	514056	302560890
2007	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	564	6	6087164	514056	302560890
2008	9490417Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	508	6	6087164	514056	302560890

Metai	Ukio subjektas	Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis	Atstumas iki ziociu	Platuma	Ilguma	Suggested id
2009	188721467Pravieniskiu 2-ieji pataisos namai-atviroji kolonija	547	6	6087164	514056	302560890
2010	188721467Pravieniskiu 2-ieji pataisos namai-atviroji kolonija	612	6	6087164	514056	302560890
2011	302560890Pravieniskiu pataisos namai-atviroji kolonija	594	6	6087164	514056	302560890
2012	302560890Pravieniskiu pataisos namai-atviroji kolonija	670	6	6087164	514056	302560890

2. Situations of different complexity may arise during the manual identification process. For example:

2.1. The records show that according to the values in the column “*Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis*” both companies „162559136 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kelmes vanduo"” and „162433828 Kelmes valstybine vandens tiekimo imone” should be treated as the same waste-water pollution source (otherwise the amount of waste-water would be over-estimated). To remove this ambiguity an additional column „*Suggested id*” was added.

2.2. Similar situation were found for two companies „165695198 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kazlu Rudos komunalininkas"” and „165600524 Teritorine Kazlu Rudos butu ir komunalinio ukio valstybine imone”. The fact that each year only one value of „*Isleistuvas*” is given shows that „*Isleistuvas*” 3 and 5 actually are the same pollution source and pollution should not be multiplied for each of them for the years where their values are not given in the database.

2.3. Table 12 illustrates the situation for yet another pollution point source in Praveniskes and its changes in company name and coordinates.

It should be noted that besides analysis of company name, coordinates and the role of the „*Isleistuvas*” there are companies for which part (not all) of the records were excluded from the database to avoid duplication of the data with digitized information. For example in situation with company “185304657 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove Vilkaviskio vandenys” a *suggested id* = 185304657_2_ was added to exclude water supplier in Kybartai (for which the data is known according to monthly data) from the database.

2.6.3. Characterisation of the major wastewater pollution sources

The same approach (as in Section 2.6.2) was used for manual processing of information for those major wastewater pollution sources which does not have clear location according to concatenation of „*Ukio subjektas*”, „*Isleistuvas*”, and coordinates.

An example is „Klaipėdos keliai” records which were split into two spatially distant pollution sources.

The changes in id codes which are made for the 72 water plants and the major pollution sources are summarised in Table 13 and Table 14. The intermediate files containing systematized information about the monthly discharges are summarised in the following files:

- *WQ.dat* (monthly water discharge data);
- *QWQ.dat* (monthly water quality data);
- *WWTP_Stations* (list of biggest city water treatment plants with identifiers and names).

The full list of the major pollution sources (at least in one year „*Buitiniu, gamybiniu NT kiekis*” is above 200 000 m³/year) and their coordinates are listed in Table 15. This Table does not include the 72 water plants with the monthly data.

The manual coordinate lookup was done for the major pollution sources in Table 16 because the database contained no coordinates or conflicting coordinates. The determined coordinates are summarised in the same Table.

Table 13. „*Ukio subjektas*” that have been replaced with other id (to avoid over-estimation of pollution)

Initial "Ukio subjektas"	Action	Suggested id
301500997 UAB "Druskininku vandenys"	replaced with	152017984
162433828 Kelmės valstybinė vandens tiekimo imone	replaced with	162559136
9560102 Kretingos valstybinė vandens tiekimo imone, Padvariu km. vandenviete	replaced with	163994426
165600524 Teritorinė Kazlu Rudos butu ir komunalinio ukio valstybinė imone	replaced with	165695198
153005999 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Siluma ir vanduo"	replaced with	253255950
175606358 KURSENU KOMUNALINIO UKIO UZDAROJI AKCINE BENDROVE	replaced with	301507301
L910363 UAB "Kursenu vandenys" siauliu raj.	replaced with	301507301
188721467 Pravieniskiu 2-ieji pataisos namai-atviroji kolonija	replaced with	302560890
9490417 Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba	replaced with	302560890
L490665 Pravieniskiu 2-osios Sustiprinto rezimo pataisos darbu kolonijos komunalinio ukio tarnyba	replaced with	302560890
L340664 UAB "Anyksciu vandenys" Anyksciu miestas	replaced with	154138664_1_
9390089 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Suduvos vandenys" Vilkaviskio cechas	replaced with	185304657_1_
156629726 Specialios paskirties uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Ruklos komunalinis ir butu ukis"	replaced with	256564350_11
188677056 Salcininku rajono savivaldybės Salcininku seniunija	replaced with	L850137
184598184 Varenos valstybinė vandens tiekimo imone	replaced with	184626819

Table 14. ID codes that are set to avoid duplication of the digitized data. Pollution information in data base for these id codes are replaced by digitized information (monthly data).

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
120545849	6060938	574855	120545849 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "VILNIAUS VANDENYS"
132751369	6085778	489677	132751369 Uždaroji akcinė bendrovė "Kauno vandenys"

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
140089260_1 01	6108512	382724	140089260 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPEDOS VANDUO"
147104754	6175410	513288	147104754 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "AUKSTAITIJOS VANDENYS"
144133366	6205597	458978	144133366 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Siauliu vandenys"
149566841	6032731	503635	149566841 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Dzukijos vandenys"
151104226	6050276	458353	151104226 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Suduvos vandenys"
183633981	6115177	599697	183633981 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Utenos vandenys"
166486116	6243819	392491	166486116 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Mazeikiu vandenys"
182743364	6121701	546808	182743364 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "UKMERMES VANDENYS"
169236961	6215709	526743	169236961 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Pasvalio vandenys"
161186428	6125631	496716	161186428 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kedainiu vandenys"
256564350	6102416	524420	256564350 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Jonavos vandenys"
177059215	6136715	337309	177059215 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove " Silutes vandenys "
180153137	6209646	391176	180153137 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove " Telsiu vandenys "
110087517	6164006	661271	110087517 Valstybes imone "VISAGINO ENERGIJA"
179249836	6121852	389014	179249836 UAB "Taurages vandenys"
173741535	6203031	597049	173741535 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Rokiskio vandenys"
169845485	6195685	363215	169845485 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Plunges vandenys"
301507301	6207985	432336	301507301 UAB "Kursenu vandenys"
163994426	6196358	324946	163994426 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kretingos vandenys"
152017984	5990023	500583	152017984 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Druskininku vandentiekis"
154850665	6226554	543043	154850665 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birzu vandenys"
171265176	6189927	471700	171265176 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Radviliskio vanduo"
181613656_1 _	6073621	552506	181613656 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "ELEKTRENU KOMUNALINIS UKIS"
281523640	6059071	567619	281523640 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "TRAKU VANDENYS"
158834726	6081827	528610	158834726 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove " Kaisiadoriu vandenys "
152447391_1 _	6217912	317369	152447391 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "PALANGOS VANDENYS"
154138664_1 _	6153067	567581	154138664 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Anyksciu vandenys"
253255950	6235512	421151	253255950 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Akmenes vandenys"
152812840_1 _	6054133	503740	152812840 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birstono vandentiekis"
158275315	6104087	420485	158275315 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Jurbarko vandenys"
162559136	6165960	434152	162559136 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kelmes vanduo"
184626819	6009223	536235	184626819 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Varenos vandenys"
172380181	6135202	446158	172380181 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Raseiniu vandenys"
185304657_1 _	6058535	436567	9390089 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Suduvos vandenys" Vilkaviskio cechas

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
164702145	6189335	558922	164702145 UAB "Kupiskio vandenys"
302560890	6087164	514056	9490417 Praveniskiu SRPDK komunalinio ukio tarnyba
187920473_1 _	6180524	643774	9430011 UAB "Zarasu vandenys" Zarasu seniunija
167524751_1 _	6121675	588014	167524751 UAB "Moletu vanduo"
165695198	6068032	465592	165695198 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Kazlu Rudos komunalininkas"
173820527	6241550	345582	173820527 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Skuodo vandenys"
178230181	6102333	560031	178230181 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Sirvintu vandenys"
174264880	6090611	446030	174264880 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Sakiu vandenys"
L850137	6018428	590708	L850137 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys", Salcininkai
152767676	6133413	309554	152767676 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Neringos vanduo"
L410857	6081348	592535	L410857 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Nemencine
L860194_1_	6114161	626806	L860194 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Svencioneliai
L860196_1_	6093573	610688	L860196 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Pabrade
185304657_2 _	6057476	419339	185304657 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Vilkaviskio vandenys"
167922698	6208756	490034	167922698 UAB "Pakruojo vandentiekis"
155461670_2 _	6134571	637464	155461670 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Ignalinos vanduo"
176523470	6150932	383446	176523470 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Silales vandenys"
165178731_1 _	6011354	468903	165178731 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Veisiejis"
L860195_1_	6111212	637604	L860195 UAB "Vilniaus vandenys" Svencionys
165717011	6031559	451138	165717011 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Kalvarijos komunalininkas"
159702357_1 00	6088307	485439	Raudondvaris un Vilkija
171668992_1 _	6177566	370330	171668992 Uždaroji akcine bendrove "Rietavo komunalinis ukis"
256564350_1 1	6102416	524420	156629726 Specialios paskirties uždaroji akcine bendrove "Ruklos komunalinis ir butu ukis"
158847944	6074160	527916	158847944 Specialios paskirties uždaroji akcine bendrove "Ziezmariu vandenys ir siluma"
253255950_1 01	6235575	421039	Akmene
253255950_1 00	6229690	417367	Venta
174992914	6004535	564277	Eisiskes
L720187	6124164	467276	Ariogala
171265176_1 00	6179490	485619	Seduva
171328687_1 00	6167674	483640	Baisogala

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
152767676_1 00	6160357	318511	Juodkrante
177390158_1 00	6112748	366609	Pagegiai
174399390_1 00	6105349	433486	Gelgaudiskis
174264880_1 00	6090611	446030	174264880 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Sakiu vandenys"
165171377_1 00	5994995	480955	Veisiejai

Table 15. The suggested id, location and name of the major pollution sources

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
110004884	6215709	526743	110004884 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "VILLON"
110012450	6060389	572403	110012450 Akcine bendrove "GRIGISKES"
110648893	6177966	319594	110648893 Akcine bendrove "Klaipėdos nafta"
110870933	6069553	540781	110870933 Akcine bendrove LIETUVOS ELEKTRINE
111760831	6059352	579073	111760831 UAB "VILNIAUS ENERGIJA"
111950962	6085751	485204	111950962 Lietuvos žemės ūkio universitetas
132285793	6085810	495547	132285793 Akcines bendroves "Kauno energija" filialas Kauno elektrine
133606476	6084046	498467	133606476 Akcine bendrove "KAUNO POPIERIAUS FABRIKAS"
140080279	6179682	317950	140080279 Valstybine imone "Klaipėdos jūrų muziejus ir akvariumas"
140089260_1 00	6173746	320557. 1	140089260 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPĖDOS VANDUO"
140249252	6178962	320442. 7	140249252 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPĖDOS ENERGIJA"
140345884	6171958	321481. 3	140345884 Akcine bendrove VAKARU LAIVU GAMYKLA
140346114	6173927	320572	140346114 Laivu krovos akcine bendrove "KLAIPĖDOS SMELTE"
140346452	6105709	381734	140346452 Akcine bendrove "BALTIJOS" LAIVU STATYKLA
140346452_2 _	6177966	319594	140346452 Akcine bendrove "BALTIJOS" LAIVU STATYKLA
140356037	6178504	319277	140356037 Akcine bendrove "LAIVITE"
140357858_1 00	6179188	320907	140357858 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPĖDOS KELIAI"
140357858_1 01	6106490	382470	140357858 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPĖDOS KELIAI"
141011268	6173746	320566	141011268 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPĖDOS KARTONAS"
147024137	6178499	522433	147024137 Akcine bendrove "SEMA"
153012463	6229587	417558	153012463 Akcine bendrove " Ventos statybines medžiagos"

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
153622317	6028786	529406	153622317 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Daugu zuvis"
154111464	6155865	569188	154111464 Akcine bendrove "Anyksciu kvarcas"
154796712	6252303	547327	154796712 Akcine bendrove " Ausruvos agrofirma "
155307117	6249159	542763	155307117 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birzu bekonas"
155461670_1 _	6090309	605876	155461670 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Ignalinos vanduo"
155480076	6131446	675980	155480076 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birvetos tvenkiniai"
155516939	6136929	633936	155516939 Ignalinos valstybine zuvivaisos imone
156667399	6106022	520437	156667399 Akcine bendrove "Achema"
157531950	6235837	477120	157531950 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Joniskio vandenys"
158827685	6087129	514068	158827685 Pataisos reikalų departamento prie Lietuvos Respublikos vidaus reikalų ministerijos Pravieniskiu sustiprinto
158852934	6087968	538169	158852934 Valstybes imone "Laukystos zuvu veislynas"
158872246	6074100	515208	158872246 Akcines bendroves "LIETUVOS ENERGIJA" filialas KRUONIO HAE
158889861	6070508	539795	158889861 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Bartzuve"
158977521	6087164	514068	158977521 Valstybes imone prie Pravieniskiu 2-uju pataisos namu
161110455	6126761	499895	161110455 Akcine bendrove "LIFOSA"
161220492	6127495	509565	161220492 Lietuvos medziotoju ir zveju draugijos Kapliu zuvu veislynas
161634276	6126474	508896	161634276 UAB "KAPLIU ZUVYS"
162496878	6182699	427869	162496878 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Silo Pavezupis"
164201999	6197765	325786	164201999 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kretingos zverininkystes ukis"
164702526	6189292	558939	164702526 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kupiskio komunalininkas"
164771134	6181588	554613	164771134 Uzdarosios akcines bendroves "Salnaiciu agraras" Kupiskio filialas "Akmenlita"
165605642	6064463	465909	165605642 Kazlu Rudos valstybinis zvininkystes ukis
165723594	6064867	449416	165723594 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "KARPIS"
165774418	6063987	455249	165774418 Specialios paskirties akcines bendroves "Stumbras" Antanavo gamykla
166451720	6248377	384931	166451720 Akcine bendrove "MAZEIKIU NAFTA"
167524751_2 _	6124978	595749	167524751 UAB "Moletu vanduo"
167900844	6209702	496841	167900844 Akcine bendrove "Dolomitas"
168411016	6151521	538211	168411016 Akcines bendroves "PANEVEZIO PIENAS" Raguvos suriu gamykla
168586873	6168837	508453	168586873 AKCINE BENDROVE "KREKENAVOS AGROFIRMA"
170606870	6042181	493446	170606870 Specialios paskirties akcines bendroves "Stumbras"

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
			Balbieriskio gamykla
170639781	6055357	497086	170639781 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Prienu vandenys"
170685259	6061366	483202	170685259 Silavoto valstybine zuvu selekcines veislininkystes imone
170694265	6070005	495064	170694265 Akcine bendrove "Islauzo zuvis"
172287193_100	6133458	433324	172287193 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Raseiniu zuvininkyste"
172287193_101	6104880	381707	172287193 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Raseiniu zuvininkyste"
173045168	6202870	611047	173045168 Akcines bendroves "Vilniaus degtine" Obeliu spirito gamykla
173057512	6160333	585426	173057512 Akcine bendrove "ROKISKIO SURIS"
173106475	6190050	605453	173106475 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Auksinis karpis"
173109051	6227276	539609	173109051 Akcine bendrove "Juodupes Nemunas"
174901124	6015359	587504	174901124 UAB "Salcininku zuvininkystes ukis"
175606739	6207985	432336	175606739 Pavenciu valstybinis cukraus fabrikas
175749153	6207985	432336	175749153 Akcine bendrove "PAVENCIU CUKRUS"
177022811	6137236	341174	177022811 Specialios paskirties akcines bendroves "Stumbras" Silutes gamykla
177155847	6143878	328145	177155847 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Kintai"
180195588	6219254	380914	180195588 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Zemaitijos zuvis"
180255117	6215035	398668	180255117 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Eigirdziu agrofirma"
181101766_1_	6071901	552155	181101766 Akcines bendroves "LIETUVOS ENERGIJA" filialas LIETUVOS ELEKTRINE
181101766_2_	6071096	541302	181101766 Akcines bendroves "LIETUVOS ENERGIJA" filialas LIETUVOS ELEKTRINE
181102291	6073018	550915	181102291 Vievio valstybinis paukstynas
181254299	6060389	572403	181254299 UZDAROJI AKCINE BENDROVE "GRIGISKIU KOMUNALINIS UKIS"
181257637	6076288	535803	181257637 Akcine bendrove Vievio paukstynas
181382772_1_	6054190	560457	181382772 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "LENTVARIO KOMUNALINIS UKIS"
184536389	5977727	519462	184536389 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "KABELIU ZUVIS"
184626819	6008933	536235	184626819 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Varenos vandenys"
186063262	6053566	589053	186063262 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Nemezio komunalininkas"
186107463	6050275	585042	186107463 Akcine bendrove "Vilniaus paukstynas"
186154228	6076732	599315	186154228 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "ARVYDAI"
187854895_1_	6169012	626366	187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"
187854895_2_	6177964	615647	187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"
187854895_3_	6176299	609808	187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
187854895_4 _	6177321	615533	187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"
188630359	6181122	646633	188630359 Zarasu rajono savivaldybes administracijos Zarasu miesto seniunija
188633088	6147300	635653	188633088 Ignalinos rajono savivaldybes administracijos Kazitiskio seniunija
190464695	6180011	317669	190464695 Lietuvos juru muziejus
191812788	6108264	623853	191812788 Lietuvos valstybinio zuvivaiss ir zuvininkystes tyrimu centro Zeimenos filialas
191812820	6027029	477903	191812820 Lietuvos valstybinio zuvivaiss ir zuvininkystes tyrimu centro Simno filialas
191813018	6061366	484559	191813018 Lietuvos valstybinio zuvivaiss ir zuvininkystes tyrimu centro Silavoto filialas
221984960	6070716	585801	221984960 Akcine bendrove "NAUJIEJI VERKIAI"
240042030	6178962	320443	240042030 Klaipedos valstybine prekybos imone
253663090	6008933	536235	253663090 UAB " Skirnuva "
255450080	6166707	662718	255450080 Valstybes imone "Ignalinos atominė elektrinė"
267548080	6103281	610047	267548080 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "ARMOLE"
267548080_7 _	6025901	548326	267548080 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "ARMOLE"
274962690	6036817	569401	274962690 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "JUODASIS GANDRAS"
275746610	6191091	445515	275746610 UZDAROJI AKCINE BENDROVE "SVENTJONIS"
277160980	6110745	381161	277160980 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Vilkyskiu pienine"
286143880_1 _	6063201	593541	286143880 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Akvilegija"
286143880_2 _	6058934	605673	286143880 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Akvilegija"
300515042	6137301	341139	300515042 AB "Biofuture"
301206814	6190010	605433	301206814 UAB "Civyliau zuvys"
302648707	6069553	540781	302648707 Lietuvos energija, AB
9010674	6059541	579168	9010674 UAB "Vilniaus energija" Termofikacine elektrine NR.2
9190986	6083777	499264	9190986 AB "Kauno energija" fil. Kauno elektrine, Petrasuonu elektrine
9210116	6178962	320443	9210116 KLaipedos silumos tinklai, elektrine
9360087	6237618	550743	9360087 Birzu akcines pieno bendroves, Medeiku cechas
9410820	6091816	543295	9410820 Anovilio mokomasis punktas
L131322	6070736	585791	L131322 AB "Grigiskes" Popieriaus gamybos cechas N. Verkiai
L290181	6202322	458978	L290181 AB "Kausta" Siauliu m.
L380251	6027374	477102	L380251 Zuvininkystes tarnybos prie Lietuvos Respublikos Zemes ukio ministerijos zuvivaiss skyriaus Simno poskyris
L410831	6090070	578360	L410831 Istekliu atkurimo skyriaus Anovilio metodinis

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
			punktas
L450302	6136939	633936	L450302 Lietuvos valstybinis zuvivaisos ir zuvininkystes tyrimu centras Ignalinos fil.
L690350	6061715	485006	L690350 Zuvininkystes tarnybos prie Lietuvos Respublikos Zemes ukio ministerijos Vidaus vandenu ir akvakulturos skyria
L730360	6187868	610594	L730360 AB "Vasaknos" Civiliu padalinys Rokiskio r.
L860203	6104123	619042	L860203 LVZZTC Zeimenos lasisiniu zuvu veislynas, Svencioniu r.

Table 16. Major pollution sources for which a manual coordinate lookup was performed.

Suggested id	Platuma	Ilguma	Name
161634276_1_	6126474	508896	161634276 UAB "KAPLIU ZUVYS"
173106475	6190050	605453	173106475 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Auksinis karpis"
188633088	6147300	635653	188633088 Ignalinos rajono savivaldybes administracijos Kazitiskio seniunija
301206814	6190010	605433	301206814 UAB "Civyliau zuvys"
L410831	6090070	578360	L410831 Istekliu atkurimo skyriaus Anovilio metodinis punktas

2.6.4. Data preprocessing for model input

The point source data were preprocessed for the automated usage in the generation of the water quality modeling system.

1. The large pollution sources with monthly discharge values ("large polluters" from the yearly point source database identified in Section 3.6.1 and all pollutions sources with monthly pollution data) were processed as follows:
 - a. The missing pollution components were filled in this data using the methodics of AAPC (2008), Table 1.2.2. Namely, if missing then (1) total nitrogen was calculated form BOD₇, (2) total phosphorus was calculated form BOD₇, (3) the inorganic nitrogen forms were calculated form total nitrogen.
 - b. The gaps shorter as 3 months in monthly values were filled by interpolation.
 - c. The yearly values were filled in the intermediate data (p.1f below) filling with data all months of the year for which data is available in the database.
 - d. The monthly values (p.1b above) were filled in the intermediate data.
 - e. The rest of the intermediate data was filled with the average values.
 - f. Thus, the full (all monthly values, all substances) intermediate dataset was formed. It included 2 files:
 - *Monthly.sta* file containing: *pointsourceID*, *Name*, *X*, *Y*, *sourceID* (*pointsourceID* – point source integer ID, *Name* - point source name, *X,Y* - point source coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates it to the original data).
 - *Monthly.txt* contains monthly point source values. Columns of this file are:
 - *ID* – the point source integer ID as defined by *.sta* file.
 - *DATE* – date of point source in *yyyy.mm.dd* format. Day for monthly point sources is always 15.

- *SS, BOD7, NO3, NO2, NH4, NTOT, PO4, PTOT, NORG, PORG* are the loads of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in g/day.
 - *Discharge* – flow of point source in m³/day
 - *rho_SS, rho_BOD7, rho_NO3, rho_NO2, rho_NH4, rho_NTOT, rho_PO4, rho_PTOT, rho_NORG, rho_PORG* are the concentrations of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in mg/l
 - *year, month* are the calendar year and month.
2. The rest of the pollution point sources were prepared as the time series of yearly pollution values.
- a. The large point sources (p.1) were excluded from the xls database.
 - b. The Excel file was converted to MS Access file *small_pointsources.mdb* of the following field structure:
 - i. *ID* (integer) - unique row id;
 - ii. *year* (integer) – year of pointsource loading;
 - iii. *name* (text) - full name of point source;
 - iv. *type* (integer) – type of point source;
 - v. *nutrient* (text) – type of substance (any one of *SS, BOD7, NO3, NO2, NH4, NTOT, PO4, PTOT*);
 - vi. *concentration* (double) – value of concentration of corresponding substance in mg/l;
 - vii. *discharge* (double) – value of discharge of pointsource in 1000 m³/year;
 - viii. *X* (double) – x coordinate of point source;
 - ix. *Y* (double) – y coordinate of point source;
 - c. The missing substances (similar to above p.1a) were filled in the data during the automated generation of the water quality modelling system.
 - d. The missing time gaps in file *small_pointsources.mdb* (similar to above pp. 1b-e) were not filled.

2.7. Drainage data (3.1.6)

DATA. TOR (p.3.1.6.1) requests that for the update (inclusion) of the drainage data in the SWAT model the spatial dataset of land reclamation conditions and wetness of the territory of Lithuania on 1:10 000 scale (Mel_DR10LT) should be used. Specification of this database is given in the document „*ŽEMIŲ MELIORACINĖS BŪKLĖS, UŽMIRKIMO, GIS DUOMENŲ RENGIMO IR ATNAUJINIMO PAGAL MELIORUOTOS ŽEMĖS IR STATINIŲ BŪKLĖS ĮVERTINIMO 2006 M. DUOMENIS SPECIFIKACIJA*“.

The development of the methodics and a tool for preparation of the model parameters is requested in TOR 3.1.6.2. The methodics is described below while the tool is a part of the script system for the automatic generation of the water quality modeling system (see Chapter 3).

1. Layer *melior_p_LKS94* was used directly, i.e. without data preprocessing. This layer contains polygon data of meliorated territories and field attributes including type of the drainage, and its condition. The fields which are relevant for the drainage conditions are:

- a. *TIPAS* – code of the type of drainage system (D – drained by drains, G – drained by ditches, N – not drained). Only areas drained by drains (*Tipas=D*) were considered.
- b. *BUKLE* – code of the status of drainage system (G – good, B – bad, N – not available/written off). The status of drainage system is neglected by methodics.
2. The melioration polygon feature (*MEL_DR10LT.gdb/melior_dissolved*) was prepared. The following parameter values were assigned to the polygons of the drained territories according to SWAT expert suggestion:
 1. *DDRAIN=1100* is a depth in mm to subsurface drains.
 2. *TDRAIN=24* is a base time in hours to drain a soil to the field capacity.
 3. *GDRAIN=24* is a drain tile lag in hours.
3. We assume that a drainage of particular HRU is switched on (activated) is the drained area of this HRU exceeds 5%.

2.8. Riverbed data (3.1.7)

Data. ToR (pp. 3.1.7.1 and 3.1.7.3) requires that data obtained from the Project “Preparation of Flood hazard and flood risk maps for the Nemunas, Venta, Lielupe and Daugava river basin districts” (further referred as FLOOD project), HNIT & METRUM (2014) have to be used for updating of the riverbed data where applicable.

Data from FLOOD project (contained in *River_Beds.gdb*) was used for calculating width, depth and slope of the rivers, i.e. reaches of SWAT model in the rivers included in the FLOOD project (Fig. 21). The reaches of rivers were considered as included in the FLOOD project if 20% of their length in the respective subbasin (Section 2.1.3) were covered by the FLOOD project data.

The respective parameters were calculated as follows:

1. Manning coefficient:

- a. The model data files from FLOOD project were used for all modelled areas (MIKE 11 .nwk and .hd11 files), which contains the geometry and Manning coefficient values for the river stretches included in the MIKE 11 hydraulic model, see the river network in Fig. 21. The average Manning coefficient for the reach of respective subbasin was assigned.
- b. The Manning coefficient values 0.03 was used for the river reaches which are not covered by the FLOOD project.

Fig. 21. River network covered with the data from FLOOD model.

2. **Slope** of the river segments was calculated from the DEM (*dem_5m.aux* prepared in Section 2.4) dividing the elevation difference between the start and end nodes of the river segment by its length. The slope was limited $10^{-4} < s < 0.1$.
3. Data from GDR geodatabase (“Lietuvos Respublikos teritorijos M1:10000 georeferencinių erdvinių duomenų rinkinio (GDR10LT)”) was used for updating river **width**, layer “*PLOTAP*”. The polygons with attribute “*GKODAS=hd...*” were selected and intersected with the catchment polygons (Section 2.1.3). The main reach was determined by spatial join of this intersection with the river segment lines. The width was calculated as $w = 2 * A / P$ (A is area and P is perimeter of the polygon). If this method failed then the width was calculated from the catchment area as $w = -1.672673E-08 A^2 + 1.673244E-03 A + 5.133688$ here A is catchment area in ha (maximum value 40000 ha), and w is river width in m.
4. The depth of rivers was calculated as follows:
 - a. For the rivers covered by FLOOD project the depth grid from the FLOOD project was intersected with the catchment polygon. The statistical depth grid parameters (average value *Ave(dgrid)*, standard deviation *Std(dgrid)*) were calculated. The depth of the river was calculated as $d = Ave(d) + Std(dgrid)$.
 - b. For the rivers not covered by the FLOOD project the depth was calculated as $d = -6.638265E-10 A^2 + 5.140400E-05 A + 0.3613521$

here A is catchment area in ha (maximum value 40000 ha), and d is river depth in m.

Requirement to use the GIS data from river, lake and pond cadastre of the territory of the Republic of Lithuania (UETK) is set in p.3.1.7.2 of ToR. It is fulfilled in creation of the river network used for SWAT model in Section 2.1.

2.9. Groundwater data (3.1.8)

Data. The results from the project “Basin Management Plan for the groundwater of the Nemunas Basin District and development and integration into the overall management plan” and “Lielupė, Venta, and Daugava river basin districts management plans” AAA (2010a, b) are required to be used for updating SWAT groundwater parameters according to p.3.1.8.1 of ToR.

Two SWAT parameters were updated from these reports while others imported to the model from the existing water quality modeling system PAIC & ELLE (2012).

- *SHALLST_N* – Initial concentration of nitrates in the shallow aquifer for different groups of land use classes (agricultural, pastures, forests and urban). We used median values from Table 1.1.4. from the report AAA (2010a) “Projekto veiklų rezultatai, III dalis, požeminio vandens būklė ir jo sąveika su paviršinio vandens telkiniais”, see Table 17.
- *GWSOLP* – Concentration of soluble phosphorus in groundwater contribution to streamflow from subbasin for different groups of land use classes (agricultural, pastures, forests and urban). We used median values from Table 1.1.3. from the same report, see Table 17.

Table 17. Nitrate and phosphate concentration in the groundwater depending on the group of land use classes.

No.	Land use	Reference in AAA (2010a)	N-NO ₃ , mg/l	P-PO ₄ , mg/l
1	Agricultural	Dirbami laukai (molingi dariniai)	2.50	0.02
2	Pastures	Plevos, sodai	1.15	0.05
3	Forests	Miškai	1.12	0.06
4	Urban	Urbanizuotas teritorijos, ūkio subj.	3.80	0.04

The updating of *ALPHA_BF* parameter by using base flow filtering program is required in p. 3.1.8.2 of ToR.

Time series of discharge Q in hydrometric stations of Lithuania and substance concentrations in water quality observation stations of Lithuania compiled in PAIC & ELLE (2012) were updated by the data supplied by the Client for the missing years. This includes the extension of time series for inflow from Belarus (respectively, Neris-Buividžiai and Nemunas-Druskininkai), years 1994-1996, 2011-2012 required in TOR 3.1.16.4.

These time series of discharge Q may be directly used by the baseflow filtering program. The use of the program has been postponed to the calibration step of the project and default values of *ALPHA_BF* parameter were set in the SWAT model as this is a parameter which may vary depending on the calibration strategy implemented.

2.10. Water extraction data (3.1.10)

Data of water extraction from the period 1997-2012 has to be used for the update of Model according to p.3.1.10.1 of ToR. Water consumer database (*1997-2011vanduo.xlsx* and *2012vanduo.xlsx*) was supplied by the Client.

The consideration of only major consumers which have an effect on the water balance are required by p.3.1.10.2 of ToR. We assessed that this criteria is fulfilled for water users which extract a water from the surface waters with the consumption amount above 0.1 m³/s. Such water users (listed in Table 18) has the following characteristics:

- They account for 98.5 % of the water extraction from surface waters.
- The water extraction below threshold <0.1 m³/s may be assumed as non influencing the water balance for reaches (subbasins) of the water quality modelling system.
- The establishment of relation between all such water users with point pollution sources was possible. This is important because the water extraction database does not contain the coordinates of the water extraction.

Table 18. Major water consumers (consumption above 0.1 m³/s).

110870933 Akcine bendrove LIETUVOS ELEKTRINE
111760831 UAB "VILNIAUS ENERGIJA"
140089260 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPEDOS VANDUO"
155480076 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Birvetos tvėnkiniai"
156667399 Akcine bendrove "Achema"
158872246 Akcines bendroves "LIETUVOS ENERGIJA" filialas KRUONIO HAE
158889861 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Bartzuve"
161110455 Akcine bendrove "LIFOSA"
162496878 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Silo Pavezupis"
166451720 AB "ORLEN Lietuva"
174901124 UAB "Salcininku zuvininkystes ukis"
184536389 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "KABELIU ZUVIS"
187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"
191812788 Lietuvos valstybinio zuvivaisos ir zuvininkystes tyrimu centro Zeimenos filialas
191812820 Lietuvos valstybinio zuvivaisos ir zuvininkystes tyrimu centro Simno filialas
255450080 Valstybes imone "Ignalinos atomine elektrine"
274962690 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "JUODASIS GANDRAS"
286143880 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Akvilegija"
9010674 UAB "Vilniaus energija" Termofikacine elektrine NR.2

It has been verified that the code of water consumer gives a possibility to link the consumer database with the waste water point source pollution database (Section 2.6) thus – obtaining the coordinates of the water extraction places.

The linking of tables identified few exceptions and problems with the water consumers listed in Table 19. This table also provides the solution adopted for handling respective exceptions. We noted also that water consumption and waste water amount in the most situations are not equal.

Table 19. Exceptions for the code for linking the consumer data base with the waste water database.

Consumer name	Exception or problem	Action
188663989 Plunges rajono savivaldybes taryba	Not found in the waste water pollution database (further referred as db)	Consumer not included
110870933 Akcine bendrove LIETUVOS ELEKTRINE	No data for the year 2010 in the waste water db	Problem does not effect water usage
140089260 Akcine bendrove "KLAIPEDOS VANDUO"	Code 140089260_101 in the waste water db	No action
158872246 Akcines bendroves "LIETUVOS ENERGIJA" filialas KRUONIO HAE	No data for the years 1997, 2010, 2011	Gap left in water consumption data
166486116 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Mazeikiu vandenys"	No data for the year 1997	Gap left in water consumption data
174901124 UAB "Salcininku zuvininkystes ukis"	No data for the year 1997	Gap left in water consumption data
187854895 Akcine bendrove "Vasaknos"	Multiple codes 187854895_1_, 187854895_2_, 187854895_3_, 187854895_4_ in point source db	Consumer linked to arbitrary point source code
255450080 VI "Ignalinos atomine elektrine"	No data for the year 2011	Gap left in water consumption data
286143880 Uzdaroji akcine bendrove "Akvilegija"	Different codes in point source db: 286143880_1_ - for years 1997, 1998, 1999; 286143880_1_, 286143880_2_ - for years 2010, 2011	Consumer linked to arbitrary point source code
302648707 Lietuvos energija, AB	Incredibly large difference in water amount between both databases	No action

The water user data was processed for further use in automated preparation of the water quality modeling system. Two text files were created:

1. *WaterUseMonthly.sta* contains columns: *waterUserID*, *Name*, *X*, *Y*, *sourceID* (*waterUserID* – water user integer ID, *Name* – water user name, *x,y* – water user coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates water user to point source).
2. *WaterUseMonthly.txt* contains the water usage values. Columns of this file contain *ID* (water user integer ID as defined in *sta* file), *DATE* (date of point source) and *WaterUse* (water usage in m³/day).

The gaps of the original water consumption database were not filled.

2.11. Crop fertilisation data (3.1.11)

ToR (3.1.11.1) requests that crop fertilisation data is updated using the latest data (data collected in agrostacionaries, crop reporting, the Department of Statistics and other publicly available sources).

The approach of calculating (modeling) the applied fertilisation amount instead of setting the applied fertiliser amount according to external data was adopted and agreed with the Client.

Section 2.11.1 summarises the data used for fertilisation modeling. Section 2.11.2 provides a model (method) for fertilisation calculation. Section 2.11.3 provides a method for setting fertilisation practise.

2.11.1. Input data

The following data and definitions were used to evaluate required amount of mineral fertiliser depending on the crop, location (region of Lithuania) and soil.

1. **Soil data** – most parameters were acquired from the soil data prepared in Chapter 2.2 according to p.3.1.1 of ToR. The following parameters are used for fertiliser amount assessment:
 - a. Aggregated soil name. Identified in soil data as *AGR_IBY-ID*;
 - b. Content of clay particles, %. Identified in soil data as *SOL_CLAYI*;
 - c. Organic carbon content, %. This parameter is used for humus content evaluation. Identified in soil data as *SOL_CBN*;
 - d. Soil phosphorus content, mg/kg. Identified in soil data as *SOL_SOLP1*;
 - e. Soil acidity, Ph. This parameter was provided by the soil expert in addition to parameters from soil data. It is identified in soil data as *SOL_PHI*.
2. **Plant data** – data was gathered by agricultural expert and preprocessed according to methodology described in ToR (3.1.11.2):
 - a. SWAT ID – SWAT land use identifiers corresponding to agricultural plants.
 - b. Calculation method – 2 methods were used for fertiliser amount assessment; they are described in Section 2.11.2.
 - c. Standard yield, t/ha – plant standard yield, provided only for those crops for what the 1st calculation method was used. In cases when it is missing the 2nd method was used and also it was assumed that a standard yield is equal to the planned yield. The summary of standard yield is given in Table 20.

Table 20. Fertilisation calculation method, standard yield and demands of nitrogen and phosphorus.

SWAT ID	Name	Fertilisation method	Standard yield, t/ha	N Demand, kg/ha	P Demand, kg/ha
AGRL	Agricultural land	2		90	15
ALFA	Perennial legumes	1	6	0	12.9
BARL	Summer barley	1	4.4	90	17.2
BARR	Fallow			170	40
BROS	Natural meadows	2		0	0
BWHT	Buckwheat	2		37	15
CANA	Winter rape	2		170	27
CANP	Annual grasses	2		60	19
CELR	Caraway	2		60	17

SWAT ID	Name	Fertilisation method	Standard yield, t/ha	N Demand, kg/ha	P Demand, kg/ha
CLVR	Fallow (sideracinis)			0	0
CORN	Corn	2		140	37
CRRT	Vegetables	2		105	38
CSIL	Corn for silage	2		140	37
GRBN	Beans/ annual legumes	2		40	23
LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops	2		40	21
LUPN	Lupine	2		40	22
OATS	Oats	1	3.5	70	17.2
ORCD	Orchards	2		0	0
PEAS	Peas	2		40	23
POTA	Potatoes	1	26	120	25.8
RYE	Rye	1	4.4	95	19.35
SCAN	Summer rape	1	2	90	25.8
SGBT	Sugar beet	1	40	125	25.8
SOYB	Soy	2		40	29
STBR	Summer barley (straw fields)	2		90	17.2
STCN	Summer rape (straw fields)	2		90	25.8
STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye	2		75	28
STRY	Rye (straw fields)	2		95	19.35
STTR	Winter triticale (straw fields)	2		100	21.5
STWH	Summer wheat (straw fields)	2		95	15.05
STWW	Winter wheat (straw fields)	2		110	25.8
SWHT	Summer wheat	1	4.4	95	15.05
VTCH	Vetch	2		40	22
WBAR	Winter barley	2		155	18
WPAS	Perennial pastures	1	6.8	120	15.05
WTRC	Winter triticale	1	4.5	100	21.5
WWHT	Winter wheat	1	4.8	110	25.8

- d. Standard nitrogen demand, kg/ha – standard nitrogen demand for specific plant. It corresponds to standard yield or in cases when the standard yield is not provided to a planned yield.
- e. Standard phosphorus demand, kg/ha – standard phosphorus demand for specific plant. It corresponds to standard yield or in cases when standard yield is not provided to a planned yield.

- f. Nitrogen amount in soil after preplant of particular plant – in cases where a preplant is not known, it was assumed that this value is 0;
 - g. Phosphorus amount in soil after preplant of particular plant - in cases where a preplant is not known, it was assumed that this value is 0.
3. **Crop yield** data was prepared by the agricultural expert:
- a. Plant ID – plant codes. Multiple crops may correspond to each of SWAT crop IDs.
 - b. Planned Yield, t/ha – data of plant yield depends on both plant and municipality (region of Lithuania). To evaluate the yield for each municipality and each plant the data from Department of Statistics was used. In this Statistical data yield was provided for multiple plants that corresponds to the same SWAT code. Using information about the yield of each agricultural plant, for each SWAT code the data of the corresponding plant with the largest area was used. Historical yields were assessed for years 2001-2012. Average of the obtained yields throughout this period was assumed as planned yield for particular plant and region.
4. **Livestock data**
- a. Region ID – regions from *counties2004.shp* were used.
 - b. Agricultural Area, ha – size of agricultural area in each county was acquired from land use data (Section 2.5, ToR 3.1.4).
 - c. Livestock amount, units – historical data of livestock amount per county from Department of Statistics was used. Average amount of livestock for each county was used.

Manure uptake – was assumed to be 30%.

2.11.2.Methodics for calculation of fertilisation

Two methods (models) were proposed for assessment of the optimal mineral fertilisation norm. This approach is in line with ToR (3.1.11.2) requesting that data gaps on crop fertilisation should be filled by using programs used in the preparation of fertilisation plans used by agronomists. The methods were prepared in co-operation with the agricultural expert.

First of these two methodologies should be used in case of crops where standard yield (t/ha) is known, while second in the cases where it is not known.

Method 1

The calculation of the fertiliser amount was done in the following steps:

1. Difference between the standard and the planned yield, t/ha was calculated as:

$$DifY = PY - StY$$

Here *DifY* is difference between the standard and the planned yield, t/ha;

PY – planned yield of the crop, t/ha;

StY – standard yield, t/ha.

2. Fertiliser demand for the planned yield, kg/ha was calculated as:

$$FD_{N,P} = StN_{N,P} + DifY * D_{N,P}$$

Here $FD_{P_{2O_5}} = FD_P/0.423$;

$FD_{N,P,P_{2O_5}}$ – fertiliser demand for the planned yield, kg/ha (either Nitrogen or Phosphorus or Phosphorus pentoxide);

$StN_{N,P}$ – standard fertiliser norm for the particular crop, kg/ha. This data was provided for all SWAT crops/crop groups that require mineral fertilisers;

$DifY$ - difference between the standard and the planned yield, t/ha;

$D_{N,P}$ – fertiliser demand for kg/t of the yield which can be calculated as

$$D_{N,P} = FD_{N,P} / StY.$$

3. Granulometric composition. The fertiliser demand was corrected according to the soil granulometric composition, see Table 21.

Table 21. Correction of fertilisation norm according to the granulometric composition of the soil.

Granulometric composition	Content of clay particles smaller than 0,01 mm, %	Coefficient for correction of the fertiliser norm	
		k_{1N}	$k_{1P_{2O_5}}$
Sand	5-10	1,1	1
Sandy loam	10,1-20	1	1
Loam	20,1-40	0,95	1
Clay	40,1-65	0,9	1
Peatland	-	0,6	1,1

4. Humus, %. The fertiliser demand was corrected according to the soil humus content, see Table 22 for correction of nitrogen demand. Phosphorus demand was not corrected ($k_{2P_{2O_5}} = 1$). The humus content in Table 22 was calculated by the following formula:

$$HC = C_{org} * 1.724, \text{ here } HC - \text{humus content, \% and } C_{org} - \text{organic carbon content, \%}.$$

5. Phosphorus content of the soil, mg/kg. The fertiliser demand was corrected according to the soil phosphorus content, see Table 23. Nitrogen demand was not corrected ($k_{3N} = 1$).

6. Soil acidity, pH. The fertiliser demand was corrected according to soil acidity, see Table 24.

Table 22. Soil classification according to humus content and correction of nitrogen norms.

Soil classification according to humus content	Humus content, %		Coefficient for correction of nitrogen norm
	Sand	Sandy loam, loam, clay	k_{2N}
Very low humus content	<0.5	<1	1.2
Low humus content	0.6-1.5	1.1-2	1.1
Medium humus content	1.5-2.5	2.1-3	1
High humus content	2.6-3.5	3.1-4	0.9
Very high humus content	>3.5	>4	0.8

Table 23. Soil classification according to phosphorus and potassium content and correction of fertilisation norms

Soil phosphorus and potassium content	Coefficients for correction of fertiliser norms	
	k _{3P₂O₅}	
Very low (<50 mg/kg)	1,5	
Low (51-100 mg/kg)	1,2	
Medium (101-150 mg/kg)	1	
High (151-200 mg/kg)	0,7	
Very high (>201 mg/kg)	0,3	

Table
24.
Soil
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ding to acidity and correction of fertiliser norms.

Soil acidity	pH _{KCl}	Coefficients for correction of fertiliser norm	
		k _{4N}	k _{4P₂O₅}
Very acid	<5,0	1,1	1,1
Acid	5,1-5,5	1,1	1,1
Slightly acid	5,6-6,0	1,05	1,05
Slightly neutral	6,1-6,5	1	1
Nearly neutral	6,6-6,9	1	1
Neutral and alkaline	>7	0,95	0,95

7. Preplant. The fertiliser demand was corrected according to preplant, expressing it as k_{5N} , $k_{5P_{2O_5}}$ – soil nutrient content after the preplant, kg/ha, see Table 25.

8. Organic fertiliser. The fertiliser demand was corrected according to a nutrient amount introduced with manure, kg/ha according to formulae:

$$K_{6N, P_{2O_5}} = 0.3 * LC * Pr_{N, P_{2O_5}} / A$$

Here LC – livestock count, number of livestock units in a community.

$Pr_{N, P_{2O_5}}$ – production of nitrogen or P_{2O_5} from one livestock unit per year (100 kg nitrogen and 40,2 kg of P_{2O_5});

A – area of agricultural land (demanding fertilisation) within the community, ha.

Table 15. Soil nutrient content after preplant, kg/ha.

SWAT ID	Preplant N	Preplant P	SWAT ID	Preplant N	Preplant P
AGRL	0	0	POTA	10	0
ALFA	25	5	RYE	0	0
BARL	0	0	SCAN	10	0
BARR	0	0	SGBT	20	10
BROS	0	0	SOYB	0	0
BWHT	0	0	STBR	0	0
CANA	10	0	STCN	10	0
CANP	0	0	STRC	0	0
CELR	0	0	STRY	0	0
CLVR	0	0	STTR	0	0
CORN	0	0	STWH	0	0
CRRT	10	0	STWW	0	0

CSIL	0	0	SWHT	0	0
GRBN	17	0	VTCH	0	0
LMIX	0	0	WBAR	0	0
LUPN	0	0	WPAS	0	0
OATS	0	0	WTRC	0	0
ORCD	0	0	WWHT	0	0
PEAS	17	0			

9. Finally a demand of mineral fertiliser for the planned yield, kg/ha was calculated as
 $DMF_N = (FD_N(k1_N + k2_N + k3_N + k4_N - 3) - k5_N - k6_N) * RA$

$$DMF_P = (FD_{P2O5}(k1_{P2O5} + k2_{P2O5} + k3_{P2O5} + k4_{P2O5} - 3) - k5_{P2O5} - k6_{P2O5}) * 0.423 * RA$$

In these formula $DMF_{N,P}$ – demand of mineral fertiliser, kg/ha, and RA – regional adjustment.

Application of chemical fertilisers in the Southern and South-eastern part of Lithuania is lower than in the rest of the country. Based on the estimates of agronomists, farmers there use no more than 2/3 of the optimal norm. Considering this, estimated optimal norm has to be multiplied by $RA=0,67$ for the Žeimena, Merkys, Nemunas upper-course, Neris small tributaries and Šventoji basins. For the rest of the country coefficient $RA = 1$ is used.

Method 2

The simplified calculation of the fertiliser demand was done as:

$$DMF_N = (StN_N - 0.3 * LC * Pr_N / A) * RA$$

$$DMF_P = (StN_{P2O5} / 0.423 - 0.3 * LC * Pr_{P2O5} / A) * 0.423 * RA$$

In these formula:

Fig. 22. Distribution of calculated nitrogen fertilization demand.

Fig. 23. Distribution of calculated phosphorus fertilization demand.

$DMF_{N,P}$ – demand of mineral fertiliser, kg/ha.

$StN_{N,P}$ – standard fertiliser norm for the particular crop, kg/ha.

LC – livestock count, number of livestock units in a community.

$Pr_{N, P2O5}$ – production of nitrogen or P_2O_5 from one livestock unit per year (100 kg nitrogen and 40,2 kg of P_2O_5);

RA – regional adjustment. Application of chemical fertilisers in the Southern and South-eastern part of Lithuania is lower than in the rest of the country. Based on the estimates of agronomists, farmers here use no more than 2/3 of the optimal norm. Considering this, estimated optimal norm has to be multiplied by 0,67 for the Žeimena, Merkys, Nemunas upper-course, Neris small tributaries and Šventoji basins.

The distributions of the calculated nitrogen and phosphorus fertilization demand are shown in Figs. 22-23.

2.11.3. Fertilisation practices

ToR (3.1.11.3) requests to fill the fertilisation information gaps in order to prepare the standard fertilisation practices.

For each considered agricultural plant corresponding to SWAT land use codes the following information was provided by agricultural expert; the information is summarised and considered plants listed in Table 26:

1. Calendar planting/sowing dates (if planting/sowing is done yearly);
2. Calendar harvest dates (if harvest is done yearly);

3. Base growing temperature – in cases where no information is given, values from SWAT database are taken;
4. Fertilisation relative to planting/sowing and harvest dates - fertilisation is done either with planting/sowing or shortly before.

From this information (Table 26) using the meteorological data (Section 2.3, ToR 3.1.2) the following SWAT plant parameters related to management practice can be estimated according to TWRI (2012), SWAT Input/Output documentation, Version 2012, Chapter 20:

1. Total number of heat units or growing degree days needed to bring plant to maturity (Table 27, column *PHU*).
2. Planting/beginning of growing season – fraction of total base zero heat units at which planting/sowing takes place (Table 27, column *PlantHU*).
3. Harvest operation – fraction of total base zero heat units at which harvest takes place. Harvest operation – fraction of total base zero heat units at which harvest takes place (Table 27, column *HarvestHU1*).
4. Fraction of plant heat units needed to bring plant to majority are calculated (table 27, column *HarvestHU2*).

Table 26. List of considered plants and their parameters.

SWAT_code	Plant name	Base T	Opt T	Sowing/ planting dates	Harvest dates
AGRL	Agricultural land	0	18	26.04-05.05	20.07-30.07
ALFA	Perennial legumes	4	20	01.05-10.05	20.08-31.08
BARL	Summer barley	0	25	15.04-25.04	01.08-10.08
BARR	Fallow	-	-	-	-
BROS	Natural meadows	8	25	-	-
BWHT	Buckwheat	4	18	20.05-10.06	10.08-20.08
CANA	Winter rape	4	21	25.07-15.08	20.07-31.07
CANP	Annual grasses	4	21	10.04-20.04	10.07-20.07
CELR	Caraway	4	22	15.05-15.06	15.07-31.07
CLVR	Fallow (sideracinis)	1	15	-	-
CORN	Corn	8	25	06.05-15.05	10.09-20.09
CRRT	Vegetables	7	24	05.05-15.05	01.10-10.10
CSIL	Corn for silage	8	25	10.04-20.04	10.09-20.09
GRBN	Beans/ annual legumes	10	19	10.04-20.04	01.08-31.08
LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops	4	18	10.04-20.04	10.08-20.08
LUPN	Lupine	4	18	01.04-25.04	15.08-31.08
OATS	Oats	0	15	01.04-25.04	10.08-20.08
ORCD	Orchards	7	20	-	-
PEAS	Peas	5	14	10.04-20.04	01.08-10.08
POTA	Potatoes	7	22	20.04-10.05	01.07-30.09
RYE	Rye	4	12.5	25.08-15.09	15.07-25.07
SCAN	Summer rape	0	18	10.04-20.04	20.08-31.08
SGBT	Sugar beet	4	18	15.04-30.04	01.10-10.10
SOYB	Soy	10	25	15.05-30.05	10.08-20.08

SWAT_code	Plant name	Base T	Opt T	Sowing/ planting dates	Harvest dates
STBR	Summer barley (straw fields)	4	18	15.04-25.04	01.08-10.08
STCN	Summer rape (straw fields)	4	18	10.04-20.04	20.08-31.08
STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye	5	18	01.04-25.04	20.07-10.08
STRY	Rye (straw fields)	4	18	25.08-23.09	15.07-25.07
STTR	Winter triticale (straw fields)	4	18	05.09-15.09	20.07-10.08
STWH	Summer wheat (straw fields)	4	18	01.04-25.04	20.08-10.09
STWW	Winter wheat (straw fields)	4	18	05.09-30.09	10.08-20.08
SWHT	Summer wheat	0	18	01.04-25.04	20.08-10.09
VTCH	Vetch	4	18	01.04-10.04	10.08-31.08
WBAR	Winter barley	4	18	15.08-15.09	10.07-20.07
WPAS	Perennial pastures	0	15	-	-
WTRC	Winter triticale	4	18	05.09-15.09	20.07-10.08
WWHT	Winter wheat	6	18	05.09-30.09	10.08-20.08

Table 27. Plant sowing/planting and harvest parameters (if applicable).

SWAT_ID	Land use class	PHU	PlantHU	HarvestHU1	HarvestHU2
AGRC	Agricultural	1255	0.13	0.56	1.1
ALFA	Agricultural	1806	0.15	0.95	1
BARL	Agricultural	1545	0.09	0.64	1.1
BWHT	Agricultural	1025	0.25	0.69	1.1
CANA	Agricultural	1834	0.63	1.57	1.1
CANP	Agricultural	867	0.08	0.50	1.1
CELR	Pasture	767	0.26	0.55	1.1
CORN	Agricultural	873	0.17	0.84	1.2
CRRT	Agricultural	1146	0.16	0.91	1.1
CSIL	Agricultural	934	0.08	0.84	1.2
GRBN	Agricultural	578	0.08	0.69	1.2
LMIX	Agricultural	1272	0.08	0.69	1.1
LUPN	Agricultural	1266	0.07	0.73	1.2
OATS	Agricultural	1775	0.07	0.69	1.1
PEAS	Agricultural	962	0.08	0.64	1.2
POTA	Agricultural	885	0.13	0.68	1.1
RYE	Agricultural	1373	0.80	1.54	1.1
SCAN	Agricultural	1888	0.08	0.75	1.1
SGBT	Agricultural	1676	0.10	0.91	1.1
SOYB	Agricultural	520	0.22	0.69	1.2
STBR	Agricultural	1138	0.09	0.64	1.1
STCN	Agricultural	1391	0.08	0.75	1.1
STRC	Agricultural	988	0.07	0.60	1.1
STRY	Agricultural	1373	0.81	1.54	1.1
STTR	Agricultural	1409	0.82	1.60	1.1
STWH	Agricultural	1455	0.07	0.77	1.1

SWAT_ID	Land use class	PHU	PlantHU	HarvestHU1	HarvestHU2
STWW	Agricultural	1608	0.85	1.69	1.1
SWHT	Agricultural	1998	0.07	0.77	1.1
VTCH	Agricultural	1239	0.06	0.72	1.2
WBAR	Agricultural	1419	0.77	1.51	1.1
WTRC	Agricultural	1409	0.82	1.60	1.1
WWHT	Agricultural	1262	0.85	1.69	1.1

5. Fertiliser application – fraction of total base zero heat units at which fertiliser application takes place. For phosphorus a single application is made, while nitrogen is applied 1-3 times. The application time (in fraction of total base zero heat units) and also percentage of total amount of required mineral fertilizers for each application are provided in table 28. In addition to that the manure application time (in fraction of base zero units) and amount (in percentage) of the total amount applied in the corresponding county are provided in table 29.

Table 28. Plant fertilization practices (if applicable).

SWAT_ID	P_AplHU	N_AplHU 1	N_AplHU U2	N_AplHU 3	N_Amount1	N_Amount2	N_Amount3
AGRC	0.12	0.12	0.23		30%	70%	
ALFA	0.14	0.14	0.23		40%	60%	
BARL	0.08	0.08	0.23	0.39	48%	48%	4%
BWHT	0.24	0.24			100%		
CANA	0.62	0.62	0.06	0.11	10%	60%	30%
CANP	0.07	0.07					
CELR	0.25	0.25	0.23	0.39	48%	48%	4%
CORN	0.16	0.16	0.28		70%	30%	
CRRT	0.15	0.15			100%		
CSIL	0.07	0.07	0.28		70%	30%	
GRBN	0.07	0.07	0.23		40%	60%	
LMIX	0.07	0.07	0.23		40%	60%	
LUPN	0.06	0.06	0.23		40%	60%	
OATS	0.06	0.06	0.18		50%	50%	
PEAS	0.07	0.07	0.23		40%	60%	
POTA	0.12	0.12			100%		
RYE	0.79	0.05	0.25	0.33	50%	25%	25%
SCAN	0.07	0.07	0.23		50%	50%	
SGBT	0.09	0.09	0.28		60%	40%	
SOYB	0.21	0.21	0.23		40%	60%	
STBR	0.08	0.08	0.23	0.39	48%	48%	4%
STCN	0.07	0.07	0.23		50%	50%	
STRC	0.06	0.06	0.23	0.39	48%	48%	4%
STRY	0.80	0.05	0.25	0.33	50%	25%	25%

SWAT_ID	P_AplHU	N_AplHU 1	N_AplHU U2	N_AplHU 3	N_Amount1	N_Amount2	N_Amount3
STTR	0.81	0.05	0.25	0.33	50%	25%	25%
STWH	0.06	0.06	0.23	0.57	40%	50%	10%
STWW	0.84	0.05	0.25	0.33	50%	25%	25%
SWHT	0.06	0.06	0.23	0.57	40%	50%	10%
VTCH	0.05	0.05	0.23		40%	60%	
WBAR	0.76	0.05	0.25	0.33	50%	25%	25%
WTRC	0.81	0.05	0.25	0.33	50%	25%	25%
WWHT	0.84	0.05	0.25	0.33	50%	25%	25%

6. Tillage operation – fraction of total base zero heat units at which operation takes place. The tillage times (in fraction of base 0 heat units) are provided in Table 30. The following types of tillages are used:
- Stubble breaking or stubble ploughing, average depth 12 cm (Tillage1);
 - Deep ploughing, 20-25 cm (Tillage2);
 - Ploughing, 14-16 cm (Tillage3);
 - Soil loosening by cultivation and harrowing (Tillage4).

Table 29. Manure application practices (if applicable).

SWAT_ID	Man_apl_HU1	Man_apl_HU2	Man_apl_amount1	Man_apl_amount2
AGRC	0.12	0.66	65%	35%
ALFA	0.14	1.05	65%	35%
BARL	0.08	0.74	65%	35%
BROS	0.06	0.87	65%	35%
BWHT	0.24	0.79	65%	35%
CANA	1.67		100%	
CANP	0.07	0.60	65%	35%
CELR	0.25	0.65	65%	35%
CLVR	0.06	0.87	65%	35%
CORN	0.16	0.94	65%	35%
CRRT	0.15	1.01	65%	35%
CSIL	0.07	0.94	65%	35%
GRBN	0.07	0.79	65%	35%
LMIX	0.07	0.79	65%	35%
LUPN	0.06	0.83	65%	35%
OATS	0.06	0.79	65%	35%
PEAS	0.07	0.74	65%	35%
POTA	0.12	0.78	65%	35%
RYE	1.64		100%	
SCAN	0.07	0.85	65%	35%
SGBT	0.09	1.01	65%	35%
SOYB	0.21	0.79	65%	35%
STBR	0.08	0.74	65%	35%

SWAT_ID	Man_apl_HU1	Man_apl_HU2	Man_apl_amount1	Man_apl_amount2
STCN	0.07	0.85	65%	35%
STRC	0.06	0.70	65%	35%
STRY	1.64		100%	
STTR	1.70		100%	
STWH	0.06	0.87	65%	35%
STWW	1.79		100%	
SWHT	0.06	0.87	65%	35%
VTCH	0.05	0.82	65%	35%
WBAR	1.61		100%	
WPAS	0.06	0.87	65%	35%
WTRC	1.70		100%	
WWHT	1.79		100%	

Table 30. Tillage practices (where applicable).

SWAT_ID	Tillage1	Tillage2	Tillage3	Tillage4
AGRC			0.57	0.12
ALFA			0.96	0.14
BARL	0.65	0.74		0.08
BWHT	0.70	0.79		0.24
CANA	1.58	1.67		0.62
CANP	0.51	0.60		0.07
CELR	0.56	0.65		0.25
CORN	0.85	0.94		0.16
CRRT			0.92	
CSIL	0.85	0.94		0.07
GRBN			0.70	
LMIX			0.70	
LUPN	0.74	0.83		0.06
OATS	0.70	0.79		0.06
PEAS			0.65	
POTA			0.69	
RYE	1.55	1.64		0.79
SCAN	0.76	0.85		0.07
SGBT			0.92	
SOYB	0.70	0.79		0.21
STBR			0.08	
STCN			0.07	
STRC			0.06	
STRY			0.80	
STTR			0.81	
STWH			0.06	
STWW			0.84	
SWHT	0.78	0.87		0.06

SWAT_ID	Tillage1	Tillage2	Tillage3	Tillage4
VTCH	0.73	0.82		0.05
WBAR	1.52	1.61		0.76
WTRC	1.61	1.70		0.81
WWHT	1.70	1.79		0.84

2.12. Buffer strips (3.1.13)

Data. The updating of SWAT *FILTERW* parameter using database of special conditions of land use (*SŽNS_DR10LT*) of the territory of Lithuania in 1: 10 000 is required by p.3.1.13.1 of ToR.

This was done using the geodatabase *SZNS_DR10LT.gdb* provided by the Client. The polygon feature class *VAND_JUOST_AZ_LKS94* allows calculating the width of the buffer strip by the river for the river network shown in Fig. 24 according to the following methodics:

Fig 24. Extent and resolution of polygon feature class *VAND_JUOST_AZ_LKS94*.

1. The polygon feature class *VAND_JUOST_AZ_LKS94* was intersected with the subbasin polygon.
2. The area *A* and perimeter *p* of the intersection was calculated.

3. The width of the buffer strip w was calculated as $w = k_{bs} * (2 * A / p)$. Empirical parameter k_{bs} was assumed equal to 0.05.

Values of w was assigned to the *FILTERW* parameter of *.mgt* files during the preparation of the SWAT modelling system (Chapter 3).

2.13. Sedimentation rate (3.1.14)

The request that the phosphorus and nitrogen sedimentation rate parameters of the model are updated using water monitoring data from the Agency is specified in p.3.1.14.1 of ToR.

Water quality measurements for Years from 1993 to 2012 were supplied by the Client as Excel files (*Ezerai nuo 1993-2000.xlsx*, *00-11ezerai.xlsx* and *Ezerai2012_1.xlsx*). They were preprocessed to match location for points where measurements were taken. In total there were 429 measurement points and for 100 of those points geographical coordinates were provided.

Two Excel files were prepared during data preprocessing. File *id.xlsx* contains the ID of observation point and its co-ordinates and location description. File *data.xlsx* contains the water quality observations. Following parameters were extracted from measurements and preprocessed:

1. SM – suspended solids, mg/l;
2. O2 – dissolved oxygen, mg/l;
3. BOD7 – biochemical oxygen consumption in 7 days, mg/l;
4. NH4 – ammonium, mg/l;
5. NO2 – nitrites, mg/l;
6. NO3 – nitrates, mg/l;
7. NMINER – mineral nitrogen, mg/l;
8. NTOT – total nitrogen, mg/l;
9. PO4 – phosphates, mg/l;
10. PTOT – total phosphorus, mg/l.

Point 3.1.14.2 of ToR requests that Model *.lwq* and *.pnd* files are updated with estimated nutrient sedimentation rate parameters. However, the provided observation data does not allow for calculation of the sedimentation rate parameters.

We expect that the established data sets will be further used in the model calibration and/or validation to either calibrate or validate the sedimentation rate parameters. The exact use of data will depend on the calibration/validation strategy.

2.14. Data for Belarus (3.1.15)

The extension of Model with a large basin level model for the Nemunas and the Neris River basin in the territory of Belarus. Requirements for model extension of the Nemunas and Neris basin in the territory of Belarus according to p.3.1.15 of ToR are less complex due to the modelling of Belarus territory should only provide data related to inflow to Lithuanian territory, therefore detalisation of Nemunas and Neris basins (from the point of view of sub-basins and hydrological response) is needed as much as pollution and water flow level

compliance with the data from cross-border monitoring stations should be secured without detailed and accurate description of spatial and temporal characteristics of water quality in Belarus.

The geometry of model extension for Belarus is given in Section 2.14.1 while collection of other data – in Section 2.14.2.

Fig. 25. A geometry of SWAT model extension to Belarus.

2.14.1. River network and subbasins

The United Nations Environment Programme DatabasinN GIS project database has to be used for setting up the SWAT model for Belarus according to p.3.1.15.2 of ToR.

The following input data from this dataset were used to create the model geometry

1. *Rivers_Nemunas.shp* of type *polyline* was used as a source for the river network geometry in the territory of Belarus.
2. *SubCatch_Nemunas.shp* of type *polygon* provides information about the ten main catchments in the territory of Belorussia, in Neris and Nemunas river basins.

The following river segment and subbasin geospatial information was prepared manually for use in SWAT model:

1. *BelVertices.shp* = *BELVERTICES* of type *point* contains the coordinates of the aggregated river network vertices. It contains the following fields:
 - "ID"- unique identification number corresponding to *VERTICES* "ID" field,
 - "IsSink"- boolean, true if a vertex is network outflow to Lithuania,
 - "IsFork"- boolean, true if a vertex has more than one outgoing river segment.
2. *BelEdges.shp* = *BELEDGES* of type *polyline* contains the coordinates of the aggregated river network edges (river segments). It contains the following fields:
 - "ID"- unique identification number,
 - "Begin"- *BELVERTICES* id at segment start, according to flow direction,
 - "End" - *BELVERTICES* id at segment end, according to flow direction,
 - "FlowTo" - river segment id to which a segment flows to,
 - "WLine"- empty field.
3. *BelPolygons.shp* = *BELPOLYGONS* of type *polygon* contains the catchment polygon coordinates corresponding to river network edges (river segments) *BELEDGES*. It contains a single field "ID", a unique identification number corresponding to *BELEDGES*.

The geometry of the SWAT model extension to Belarus is shown in Fig. 25.

2.14.2. Other data for model extension to Belarus

The United Nations Environment Programme DatabasinN GIS project database has to be used for acquiring the land use, topography and soil data for setting up the SWAT model for Belarus according to p.3.1.15.2 of ToR. This dataset contains rasters of relevant information which were extracted for the area of the model extension described in Section 2.14.1.

The DEM, land use and soil distributions for the model extension area are shown in, respectively, Figs. 26-28. There are territories with missing land use (Fig. 27) in Belarus. Filling of these gaps is performed automatically by SWAT proportionally assigning the known land use fractions to the "blank" areas.

Preparation of meteorological data (3.1.15.3, 3.1.15.6) is summarized in Section 2.3.

Fig. 26. DEM in the territory of model extension to Belarus.

Fig. 27. Land use distribution in the territory of model extension to Belarus.

Fig. 28. Soil distribution in the territory of model extension to Belarus.

No data for point sources, water users, crop fertilization, drainage is available for Belarus. The default SWAT values are automatically applied for initial values of nutrients in groundwater.

Riverbed parameters (slope, width) are calculated for Belarus rivers as in Section 2.8, and Manning coefficient 0.03 is applied.

3. Renewal of SWAT modelling system

3.1. Model preparation process

The data collected and preprocessed in Chapter 2 is further used for the renewal of SWAT water quality modeling system of Lithuania, PAIC&ELLE (2012) according to p.3.1.16 of ToR.

The use of SWAT2012, release 613 was decided on the kick-off meeting of the project to comply with request of p.3.1.16.1 of ToR stating that the newest SWAT version is considered the one, which is available at the beginning of the Project and which is coordinated with the Client.

Model preparation process is designed to be fully automated (provided the input data is preprocessed as in Chapter 2) according to p.3.1.16.2 of ToR. The same automated procedure and scripts are used for creating the water quality modeling systems of Lithuania (LT) and Belarus (BY) – the later requested by TOE 3.1.15. This is achieved by development of a system of Python v.2.6 scripts which perform the generation of the SWAT setups. The list of

scripts is given and their functionality summarised in Chapter 4. Contrary to preparation process of PAIC & ELLE (2012) the use of ArcSWAT software is not included in the preparation process of the modeling system.

All preparation of modeling system (as well as the set of tools for this task) can be split into two parts (the same for LT and BY modeling systems):

- Geospatial data processing
- SWAT Database filling and updating

The first part includes usage of scripts which processes all the geospatial data and creates tables and features which can be linked to each other through attributes without using spatial tools.

The second part creates the SWAT modeling system and file structure itself. It works with the created tables, features and other non-spatial data to fill the needed Watershed databases and create SWAT setups.

The chosen approach – automated generation (and if needed – re-generation) of the modeling system from the extensive set of preprocessed data – is a cornerstone to fulfillment of the requirement of TOR 3.1.16.3 (prepare tools designed to help updating the database of model for future SWAT model versions). The tailor made scripts constitute a modular system. The particular scripts are specialized for handling particular (thematic) data blocks or building particular parts of SWAT modeling system. This approach allow for easy adaptation to the main possible changes in SWAT (1) change of data formats, (2) changes of data structure, (3) change of organisation of information in SWAT, (4) change of input/output data nomenclature in SWAT including need for new data types. In case of future changes in SWAT software, user has to change the respective scripts and re-generate the modeling system without need in revising the data.

Similarly, if the new input data is available then user may choose:

- If the data is upgrade of the existing data then – replace the input data sets and re-generate the modelling system;
- If the new types of data appear which may substitute assumptions or default values then the respective modules of data processing may be upgraded and the modelling system re-generated.

The Sections 3.2 and 3.3 of the report contains a step by step explanation and description of the process of creating the Watershed projects using the original Python v.2.6 script system created within this Project. The same steps are required for LT and BY water quality modeling systems.

Section 3.4.1 describes the file structure of the created water quality modeling system of Lithuania and Belarus. Section 3.4.2 describes the settings of the system in detail; the system of settings is essentially the same for LT and BY water quality models.

3.2. Geospatial data processing

All possible geospatial operations are included in and called from *GISoperations.py*. The specific actions (particular scripts) to be run are specified in *main.py*. There are the following steps of the geospatial data processing:

1. Calculation of the catchment centre and area adds the X and Y coordinate of the centre point in LKS_94 (X and Y) and WGS84 (LON and LAT) coordinate systems and area (AREA) to the polygon feature file created during the spatial division of the model (Section 2.1.3).

Used script: *catchments.py*, function **CalculateCatchmentCentroidsAndArea()**.

Input/output data: **CatchmentFile**

2. Calculation and adding the parameter segment length (LENGTH) to the line feature file created during the spatial division of the model (Section 2.1.3).

Used script: *catchments.py*, function **CalculateSegmentLength()**.

Input/output data: **RiverSegmentFile**

3. Calculation of the river depth either by (1) using a raster provided from the Lithuanian FLOOD project (**riverDepthGrid**) and polygon derived from the grid (**riverFPPolygons**) for the territories covered by the FLOOD project or by (2) using a formula depending on the river basin size (Section 2.8). Creating a table for each segment (**segmentDepthTable**).

Used script: *riverdata.py*, function **PrepareRiverData()**.

Input/output data: **riverDepthGrid**, **riverFPPolygons**, **segmentDepthTable**.

4. Calculation of the river width using GDR water polygons (**GDR10LTPolygons**) and creating a table of the river width for each segment (**riverWidthGDR_table**), Section 2.8.

Used script: *riverdata.py*, function **PrepareRiverData()**.

Input/output data: **GDR10LTPolygons**, **riverWidthGDR_table**.

5. Joining catchments (**CatchmentFile**) to the hydrological regions (**regionFC**) and adding it to the catchments. The shape file of the hydrological regions of Lithuania is provided by the Client.

Used script: *regionalization.py*, function **PrepareCatchmentRegions()**.

Input/output data: **CatchmentFile**, **regionFC**.

6. Calculation of elevation at the river nodes by extracting DEM (**DEMFile**) values at the nodal points for the calculation of river slopes (**RiverNodeFile**), Section 2.8.

Used script: *riverdata.py*, function **ElevationAtNodes()**.

Input data: **DEMFile**, **RiverNodeFile**.

Output data: **nodeElevationFile**

7. Slope calculation from the digital elevation model prepared in Section 2.4 is done by using script. creating a raster which contains slope values on 5x5 m grid, Section 2.8.

Used script: *HRUrasterOps.py*, function **CalculateSlopeRaster**.

Input data: **DEMFile**

Output data: **SlopeFile**

8. First step of HRU delineation creates four rasters with the same resolution and spatial extent as the slope raster **SlopeFile**:
 - a. Landuse raster is created using a landuse polygon feature (**LanduseFile**) containing landuse codes and a lookup table (**LUvsSWATTable**) containing a link between the landuse codes and SWAT codes found in the SWAT crop and urban databases. The input data are prepared in Section 2.5.
 - b. Soil raster is created using a soil polygon feature (**SoilFile**) containing soil codes and a lookup table (**SoilvsSWATTable**) which contains a link between the soil codes and SWAT codes found in the SWAT *user_soil* database. The input data are prepared in Section 2.2.
 - c. Slope-class raster is created using the slope raster (**SlopeFile**, prepared in above step 7) and predefined slope classes (defined in **settings.py.SlopeClasses**).
 - d. Catchment raster is created using catchment polygon feature file (**CatchmentFile**) modified in above step 1.

Used script: *HRUrasterOps.py*, function **prepareHRUs** (“Landuse”, ”Soil”, ”Slopeclasses”, ”CatchmentID”)

Input data: **LanduseFile**, **LUvsSWATTable**, **SoilFile**, **SoilvsSWATTable**, **SlopeFile**, **CatchmentFile**.

Output data: **LanduseRasterFile**, **SoilRasterFile**, **slopeClassRaster** and **CatchmentIDRaster**.

9. The second step of HRU delineation intersects the created Landuse, Soil, Slope-class and Catchment rasters using the same Python script as in step 8. It creates a HRU raster (**globalHRUraster**) each cell of which contains a combination of landuse, soil, slope-class and catchment as well as a unique value for each of the combinations. This value defines a single HRU. After this the average slope value for each HRU is calculated and stored in a table.

Used script: *HRUrasterOps.py*, function **prepareHRUs** (“GlobalHRUs”)

Input data: **LanduseRasterFile**, **SoilRasterFile**, **slopeClassRaster**, **CatchmentIDRaster**.

Output data: **globalHRUraster**.

Fig. 29. Illustration of the HRU raster in the central part of Lithuania (river Neris).

The illustration of the HRU raster is shown in Fig. 29. The total number of HRU's in Lithuanian water quality model is 1342464 (195693 of them larger than 5 ha) and in Belarus water quality model – 379 (354 of them larger than 5 ha).

10. Other data which needs to be added to the HRUs are processed creating tables containing the unique HRU identifier and corresponding parameter values:
 - a. Melioration data from the melioration polygon feature (**MELIORATION_DATA_FILE**) prepared in Section 2.7 is intersected with every HRU and a value of the fraction meliorated in each HRU is added to a table (**HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE**).
 - b. County data from the county polygon feature (**countiesFC**) is intersected with every HRU and a value of the county for every HRU added to a table (**countiesHRU**).
 - c. Large farm data from the landuse reported data dissolved for farms which are larger than 500ha (**largefarmsFC**) is intersected with every HRU. A cell count of the large farms in each HRU is calculated and a table is created (**hrulargefarms**).

Used scripts:

HRUrasterOps.py, function **prepareHRUs** ("Drainage", "Counties", "Regions"),
management.py, function **prepareLargeFarms()**.

Input data: **globalHRUraster, MELIORATION_DATA_FILE countiesFC, largefarmsFC.**

Output data: **HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE, countiesHRU, hrulargefarms.**

11. The geospatial data which needs to be added at the catchment level is processed:

- a. A polygon feature (**ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS**) containing atmospheric deposition values in every catchment is created using the atmospheric deposition data (**ATMDEP_POLYGONS**) and catchment polygon feature (**CatchmentFile**).
- b. Buffer strip polygon feature **BUFFERZONES_POLYGONS**, see Section 2.12, is processed creating a table containing buffer zone statistics in every catchment (**BUFFERZONES_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS**) by intersecting the buffer strip areas with the catchment polygons and calculating the average buffer strip width in the catchment.
- c. Parameter depending on fertilization region (**fertilizerRegionalCoefficients**) is added to each catchment and table for each catchment created (**fertCoefByCatchments**), see also Section 2.11.
- d. Hydrological region data from the river basin polygon feature (**regionFC**) is intersected with every HRU and a value of the region for every catchment is added to a table (**catchmentsRegions**).
- e. Data about lakes and reservoirs are prepared for each catchment by intersecting the lake and reservoir data (**reservoirlakefc**) with catchments (**CatchmentFile**) and spatially joined with segments (**RiverSegmentFile**) creating a feature (**lakesreservoirsbycatchments**) which contains the information about the catchment to which the reservoir or pond belongs and if it is on a modelled reach.
- f. Average annual catchment precipitation is calculated from the annual precipitation raster (**AnnualPrecipitationRaster**) and a table created with a value for each catchment (**catchmentPrecipitationtable**).

Used scripts:

atmosphericdeposition.py, function **prepareAtmosphericDepositionLayers()**,
bufferstrips.py, function **prepareBufferStripLayers()**,
lakesReservoirs.py, function **prepareLakesByCatchments()**,
precipCorrection.py, function **calcCatchmentPrecipitation()**.

Input data: **globalHRUraster, CatchmentFile, ATMDEP_POLYGONS, BUFFERZONES_POLYGONS, fertilizerRegionalCoefficients, regionFC, reservoirlakefc, RiverSegmentFile, AnnualPrecipitationRaster.**

Output data: **ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS, BUFFERZONES_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS, fertCoefByCatchments, catchmentsRegions, lakesreservoirsbycatchments, catchmentPrecipitationtable.**

12. Point sources (Section 2.6) are assigned to the catchments using the point source data file (**PS_MONTHLY_FILE**) and creating a table which contains the information to which catchment each point source belongs (**PS_catchment_table**).

Used scripts: **pointsources.py**, function **pointSourcesbyCatchments()**

Input data: **PS_MONTHLY_FILE**

Output data: **PS_catchment_table**

13. Landuse updates are prepared for landuse groups per catchment. We use two CORINE landuse polygons (**landuse_1_catchments**, **landuse_2_catchments**), Section 2.5). The polygons must contain the defined landuse groups (**groupCode**). A table containing information for a landuse update (**landuse_update_fractions**) is created.

Used scripts: *lup.py* function **prepareLUPbyCatchments()**

Input data: **landuse_1_catchments**, **landuse_2_catchments**

Output data: **landuse_update_fractions**

14. The geospatial data processing is finalised by checking whether the Landuse and Soil SWAT codes included in the HRU raster (**globalHRUraster**) are found in the SWAT database (**SWAT_DB_FILE**).

Used scripts: *checks.py*, functions **checkLanduseSWATtable**, **checkSoilSWATtable**.

Input data: **globalHRUraster**, **SWAT_DB_FILE**.

3.3. Creating SWAT modeling system

Rest of the operations for the creation of the SWAT model are done without using geospatial tools and mostly includes the creation, filling and updating of SWAT parameters in the different SWAT Watershed databases.

The sequential steps of automated model generation are as follows:

1. To start building the databases the model must be split into Watersheds and the catchments and rivers must be assigned to them to create the model geometry. For this we need to read all the information needed for the creation of the networks. The script *Catchments.py*.**ReadAll(CatchmentInfo)** is used to read the following data prepared in Section 2.1.3 for the further processing:
 - a. River segments prepared in as a line feature containing information of connection between river segments and the catchment they belong as well as the ID to which river it belongs (**RiverSegmentFile**) is read.
 - b. Nodes as point features which correspond to river endpoints (**RiverNodeFile**) prepared in are read.
 - c. Table containing rivers and their IDs (**RiverTableFile**) for connecting the river names to river segments is read.
 - d. Table containing the definition of watersheds, their name and ID (**WatershedTableFile**) is read.
 - e. Table containing the connection between catchments and Watersheds including all catchments and the ID of the corresponding Watershed (**CatchmentsByWatershedTableFile**) is read.
 - f. Table containing all the outlets of river segments that flow out of the modelling system which includes a unique identifier corresponding to the FlowTo field in the river segment file (**OutletTableFile**) is read.

- g. Table containing all the inlets in to the system from transboundary sources containing an ID of the inlet as well as the ID of the river segment it flows into (**TransboundaryInletFile**) is read.
- h. Table containing all the catchments which have a part of their area outside of Lithuania containing the ID of the catchments and area outside of the Lithuanian territory (**TransboundaryCatchmentFile**) is read.
- i. Table containing all special water transfer points (for example, Sanžile canal, Merkys-Voke canal, Gilijos vanal etc.) containing the outletID from which the water is transferred, the river segment to which the water is added and a coefficient by which the amount of water transferred must be multiplied is read.

Used scripts: *Catchments.py* function **ReadAll(CatchmentInfo)**

Input data: **RiverSegmentFile, RiverNodeFile, RiverTableFile, WatershedTableFile, CatchmentsByWatershedTableFile, OutletTableFile, TransboundaryInletFile, TransboundaryCatchmentFile.**

2. All other information needed for the updating of SWAT databases is read: :
 - a. Table containing the weather stations for the model including the coordinates (LKS94) and names of the stations .sta file (**WEATHER_DATA**) prepared during weather data processing in Section 2.3 is read.
 - b. File containing meteorological observations .txt file (**WEATHER_DATA**) prepared during weather data processing in Section 2.3 is read.
 - c. Table of the raster containing the information from HRU delineation (**globalHRUraster**) including Landuse codes, Soil code, cell size of the raster is read. During this procedure processing of the HRUs is performed.
 - i. The HRUs that do not belong to any of catchments are excluded.
 - ii. The HRU with the largest size is found in each catchment.
 - iii. All HRUs smaller than 1 ha are removed, except if there are no HRUs left after this, than the biggest is added.
 - iv. HRU are appended to catchments and the local number in catchment is assigned for each of the HRUs left.
 - v. Calculation of total area of the HRUs left is done.
 - vi. Closest weather station is assigned to each catchment.
 - d. Table containing drainage fraction for each HRU (**HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE**) created in Section 3.2 during the processing of geospatial drainage data is read.
 - e. Table containing atmospheric deposition in catchments created in Section 3.2 during the processing of the geospatial data on atmospheric deposition (**ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS**) is read.
 - f. Table containing the width of the bufferzones in catchments (**BUFFERZONES_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS**) created in Section 3.2 during processing of geospatial data on buffer strips is read.

Used scripts: *Catchments.py* function **ReadAll ("HRU","METEO")**

Input data: **WEATHER_DATA**, **globalHRUraster**, **HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE**,
ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS,
BUFFERZONES_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS.

3. All Watershed databases are created together with the respective SWAT file structure. To do this the following sequential steps are taken using the script *InitializeSetups.py*.
 - a. File structure is created containing the name of the Watershed as the project folder.
 - b. An empty database is created for each Watershed.
 - c. Table structure is copied to empty database from the template database (**mdbTemplateFile**)
 - d. Catchments are added to the database of each Watershed and the sequential subbasin numbers are assigned.
 - e. River segments are added to the Reach table and (1) subbasin and (2) subbasin to which the reach flows numbers are assigned to them.
 - f. Monitoring point with the point source type is added for each river end point.
 - g. GRIDCODE equal to the subbasin number is assigned.
 - h. Inlets and Outlets for the Watershed are created.
 - i. HRU tables are filled with the relevant HRU data.

Used script: *InitializeSetups.py*.

Input data: **mdbTemplateFile**.

Output: The SWAT file structure and the databases for watersheds/ subbasins/ reaches.

4. Batch file for the parallelization of the model calculation (sequence of Watershed-by-watershed runs) is created to be allow the run the modeling system in correct order depending on the hierarchy level using the script **prepareRuns.py**.
5. The rest of the procedures are done one by one through all Watersheds filling and updating parameters in respective Watershed databases created in p.3 above. These final steps by the functions of **mdbSetup.py** script are:
 - a. **FillTablesDefault()** fills the database with default values from the template database.
 - b. **SetSimulationPeriod()** updates the simulation period info in the .cio file using the simulation period defined in the **settings.py**.
 - c. **FillHRUParameters()** updates the HRU parameter table with HRU slope, *SLSUBBSN* and area distributing the area missing after the dropping out the smallest HRUs.
 - d. **FillWeatherTables()** updates the tables related to weather data (1) filling station names for the catchments for all parameters (temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed, solar radiation) and (2) writing the number of stations in the .cio file.
 - e. **FillWgn()** updates the weather generator table (Section 2.3) with all the parameters and stations included in the model.
 - f. **FillSubParameters()** updates the SUB table with parameters which are dependent on geospatial data (subbasin area, subbasin latitude, subbasin terrain, number of weather stations and total number of HRUs in the subbasin).

- g. FillRteParameters()** updates the RTE table with parameters which are dependent on geospatial data (segment length, slope, width, depth and manning coefficient).
- h. updateReservoirs()** updates all reservoir parameters in the RES table.
- i. updateLakes()** updates all lake parameters in PND table.
- j. updateWetlands()** update all wetland parameters in PND table.
- k. FillPointSources()** updates the pp table with point source data.
- l. FillInlets()** prepares the model inlets for filling with inflow time series by making empty constant point sources in the ppi table and setting the time step to day.
- m. FillSolParameters()** fills the soil parameters from usersoil table containing the default parameters for every soil class.
- n. FillCHMParameters()** fills CHM parameter table with default values from soil data.
- o. FillMGTParameters()** fills default values of *mgt1.cn2* from usersoiltable, sets the plant identifier *plant_id* dependent on the landuse and urban tables, sets urban landuse (*IURBAN* and *URBLU*) flag for identifying urban territories.
- p. updateManagement()** fills MGT2 and MGT1 tables with values for management practices and fertilization.
- q. updateGW_NPConcentration()** sets initial groundwater nutrient concentration parameters in GW table.
- r. updatePrecipCorrection()** fills parameters RFINC fields in the SUB table by comparing the annual long term precipitation of catchment by the corresponding annual precipitation form the station assigned.
- s. updateDrainage()** updates drainage parameters depending on the fraction of HRU meliorated, calculates and updates the parameters (*DDRAIN*, *GDRAIN*, and *TDRAIN*).
- t. updateAtmosphericDeposition()** updates atmospheric deposition parameters according to table (**ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS**) with parameters (*RAMMO_SUB*, *RCN_SUB*, *DRYDEP_NH4*, *DRYDEP_NO3*)
- u. updateBufferStrips()** updates buffer strip parameter (*FILTERW*) in catchments using the table (**BUFFERZONES_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS**).
- v. SetDefaultCoefficients()** updates coefficient values specified in the *settings.py* files (**defaultCoefficients**).
- w. updateRegionalCoefficients()** applies the model coefficients by hydrological regions using the table specified in (**REGIONALCOEFFICIENT_TABLE**).
- x. updateMonthlyPointSources()** applies monthly point source data to the point sources added to the catchments.
- y. updateWUS()** updates and applies data for water usage to WUS table.
- z. updateLup()** fills land use update coefficients to LUP data table.
- aa. WriteSWATsetup()** writes information from the Watershed database into SWAT setup files by calling an executable **MDB_TO_SWAT.exe**.
- bb. updateTransboundaryInlets()** updates transboundary inlets directly into SWAT setups. This script can only be executed after the SWAT setups have

been written. The inflows from Nemunas and Neris can be chosen from either the observation data or from SWAT model of Belarus according to TOR 3.1.16.7.

Used script: **mdbSetup.py**, functions **FillTablesDefault()**, **SetSimulationPeriod()**, **FillHRUParameters()**, **FillWeatherTables()**, **FillWgn()**, **FillSubParameters()**, **FillRteParameters()**, **updateReservoirs()**, **updateLakes()**, **updateWetlands()**, **FillPointSources()**, **FillInlets()**, **FillSolParameters()**, **FillCHMParameters()**, **FillMGTPParameters()**, **updateManagement()**, **updateGW_NPCConcentration()**, **updatePrecipCorrection()**, **updateDrainage()**, **updateAtmosphericDeposition()**, **updateBufferStrips()**, **SetDefaultCoefficients()**, **updateRegionalCoefficients()**, **updateMonthlyPointSources()**, **updateWUS()**, **updateLup()**, **WriteSWATsetup()**, **updateTransboundaryInlets()**.

Output: ready-to-run system of SWAT setups.

3.4. Structure of modeling system

3.4.1. Folder structure

The folder structure of the water quality modeling system is given relative to the root folder (**MAINPATH** of *settings.py*). The folder names are defined in *settings.py* file and they are summarised in Table 31. The folder structure has changed in comparison with PAIC & ELLE (2012):

Table 31. Values of variables in *settings.py* defining the water quality modeling systems for Lithuania and Belarus.

Name	Variable Type	Data type	Value for LT	Value for BY
MAINPATH	str	Path	c:/WQMS	c:/WQMS
dataDir	str	Path	MAINPATH+Data/	MAINPATH+DataBY/
pyPAICSWAT_DIR	str	Path	MAINPATH+lib/	MAINPATH+lib/
LIBRARYPATH	str	Path	pyPAICSWAT_DIR+py/	pyPAICSWAT_DIR+py/
binPath	str	Path	pyPAICSWAT_DIR+bin/	pyPAICSWAT_DIR+bin/
projectDir	str	Path	MAINPATH+Setup/	MAINPATH+SetupBY/
setupsDir	str	Path	projectDir+Watersheds/	projectDir+Watersheds/
PAICSWAT_ROOT	str	Path	projectDir+PAICSWAT/	projectDir+PAICSWAT/
externalInflowDir	str	Path	projectDir of BY modeling system	None

- Folders **dataDir** (default value for LT setup is *Data* but for BY setup – *DataBY*) contain the data prepared in Chapter 2 and other data – including the data prepared in PAIC & ELLE (2012) which serve as an input data for the scripts used in the automated creation of the modelling system (Sections 3.2 – 3.3).
- Folder **pyPAICSWAT_DIR** (default value *lib*) contains the software modules created in this project:

- The python modules are placed in folder **LIBRARYPATH** (default value *lib/py*).
- The executable modules are placed in folder **binPath** (default value *lib/bin*).
- Folders **projectDir** (default value for LT setup is *Setup* but for BY setup – *SetupBY*) contain the SWAT setups of, respectively Lithuania and Belarus:
 - Subfolder *Script* contains the main script module (*main.py*) and the settings module (*settings.py*) configured for the respective SWAT setup (of Lithuania or Belarus).
 - Subfolder *catchmentdata.gdb* is the ArcMap file geodatabase that contains the geospatial information – catchment definition feature classes and tables (Annex 2, Table 1).
 - Subfolder *Data* contains SWAT setup specific data, including *SWAT2012.mdb* file, and fertilization algorithm specific data (Annex 2, Table 1).
 - Subfolder *GIS* is a placeholder for the results of the geospatial operations by scripts described in Section 3.2 (Annex 2, Table 1).
 - Subfolder **setupsDir** (default value *Watersheds*) contains the setups of SWAT models created in Section 3.3.
 - Folder *PAICSWAT* contains the data necessary for running PAICSWAT software PAIC (2012) as well as data for a program for intercommunication of setups *Inlets.exe*.

The above folder structure of SWAT setups for Lithuania and Belarus should correspond to the values of the variables defining the directory structure in the corresponding files *settings.py* see also Table 31:

1. **projectDir** must be set to the root folder of the respective modelling system.
2. **setupsDir** must be set to folder where setups of SWAT models will be located. By default it is folder *Watersheds* relative to **projectDir**.
3. **dataDir** must be set to folder where the input data is located.
4. **PAICSWAT_ROOT** must be set to root directory of PAICSWAT software (if used by the Client) for the project. Default value is **projectDir**+ "*PAICSWAT*".

The water quality modeling system is electronically delivered as an data archive. Un-archiving of it creates a folder structure in **MAINPATH** (folders *Data*, *DataBY*, *lib*, *SETUP* and *SetupBY*). The water quality modeling system is generated automatically by executing the script *main.py* from folders *Setup/Scripts* and *SetupBY/Scripts*.

3.4.2. Structure of information in *Settings.py*

The file *Settings.py* contains information and links to all of the input/output data and intermediate result locations needed for other scripts. Both water quality modeling systems (of LY and BY) have their respective *Settings.py* files. The input/output data and other parameters are assigned to the variables of the *Settings.py*. The default values of these parameters are summarised in Annex 2:

1. The variables defining the file names of input data are summarised in Table 1 of Annex 2 (both for LT and BY modeling systems).

2. The variables defining the file names of output data are summarised in Table 2 of Annex 2 (both for LT and BY modeling systems).
3. The default values of numerical (or text) variables are summarised in Table 3 of Annex 2.
4. The default values of parameters defining the field names of the input files (databases) are summarised in Table 4 of Annex 2.
5. The values of variables defining the executables and configuration files are summarised in Table 5 of Annex 2.
6. The variables defining the structure of the modeling system are described in Section 3.4.1 and summarised in Table 31.

The contents of this file, i.e. the description of the water quality modeling system is given below:

3. Description of the digital elevation model data.
 - a. Variable *DEMFile* is set to the location of the digital elevation raster. This raster should contain one raster band with Z values of topography. Default value of the variable is *dataDir+"DEM/CombinedDEMs/dem_5m"*.
 - b. Variable *SlopeFile* is set to the location of the topography slope raster. This raster could be calculated by the function *HRUrasterOps.calculateSlopeRaster*. Default value of the variable is set to *dataDir+"DEM/CombinedDEMs/slope_5m"*.
 - c. Variable *SlopeClasses* is a list of slopes (in percent rise!) used for defining slope classes. List should contain a list containing ranges of slope classes and class number as a list of python types [(startvalue1, endvalue1, classnumber1),...]. By default there are 2 slope classes 0.0 – 4.0 % is a slope class 1, and >4.0% is slope class 2.
(*SlopeClasses=[(4.0,99999,2),(0.0,4.0,1)]*)
 - d. Variable *slopeClassRaster* represents a slope class raster file that will be prepared for classification of HRUs. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/slopeclasses"*.
4. Description of the landuse geospatial data.
 - a. Variable *LanduseFile* contains the location of the polygon feature class representing landuse. This file should contain at least an attribute *LUCODE* representing the landuse name. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"LandUse/Landuse.gdb/landuse"*.
 - b. Variable *LUvsSWATTable* contains a location of the table of remapping of the original landuse classes to SWAT landuse classes. This table should contain at least two attributes (1) *globalcode* – the landuse name corresponding to the landuses in landuse feature class; (2) *SWATCODE* – the SWAT landuse name corresponding to the names in the tables *crop* and *urban* from SWAT2012.mdb (maximum 4 characters long). Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"LandUse/Landuse.gdb/globallookup"*.

- c. Variable *LanduseRasterFile* represents a landuse raster file that will be prepared for the classification of HRUs. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/Landuse/LUraster"*.
 - d. Variable *LANDUSEFileVars* provides a possibility for user to enter the fieldnames used for *LUCODE*, *globalcode* and *SWATCODE*.
5. Description of the soil geospatial data.
 - a. Variable *SoilFile* contains the location of the polygon feature class representing the soil classes. This file should contain at least an attribute *SoilCode* representing the soil name. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"/Soil/soil.gdb/union"*.
 - b. Variable *SoilvsSWATTable* contains the location of the table of remapping of the original soil classes into the SWAT soil types. This table should contain at least two attributes (1) *DetailedCode* – the soil name corresponding to *SoilCode* in the soil feature class and (2) *SWATCODE* – the SWAT soil name corresponding to the names in table *usersoil* from *SWAT2012.mdb*. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"Soil/Soil.gdb/globallookup"*.
 - c. Variable *SoilRasterFile* is a name of the soil raster file that will be prepared for classification of HRUs. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/Soil/soilraster"*.
 - d. Variable *SoilFileVars* provides possibility for user to enter the fieldnames used for *SoilCode*, *DetailedCode* and *SWATCODE*.
6. Subbasin and watershed definition data block provides geospatial data of catchments and river segments, catchment connection to watersheds, river network connectivity, outlets and inlets.
 - a. We use the following meanings (definitions):
 - i. **Subbasin** is a polygonal entity representing one river catchment and eventually one subbasin in SWAT setup.
 - ii. **River segment** is a polyline representing main river in one subbasin.
 - iii. **River node** is a point that is placed on either of the ends of a river segments.
 - iv. **Watershed** is a collection of spatially connected subbasins representing one river basin that corresponds to one SWAT setup.
 - v. Two level naming of watersheds is provided allowing to group them into **Basins**.
 - vi. **Outlet** is an object that is placed on any external outflows from the river network. Outlets should be placed on all outflows.
 - vii. **Inlet** is an object at the external inflows into the river network.
 - viii. **External catchment** is a representing additional area outside the modelling domain that is not directly modeled, but rather accounted by increased area of receiving catchment.
 - ix. **Water transfer** is an object which allows for [fractional] water transfer from a predefined outlet to predefined river segment.
 - b. The following variables are used for definition of rivers, subbasins and watersheds:

- i. Location of the subbasin polygon feature class is provided by variable *CatchmentFile*. Default value of it is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/Catchments"*. One entity of the file should correspond to one SUBBASIN. Subbasins should fill all modeling domain (Lithuania territory). They should not overlap, and boundaries of the neighbouring catchments should topologically correspond to each other. Each subbasin should correspond to only one river segment. Integer attribute *CatchmentID* must be present, and it must correspond to unique catchment identifier.
- ii. Location of polyline feature class representing river segments is provided by variable *RiverSegmentFile*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/riversegments"*. River segments should start and end at nodes. Rivers should be split at catchment boundaries. Only one node could be placed at each particular river confluence or splitting point. Following attributes must be present in the *RiverSegmentFile*:
 1. *segmentID* – an unique integer river segment identifier of the same value as corresponding *catchmentID*.
 2. *catchmentID* – an id of the catchment that contains the river segment.
 3. *nodeFrom* - id of the (upstream) node from which the segment starts.
 4. *nodeTo* - id of the (downstream)node at which the segment ends.
 5. *FlowTo* – a *segmentID* of the receiving river segment or *outletID* of the receiving outlet.
 6. *riverID* - an id of the river in the supplemental rivers table
- iii. Location of the point feature class representing river nodes is provided by variable *RiverNodeFile*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/nodes"*. An attribute *node_ID* representing unique node identifier must be present.
- iv. Location of the watershed table is provided by variable *WatershedTableFile*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/Watersheds"*. It should contain three attributes:
 1. *watershedID* is an unique watershed identifier;
 2. *BasinName* – a basin name to which the watershed belongs;
 3. *watershedName* – name of the watershed.
- v. Location of table that provides a grouping of the subbasins into watersheds is provided by variable *CatchmentsByWatershedTableFile*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/CatchmentsByWatersheds"*. It must contain two attributes:
 1. *watershedID* – is the watershed identifier;
 2. *catchmentID* is a catchment identifier of the subbasin. One subbasin could belong to only one watershed.

- vi. Location of a table of the outlets is provided by variable *OutletTableFile*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/outlets"*. It must contain two attributes:
 1. *outletID* – an unique integer identifier of outlet, it must be different from any of the river segment identifiers;
 2. *outletName* is the name of the outlet.
 - vii. Location of a table of external inlets is provided by variable *TransboundaryInletFile*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/inlets"*. It must contain the following three attributes:
 1. *inletID* – an unique integer identifier of inlet, it must be different from any of the river segment identifiers and any outlet identifiers;
 2. *inletName* – the name of inlet;
 3. *segmentID* – river segment identifier to which the inflow is directed.
 - viii. Location of table of external catchments is provided by variable *TransboundaryCatchmentFile*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/transboundary"*. Two attributes must be present:
 1. *catchmentID* – a catchment identifier of the subbasin with external contribution;
 2. *AddedArea* – an area in km² of the catchment located outside of the modelling domain.
 - ix. Location of the table that provides possibility of the water transfer between an outlet and another segment is given by variable *WaterTransferTable*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"catchmentData.gdb/WaterTransfer"*. Following fields must be present in the table:
 1. *transferID* – an unique identifier of an object;
 2. *outletID* – an identifier of the outlet from which the water transfer occurs;
 3. *flowTo* – a river segment identifier of the receiving river segment;
 4. *multiplier* – a coefficient by which an amount of the transferred water in outlet is multiplied.
 - x. Variable *WatershedDefinitionVars* provides possibility for user to enter the fieldnames used in subbasin and watershed definition.
 - xi. Variable *CatchmentIDRaster* represents a raster file containing spatially distributed catchment IDs that are prepared for classification of HRUs (Section 3.2). Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/catchmentraster"*.
7. The block of HRU definition variables:

- a. Variable *globalHRUraster* shows the location of global HRU raster that is prepared by HRU definition script (see section 3.2). Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/globalhru"*.
 - b. Location of a table where the mean slope of each of the HRUs is stored is provided by variable *HRUslopeTable*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/hruslopes"*.
 - c. Location of a table where the mean elevation of each of the subbasins is stored is provided by a variable *CatchmentelevationTable*. Default value is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/catchelev"*.
 - d. Minimal HRU area in hectares is provided by a variable *HRUDefinitionVars["MinimalHruArea"]*. It's default value is 5.0.
8. Observations data. It should be provided in PAICSWAT format. Any observation data consists of two tab delimited text files. Both files should be in the same directory and have the same basename. The file with extension *.sta* that contains station coordinates and names. Columns of *.sta* file are: *stationID Name X Y* (*stationID* - station integer ID, *Name* - station name, *X, Y* - station coordinates). Coordinates must be in a coordinate system defined by variable *defcoordSystTxt*. The file with extension *.txt* contains the daily measurements of respective parameters
- a. Meteorological parameters: a variable *WEATHER_DATA* provides the location of meteorological observation file. Its default value is *dataDir+"observations/weatherdata.txt"*. The following observation data should be provided in the columns of the corresponding *.txt* file: *Station Date T Tmin Tmax Prec W10 RHUM Solar*:
 - i. Station – a stationID corresponding to ID in *.sta* file,
 - ii. DATE – date in yyyy.mm.dd format,
 - iii. T, Tmin, Tmax - daily average, minimal and maximal temperatures, in degC,
 - iv. Prec - daily precipitation amount in mm/day,
 - v. W10 - daily average wind speed at 10m in m/s,
 - vi. RelHum - daily average relative humidity in %,
 - vii. Solar - daily amount of solar radiation in MJ/m²/day.
 - b. Variable *Q_DATA* provides a location of daily discharge observation data. Its default value is *dataDir+"Observations/qobs.txt"*. Columns of the corresponding *.txt* file are *StationID Date Q*:
 - i. StationID - stationID corresponding to ID in *.sta* file,
 - ii. DATE – date in in yyyy.mm.dd format,
 - iii. Q – discharge in m³/s.
 - c. Variable *WQ_DATA* provides location of daily water quality observation data. Its default value is *dataDir+"Observations/wqobs.txt"*. Columns of the corresponding *.txt* file are: *StationID Date Flow SS DO BOD7 NH4-N NO2-N NO3-N N mineral N total PO4-P P total N-Org P-Org*:
 - i. StationID - stationID corresponding to ID in *.sta* file,
 - ii. DATE – date in yyyy.mm.dd format,

- iv. *FN_NO3_wet* - fieldname containing the wet deposition values of nitrate (mgN/m²/year). Default – “*NO3_wet*”.
 - v. *FN_precip* - fieldname containing the precipitation values as used for calculation of the wet deposition (mm/year). Default – “*precipitation*”.
 - vi. *FN_area* - fieldname containing shape area in m². Default – “*Shape_Area*”.
11. Buffer zone data
- a. Variable *BUFFERZONES_POLYGONS* provides the location of polygon feature class representing the buffer zones. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"SZNS_DR10LT/SZNS_DR10LT.gdb/VAND_JUOST_AZ_LKS94"*.
 - b. Location of the feature class for storing intersection of buffer zones with catchments is provided by variable *BUFFERZONES_BY_CATCHMENTS*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/buffzonesCatchm"*.
 - c. Location of table for storing summary statistics about lengths and areas of buffer strip polygons by catchments is provided by a variable *BUFFERZONES_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/buffzonesStat"*.
 - d. Variable *BUFFERZONES_COEFFICIENT* is the value by which an average width of the buffer zone is multiplied to obtain the *FILTERW* parameter of *MGT* table. Default value 0.05.
12. Administrative county data
- a. Variable *countiesFC* provides filename of polygonal feature class containing administrative county boundaries (default value is *dataDir+"Counties/counties.shp"*). Variable *countiesIDField* contains the field name of unique integer county identifier. Default value is “*KODAS*”.
 - b. Variable *countiesraster* provides file name of raster of county identifiers that will be prepared by script. Default value is *projectDir+"GIS/landuse/counties"*.
 - c. Variable *countiesHRU* contains file name of raster where correspondence of HRUs to counties is stored. Default value is *projectDir+"GIS/landuse/combi_cohru"*.
13. River parameter data
- a. River slope
 - i. Variable *nodeElevationFile* contains the name of point feature class where node elevations will be stored. Node elevations are used to calculate river slope. Default value of variable is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/node_elevation"*.
 - ii. Variable *RiverSlopeBounds* defines minimal and maximal allowed river slope. Default value (0.0001, 0.1).
 - b. River width
 - i. Variable *GDR10LTPolygons* contains name of polygon layer *PLOTAI* of database *GDR10LT*. Default value of variable is *dataDir+"GDR/GDR10LT.gdb/PLOTAI"*.

- ii. *Plant_Name* (text) – name of the plant.
 - iii. *Method* (integer) – method number for calculation of the fertilization amount (1 or 2). Blank may be left in case if fertilization is not calculated for the particular plant.
 - iv. *Std_yield* (double) – standard yield for the plant (tons/ha/year).
 - v. *N_Demand* (double) – nitrogen demand (kgN/ha/year).
 - vi. *P_Demand* – phosphorus demand (kgP/ha/year).
 - vii. *Preplant_N* – preplant nitrogen amount (kgN/ha/year).
 - viii. *Preplant_P* – preplant phosphorus amount (kgP/ha/year).
- c. Variable *LIVESTOCK_TABLE* contains the location of the MS Access database and tablename of the table storing the number of livestock units in the counties. This table must be in *MSAccess* format and contain the following fields:
- i. *Kodas* (integer) – unique integer county identifier that corresponds to the *countiesIDField* of *countiesFC*.
 - ii. *livestock_units* (double) – number of standard animal units in county.
- d. Variable *PLANNEDIYIELD_TABLE* contains location of the MS Access database and tablename of table storing yield by county and crop. It must contain following fields:
- i. *SWAT_ID* (integer) - SWAT code of the plant, corresponding to the crop table's field *SNAM*.
 - ii. *Kodas* (integer) - unique integer county identifier that corresponds to *countiesIDField* of *countiesFC*.
 - iii. *Planned_yield* – yield amount in tons/ha/year.
- e. Variable *PLANTMGT_TABLE* provides the location of the MS Access database and tablename of table storing management practices for each of the SWAT landuse codes. This table must be in *MSAccess* format and contain the following fields:
- i. *SWAT_ID* (integer) - SWAT code of the landuse, corresponding to crop table's field *SNAM* or urban table's field *URBNAME*.
 - ii. *LUClass* (text) – text identifier of landuse group. Possible values are *Agricultural*, *Barren*, *Forest*, *Pasture*, *Urban*, *Water*, *Wetland*.
 - iii. *PHU* (double) – plant heat units to bring a plant to maturity. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*.
 - iv. *PlantHU* (double)– base zero heat units for planting. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*.
 - v. *HarvestHU* (double) – base zero heat units for harvest. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*. For winter crops it should be larger than 1.0, to indicate the next year.
 - vi. *HarvestHU2* (double) – plant heat units for harvest. This variable applies if *LUClass* is *Agricultural*.
 - vii. *P_AplHU* (double) – base zero heat units for mineral phosphorus application.
 - viii. *Tillage1*, *Tillage2*, *Tillage3*, *Tillage4* (double) – these four fields represent the base zero heat units for application of 4 types of the

- tillage operations. For winter crops these fields should be larger than 1.0, to indicate the next year.
- ix. *N_AplHU1*, *N_AplHU2*, *N_AplHU3* (double) – these three fields represent base zero heat units for application of the mineral nitrogen up to 3 times per year. For winter crops value of these fields should be larger than 1.0, to indicate the next year.
 - x. *N_Amount1*, *N_Amount2*, *N_Amount3* (double) – the fields contain fractions of total mineral nitrogen application up to 3 times per year. The total sum of fractions should equal to 1.0.
 - xi. *Man_apl_HU1*, *Man_apl_HU2* (double) – these two fields represent base zero heat units for application of manure up to 2 times per year. For winter crops the values larger than 1.0 indicates the next year.
 - xii. *Man_apl_amount1*, *Man_apl_amount2* (double) – the fields contain the fractions of the total manure application up to 2 times per year. The total sum of fractions should equal to 1.0.
- f. Variable *landusegroup raster* is the name of raster that will contain a spatial distribution of the landuse groups. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/Landuse/lugroups"*.
- g. Variable *lugroupbycountyraster* is the name of raster that will contain geospatial distribution of the landuse groups by counties. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/Landuse/lugrcounty"*
- h. Variable *agriculturalgroups* is the list of land use groups for agricultural land calculations and fertilization. Default value is [*"AGRICULTURAL"*, *"PASTURE"*].
- i. Variable *mineralFertilizertable* is the name of the table where calculated mineral fertilizer application per HRU will be stored. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/fertilizer"*.
- j. Variable *management_vars* is a python dictionary containing the information related to the management:
- i. *"past_bioint"* is the initial biomass on the pastures (kg/ha). Default value of this variable is *5000.0*.
 - ii. *"past_phu"* is the number of heat units to bring the pastures to maturity (chosen larger than typical heat units per year to not mature the grass!). Default value of this variable is *3000.0*.
 - iii. *"frst_bioint"* is the default initial biomass of forests (kg/ha). Default value of this variable is *100000.0*. It is used if *FORESTBIOMASS TABLE* does not provide the information about the forest biomass for particular *SWAT ID*.
 - iv. *"frst_phu"* – is heat units to bring forests to maturity (chosen larger than typical heat units per year to not mature the trees!). Default *3000.0*.
 - v. *"ID_MineralN"* – is id of the elemental nitrogen fertilizer from *fert* table in *SWAT_DB*. Default value of this variable is *1*.

- vi. "*ID_MineralP*" – is id of the elemental phosphorus fertilizer from *fert* table in *SWAT_DB*. Default value of this variable is 2.
 - vii. "*ID_Manure*" – is id of the manure fertilizer from *fert* table in *SWAT_DB* (this fertilizer should have 1.0 units of total nitrogen!). Default value of this variable is 55.
 - viii. "*ID_Tillage*" – is a python table of length 4 containing tillage identifiers for the 4 predefined tillage types corresponding to the tillage fields in *PLANTMGT_TABLE*. Default value of this variable is (108, 109, 1, 111).
- k. Information about the large farms:
- i. Variable *largefarmsFC* is the name of the polygonal feature class containing the geospatial location of “large farms” which are used for the fertilizer amount calculations. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+ "LandUse/landuse.gdb/large_farms"*
 - ii. Variable *largefarmsraster* is the name of raster that will contain geospatial location of “large farms”. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+ "GIS/landuse/rlargefarms"*.
 - iii. Variable *hrulargefarms* is the name of the raster storing information of the large farms per each of the HRUs. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+ "GIS/landuse/hrufarms"*.
 - iv. Variable *largefarmFertilizerCoef* is a coefficient by which to multiply mineral fertilizer amount in "large farms". Default value of this variable is 1.2.
- l. Information about the fertilization regional coefficients:
- i. Variable *fertilizerRegionalCoefficients* is the name of polygonal feature class that contains the regional multipliers to the calculated amount of the mineral fertilizer amounts. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+ "Data/FertCoeff/FertCoeff.shp"*. Field name of multiplier is provided by variable *fieldname_fertcoeff*.
 - ii. Variable *fertCoefByCatchments* is the name of the polygonal feature class where intersection of *fertilizerRegionalCoefficients* with subbasin polygons will be stored. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+ "GIS/hru.gdb/fertCoefByCatchm"*
- m. Variable *FORESTBIOMASS_TABLE* provides a location of the MS Access database and tablename of the table containing the initial forest biomass in kg/ha for forest landuses. It must contain the following fields:
- i. *SWAT_ID* (integer) - SWAT code of the plant, corresponding to the crop table’s field *SNAM*.
 - ii. *Biomass* (double) – forest biomass in kg/ha.
15. Initial nutrient concentration in groundwater:
- a. Variable *GW_ConcN* is a Python dictionary which contains the initial concentrations (mg/l) of nitrate in the shallow aquifer per landuse groups. Default values are:
 - i. “*AGRICULTURAL*”: 2.50

- ii. "PASTURE": 1.15
 - iii. "FOREST": 1.12
 - iv. "URBAN": 3.8
 - b. Variable *GW_ConcP* is a Python dictionary which contains the initial concentrations (mg/l) of soluble phosphorus in the shallow aquifer per landuse groups. Default values are:
 - i. "AGRICULTURAL":0.02
 - ii. "PASTURE":0.05
 - iii. "FOREST":0.06
 - iv. "URBAN":0.04
 - v. Lake and reservoir related variables.
- 16. Reservoir and lake data.
 - a. Variable *reservoirlakefc* is the name of polygonal feature class containing the reservoir and lake data. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"Lakes&Reservoirs/lakeresr.shp"* This feature class must contain at least the following attributes:
 - i. *Snpl* - surface area at the normal water level (ha). If value of *Snpl* is zero, it is assumed that for a particular polygon *Snpl*, *Savl*, *Vnpl* and *Vavl* are not given.
 - ii. *Savl* - surface at the highest water level (ha).
 - iii. *Vnpl* - volume at the normal water level (in 1000 of m³).
 - iv. *Vavl* - volume of the water needed to fill the reservoir to the emergency spillway (in 1000 of m³).
 - v. *Gylis* - average depth of lake/reservoir (m). If it is zero, then it is assumed, that the average depth is not given.
 - vi. *Shape_area* – the area of lake or reservoir polygon in m², corresponding to the geometric area of a feature.
 - b. Variable *reservoirlakeFields* contains the field names of above mentioned fields of *reservoirlakefc*.
 - c. Variable *lakesreservoirsbycatchments* is a name of the polygon feature class which will contain the intersection of the *reservoirlakefc* with the subbasin polygons. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/lakesreservoirs"*.
 - d. Variable *reservoirParams* contains the default depth of reservoirs (used for volume calculations if volumes are not given) and default difference between the highest and normal waterlevel (used for highest volume calculations if they are not given). Default values of this variable are 3.0 and 0.3, respectively.
 - e. Variable *lakeParams* contains the default depth of lakes (used for volume calculations if volumes are not given) and the default difference between the highest and normal waterlevel (used for highest volume calculations if they are not given). Default values of this variable are 2.0 and 0.2, respectively.
 - f. Variable *reservoirReleasetime* is a time in days to release the reservoirs from maximum to normal level. It is used for calculation of the average daily release rate

17. Parameters for annual average precipitation correction:
 - a. Variable *AnnualPrecipitationRaster* is the name of a raster containing the geospatial distribution of the annual average precipitation values. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"Observations/AnnualPrecipitation/Precip.TIF"*.
 - b. Variable *AnnualPrecipitationStationtable* is the name of a table containing the annual precipitation values for observation stations, corresponding to the stations in *WEATHER_DATA*. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"Observations/AnnualPrecipitation/statpcp.dbf"*. Variable *AnnualPFieldNames* determines the field names for the station ID and the annual average precipitation.
 - c. Variable *catchmentPrecipitationtable* is a name of the table where the catchment annual average precipitation will be stored. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/hru.gdb/precipByCatch"*.
18. Wetland parameters:
 - a. Variable *WetlandsVars* contains:
 - i. *"wet_normD"* - average normal depth of water in the wetlands (m). Default value of this variable is 2.0.
 - ii. *"wet_maxD"* - average maximal depth of water in the wetlands (m). Default value of this variable is 3.0.
 - iii. *"WetlandLandUseIDs"* is a list of landuse codes that define a wetland. Default value of this variable is [*"WETN", "WETF"*].
19. Landuse update (LUP) related variables:
 - a. Variable *landuse_update_fractions* contains a table name of the table where landuse update proportional fractions per catchment are stored. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/lupupdate"*. This table must contain the following fields:
 - i. *catchmentID* (integer) – catchment ID of subbasin as defined in *CatchmentFile*.
 - ii. *Agricultural, Barren, Forest, Pasture, Urban, Water, Wetland* (double) – these fields provide values of update fractions per each landuse group.
 - b. Variable *lup_date* is a start date of landscape update (*yyyy,mm,dd*), if it is empty () then the landscape update is not applied. Default value of this variable is ().
 - c. Variables for preparation of the landuse update fractions:
 - i. Variables *landuse_classes_1* and *landuse_classes_2* define the names of the two polygon feature classes which define two sequential landuses. Default values of these variables are *dataDir+"Corine/corine 2000/ clc00.shp"* and *dataDir+"Corine/corine 2006 revised/corine_2006_revised.shp"*.
 - ii. Variable *lup_lookup_table* is the name of the table that defines the relations between the landscape update polygons and the general landuse groups as defined by *PLANTMGT_TABLE* field *LUClass*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/luplookup"*.

- iii. Variable *lupfields* defines the field names of *landuse_classes_1*, *landuse_classes_2* and *lup_lookup_table*.
- iv. Variables *landuse_1_catchments* and *landuse_2_catchments* contain the names of the polygon classes which will contain the intersection of the *landuse_classes_1* and *landuse_classes_2* with the subbasin polygons. Default values of these variables are *projectDir+"GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/corine2000"* and *projectDir+"GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/corine2006"*.
- v. Variables *landuse_1_table* and *landuse_2_table* are names of tables where amounts of landuse groups per subbasin will be stored.

20. Pointsource variables:

- a. Variable *PS_catchment_table* is the name of the table that will contain *catchmentID* of the subbasin for each of the pointsources. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"Data/PointSources/ps.gdb/ps_catchment"*.
- b. Variables *Field_PS_ID* and *Field_PS_Name* are the field names of the point source integer ID and point source name in *PS_catchment_table*.
- c. Variable *PS_MONTHLY_FILE* contains the name of the monthly point source file in PAICSWAT format. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"Data/PointSources/monthly.txt"*. The monthly pointsource data consists of two tab delimited text files. Both files should be in the same directory and have the same basename.
 - i. Columns of .sta file are: *pointsourceID*, *Name*, *X*, *Y*, *sourceID* (*pointsourceID* – point source integer ID, *Name* - point source name, *X,Y* - point source coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates it to the original data). Coordinates must be in a coordinate system defined by the variable *defcoordSystTxt*.
 - ii. The file with extension *.txt* contains monthly point source values. Columns of this file are:
 - 1. *ID* – the point source integer ID as defined by *.sta* file.
 - 2. *DATE* – date of point source in *yyyy.mm.dd* format. Day for monthly point sources is always 15.
 - 3. *SS*, *BOD7*, *NO3*, *NO2*, *NH4*, *NTOT*, *PO4*, *PTOT*, *NORG*, *PORG* are the loads of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in g/day.
 - 4. *Discharge* – flow of point source in m³/day
 - 5. *rho_SS*, *rho_BOD7*, *rho_NO3*, *rho_NO2*, *rho_NH4*, *rho_NTOT*, *rho_PO4*, *rho_PTOT*, *rho_NORG*, *rho_PORG* are the concentrations of suspended solids, BOD7, N-NO3, N-NO2, N-NH4, total nitrogen, P-PO4, total phosphorus, organic nitrogen, and organic phosphorus in mg/l
 - 6. *year*, *month* are the calendar year and month.

- d. Variable *PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE* is a file name of MSAccess database and table name where catchmentIDs of pointsources defined by *PS_YEARLY* will be stored.
 - e. Variable *PS_YEARLY* contains file name of MSAccess database and table name of yearly pointsource data of those pointsources that are not included in the *PS_MONTHLY_FILE*. This table must contain following fields, the field names are defined in variable *PS_YEARLY_FIELDS*:
 - i. *ID* (integer) - unique id.
 - ii. *year* (integer) – year of pointsource loading.
 - iii. *name* (text) - full name of point source.
 - iv. *type* (integer) – type of point source.
 - v. *nutrient* (text) – type of substance (either of *SS*, *BOD7*, *NO3*, *NO2*, *NH4*, *NTOT*, *PO4*, *PTOT*).
 - vi. *concentration* (double) – value of concentration of corresponding substance in mg/l.
 - vii. *discharge* (double) – value of discharge of pointsource in 1000 m³/y.
 - viii. *X* (double) – x coordinate of point source in coordinates defined by *defcoordSystTxt*.
 - ix. *Y* (double) – y coordinate of point source in coordinates defined by *defcoordSystTxt*.
21. Water users related variables.
- a. *WUS_FILE* contains name of file in PAICSWAT format that contains data about water users. Default value of this variable is *dataDir+"PointSources/WaterUseMonthly.txt"*.
 - b. Water users' data consists of two tab delimited text files (*.sta* and *.txt*). Both files should be in the same directory and have the same basename.
 - i. Columns of *.sta* file are: *waterUserID*, *Name*, *X*, *Y*, *sourceID* (*waterUserID* – water user integer ID, *Name* – water user name, *x,y* – water user coordinates, *sourceID* - text identifier of point source that relates water user to point source). Coordinates must be in a coordinate system defined by a variable *defcoordSystTxt*.
 - ii. The file with extension *.txt* contains water usage values. Columns of this file are:
 - 1. *ID* – water user integer ID as defined by *.sta* file.
 - 2. *DATE* – date of point source in *yyyy.mm.dd* format.
 - 3. *WaterUse* – water usage in m³/day
22. Block of the SWAT setup related variables.
- a. Location of SWAT2012.mdb file is provided by variable *SWAT_DB_FILE*. Default value of this variable is *projectDir+"Data/SWAT2012.mdb"*.
 - b. A weather generator input table must be in MSAccess format. It must contain field *ID*, that corresponds to station ID in *WEATHER_DATA* file. Variable *WGN_TABLE* provides location of the MS Access database, tablename and fieldname for station.

- c. *Usersoil* table provides the soil parameters. It must be in MS Access format and contain soil name field *SNAM*. Variable *USERSOIL_TABLE* provides location of the MS Access database and tablename.
 - d. Crop table provides crop parameters corresponding to the crops and the forest plants in the landuse table. It must be in MS Access format and contain the crop abbreviation field *CPNM*. Variable *CROP_TABLE* provides a location of the MS Access database and tablename.
 - e. Urban table provides the urban parameters corresponding to the urban landuses in the landuse table. It must be in MS Access format, and it must contain urban landuse abbreviation field *URBNAME*. Variable *URBAN_TABLE* provides a location of the MS Access database and tablename. Variable *URBAN_PLANT_CODE* provides a crop code from the crop table that will be used for HRUs with urban landuse.
 - f. *CST_user* table stores the information for generating of the weather forecast scenarios (CST). The format of the table is identical to the weather generator input table. The forecast regions correspond to the meteorological stations. Variable *CST_TABLE* provides location of the MS Access database, tablename and fieldname for station.
 - g. Variable *SimulationPeriod* allows the modification of the simulation start year and date, number of years simulated, and a number of years for the simulation warm-up period.
 - h. Variable *defaultCoefficients* provides possibility for the user of the script to enter the default global values of SWAT variables. This variable is a python list of tuples. Each tuple consisting of four values:
 - i. type of variables – either “V” if a constant value is entered or “R” if a value relative to initial value is entered. Entering of relative values of the soil coefficients (*SOL* table) and *CN2* coefficient is supported.
 - ii. Name of SWAT table.
 - iii. Name of SWAT variable.
 - iv. Value of SWAT variable.
23. Block of variables related to transboundary inflows from Belorussia.
- a. Variable of type Boolean *inflowFromBelarus* determines whether the inflow is taken from measured data (if *False*) or from Belarus SWAT model (if *True*). Such alternatives are requested by TOR 3.1.15.5 and 3.1.16.7. Default value of this variable is *False*.
 - b. Variables *external_Nemunus* and *_external_Neris* provide the location of the output files generated by Belarus model for Nemunas and Neris rivers. Variable *externalInflowDir* contains the folder name of Belorussia SWAT setup.

Variable *transBoundaryInlets* is the Python dictionary, containing the list of the identifiers of the external inlets as provided by *TransboundaryInletFile*. For each of the identifiers *stationID* for discharge and water quality stations must be provided. The measured data for these stations from *Q_DATA* and *WQ_DATA* will be used as a transboundary inflows in case if *inflowFromBelarus* is *False*.

4. System of Python scripts

Water quality model preparation process is designed to be fully automated. The system of Python v.2.6 scripts which perform the generation of the SWAT setups is included in the electronic deliverables. The functionality of the main scripts is described throughout the Sections 3.2 - 3.3 dealing with the model preparation process. In this Chapter we provide the overall scheme of developed scripts as well as their list.

Fig. 30. The hierarchy of Python scripts used for the automated preparation of the SWAT water quality modeling system of Lithuania.

The hierarchy of the Python scripts used in the system is shown in Fig. 30. The structure of folders of the system is described in Section 3.4.1, Two scripts are on the top of the hierarchy:

- **Settings.py** – contains the description of the information used by the SWAT water quality modeling system as well as links to all of the input data and intermediate result locations needed for other scripts of the system. The detailed description of the contents of **Settings.py** is given in Section 3.4.2.
- **Main.py** – contains the sequence and parameter references needed to run the other scripts during the automated preparation of modeling system. **Main.py** is divided into two parts – „geospatial” and „database”. It invokes all other scripts to run them sequentially as well as provides the necessary iterations through the Watersheds (setups) of the modeling system for database scripts. Thus, this script is running the sequence of model preparation described in Sections 3.2 – 3.3.

The rest of the scripts may be divided as (a) the ones processing the geospatial information (their functionality is described in Section 3.2, and they are invoked via **GISoperations.py**), (b) the others processing the SWAT file structure and SWAT databases (their functionality is described in Section 3.3) and (c) the service scripts. The list of the scripts used in the system is provided below in alphabetical order:

- **accessLnk.py** – utility script used for linking to Microsoft Access tables.
- **atmosphericdeposition.py** – script which creates a table of atmospheric deposition in catchments and updates the atmospheric deposition parameters in the database.
- **bufferstrips.py** - script which creates a table of buffer strips in catchments and updates the buffer strip parameters in the database.
- **calculateSlopeRaster.py** – script which prepares a slope raster from the DEM raster.
- **catchments.py** – defines classes needed for holding all the information needed for creating the geometry of the modeling system: catchments, watersheds and rivers.
- **checks.py** – utility which checks whether all landuses and soils defined in HRUs exist also in the SWAT database.
- **coefficients.py** – script which defines how to change the SWAT parameters in the database.
- **common.py** – utility which defines a set of common functions needed for conversion of data types.
- **config.py** – configuration file referring to the executables and databases needed for other scripts.
- **drainage.py** - script which creates a table of drainage fraction in HRUs and updates the melioration (drainage) parameters in the SWAT database.
- **gdbtools.py** – utility script containing the functions for the work with ESRI file geodatabases.
- **GISoperations.py** – script through which all other geospatial scripts are called, it lists all possible GIS operations.
- **gw.py** – script which applies initial concentrations of nutrients in the ground water.
- **HRU.py** – utility script for data importing.

- **HRUrasterOps.py** – script containing multiple geospatial functions needed to create HRUs.
- **initializeSetups.py** – subroutine for preparation of the directory hierarchy of the watersheds and creating empty Microsoft Access databases for each Watershed.
- **initPAICSWAT.py** – script which prepares all PAICSWAT, PAIC(2012) related files.
- **lakesReservoirs.py** – script which contains all operations done with lake and reservoir information.
- **lup.py** – script which creates and updates the tables of land use update data.
- **management.py** – script which calculates and updates all information associated with agricultural management practice (fertilizers, plowing, etc.).
- **MDB2SWAT.py** – script which runs *MDB_TO_SWAT.exe* utility for creating SWAT data files from the SWAT database.
- **MDBconnection.py** – utility script which helps to connect to Microsoft Access databases and update them.
- **mdbSetup.py** – script used for filling MDB databases with default values.
- **observations.py** – script used for reading observation data from respective files.
- **pointsources.py** – script which contains all operations to read observed point source data and update it in the model.
- **precipCorrection.py** – script containing functions needed to implement precipitation correction in the model.
- **prepareRuns.py** – script used for creating and management of the hierarchical SWAT model runs in the modeling system.
- **regionalization.py** – script containing routines to account for regionalization (hydrological regions).
- **riverdata.py** – script containing functions needed for the calculation of river depth, width and Manning coefficient.
- **RunExe.py** – utility script used for running executables in Python environment.
- **SWATdefs.py** – defines SWAT tables and their types.
- **transboundary.py** – script used for updating of transboundary inlets; depending on the variable of *inflowFromBelarus* in **settings.py** it takes the inflow from either measured data (if *False*) or from Belarus SWAT model (if *True*). Such alternatives are requested by TOR 3.1.15.5.
- **txtReader.py** – utility script for reading .txt files.
- **wetlands.py** – script for updating wetland parameters in the PND table.

Annex 1: List of electronic deliverables

The principal electronic deliverable – SWAT water quality modeling system with the necessary scripts for its automated generation is described in Section 3.

The water quality modeling system is electronically delivered as an data archive. Un-archiving of it creates a folder structure in **MAINPATH** (folders *Data*, *DataBY*, *lib*, *SETUP* and *SetupBY*). The water quality modeling system is generated automatically by executing the script *main.py* from folders *Setup/Scripts* and *SetupBY/Scripts*.

Table in this Annex lists the deliverables outside the scope of SWAT water quality modeling system.

#	Name	Contents	Section of report	ToR reference
1	<i>Vertices.shp</i>	Vertices of river network	2.1.1	3.1.9.3
2	<i>Edges.shp</i>	Segments of river network	2.1.1	3.1.9.3
3	<i>Network.gdb</i>	Geometric network of rivers	2.1.1	3.1.9.5
4	<i>Polygons.shp</i>	Catchment polygons	2.1.2	3.1.9.7
5	<i>soil.gdb</i>	Soil polygons for LT	2.2	3.1.1
6	<i>dem_5m.aux</i>	Digital terrain	2.4	3.1.3.1
7	<i>landuse.gdb</i>	Land use polygons for LT	2.5	3.1.4, 3.1.12
8	<i>WQ.dat, QWQ.dat, WWTP_Stations</i>	Systematized monthly point source data	2.6	3.1.5
9	<i>Id.xlsx, data.xlsx</i>	Water quality monitoring points and data in lakes	2.13	3.1.14
9	<i>BelVertices.shp BelEdges.shp BelPolygons.shp</i>	Vertices, segments and catchments of river network in Belarus	2.14.1	3.1.15.2

Annex 2: Tables of system variables

Table 1. System variables defining the location of input data.

Variable name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT	Value for BY
countiesFC	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Administrative counties	DATADIR+Counties/counties.shp	N/A
ATMDEP_POLYGONS	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Atmospheric deposition	DATADIR+AtmosphericDeposition/deposition.gdb/fishnet	SAME
BUFFERZONES_POLYGONS	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Buffer zones	DATADIR+Bufferstrips/Bufferstrips.gdb/polygons	N/A
CROP_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Crops	PROJECTDIR+Data/ SWAT2012.mdb	SAME
CROP_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Crops	Crop	SAME
CST_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	CST	PROJECTDIR+Data/ SWAT2012.mdb	SAME
CST_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	CST	CST_User	SAME
MELIORATION_DATA_FILE	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Drainage	DATADIR+MeliorationDB/MEL_DR10LT.gdb/melior_dissolved	N/A
DEMFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP raster	Elevation	DATADIR+DEM/CombinedDEMs/dem_5m	MAINDIR+DataBY/DEM/dem_lks94
ADMINREGIONS_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+Data/ FertCalcData.mdb	MAINDIR+SetupBY/Data/FertCalcData.mdb
ADMINREGIONS_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Fertilization	region_relation	SAME
FERT_DB	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+Data/ FertCalcData.mdb	MAINDIR+SetupBY/Data/FertCalcData.mdb
fertilizerRegional Coefficients	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+Data/FertCoeff/FertCoeff.shp	N/A
largefarmsFC	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Fertilization	DATADIR+LandUse/landuse.gdb/large_farms	N/A
LIVESTOCK_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+Data/ FertCalcData.mdb	MAINDIR+SetupBY/Data/FertCalcData.mdb

Variable name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT	Value for BY
LIVESTOCK_TABLE [Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Fertilization	livestock_Data	SAME
mineralFertilizertable	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/ fertilizer	SAME
PLANNEDIYIELD_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+Data/ FertCalcData.mdb	MAINDIR+SetupBY/ Data/FertCalcData.mdb
PLANNEDIYIELD_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Fertilization	yield_data	SAME
PLANTFERT_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+Data/ FertCalcData.mdb	MAINDIR+SetupBY/Data/ FertCalcData.mdb
PLANTFERT_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Fertilization	Plant_Data	SAME
reservoirlakefc	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Lakes	DATADIR+Lakes&Reservoirs/ lakeresr.shp	MAINDIR+DataBY/Lakes/lakes. gdb/Lakes_Nemunas_lks94
FORESTBIOMASS_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Landuse	PROJECTDIR+Data/ FertCalcData.mdb	MAINDIR+SetupBY/Data/ FertCalcData.mdb
FORESTBIOMASS_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Landuse	Forest_biomass	SAME
LanduseFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP raster	Landuse	DATADIR+LandUse/Landuse.gdb/ landuse	N/A
LUvsSWATTable	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Landuse	DATADIR+LandUse/Landuse.gdb/ globallookup	MAINDIR+DataBY/LandUse/ Landuse.gdb/globallookup
URBAN_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Landuse	PROJECTDIR+Data/ SWAT2012.mdb	SAME
URBAN_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Landuse	urban	SAME
landuse_classes_1	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Landuse update	DATADIR+Corine/corine 2000/ clc00.shp	N/A
landuse_classes_2	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Landuse update	DATADIR+Corine/corine 2006 revised/corine_2006_revised.shp	N/A
lup_lookup_table	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Landuse update	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/ luplookup	N/A
PLANTMGT_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Management	PROJECTDIR+Data/ FertCalcData.mdb	MAINDIR+SetupBY/Data/ FertCalcData.mdb

Variable name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT	Value for BY
PLANTMGT_TABLE [Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Management	PlantMNGPractices	SAME
Q_DATA	str	Input file	ASCII file	Observations	DATADIR+Observations/qobs.txt	SAME
WEATHER_DATA	str	Input file	ASCII file	Observations	DATADIR+observations/ weatherdata.txt	MAINDIR+DataBY/observations/bel arusdata.txt
WGN_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Observations	PROJECTDIR+Data/ SWAT2012.mdb	SAME
WGN_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Observations	WGEN_User	SAME
WQ_DATA	str	Input file	ASCII file	Observations	DATADIR+Observations/wqobs.txt	SAME
PS_MONTHLY_FILE	str	Input file	ASCII file	Point Source	DATADIR+PointSources/ monthly.txt	N/A
PS_YEARLY[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Point Source	DATADIR:PointSources/ Small_PointSources.mdb	N/A
PS_YEARLY[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Point Source	Small_Points	N/A
WUS_FILE	str	Input file	ASCII file	Point Source	DATADIR+PointSources/ WaterUseMonthly.txt	N/A
AnnualPrecipitation Raster	str	Input file	ARCMAP raster	Precipitation correction	DATADIR+Observations/ AnnualPrecipitation/Precip.TIF	SAME
AnnualPrecipitation Stationtable	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Precipitation correction	DATADIR+Observations/ AnnualPrecipitation/statpcp.dbf	SAME
GDR10LTPolygons	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	River data	DATADIR+GDR/GDR10LT.gdb/ PLOTAI	N/A
ManningCoefFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP polyline feature class	River data	DATADIR+RiverParameters/ MANNING/manning.shp	SAME
riverDepthGrid	str	Input file	ARCMAP raster	River data	DATADIR+DEM/Bathymetry/River_beds/ River_beds.gdb/bath_5m	N/A
riverFPPolygons	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	River data	DATADIR+DEM/Bathymetry/River_beds/ River_beds.gdb/polygon	N/A
RiverNodeFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP point feature class	River data	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/node s	SAME

Variable name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT	Value for BY
RiverSegmentFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP polyline feature class	River data	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/river segments	SAME
RiverTableFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	River data	PROJECTDIR+Data/catchmentData.gdb/rivers	SAME
SoilFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Soil	DATADIR+/Soil/soil.gdb/union	MAINDIR+DataBY/Pedology& Topography/pedology_soiltypes_nemunas.shp
SWAT_DB_FILE	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Soil	PROJECTDIR+Data/ SWAT2012.mdb	SAME
USERSOIL_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Soil	PROJECTDIR+Data/ SWAT2012.mdb	SAME
USERSOIL_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Soil	usersoilLT	usersoilBY
CatchmentFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Catchments	SAME
CatchmentsByWatershedTableFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/CatchmentsByWatersheds	SAME
OutletTableFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/outlets	SAME
REGIONALCOEFFICIENT_TABLE[DB]	str	Input file	MsAccess database	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+Data/Regionalization/coefficients.mdb	SAME
REGIONALCOEFFICIENT_TABLE[Table]	str	Input file	MsAccess table	Subbasin and watershed	RegionalCoefficients	SAME
regionFC	str	Input file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+Data/Regionalization/Regionalization.gdb/hydro_regions	N/A
Transboundary CatchmentFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/transboundary	SAME
TransboundaryInletFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/inlets	SAME
WatershedTableFile	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Watersheds	SAME
WaterTransferTable	str	Input file	ARCMAP table	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/WaterTransfer	SAME

Variable name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT	Value for BY
external_Nemunus	str	Input file	ASCII file	Transboundary inlets	externalInflowDir+Watersheds/ Nemunus/Nemunus/SWAT/default/watout.dat	N/A
external_Neris	str	Input file	ASCII file	Transboundary inlets	externalInflowDir+Watersheds/ Nemunus/Neris/SWAT/default/ watout.dat	N/A

Table 2. System variables defining the location of output (intermediate) data for LT and BY (in parenthesis) modeling systems.

Variable Name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)
countiesHRU	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Administrative counties	PROJECTDIR+GIS/landuse/combi_cohru
countiesHRUtxt	str	Output file	ASCII file	Administrative counties	PROJECTDIR+GIS/landuse/combi_cohru.txt
countiesraster	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Administrative counties	PROJECTDIR+GIS/landuse/counties
ATMDEP_BY_CATCHMENTS	str	Output file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Atmospheric deposition	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/atmdepCatchm
BUFFERZONES_BY_CATCHMENTS	str	Output file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Buffer zones	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/buffzonesCatchm
BUFFERZONES_STATISTICS_BY_CATCHMENTS	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Buffer zones	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/buffzonesStat
DRAINAGE_RASTER	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Drainage	PROJECTDIR+GIS/drainage
HRUDRAINAGE_TABLE	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Drainage	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/hrudrainage
HRUDRAINAGE_TABLEtxt	str	Output file	ASCII file	Drainage	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hrudrainage.txt
fertCoefByCatchments	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/fertCoefByCatchm
hrulargefarms	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+GIS/landuse/hrufarms
hrulargefarms_txt	str	Output file	ASCII file	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+GIS/landuse/hrufarms.txt

Variable Name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)
largefarmsraster	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+GIS/landuse/rlargefarms
lugroupbycountyraster	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Landuse/lugrcounty
lugroupbycountyrasterTxt	str	Output file	ASCII file	Fertilization	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Landuse/lugrcounty.txt (N/A)
CatchmentelevationTable	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	HRU	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/catchelev
globalHRUraster	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	HRU	PROJECTDIR+GIS/globalhru
globalHRUraster_filtered	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	HRU	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hrufiltered
globalHRUtxt	str	Output file	ASCII file	HRU	PROJECTDIR+GIS/globalhru.txt
HRUslopeTable	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	HRU	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/hruslopes
HRUslopetxt	str	Output file	ASCII file	HRU	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hruslopes.txt
landusegroup raster	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Landuse	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Landuse/lugroups
LanduseRasterFile	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Landuse	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Landuse/LUraster
Lakesreservoirsby catchments	str	Output file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Landuse update	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/lakesreservoirs
landuse_1_catchments	str	Output file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Landuse update	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/corine2000 (N/A)
landuse_1_table	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Landuse update	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/lup_table1
landuse_2_catchments	str	Output file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	Landuse update	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/corine2006 (N/A)
landuse_2_table	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Landuse update	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/lup_table2
landuse_update_fractions	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Landuse update	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/lupupdate (N/A)
Q_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Observations	PROJECTDIR+Obs/obs.gdb/qobs_catchments

Variable Name	Type	Data type	Storage type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)
WQ_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS	str	Output file	ARCMAP point feature class	Observations	PROJECTDIR+Obs/obs.gdb/wqobs_catchments
PS_catchment_table	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Point Source	PROJECTDIR+Data/PointSources/ps.gdb/ps_catchment
PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE[DB]	str	Output file	MsAccess database	Point Source	PROJECTDIR:Data/PointSources/yearly_PointSources.mdb (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE[Table]	str	Output file	MsAccess table	Point Source	Small_Points(N/A)
catchmentPrecipitation table	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Precipitation correction	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/precipByCatch
GDRintersectCatchments	str	Output file	ARCMAP polygon feature class	River data	PROJECTDIR+GIS/riverParam.gdb/GDR_water_catchments
nodeElevationFile	str	Output file	ARCMAP point feature class	River data	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/node_elevation
nodeElevationASCII file	str	Output file	ASCII file	River data	PROJECTDIR+GIS/node_elevation.txt (N/A)
riverPolyCatchment Intersect	str	Output file	ARCMAP polyline feature class	River data	PROJECTDIR+GIS/riverParam.gdb/riverpolyIntersectCatchm
riverWidthGDR_table	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	River data	PROJECTDIR+GIS/riverParam.gdb/riverWidth
segmentDepthTable	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	River data	PROJECTDIR+GIS/riverParam.gdb/segmentDepth
segmentManningtable	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	River data	PROJECTDIR+GIS/riverParam.gdb/segmentManningCoef
slopeClassRaster	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Slope	PROJECTDIR+GIS/slope/slopeclasses
SlopeFile	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Slope	DATADIR+DEM/CombinedDEMs/slope_5m (PROJECTDIR+GIS/DEM/slope)
SoilRasterFile	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Soil	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Soil/soilraster
SoilvsSWATTable	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Soil	DATADIR+/Soil/soil.gdb/globallookup (DATADIR+/Pedology&Topography/soiltypes.dbf)
CatchmentIDRaster	str	Output file	ARCMAP raster	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+GIS/cmentIDraster
tableCatchmentRegion	str	Output file	ARCMAP table	Subbasin and watershed	PROJECTDIR+GIS/hru.gdb/catchmentsRegions

Table 3. The default values of numerical (or text) variables of water quality modeling system.

Variable name	Type	Data type	Action group	Value
inflowFromBelarus	bool	Parameter	Belarus	FALSE
BUFFERZONES_ COEFFICIENT	float	Parameter	Buffer zones	0.05
SimulationPeriod [FCSTCYCLES]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	0
SimulationPeriod [FCSTDAY]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	0
SimulationPeriod [FCSTYR]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	0
SimulationPeriod[IDAF]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	1
SimulationPeriod[IDAL]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	365
SimulationPeriod [IPRINT]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	1
SimulationPeriod[IYR]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	1994
SimulationPeriod [NBYR]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	19
SimulationPeriod [NYSKIP]	int	Parameter	Calculation period	3
defaultCoefficients	list	Parameter	Default parameters	[('V', 'HRU', 'DEP_IMP', 3100.0), ('R', 'MGT1', 'CN2', 0.0)]
DrainageVars[DDRAIN]	float	Parameter	Drainage	1100
DrainageVars[GDRAIN]	float	Parameter	Drainage	24
DrainageVars[LIMREL]	float	Parameter	Drainage	0.05
DrainageVars[TDRAIN]	float	Parameter	Drainage	24
MELIORATION_ ALLOWED_TYPES	list	Parameter	Drainage	['D']
agriculturalgroups	list	Parameter	Fertilization	['AGRICULTURAL', 'PASTURE']
largefarmFertilizerCoef	float	Parameter	Fertilization	1.2
GW_ConcN [AGRICULTURAL]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	2.5
GW_ConcN[FOREST]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	1.12
GW_ConcN[PASTURE]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	1.15
GW_ConcN[URBAN]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	3.8

Variable name	Type	Data type	Action group	Value
GW_ConcP [AGRICULTURAL]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	0.02
GW_ConcP[FOREST]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	0.06
GW_ConcP[PASTURE]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	0.05
GW_ConcP[URBAN]	float	Parameter	Groundwater	0.04
HRUDefinitionVars [MinimalHruArea]	float	Parameter	HRU	5
lakeParams [Default_depth]	float	Parameter	Lakes	2
lakeParams[Default_ waterlevel_range]	float	Parameter	Lakes	0.2
reservoirlakeFields [Area]	str	Parameter	Lakes	Shape_area
reservoirlakeFields [Depth]	str	Parameter	Lakes	gylis
reservoirlakeFields [RES_ESA]	str	Parameter	Lakes	Savl
reservoirlakeFields [RES_EVOL]	str	Parameter	Lakes	Vavl
reservoirlakeFields [RES_PSA]	str	Parameter	Lakes	Snpl
reservoirlakeFields [RES_PVOL]	str	Parameter	Lakes	Vnpl
reservoirParams [Default_depth]	float	Parameter	Lakes	3
reservoirParams[Default_ waterlevel_range]	float	Parameter	Lakes	0.3
reservoirReleasetime	float	Parameter	Lakes	2
URBAN_PLANT_CODE	str	Parameter	Landuse	WPAS
groupCodeAgriculture	str	Parameter	Landuse update	AGRICULTURAL
groupCodeForest	str	Parameter	Landuse update	FOREST
groupCodePasture	str	Parameter	Landuse update	PASTURE
groupCodeUrban	str	Parameter	Landuse update	URBAN
lup_date	tuple	Parameter	Landuse update	()
management_vars	float	Parameter	Management	100000

Variable name	Type	Data type	Action group	Value
[frst_bioinit]				
management_vars [frst_phu]	float	Parameter	Management	3000
management_vars [ID_Manure]	int	Parameter	Management	55
management_vars [ID_MineralN]	int	Parameter	Management	1
management_vars [ID_MineralP]	int	Parameter	Management	2
management_vars [ID_Tillage]	tuple	Parameter	Management	(108, 109, 1, 111)
management_vars [past_bioinit]	float	Parameter	Management	5000
management_vars [past_phu]	float	Parameter	Management	3000
riverDefaults [defaultDepth]	float	Parameter	River data	2
riverDefaults [defaultManningCoef]	float	Parameter	River data	0.03
riverDefaults [defaultWidth]	float	Parameter	River data	5
RiverSlopeBounds	tuple	Parameter	River data	(0.0001, 0.10000000000000001)
defcoordSystTxt	str	Parameter	Settings	PROJCS['LKS_1994_Lithuania_TM',GEOGCS['GCS_LKS_1994', DATUM['D_Lithuania_1994',SPHEROID['GRS_1980',6378137.0,298.257222101]], PRIMEM['Greenwich',0.0],UNIT['Degree',0.0174532925199433]], PROJECTION['Transverse_Mercator'],PARAMETER['False_Easting',500000.0], PARAMETER['False_Northing',0.0],PARAMETER['Central_Meridian',24.0], PARAMETER['Scale_Factor',0.9998],PARAMETER['Latitude_Of_Origin',0.0], UNIT['Meter',1.0]];-5122000 -10000100 10000;-100000 10000;-100000 10000; 0.001;0.001;0.001;IsHighPrecision
SETUPDIRNAME	str	Parameter	Settings	Setup
SlopeClasses	list	Parameter	Slope	[(4.0, 99999, 2), (0.0, 4.0, 1)]
transBoundaryInlets [88801]	dict	Parameter	Transboundary inlets	{'WQStation': 1, 'QStation': 19, 'External_WATOUT': ''}
transBoundaryInlets	dict	Parameter	Transboundary inlets	{'WQStation': 13, 'QStation': 28, 'External_WATOUT': ''}

Variable name	Type	Data type	Action group	Value
[88802]				
WetlandsVars [wet_maxD]	float	Parameter	Wetland	3
WetlandsVars [wet_normD]	float	Parameter	Wetland	2
WetlandsVars [WetlandLandUseIDs]	list	Parameter	Wetland	['WETN', 'WETF']

Table 4. The default values of parameters defining the field names of the input files (databases) of water quality modeling system.

Variable name	Type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)	Linked Variable name	File name LT (BY)
countiesIDField	str	Administrative counties	KODAS	countiesFC	DATADIR+Counties/counties.shp (N/A)
ATMDEP_VARS[FN_area]	str	Atmospheric deposition	Shape_Area	ATMDEP_POLYGONS	DATADIR+AtmosphericDeposition/deposition.gdb/ fishnet
ATMDEP_VARS[FN_NH4_dry]	str	Atmospheric deposition	NH4_dry	ATMDEP_POLYGONS	DATADIR+AtmosphericDeposition/deposition.gdb/f ishnet
ATMDEP_VARS[FN_NH4_wet]	str	Atmospheric deposition	NH4_wet	ATMDEP_POLYGONS	DATADIR+AtmosphericDeposition/deposition.gdb/f ishnet
ATMDEP_VARS[FN_NO3_dry]	str	Atmospheric deposition	NO3_dry	ATMDEP_POLYGONS	DATADIR+AtmosphericDeposition/deposition.gdb/ fishnet
ATMDEP_VARS[FN_NO3_wet]	str	Atmospheric deposition	NO3_wet	ATMDEP_POLYGONS	DATADIR+AtmosphericDeposition/deposition.gdb/ fishnet
ATMDEP_VARS[FN_precip]	str	Atmospheric deposition	precipitation	ATMDEP_POLYGONS	DATADIR+AtmosphericDeposition/deposition.gdb/ fishnet
CST_TABLE[StationIDField]	str	CST	STATIONID	CST_TABLE[Table]	CST_User
MELIORATION_FIELDNAME_TYPE	str	Drainage	TIPAS	MELIORATION_DATA_FILE	DATADIR+MeliorationDB/MEL_DR10LT.gdb/melior_dissolved (N/A)
fieldname_fertcoeff	str	Fertilization	FertCoeff	fertilizerRegional Coefficients	PROJECTDIR+Data/FertCoeff/FertCoeff.shp (N/A)
fieldname_RegionCode	str	Fertilization	Code	regionFC	PROJECTDIR+Data/Regionalization/Regionalization.gdb/hydro_regions (N/A)
LANDUSEFileVars[FIELD_NAME_LANDUSENAME_LU]	str	Landuse	LUCODE	LanduseRasterFile	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Landuse/Luraster

Variable name	Type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)	Linked Variable name	File name LT (BY)
LANDUSEFileVars[FIELDNAME_LANDUSENAME_RM]	str	Landuse	globalcode	LanduseRasterFile	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Landuse/Luraster
LANDUSEFileVars[FIELDNAME_SWATLUNAME]	str	Landuse	SWATCODE	LanduseRasterFile	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Landuse/Luraster
lupfields[groupfield]	str	Landuse update	GROUP CODE (N/A)	lup_lookup_table	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/luplookup (N/A)
lupfields[lookupfield]	str	Landuse update	CODE_00 (N/A)	lup_lookup_table	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/luplookup (N/A)
lupfields[lu_1_field]	str	Landuse update	CODE_00 (N/A)	lup_lookup_table	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/luplookup (N/A)
lupfields[lu_2_field]	str	Landuse update	CODE_00 (N/A)	lup_lookup_table	PROJECTDIR+GIS/LUP/LUP.gdb/luplookup (N/A)
OBS_FIELD_STAID	str	Observations	stationID	WQ_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS	PROJECTDIR+Obs/obs.gdb/wqobs_catchments
OBS_FIELD_STANAME	str	Observations	name	WQ_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS	PROJECTDIR+Obs/obs.gdb/wqobs_catchments
WGN_TABLE[StationIDField]	str	Observations	STATIONID	WGN_TABLE[Table]	WGEN_User
Field_PS_ID	str	Point Source	PSID	PS_catchment_table	PROJECTDIR+Data/PointSources/ps.gdb/ ps_catchment
Field_PS_Name	str	Point Source	PSName	PS_catchment_table	PROJECTDIR+Data/PointSources/ps.gdb/ ps_catchment
AnnualPFieldNames [Precipitation]	str	Precipitation correction	Precip	AnnualPrecipitation Stationtable	DATADIR+Observations/AnnualPrecipitation/ statpcp.dbf
AnnualPFieldNames[StationID]	str	Precipitation correction	ID	AnnualPrecipitation Stationtable	DATADIR+Observations/AnnualPrecipitation/ statpcp.dbf
fieldNameManningCoef	str	River data	n	ManningCoefFile	DATADIR+RiverParameters/MANNING/manning.shp
fieldnameWidth	str	River data	Width	riverWidthGDR_table	PROJECTDIR+GIS/riverParam.gdb/riverWidth
SoilFileVars[FIELDNAME_SOILNAME_RM]	str	Soil	DetailedCode (SoilCode)	SoilRasterFile	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Soil/soilraster
SoilFileVars[FIELDNAME_SOILNAME_SO]	str	Soil	SoilCode (Soil1)	SoilRasterFile	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Soil/soilraster
SoilFileVars[FIELDNAME_SWATSOILNAME]	str	Soil	SWATCODE	SoilRasterFile	PROJECTDIR+GIS/Soil/soilraster
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_ADDEDAREA]	str	Subbasin and watershed	AddedArea	Transboundary CatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/transboundary

Variable name	Type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)	Linked Variable name	File name LT (BY)
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_AREA]	str	Subbasin and watershed	AREA	CatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Catchments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_BASINNAME]	str	Subbasin and watershed	BasinName	WatershedTableFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Watersheds
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CATCHMENTID_C]	str	Subbasin and watershed	catchmentID	CatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Catchments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CATCHMENTID_CW]	str	Subbasin and watershed	catchmentID	CatchmentsBy WatershedTableFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/ CatchmentsByWatersheds
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CATCHMENTID_R]	str	Subbasin and watershed	catchmentID	RiverSegmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/riversegments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CATCHMENTID_TB]	str	Subbasin and watershed	catchmentID	TransboundaryCatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/transboundary
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CENTROID_LAT]	str	Subbasin and watershed	LAT	CatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Catchments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CENTROID_LON]	str	Subbasin and watershed	LON	CatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Catchments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CENTROID_X]	str	Subbasin and watershed	X	CatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Catchments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_CENTROID_Y]	str	Subbasin and watershed	Y	CatchmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Catchments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_FLOWTO]	str	Subbasin and watershed	flowTo	RiverSegmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/riversegments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_FLOWTO_IL]	str	Subbasin and watershed	flowTo	TransboundaryInletFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/inlets
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_FLOWTO_WT]	str	Subbasin and watershed	flowTo	WaterTransferTable	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/WaterTransfer
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_ID_WT]	str	Subbasin and watershed	OBJECTID	WaterTransferTable	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/WaterTransfer
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_INLETID]	str	Subbasin and watershed	InletID	TransboundaryInletFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/inlets
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_INLETNAME]	str	Subbasin and watershed	InletName	TransboundaryInletFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/inlets
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_LENGTH]	str	Subbasin and watershed	LENGTH	RiverSegmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/riversegments
WatershedDefinitionVars [FIELDNAME_Multiplier]	str	Subbasin and watershed	Multiplier	WaterTransferTable	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/WaterTransfer

Variable name	Type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)	Linked Variable name	File name LT (BY)
AME_MULTIPLIER_WT]		watershed			
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_NODEFROM]	str	Subbasin and watershed	nodeFrom (Begin)	RiverSegmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/riversegments
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_NODEID]	str	Subbasin and watershed	node_ID (ID)	RiverNodeFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/nodes
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_NODETO]	str	Subbasin and watershed	nodeTo (End)	RiverSegmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/riversegments
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_OUTLETID]	str	Subbasin and watershed	OutletID	OutletTableFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/outlets
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_OUTLETID_WT]	str	Subbasin and watershed	OutletID	WaterTransferTable	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/WaterTransfer
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_OUTLETNAME]	str	Subbasin and watershed	OutletName	OutletTableFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/outlets
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_RIVERID]	str	Subbasin and watershed	riverID	RiverTableFile	PROJECTDIR+Data/catchmentData.gdb/river
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_RIVERNAME]	str	Subbasin and watershed	riverName	RiverTableFile	PROJECTDIR+Data/catchmentData.gdb/river
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_RIVERSEGMENTID]	str	Subbasin and watershed	segmentID	RiverSegmentFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/riversegments
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_WATERSHEDID_CW]	str	Subbasin and watershed	watershedID	CatchmentsBy WatershedTableFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/CatchmentsByWatersheds
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_WATERSHEDID_W]	str	Subbasin and watershed	watershedID	WatershedTableFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Watersheds
WatershedDefinitionVars[FIELDN AME_WATERSHEDNAME]	str	Subbasin and watershed	watershedName	WatershedTableFile	PROJECTDIR+catchmentData.gdb/Watersheds
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS[FN_FLOW]	str	Point Source	Discharge (N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS[FN_ID]	str	Point Source	ID(N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS [FN_NAME]	str	Point Source	name(N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS [FN_SUBSTANCE]	str	Point Source	Nutrient (N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS [FN_TYPE]	str	Point Source	Type (N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT	Small_Points (N/A)

Variable name	Type	Action group	Value for LT (BY)	Linked Variable name	File name LT (BY)
				NT_TABLE[Table]	
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS [FN_VALUE]	str	Point Source	concentration(N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHME NT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS[FN_X]	str	Point Source	X(N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHME NT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS [FN_YEAR]	str	Point Source	year(N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHME NT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)
PS_YEARLY_FIELDS[FN_Y]	str	Point Source	Y(N/A)	PS_YEARLY_CATCHME NT_TABLE[Table]	Small_Points (N/A)

Table 5. The values of variables defining the executables and configuration files of water quality modeling system.

Variable name	Type	Data type	Value
mdbTemplateFile	str	MsAccess db	PYPAICSWAT_DIR+config/template.mdb
SWAT_EXE	str	Executable	BINPATH+SWAT2012_AAA.exe
MDB_TO_SWATEXE	str	Executable	BINPATH+MDB_TO_SWAT.exe
UPDATEINLETS_EXE	str	Executable	BINPATH+inlets.exe
ExtractObservedLoads_EXE	str	Executable	BINPATH+ExtractObservedLoads.exe

Annex 3: Database of Lithuanian soil parameters for SWAT model and its methodology

Rengiant Lietuvos teritorijos dirvožemio rodiklių, skirtų SWAT modeliui, paskaičiavimo principus buvo optimizuota ir atnaujinta Lietuvos dirvožemių GIS duomenų bazė Dirv_DR10LT. Jos atnaujinimui bei pritaikymui SWAT modeliavimui buvo panaudota Lietuvos miško ūkio teritorijų augaviečių (SKL_Atdb), Lietuvos kvartero geologijos bei Lietuvos pelkių ir durpynų GIS duomenų bazės.

Rengiant dirvožemių rodiklių duomenų bazę buvo vadovaujama SWAT modelio naudojimo nuostatomis [40], harmonizuota pasaulio dirvožemių duomenų baza (HWSD) [38], ISRIC ir JRC teikiamomis harmonizuotos pasaulio dirvožemių duomenų bazės ataskaitomis [35], [36], [41], [42].

Rengiant SWAT modelio dirvožemio parametrų lentelę vadovautasi Juodosios jūros SWAT modelio dirvožemio parametrų lentelės modeliu.

SWAT modelio lentelėse dirvožemių parametrai yra adaptuoti pagal SWAT modelio reikalavimus. Konkrečios parametrų ir dirvožemio tipų adaptacijos yra pateikiamos prie SWAT modelio parametrų aprašymų.

Metodika susideda iš dviejų dalių:

1. GIS duomenų bazės parengimo bei projekto detalumo reikalavimus atitinkančių dirvožemių tipologinių vienetų, kuriems bus skaičiuojami parametrai, išskyrimo. Šio etapo metu, naudojant Dirv_DR10LT ir SKL_Atdb Lietuvos GIS duomenų bazes, bei Baltarusijos duomenis apimančius Nemuno baseiną buvo suformuluota vientisa GIS duomenų bazė ir sudaryta dirvožemio parametrų lentelė.

2. Principų dirvožemio parametrams, reikalingiems SWAT modelio sudarymui, nustatymas bei rodiklių skaičiavimo metodikos sudarymas.

Dirv_DR10LT ir SKL_Atdb duomenų bazių apjungimo principai

TIKSLAS: apjungti žemės ūkio teritorijų dirvožemių ir miškų ūkio teritorijų augaviečių GIS duomenų bazes miško ūkio teritorijoms suteikiant dirvožemių tipologinę informaciją.

Apjungiant žemės ūkio teritorijų dirvožemių (Dirv_DR10LT) ir miško ūkio teritorijų augaviečių (SKL_Atdb) GIS duomenų bazes buvo atlikti šie veiksmai:

Koreliacija tarp duomenų atlikta keliais pjūviais:

Miško augavietės susietos tarpusavyje pagal dvi sistemas įvertinant jų maistingumą ir drėgnumą.

Tarpusavyje susieti augimo sąlygų tipai (Augavietė (1)) ir augaviečių tipų eilės (Augavietė (2)). Šąsaja atlikta vadovaujantis literatūros šaltiniais [2], [3], [4].

Miško augavietės susietos su TDV-96 dirvožemio sistema. Šąsaja atlikta vadovaujantis literatūros šaltiniais [1], [2], [3].

Miškotvarkos darbų vykdymo instrukcijoje [1] nėra pateikiama šąsaja tarp dirvožemio tipų indeksų ir jų eilės numerio sistematiniame sąrašė. Taip pat nėra pateikiamas ir pats sisteminis sąrašas. Tačiau šis sisteminis sąrašas (32 - 38 lentelės, [3]), taip pat Lietuvos miškų augimviečių tipų schema (3 pav.) yra pateikiama miško dirvožemių žinyne [3]. Nepaisant to, su šio sąrašo naudojimu yra susijusi viena problema – sąrašė pateikiamas dirvožemių sąrašas nėra sunumeruotas. Šio sąrašo numeracija yra atkuriamą vadovaujantis 4 pav. pateikiamu principiniu dirvožemio tipų išsidėstymu miško augaviečių atžvilgiu [1] bei atliekant kontrolinę patikrą vadovaujantis [2] ir [4] šaltinyje pateikiamų miško augimo sąlygų (A₁ – D₅) bei augaviečių 4 pav. [1] aprašu. Atliekant šią koreliaciją taip pat vadovautasi dirvotyros, dirvožemio bei kraštovaizdžio geografijos žiniomis.

Atrinkti ir 1 lentelėje, su miško augavietėmis susiejant, pateikti tik vyraujantys dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai. Taip pat, vadovaujantis Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazės

struktūra (PAVKOMP1-5 stulpeliai), pateikta nedaugiau kaip 5 vyraujantys dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai, kurie galiausiai apibendrinami iki vieno pagrindinio vyraujančio dirvožemio tipologinio vieneto pagal FAO.

Susiejus miško sklypų SKL_Atdb duomenų bazę su kvartero geologijos duomenimis bus sudaryta galimybė patikslinti ir detalizuoti juose esančius dirvožemio tipus. Pvz. atskirti smėlyje susiformavusius jaurinius nuo aliuvinių dirvožemių ir pan.

Suliejant miškų duomenis (SKL_Atdb) su kvartero geologiniais duomenis vyksta miško augaviečių kontūrų perdengimas su teritorijos genezės ir granulimetrinės sudėties informacija. Tokiu būdu kiekvienai augavietei yra priskiriama atitinkamai skirtinga teritorijos genezė bei granulimetrinė sudėtis. Po šio persidengimo tos pačios augavietės tipas pradeda varijuoti pagal geologinę informaciją. Šio perdengimo metu yra sukuriamas stulpelis Aug_G_gran, kuriame yra patalpinta išsami augaviečių, teritorijos genezės bei granulimetrinės sudėties informacija. Taip pat yra sukurtas Aug_G_gr1 stulpelis, kuriame paprastumo ir aiškumo dėlei ta pati informacija patalpinta indeksų pavidalu.

Kadangi miškų dirvožemių tipologijoje vienam augavietės tipui yra priskiriama keli skirtingo tipo dirvožemiai, toks perdengimas, atsižvelgiant į teritorijos kilmę ir granulimetrinę sudėtį įgalina to paties tipo augavietes detalizuoti ir tiksliau joms priskirti konkretų dirvožemio tipologinį vieneta, o granulimetrinės sudėties diferenciacija – maksimaliai tiksliai įvardinti priskirtų dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų fizines ir chemines savybes.

```
# -----  
# miskai_kvarteras_suderinta.py  
# Created on: 2014-04-08 15:50:38.00000  
# (generated by ArcGIS/ModelBuilder)  
# Description:  
# -----  
  
# Set the necessary product code  
# import arcinfo  
  
# Import arcpy module  
import arcpy  
  
# Local variables:  
SKL_Atdb_shp = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb.shp"  
kvartero_geologinis_shp = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu  
duomenys\\Kvartero_geologinis\\kvartero_geologinis.shp"  
miskai_new_dbf = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\miskai_new.dbf"  
miskai_new_2_dbf = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\miskai_new_2.dbf"  
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu  
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"  
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__2_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu  
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"  
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__11_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu  
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"  
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__4_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu  
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"  
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__5_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu  
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"  
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__12_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu  
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"  
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__9_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
```

```
duomenys\Forest_data\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__10_ = "C:\Users\GMF\Desktop\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\Forest_data\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__8_ = "C:\Users\GMF\Desktop\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\Forest_data\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__3_ = "C:\Users\GMF\Desktop\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\Forest_data\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"

# Process: Intersect
arcpy.Intersect_analysis("C:\Users\GMF\Desktop\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\Kvartero_geologinis\kvartero_geologinis.shp' #;'C:\Users\GMF\Desktop\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\Forest_data\SKL_Atdb.shp' #", SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp, "ALL", "", "INPUT")

# Process: Add Field-Augalija_genezė_gran-sudėtis
arcpy.AddField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp, "Aug_G_gran", "TEXT", "", "",
"100", "", "NON_NULLABLE", "NON_REQUIRED", "")

# Process: Calculate Field
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__2_, "Aug_G_gran",
"[augaviete] & [GENEZE] & [LITOLOGIJA]", "VB", "")

# Process: Add Field-Aug_G-gran_trumpiniai
arcpy.AddField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__8_, "Aug_G_gr2", "TEXT", "",
"", "100", "", "NON_NULLABLE", "NON_REQUIRED", "")

# Process: Join Field (2)
arcpy.JoinField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__10_, "Aug_G_gran",
miskai_new_2_dbf, "Aug_G_gran", "")

# Process: Calculate Field (4)
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__3_, "Aug_G_gran",
"[Aug_G_gr1]", "VB", "")

# Process: Add Field-Dirv_tipas
arcpy.AddField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__11_, "SNS_KOM1_T", "TEXT",
"", "", "30", "", "NON_NULLABLE", "NON_REQUIRED", "")

# Process: Add Field-Dirv_tipas (2)
arcpy.AddField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__4_, "SNS_KOM1", "TEXT", "",
"", "30", "", "NON_NULLABLE", "NON_REQUIRED", "")

# Process: Join Field
arcpy.JoinField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__5_, "Aug_G_gran",
miskai_new_dbf, "Aug_G_gran", "")

# Process: Calculate Field (2)
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__12_, "SNS_KOM1_T",
"[Dirv_gran]", "VB", "")

# Process: Calculate Field (3)
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp__9_, "SNS_KOM1",
"[Dirv_tipas]", "VB", "")
```

Miško augavietės susietos su miškininkų pateikiama LTDK-99 sistema. Šąsaja atlikta vadovaujantis literatūros šaltiniu [13].

Miško augavietėms priskirtų dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų kodai atkoduoti vadovaujantis [13] šaltinyje pateiktu dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų, atitinkančių LTDK_99 kodifikatorių, sąrašu.

Atrinkti ir *1 lentelėje*, su miško augavietėmis susiejant, pateikti tik vyraujantys dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai. Taip pat, vadovaujantis Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazės struktūra (SNS_N_KOM1-5, SNS_KOM1-5 ir SNS_KOM1-5T stulpeliai), pateikta nedaugiau kaip 5 vyraujantys dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai. Šio principo laikomasi todėl, nes Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje vienam dirvožemio kontūrai yra pateikiama iki penkių tipologinių vienetų dirvožemių kompleksas. Šio principo laikymasis leis:

Miško sklypui formuoti dirvožemio tipų kompleksą ir tokiu būdu optimizuoti dirvožemių identifikavimo miško sklype tikslumą.

Susiejus miško sklypų SKL_Atdb duomenų bazę su pelkių ir durpynų bei kvartero geologijos duomenimis bus sudaryta galimybė patikslinti ir detalizuoti juose esančius dirvožemio tipus. Pvz. atskirti seklius durpžemius nuo gilių, atskirti smėlyje susiformavusius jaurinius nuo aliuvinių dirvožemių ir pan.

Miškininkų pateikta LTDK-99 miškų dirvožemių sistema konvertuota į LTDK-99 dirvožemių sistemos kodavimą pateikiamą Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje. Konvertavimas atliktas vadovaujantis literatūros šaltiniais [5], [6], [8], [10], [13]

Konvertavimas yra būtinas, nes [13] šaltinyje pateikiamas LTDK-99 sisteminis dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų sąrašas yra optimizuotas pagal šaltinio autorių poreikius ir jis neatitinka oficialaus LTDK-99 kodifikatoriaus. Tačiau jis yra susietas su miško augavietėmis. Remiantis [5], [6], [8], [10] šaltiniais buvo nustatyta, jog [13] šaltinyje pateiktas LTDK-99 sąrašo numeravimas buvo pakeistas iš numeracijos atmetus I ir II lygmens dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų numeravimą. Taigi, papildžius [13] šaltinyje pateiktą numeraciją atmestais numeriais ir sulyginus tai su [5], [6], [8], [10] šaltiniuose pateikiamais kodifikatoriais, buvo atstatyta oficiali dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų numeracija, kuri taip pat yra pateikiama ir Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje.

Atlikta dirvožemių tipologinių vienetų pavadinimų patikra ir korektūra pagal LTDK-99 dirvožemių sistemos pavadinimus pateikiamus Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje.

Nedideli netikslumai dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų įvardijime egzistuoja visuose šaltiniuose pateikiančiuose LTDK-99 dirvožemių sisteminį sąrašą. Netikslumai atsiradę todėl, kad nuo 2001 m., kuomet pirmą kartą oficialiai buvo paskelbta, iki dabar, LTDK-99 dirvožemių klasifikacija buvo tobulinama. Jos patikslinimai ir papildymai buvo atlikti 2005, 2006 bei 2011 metais. Kadangi darbo tikslas yra GIS duomenų bazę parengti ją suderinus su Dirv_DR10LT duomenų baze, todėl miškų augavietėms priskiriamų dirvožemių tipologinių vienetų pavadinimai yra koreguojami Dirv_DR10LT pateikiamo kodifikatoriaus pagrindu.

Miškų augavietėms priskirtų vyraujančių dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų priskyrimo konkrečiam miško augavietės kontūrai principai:

Kiekvienam kontūrai yra priskirta iki penkių tipologinių dirvožemio vienetų indeksų. Jie skiriasi ne tik pagal savo atskiras savybes, tačiau, kai kuriais atvejais yra priskiriami ir skirtingoms I lygmens dirvožemių grupėms. Dirvožemių, juos priskiriant konkrečiam miško kontūrai, pagal jo augavietės tipą, savybių skirtumai grupės viduje sprendžiami formuojant dirvožemių teritorinius kompleksus, t.y. juos išdėstant Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazės SNS_N_KOM1-5, SNS_KOM1-5 ir SNS_KOM1-5T stulpeliuose eilės tvarka kuria jie yra pateikti *1 lentelėje*. Eiliškumas apsprendžia jų svarbą ir vyravimą miško kontūre. Pagrindiniu yra pirmasis eilėje esantis ir į stulpelius SNS_N_KOM1, atitinkamai SNS_KOM1 ir SNS_KOM1T, įrašomas dirvožemio tipas ir su jo užkodavimu susijusi informacija. Visi kiti yra papildantys. Toks išdėstymas yra korektiškas, kai į kompleksą viename kontūre yra įtraukiami tarpusavyje mažai besiskiriantys dirvožemio tipai. Mažai besiskiriančiais laikomi to paties I lygmens dirvožemio tipologinio vieneto ribose esantys, tomis pačiomis savybėmis

tik skirtingu jos raiškumu besiskiriantys dirvožemiai. Pvz. giliai ir sekliai glėjiški – abu jie yra glėjiški, paprastasis, pasotintas ir nepasotintas – visi jie nepasižymi karbonatingumu, arba giliai ir sekliai karbonatingi – abu jie pasižymi karbonatais, bet pastarieji prasideda ne nuo paviršiaus. Šie skirtumai nėra reikšmingi dirvožemio profilio struktūros kontekste, todėl iš esmės netūrėtų įtakoti konkretaus miško kontūro bendrų dirvožemio savybių interpretavimo bei kitų su tuo susijusių dirvožemio rodiklių išskaičiavimo.

Skirtingoms I lygmens dirvožemių tipologinėms grupėms priklausančių dirvožemio vienetų, priskirtų tai pačiai miško augavietei priskyrimas jos miško kontūrai bus apsprendžiamas atsižvelgiant į atliktas pildomas miško kontūrų ir kvartero geologinės informacijos koreliacijas.

Papildoma Miško duomenų bazės SKL_Atdb koreliacija:

Susieti su kvartero geologine M1:200 000 DB būtų patikslinti miškų sklypų litologiją, atskirti palvažemiai, salpžemiai, o taip pat dugninės ir pakraštinės morenos sritys. Ši koreliacija aktuali Detalizuojant dirvožemius Pa, Pb, Pc ir Pd augavietėse.

Susiejus miškų augavietes su kvartero geologinių duomenų litologinę informacija, miško augavietės ribose bus detalizuojama dirvožemio granulimetrinės sudėties informacija: išskiriami smėliai, žvyras, priesmėlis, smėlingas, lengvas, vidutinis ir sunkus priemolis bei molis.

Teritorijos genezės ir amžiaus įvertinimas, konkrečios augavietės miškų kontūrų ribose sudarys galimybę, skirtingus I lygmens dirvožemio tipologinius vienetus priskirti skirtingiems miškų kontūrams. Šiuo atveju svarbus dugninės ir pakraštinės morenos darinių atskyrimas leidžiantis tos pačios miškų augavietės ribose, sunkios granulimetrinės sudėties dirvožemius detalizuoti į rudžemius ir išplautžemius (duginės morenos srityse) bei balkšvažemius (pakraštiniuose moreniniuose dariniuose).

Duomenų bazės kūrimas:

Miškų duomenų bazės papildymas dirvožemių informacija:

Sukuriami atitinkami stulpeliai esantys Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje kuriuose talpinama dirvožemių informacija pagal TDV-96 ir LTDK-99 klasifikacijas ir jų granulimetrinė sudėtis.

Dirv_DR10LT ir SKL_Atdb duomenų bazių apjungimas:

Dirvožemio duomenų bazės Dirv_DR10LT ir miškų duomenų bazės SKL_Atdb apjungimas pagal PAVKOMP1 M kodą. T.y. M kodo plotai pakeičiami miškų plotais su dirvožemių informacija.

Atliekama automatinė miškų ir dirvožemių arealų ribų korektūra, kad nebūtų persidengiančių plotų.

```
# -----  
# miskai_dirv_apjungimas.py  
# Created on: 2014-04-08 15:50:19.00000  
# (generated by ArcGIS/ModelBuilder)  
# Description:  
# -----  
  
# Set the necessary product code  
# import arcinfo  
  
# Import arcpy module  
import arcpy  
  
# Local variables:  
SKL_Atdb_shp = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb.shp"  
kvartero_geologinis_shp = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
```

```
duomenys\\Kvartero_geologinis\\kvartero_geologinis.shp"
konturas_LKS94 = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Dirv_DR10LT_apjungta\\Dirv_DR10LT.gdb\\konturas_LKS94"
miskai_new_dbf = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\miskai_new.dbf"
miskai_new_2_dbf = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\miskai_new_2.dbf"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
Dirvozemiai_miskai_union_shp = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\Dirvozemiai_miskai_union.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_2_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_11_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_4_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_5_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_12_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_9_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_10_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_8_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"
SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_3_ = "C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp"

# Process: Intersect
arcpy.Intersect_analysis("C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Kvartero_geologinis\\kvartero_geologinis.shp' #:'C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu
duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb.shp' #", SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp, "ALL", "", "INPUT")

# Process: Add Field-Augalija_genezė_gran-sudėtis
arcpy.AddField_management(SKLAtdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp, "Aug_G_gran", "TEXT", "", "",
"100", "", "NON_NULLABLE", "NON_REQUIRED", "")

# Process: Calculate Field
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKLAtdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_2_, "Aug_G_gran",
"[augaviete] & [GENEZE] & [LITOLOGIJA]", "VB", "")

# Process: Add Field-Aug_G-gran_trumpiniai
arcpy.AddField_management(SKLAtdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_8_, "Aug_G_gr2", "TEXT", "",
"", "100", "", "NON_NULLABLE", "NON_REQUIRED", "")

# Process: Join Field (2)
arcpy.JoinField_management(SKLAtdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_10_, "Aug_G_gran",
miskai_new_2_dbf, "Aug_G_gran", "")

# Process: Calculate Field (4)
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKLAtdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_3_, "Aug_G_gran",
"[Aug_G_gr1]", "VB", "")

# Process: Add Field-Dirv_tipas
arcpy.AddField_management(SKLAtdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_11_, "SNS_KOM1_T", "TEXT",
```

```
"" , "" , "30" , "" , "NON_NULLABLE" , "NON_REQUIRED" , "" )
```

```
# Process: Add Field-Dirv_tipas (2)
```

```
arcpy.AddField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_4_ , "SNS_KOM1" , "TEXT" , "" , "" , "30" , "" , "NON_NULLABLE" , "NON_REQUIRED" , "" )
```

```
# Process: Join Field
```

```
arcpy.JoinField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_5_ , "Aug_G_gran" , miskai_new_dbf , "Aug_G_gran" , "" )
```

```
# Process: Calculate Field (2)
```

```
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_12_ , "SNS_KOM1_T" , "[Dirv_gran]" , "VB" , "" )
```

```
# Process: Calculate Field (3)
```

```
arcpy.CalculateField_management(SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas_shp_9_ , "SNS_KOM1" , "[Dirv_tipas]" , "VB" , "" )
```

```
# Process: Union
```

```
arcpy.Union_analysis("C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\Dirv_DR10LT_apjungta\\Dirv_DR10LT.gdb\\konturas_LKS94' #;C:\\Users\\GMF\\Desktop\\Dirvozemiu duomenys\\Forest_data\\SKL_Atdb_intersect_kvartetas.shp' #" , Dirvozemiai_miskai_union_shp , "ALL" , "" , "GAPS")
```


1 lentelē. Miško augaviečių ir dirvožemio tipų tarpusavio sąsaja.

Augavietē	Dirvožemio indeksai pagal TDV-96	Dirvožemio indeksai pagal LTKD-99
Nal	J1/s/s	SDp-n/s/s
Nal	AS ^v /s/s	ADk-s/s/s
Šal	J2/s/s	SDe-p/s/s
Nbl	Jt1/s/s	SDp-b/s/s
Nbl	AJ/s/s	ADn1/s/s
Lal	JP1/s/s	SDg4-n/s/s
Lal	AJ/s/s	ADn1/s/s

Augavietė	Dirvožemio indeksai pagal TDV-96	Dirvožemio indeksai pagal LTK-99
Ual	JP2/s/s	GLn-s/s/s
Ual	AJ/s/s	ADn1/s/s
Pa	Pa1/d/s	PDa1/d/s
	Pa2/d/d	PDa2/d/d
Pan	Pa1/d/s	PDa2-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/s
	Pa2/d/d	PDa2-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/s
Nbl	Jt1/s/s	SDp-n/s/s
Nbl	AJ/s/s	ADn1/s/s
Nbp	Jt1/s/p	SDp-n/s/p
Nbp	Jt1/s/p	PLn-g4/s/p
Šbl	E2/s/s	PRk-p/z/z
Lbl	JtP1/s/s	SDg8-n/s/s
Lbl	AJ/s/s	ADn1/s/s
Lbp	JtPh2/s/p	SDg8-n/ps/s
Ubl	JtP2/s/s	JDg5-ih/s/s
	JtPpd2/s/s	GLd-s/s/s
Ubl	APu/d/s	ADd-u/d/s
Ubp	JtPpd2/s/p	JDg8-h/s/p
Pb	Pt1	PDt1/d/s
	Pt2	PDt2/d/d
Pbn	Pt1	PDt1-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/s
	Pt2	PDt2-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/s
Ncl	Jv2/s/s	IDp-t/ps/ps
Ncl	A/s/s	ADk-p/s/s
Ncp	Jv2/s/p	PLn1/ps/s/p1
Ncs	VKj/p/p	JIn2/p/p
Lcl	JvP1/s1/s1	IDp-g0/s1/s1
Lcl	AG/s/s	ADn-g4/s/s
Lcp	JvP1/s/p	PLn-g4/s/p
Šcl	E2/s/s	PRb2/s/s
Šcp	E2/s/p	PRb2/s/p
Šcs	E2/p/p	PRb2/p/p
Lcs	VGj1/p/p	Jlb-g0/p/p
Lcs	DG1/p/p	RDg8-y/p/p
Ucl	JvP2/s/s	GLb-s/s/s
Ucl	ASG/s/s	ADn-g5/s/s
Ucl	DG1/ps/ps	GLb-y/ps/ps
Ucp	JvP2/ps/p	IDg5-n1/sp/p
Ucs	JvP2/p/p	IDg5-e/p/p
Ucs	DG2/p/p	GLb-y/p/p
Pc	Pž1/d/s	PDz1-m/d/s
	Pž2/d/d	PDz2-m/d/d
Pcn	Pž1/d/s	PDž2-m-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/d
	Pž2/d/d	PDž2-m-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/d
Ndp	Jv2/ps/p	Jlb2/ps/p
Nds	VKi/p/p	RDk1/p/p
Nds	AS/s/s	ADk-p/s/s
Šdp	E2/s/p	RDb2-e1/p2/m
Šds	E2/p/p	RDb2-e1/sp/sp, m
Ldl	JvP1/s/s	SDg5-b-wl-(s)/s/s
Ldl	ASG/s/s	ADk-g4/ps/ps
Ldp	JvP1/ps/p	Jlj2-b/sp/p2
Udl	JtPpd2/d/s/s	GLv-s/d/s
Udl	ASG/s/s	ADk-g5/ps/ps
Udp	JvP2/ps/p	Jlg5-b/ps/ps
Uds	VGi2/p2/m	RDg5-k2/p2/m
Uds	DG2/p2/p2	GLk-y/p2/p2
Pd	Pž1/d/sp, m	PDž1/d/sp, m
	Pž2/d/d	PDž2/d/d
Pdn	Pž1/d/sp, m	PDž2-e-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/d
	Pž2/d/d	PDž2-e-(n)-(s)-(r)/d/d
Nfp	Jv1/s/p	PLb2/s1/p1
Nfp	A/ps/ps	ADb2/ps/ps

Augavietė	Dirvožemio indeksai pagal TDV-96	Dirvožemio indeksai pagal LTKD-99
Nfs	VK/p/p, m	RDk1/p/p, m
Nfs	D/p/p	RDk-y/p/p
Lfp	VG1/p/m	RDk1-j2/p/m
Lfl	ASG/s/ps	ADk-g4/s/ps
Lfl		KDz-z-(n)/s/s
Lds	VGj1/p/p, m	IDg4-p/p/p, m
Lds	DG1/p/p	RDg8-y/p/p
Lfs	VG1/p/p, m	RDk1-g1/p/p, m
Lfs	DG1/p/p	ADk-y-g4/p/p
Ufl	ASG/s/s	GLk-s/s/s
Ufp	AG/ps/ps	ADy-k-g5/s/ps
Ufs	VG2/p2/p2, m	RDg5-k1/p2/p2, m
Ufs	DG2/p2/p2	GLk-y/p2/p2

Minimalaus ploto reikalavimo tenkinimas

Pagal SWAT modelio reikalavimus minimali vienatipių dirvožemio plotų suma turi būti nemažesnė kaip 2500 ha.

SWAT parametrų lentelė yra sudaryta pagal Dirv_DR10LT SNS_KOM1_T stulpelį, t.y. pagal dirvožemio tipą pagal FAO ir granulimetrinę sudėtį. Toks parametrų detalumas netenkina SWAT minimalios ploto sumos reikalavimo. Tam kad reikalavimai būtų tenkinami, sudaryta SWAT modelio parametrų lentelė bus agreguota (vidurkinant reikšmes) iki trečio lygmens dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų detalumo, generalizacijos metu žemesnio lygmens vienetus prijungiant prie aukštesnio lygmens vienetų, trečio lygmens vienetus, kurie netenkina ploto reikalavimo, apjungiant su pagal savybes panašiais vienetais. (pvz. sekliai ir giliai glėjiškus konkreta tipo dirvožemius apjungiant į glėjiškus to tipo dirvožemius).

Apjungimas bus pateikiamas pagal atskirą, SWAT lentelėje pateikiamą generalizuotą dirvožemio tipų stulpelį.

SWAT modelio duomenų susiejimas su Nemuno baseino sluoksniu duomenimis

Nemuno baseino dirvožemių GIS sluoksnyje duomenys yra pateikiami tarptautiniais FAO klasifikacijos pavadinimais, II klasifikacinio lygmens detalume. Siekiant Lietuvos teritorijos dirvožemių duomenis suderinti su viso Nemuno baseino duomenimis turi būti išspręsti šie uždaviniai:

1. Tarptautiniai II lygmens dirvožemių FAO pavadinimai perversi į Lietuviškus LTKD-99 dirvožemių pavadinimus.
2. Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje esantys IV ir III lygmens LTKD-99 dirvožemių pavadinimai turi būti generalizuoti iki II lygmens pavadinimų.
3. Sugeneruotos SWAT modelio dirvožemių rodiklių vidutinės reikšmės pagal LTKD-99 klasifikacijos II lygmens pavadinimus.

Tarptautiniai II lygmens dirvožemių FAO pavadinimai perversi į Lietuviškus LTKD-99 dirvožemių pavadinimus vadovaujantis LTKD-99 klasifikacijos dirvožemių sąraše [8] pateikiama tarptautinių ir lietuviškų pavadinimų sąsaja.

FAO tarptautinis dirvožemio II lygmens klasifikacinio vieneto indeksas	LTKD-99 klasifikacijos II lygmens klasifikacinio vieneto indeksas	FAO tarptautinis dirvožemio II lygmens klasifikacinio vieneto indeksas	LTKD-99 klasifikacijos II lygmens klasifikacinio vieneto indeksas
ARb	SDr – rudžemiškieji smėlžemiai	HSf	PDa – aukštapelkės durpžemiai
ARh	SDp – paprastieji	HSs	PDz – žemapelkės durpžemiai

	smėlžemiai		
CMd	RDN – nepasotintieji rudžemiai	LPk	KDk-z – žvyriniai kalkžemiai
CMe	RDb – pasotintieji rudžemiai	LVg	IDg – glėjiškieji išplautžemiai
CMg	RDg – glėjiškieji rudžemiai	LVh	IDp – paprastieji išplautžemiai
FLd	ADn – nepasotintieji salpžemiai	LVj	IDj – stagniniai išplautžemiai
FLe	ADb – pasotintieji salpžemiai	LVk	IDk – karbonatingieji išplautžemiai
FLu	ADd – durpiškieji salpžemiai	PDd	JIn – nepasotintieji balkšvažemiai
GLd	GLn – nepasotintieji šlynžemiai	PDe	JIb – pasotintieji balkšvažemiai
GLe	GLb – pasotintieji šlynžemiai	PDg	JIg – glėjiškieji balkšvažemiai
GLk	GLk – karbonatingieji šlynžemiai	PDj	JIj – stagniškieji balkšvažemiai
GLm	GLv – puveningieji šlynžemiai	PZg	JDg – glėjiškieji jauražemiai
GLu	GLd – durpiškieji šlynžemiai	PZh	JDp – paprastieji jauražemiai

Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje esantys IV ir III lygmens LTDK-99 dirvožemių pavadinimai generalizuoti iki II lygmens pavadinimų ir jie įrašyti į AGR_1BY stulpelį. Šis stulpelis integruotas į visas SWAT modeliui skirtas dirvožemių parametrų lenteles.

Sugeneruotos SWAT modelio dirvožemių rodiklių vidutinės reikšmės pagal LTDK-99 klasifikacijos II lygmens pavadinimus patalpintos į atitinkamus SWAT modelio stulpelius ir sukurta dbf lentelė pavadinimu Dirvožemiai_new_2_agregat_1BY.

SWAT modelio lentelės

Miskai_new – pateikiama miškų, teritorijos genezės, granuliometrinės sudėties ir dirvožemio tipų tarpusavio sąsajos.

Aug_G_gran – išsami lietuviška informacija apie miško sklypo genezę ir granuliometrinę sudėtį.

Aug_G_gr1 – miško sklypo genezės ir granuliometrinės sudėties indeksai.

Augavietė – augavietės tipas.

Dirv_gran – dirvožemio tipas ir jo granuliometrinės sudėties.

Dirv_tipas – dirvožemio III lygmens tipologinio vieneto pavadinimas.

AGR_1By – dirvožemio tipologinio vieneto pavadinimo generalizacija iki II lygmens.

Dirvožemiai_new_2 – SWAT modelio dirvožemio rodiklių išsami lentelė su papildomais dirvožemio tipų generalizacijos stulpeliais.

AGR_SNAM – SNAM stulpelio informacijos generalizacija iki tipologinių vienetų kurių bendras užimamas plotas Lietuvos teritorijoje yra nemažesnis kaip 2500ha.

AGR_1By – dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų pavadinimų generalizuota informacija iki II lygmens tipologinių vienetų pavadinimų ir tenkinanti Nemuno baseino informacinio sluoksnio detalumo reikalavimus.

Dirvožemiai_new_2_agregat – pagal minimalaus ploto (2500ha) reikalavimus generalizuota SWAT rodiklių informacija. Generalizacija atlikta pagal AGR_SNAM stulpelio informaciją.

Dirvožemiai_Baltarusija – Nemuno baseino informacinio sluoksnio FAO dirvožemių tipologinių vienetų tarptautinių pavadinimų pervedimas į LTDK-99 pavadinimus.

Siol1 – dirvožemių tipologinių vienetų II lygmens pavadinimai pagal FAO tarptautinę nomenklatūrą.

FAO_LT – FAO tarptautinių dirvožemių pavadinimų lietuviški variantai pagal LTDK-99.

Dirvožemiai_new_2_agregat_1BY – generalizuoti SWAT modelio dirvožemio rodikliai pagal II lygmens dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų pavadinimus (tenkinant Nemuno baseino GIS sluoksnio detalumo lygmenį).

Dirvožemio rodikliai SWAT modeliui

SNR	Dirvožemio numeris pagal LTDK-99	Pateikiamas Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje
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SNAM	Dirvožemio pavadinimas pagal LTDK-99	Pateikiamas Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje
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HYDGRP	Dirvožemio hidrologinės grupės (A, B, C, D)	Dirvožemio kontūrai indeksas suteikiamas pagal jo granulimetrinę sudėtį ir hidrologinių grupių kriterijus (SWAT, Chapter 22, table 22-1, p. 302-303) A – stiprios infiltracijos – smėlis (s, s1), žvyras (z) B – vidutinės infiltracijos – priemolis (ps), smėlingas priemolis (sp), lengvas ir vidutinis priemolis (p1, p), arba dvinarės, kuomet dulkiškas priemolis (dp) yra giliau kaip 50 cm, arba molis (m) – giliau kaip 100 cm C – silpnos infiltracijos – sunkus priemolis (p2), dulkiškas priemolis (dp, d) lengvas molis (m1), smėlingas molis (sm) arba dvinarės nuogulos, kai sunkus priemolis yra giliau kaip 50 cm, arba lengvas molis 50 - 100 cm gylyje. D – labai silpnos infiltracijos – vidutinis ir sunkus molis (dm, m, m2).
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Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje dirvožemio kontūro granulimetrinė sudėtis yra pateikiama pagal Kačinskį (**TEX_K_D**) ir pagal Fere, (**TEX_F_D**). Nustatant hidrologines grupes rekomenduojama rinktis dirvožemio granulimetrinę grupę pagal Fere, nes tolimesnius SWAT rodiklius (**TEXTURE**, **SOL_CIAY(layer)**, **SOL_SILT(layer)**, **SOL_SAND(layer)**, **SOL_ROCK(layer)**) galima išskaičiuoti naudojantis tik Fere granulimetriniais indeksais.

TEX_K_D: d, d/k, d/m, d/m2, d/p, d/p1, d/p2, d/ps, d/s, d/s1, d/z, k, k/d, k/m, k/p, k/p1, k/p2, k/ps, k/s, k/s1, m, m/d, m/m, m/m1, m/m2, m/p, m/p1, m/p2, m/ps, m/s, m/s/p, m/s1, m/s1/s1, m/z, m1, m1/d, m1/m, m1/m2, m1/p, m1/p1, m1/p2, m1/ps, m1/s, m1/s1, m2, m2/d, m2/m, m2/m1, m2/p, m2/p1, m2/p2, m2/ps, m2/s, m2/z, p, p/d, p/k, p/m, p/m1, p/m2, p/p, p/p1, p/p2, p/ps, p/pv, p/s1, p/z, p/z/s, p1, p1/d, p1/k, p1/m, p1/m1, p1/m2, p1/p, p1/p1, p1/p2, p1/ps, p1/s, p1/s1, p1/z, p2, p2/d, p2/m, p2/m1, p2/m2, p2/p, p2/p1, p2/p2, p2/ps, p2/s, p2/s1, p2/z, ps, ps/d, ps/m, ps/m1, ps/m2, ps/p, ps/p1, ps/p2, ps/ps, ps/ps/p, ps/pv, ps/s, ps/s1, ps/z, pv, pv/m, pv/m2, pv/p, pv/p1, pv/p2, pv/ps, pv/s, pv/z, s, s/d, s/m, s/m1, s/m2, s/p, s/p/s, s/p/z, s/p1, s/p2, s/p2/p, s/ps, s/ps/s, s/s, s/s/z, s/s1, s/z, s1, s1/d, s1/m, s1/m1, s1/m2, s1/p, s1/p/s,

s1/p1, s1/p2, s1/ps, s1/s, s1/s1, s1/z, sapr, sapr/p, sapr/ps, z, z/d, z/m, z/m2, z/p, z/p1, z/p2, z/ps, z/s, z/s1, z/z

TEX_F_D: d, dm, dp, dp/dm, dp/dp2, dp1, dp1/dm, dp1/dp2, dp2, dps, dps/dm, dps/dp, dps/dp1, dps/dp2, m, p1, p1/m, p1/p2, p1/sp2, p2, ps, ps/m, ps/p1, ps/p2, ps/sm, ps/sp, ps/sp2, s, s/dm, s/dp, s/dp1, s/dp2, s/m, s/p1, s/p2, s1, s1/dm, s1/dp, s1/dp1, s1/dp2, s1/m, s1/p1, s1/p2, s1/sp, s1/sp2, sm, sp, sp/m, sp/p2, sp/sm, sp/sp2, sp2

Dirvožemio granulometrija pagal Fere ir hidrologines grupes.

A – s, s1,

B – dps, dps/dm, dps/dp, dps/dp1, p1, ps, ps/p1, ps/sp, s/dp, s/dp1, s/p1, s1/dp, s1/dp1, s1/p1, s1/sp, s1/sp2, sp, sp2

C – dp, dp/dm, dp/dp2, dp1, dp1/dm, dp1/dp2, dp2, dps/dp2, p1/m, p1/p2, p1/sp2, p2, ps/m, ps/p2, ps/sm, ps/sp2, s/dm, s/dp2, s/m, s/p2, s1/dm, s1/dp2, s1/m, s1/p2, sp/m, sp/p2, sp/sm, sp/sp2, sp2

D - d, dm, m, sm,

SOL_ZMX	šaknų įsiskverbimo į dirvožemio profilį gylis.	Žolinės ir sumedėjusios augalijos šaknų ilgis labai skiriasi. Sumedėjusios augalijos šaknų įsiskverbimo gylis priklauso ne tik nuo rūšies tačiau ir nuo dirvožemio granulimetrinės sudėties (pagal P. Crow, 2005) [15] Sumedėjusios augalijos šaknų gylis gali siekti 3-4 metrų gylį [15]. Remiantis Water quality modeling system for Lithuania ID Nr. 100054, User manual (2012) ir Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) rekomendacija, žemės ūkio teritorijoms rekomenduojamas šaknų maksimalus gylis – 1000mm, miškų teritorijoms – 3500 mm Lietuvoje esantiems dirvožemiams būdinga susiklojimo struktūra, įgalinti augalų šaknims potencialiai prasiskverbti per visą dirvožemio profilį. Todėl, priklausomai nuo dirvožemio tipo ir jo profilio gylio, šaknų įsiskverbimo gylis juose atitiks dirvožemio profilio gylį ir svyruos nuo 1200 iki 3200mm.
ANION_EXCL	Dirvožemio poringumo frakcija, pro kurią nepraleidžiami anijonai	Remiantis Water quality modeling system for Lithuania ID Nr. 100054, User manual (2012) rekomendacija – 0,5
SOL_CRK	Potencialus arba maksimalus dirvožemio profilio plyšiuotumas (sutrūkinėjimas)	Šis rodiklis (pagal SWAT Chapter 22, p. 304) skaičiuojamas tik tai dirvožemio dangai, kurioje vyrauja verstžemiai (vertisols) Lietuvos teritorijoje tokie dirvožemiai nėra išskiriami [6], [8], [9], [10]. Šis rodiklis galėtų būti taikomas nebent molyje ir sunkiame priemolyje susiformavusiems dirvožemiams. Tokiu atveju turėtų būti vadovaujama Water quality modeling system for Lithuania ID Nr. 100054, User manual

		(2012) rekomendacija – 0,5
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TEXTURE	dirvožemio sluoksnio granulimetrinė sudėtis	Granulimetrinė sudėtis pateikiama pagal reikšmes esančias su miškais apjungtoje Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje iš stulpelio TEX_F_D (pagal Fere), ir pagal JRC rekomendacijas [35], [36] Optional
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TEX_F_D: d, dm, dp, dp/dm, dp/dp2, dp1, dp1/dm, dp1/dp2, dp2, dps, dps/dm, dps/dp, dps/dp1, dps/dp2, m, p1, p1/m, p1/p2, p1/sp2, p2, ps, ps/m, ps/p1, ps/p2, ps/sm, ps/sp, ps/sp2, s, s/dm, s/dp, s/dp1, s/dp2, s/m, s/p1, s/p2, s1, s1/dm, s1/dp, s1/dp1, s1/dp2, s1/m, s1/p1, s1/p2, s1/sp, s1/sp2, sm, sp, sp/m, sp/p2, sp/sm, sp/sp2, sp2
0 - No information
9 – No texture (histosols, ...)
1 – Coarse (clay \leq 18 % and sand > 65 %)
2 – Medium (18% \leq clay < 35% and sand > 15%, or clay \leq 18% and 15% \leq sand < 65%)
3 – Medium fine (clay < 35 % and sand < 15 %)
4 – Fine (35 % \leq clay < 60 %)
5 - Very fine (clay \geq 60 %)

SOIL_Z(layer)	dirvožemio profilio sluoksnio gylis (mm)	Dirvožemio profilio gylis (mm) – karbonatingose nuogulose jis tapatinamas su karbonatų slūgsojimo gyliu – išskaičiuojamas pagal tipologinei dirvožemių grupei (pagal TDV-96) būdingą vyraujančią karbonatų slūgsojimo gylį [23]. Nekarbonatingose nuogulose jis turėtų būti tapatinamas su C horizonto gyliu, arba maksimaliu karbonatų išplovimo gyliu Lietuvoje, t.y. – apie 3m. [23] Į duomenų bazę būtų įrašomas maksimalus interval gylis, t.y. jei turime 400-700mm, į DB įrašoma 700mm. Tokiu būdu bus parodomas maksimalus tai dirvožemių grupei, Lietuvos sąlygomis galimas dirvožemio dangos storis. Duomenų bazėje, atsižvelgiant į kiekvieno dirvožemio tipologinius diagnostikos ypatumus bus nurodomas A, B ir C horizontų pabaigos gylis. C horizonto pabaigos minimaliu gyliu (toms dirvožemio tipologinėms grupėms, kurių profilis yra seklesnis nei 1200mm), atsižvelgiant į SWAT modelio reikalavimus, bus nurodomas 1200mm gylis. Nustatant pagrindinių horizontų gylius bus vadovaujamas TDV-96 klasifikacija, tačiau duomenų bazėje reikšmės bus pateikiamos jas koreliuojant su LTK-99 tipologija.
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Dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai pagal TDV-96, esantys Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje**.	A*	B*	C*
VG1t, VG1, VKE1, VKS, VKt, VKtg, VG2p, VG2t,	250	300	1200

AVS, AkV, AkVS, ASV	100	-	1200
E3,	100	300	1200
VG2i, VG2ip, VG1i, VG1ip, VKi, VKig, VKip, VKipg,	250	400	1200
E2, JvN2,	100	500	1200
VG1j, VG1jp, VKj, VKjg, VKjp, VKjpg, VG2j, VG2jp,	250	700	1200
A1k, A1kG1, Ak1, Ak1G1, Ak1G2, Ak1G2p,	600	700	1200
Ak, AkG1, AkG2, AG	500	700	1200
Nkm, Ns,	100	700	1200
APt1, APz1, Ad, AdG, Apz,	700	1000	1500
D, DG1, DG2, Nu,	400	1000	1500
ASG, AS	500	1000	1500
A1, A1G1, A1G2,	700	1000	1200
AG1, AG2, Aj,	500	1000	1200
AjP1, AjP2,	300	1000	1200
JP2d, JP2p, JP2v,	300	800	1200
Jv1, Jv1g,	250	1000	1500
JvE1, JvN1, JvP1N1,	150	1000	1200
Nkd, Nkda, Nkdt, Nkdz, Rd, Rkm, Rm,	150	1000	1200
JvP1, JvP2ih, JvP2p, JvS, JvP2	250	800	1200
APt2, APu, APz2,	1000	-	1200
An,	500	700	1200
Jv2, Jv2g,	300	2000	2000
J1, Jt1,	250	1500	1700
J2, Jt2,	300	2000	2200
Jv3, Jv3g, J3,	400	3000	3200
JP ₁ , JP ₂ , JtP2, JtPhpd2, JtP1, JtPh2, JtpdP2,	250	700	1200
Pa1, Pt1, Pz1,	1000	-	1200
Pa2, Pt2, Pz2,	1500	-	1700

*A, B, C horizontu vidutiniai gyliai nurodyti pagal [2] šaltinyje pateikiamas dirvožemio diagnostikos lenteles, karbonatų slūgsojimo gylį. Minimalus C horizonto gylis nurodytas vadovaujantis SWAT modelio reikalavimais.

** Dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų indeksai pateikiami pagal Dirv_DR10LT specifikaciją. SWAT modelyje bus pervedami į LTDK-99 bendrąją tvarką pagal šioje duomenų bazėje pateiktą sąsają.

SOL_BD(layer)	drėgno dirvožemio tankis (Mg/m ³ , arba g/cm ³)	Dirvožemio tankis priklauso nuo dirvožemio granulometrinės sudėties. Jis svyruoja tarp 1.1 ir 1.9 Mg/m ³ . Tankumas, vadovaujantis dirvožemio profilio granulometrine struktūra bus nustatomas A, B ir C horizontams. Nustatant tankumą bus atsižvelgta į organikos buvimą.* Dirvožemio tankį gali įtakoti ir žmogaus taikomos agrotechninės priemonės. Tačiau geografinių tokio tipo duomenų nėra, o ir jie modeliavimo ir šio projekto kontekste nėra aktualūs.
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* Organika yra susitelkusi A horizonte. Yra žinomas dėsningumas jog organika sunkina granulimetrinę sudėtį [2]. Todėl smėlingus (s) horizontus verčia priesmėlingais (ps), priemolį sunkina per vieną sunkumo klasę. T.y. sp1 tampa sp2 ir t.t.

Granulimetrinė sudėtis pagal Fere.	Tankis (Mg/m ³)
Smėlis (s, s1)	1,55

Priemēlis (ps)	1,50
Dulkiškais priemēlis (dps)	1,45
Smēlingais priemolis (sp1, sm)	1,40
Sunkus smēlingais priemolis (sp2)	1,30
Priemolis (p1)	1,20
Dulkiškais priemolis (dp1, dp2)	1,15
Sunkus priemolis (p2)	1,10
Molis (dm, m)	1,05
Durpē (d)	0,40

A horizonta granulometrinēs sudēties tips bus nustatams pagal B horizonta jo granulometrinā tipā sunķinant per vienu tipā [2], t.y. smēļi (s) verķiant priemēliu (ps), priemēļi (ps) – priemoliu (p), lengva priemolē (p1) - vidutiniu (p2) ir t.t.

B ir C horizontu granulometrinē sudētijs yra nurodyta Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje prie dirvožemio tipo indekso. Jei nurodomas tik vienas indeksas – B ir C horizontu granulometrinē sudētijs yra vienoda, jei nurodomas dvigubas indeksas – pirmasis simbolis yra priskiriamas B horizontui, antrasis – C.

dps/dm, dps/dp, dps/dp1, ps/p1, ps/sp, s/dp, s/dp1, s/p1, s1/dp, s1/dp1, s1/p1, s1/sp, s1/sp2, dp/dm, dp/dp2, dp1/dm, dp1/dp2, dp2, dps/dp2, p1/m, p1/p2, p1/sp2, ps/m, ps/p2, ps/sm, ps/sp2, s/dm, s/dp2, s/m, s/p2, s1/dm, s1/dp2, s1/m, s1/p2, sp/m, sp/p2, sp/sm, sp/sp2,

SOL_AWC(layer)	dirvožemio storymēs vandentalpa (mm H ₂ O/mm soil)	Dirvožemio storymēs vandentalpa priklauso nuo dirvožemio granulometrinēs sudēties. Į duomenų bazę būtū įrašoma vidutinēs reikšmēs A, B ir C horizontams.
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granulometrinēs sudēties pavadinimas pagal Fere	Vandens kiekis (mm), kuris sukaupiamas 1 m gylio dirvožemio profilyje
	Vid. mm H ₂ O/mm
Rupus smēlis (s)	0,048
Vidutiniškai rupus smēlis, smulkus smēlis, rišlus smēlis (s1)	0,084
Priemēlis (dps, ps) ir smēlingais priemolis (sp1)	0,125
Priemolis (p1), dulkiškais priemolis (dp1, dp2)	0,159
Sunkus priemolis (p2), smēlingais sunkus priemolis (sp2)	0,177
Smēlingais molis (sm), dulkiškais molis (dm), molis (m)	0,171
Organinis dirvožemis	0,209

Dirvožemio vandentalpa yra nustatoma A, B ir C horizontams vadovaujantis dirvožemio horizontu granulometrine sudētimi.

A horizonta granulometrinēs sudēties tips yra nustatams pagal B horizonta jo granulometrinā tipā sunķinant per vienu tipā [2], t.y. smēļi (s) verķiant priemēliu (ps), priemēļi (ps) – priemoliu (p), lengva priemolē (p1) - vidutiniu (p2) ir t.t.

B ir C horizontu granulometrinē sudētijs yra nurodyta Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje prie dirvožemio tipo indekso. Jei nurodomas tik vienas indeksas – B ir C horizontu granulometrinē sudētijs yra vienoda, jei nurodomas dvigubas indeksas – pirmasis simbolis yra priskiriamas B horizontui, antrasis – C.

dps/dm, dps/dp, dps/dp1, ps/p1, ps/sp, s/dp, s/dp1, s/p1, s1/dp, s1/dp1, s1/p1, s1/sp, s1/sp2, dp/dm, dp/dp2, dp1/dm, dp1/dp2, dp2, dps/dp2, p1/m, p1/p2, p1/sp2, ps/m, ps/p2, ps/sm, ps/sp2, s/dm, s/dp2, s/m, s/p2, s1/dm, s1/dp2, s1/m, s1/p2, sp/m, sp/p2, sp/sm, sp/sp2,

SOL_K(layer)	hidraulinis laidumas (mm/val.)	Dirvožemio hidraulinis laidumas priklauso nuo dirvožemio granulimetrinės sudėties. Kiti veiksniai neturėtų reikšmingai įtakoti šio rodiklio, juolab, kad nėra galimybės Lietuvos mastu tokios įtakos įvertinti. Į duomenų bazę šis rodiklis būtų įrašomas kiekvienam dirvožemio horizontui (A,B,C) atsižvelgiant į jo granulimetrinę sudėtį bei organinės medžiagos buvimą ar nebuvimą.
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Granulimetrinė sudėtis pagal Fere.	Pralaidumo vandeniui	Pralaidumas (mm/ h-1)	Vid. (mm/ h-1)
Smėlis (s,s1)	Labai didelis	> 120	120
Priesmėlis (ps)	Labai didelis	> 120	120
Dulkiškas priesmėlis (dps)	Didelis	60-120	90
Smėlingas priemolis (sp1)	Didelis	60-120	90
Priemolis (p1)	Vidutiniškai didelis	20-60	40
Sunkus smėlingas priemolis (sp2)	Vidutiniškai didelis	20-60	40
Sunkus priemolis (p2)	Vidutiniškas	5-20	12,5
Dulkiškas priemolis (dp1, dp2)	Lėtas	2,5-5	3,75
Smėlingas molis (sm)	Vidutiniškas	5-20	12,5
Lengvas molis (m1)	Lėtas	2,5-5	3,57
Vidutinio sunkumo molis (m)	Vidutiniškas	8,0	8
Dulkiškas molis (dm)	Labai lėtas	< 2,5	2,5
Molis (m2)	Išimtinai lėtas	< 1,0	1,0
Durpės	Labai didelis	300	300

Dirvožemio hidraulinis laidumas yra nustatoma A, B ir C horizontams vadovaujantis dirvožemio horizontų granulimetrine sudėtimi.

A horizonto granulimetrinės sudėties tipas yra nustatomas pagal B horizontą jo granulimetrinės sudėties tipą, dėl organikos santykinai didelio kiekio, lyginant su kitais horizontais, buvimo, sunkinant per vieną tipą [2], t.y. smėlį (s) verčiant priesmėliu (ps), priesmėlį (ps) – priemoliu (p), lengva priemolį (p1) - vidutiniu (p2) ir t.t.

B ir C horizontų granulimetrinė sudėtis yra nurodyta Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje prie dirvožemio tipo indekso. Jei nurodomas tik vienas indeksas – B ir C horizontų granulimetrinė sudėtis yra vienoda, jei nurodomas dvigubas indeksas – pirmasis simbolis yra priskiriamas B horizontui, antrasis – C.

dps/dm, dps/dp, dps/dp1, ps/p1, ps/sp, s/dp, s/dp1, s/p1, s1/dp, s1/dp1, s1/p1, s1/sp, s1/sp2, dp/dm, dp/dp2, dp1/dm, dp1/dp2, dp2, dps/dp2, p1/m, p1/p2, p1/sp2, ps/m, ps/p2, ps/sm, ps/sp2, s/dm, s/dp2, s/m, s/p2, s1/dm, s1/dp2, s1/m, s1/p2, sp/m, sp/p2, sp/sm, sp/sp2,

SOL_CBN(layer)	organinės anglies kiekis (%)	Lietuvos klimato sąlygomis humuso kiekis labiausiai priklauso nuo dirvožemio genetinio tipo, granulimetrinės sudėties, įmirkimo ir sukultūrinimo lygio [9]. Humuso mažiausiai (0,5 – 1,5%) yra sausuose smėlių, daugiausiai (>4 %) – sunkesnės granulimetrinės sudėties
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		<p>labai įmirkusiuose dirvožemiuose, kai kuriuose salpžemiuose. Kituose, dažniausiai glėžiškuose dirvožemiuose humuso yra apie 2-4%, mažiau tų pačių sistematinų vienetų granulimetrinės sudėties automorfiniuose dirvožemiuose [9]. Paskaičiuota pagal metodiką pateiktą [16] šaltinyje. Skaičiuojama humuso kiekį dalinant iš 1,724.</p> <p>Kadangi apie humuso ir atitinkamai organinės anglies pasiskirstymą pilnesnė informacija yra pateikiama TDV-96 dirvožemių klasifikacijos sistemoje, įvedant šiuos duomenis rekomenduojama vadovautis šios klasifikacijos sistematiniais vienetais.</p> <p>Dirvožemių, patenkančių į miškų teritorijas, C_{org} reikšmėms yra taikomas 1,5 koeficientas.</p>
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Organinės anglies kiekis dažniausiai yra skaičiuojamas A horizontui. Čia jis labiausiai ir įvairuoja. Atskirais atvejais, kai kalbama apie specifinius dirvožemio tipus (deliuvinius, kai kuriuos aliuvinius ir pan.), ir gilesniuose sluoksniuose gali būti sutinkami dideli kiekiai organinės medžiagos – tame tarpe ir humuso. Nesant išsamių duomenų, vadovaujantis deliuvinių ir aliuvinių dirvožemių dirvodaros ypatumais, visuose jų genetiniuose horizontuose yra suteikiamas tas pats organinės anglies kiekis. Kitiems dirvožemio tipologiniams vienetais, B horizontui yra suteikiama vidutinė 0,5 %, o C horizontui – 0,25% humuso. **C_{org} atitinkamai B - 0,29% ir C – 0,15%** [43]. Ariamų laukų dirvožemiai turi mažesnę humuso kiekį nei miškų [2], todėl vadovaujantis miško augaviečių tipais [14] bei jiems pateikiamų miškų dirvožemių humusingumu, dirvožemio tipų, patenkančių į miškų teritorijas, humusingumo ir C_{org} reikšmėms turėtų būti taikomas vidutinis 1,5 koeficientas.

Humusas / C_{org} , %*

	s, sl	ps	p	m
Pagal TDV-96**				
VKt, VKtg, VKip, VKipg, VKS, VKE1, VKi, VKig, VKjp, VKjpp, VKj, VKjg		1,7/ 0,99	2,6/ 1,51	
VG1t, VG1, VG1jp, VG1i, VG1ip, VG1j, VG2i, VG2jp, VG2t, VG2ip, VG2p, VG2j,		2,4/ 1,39	2,7/ 1,57	
Jv1, Jv2, Jv3, Jv1g, Jv3g, Jv2g, JvS, JvE1	1,2/ 0,70	1,4/ 0,81	2,1/ 1,22	3,7/ 2,15
J1, J2, J3, Jt1, Jt2,	0,8/ 0,46			
JvN1,	0,8/ 0,46			
JP2v, JvP2, JvP2ih, JP2, JP2d, JP2p, JvP2p, JtP2, JtPhpd2, JtPh2, JtpdP2,	3,6/ 2,08		8,2/ 4,76	
JP1, JvP1N1, JvP1, JtP1,	2,6/ 1,51	3,0/ 1,74	3,2/ 1,86	3,5/ 2,03
AVS, ASV, A1, AkV, AkVS, A1k, Ak, Ak1, AS, Aj,	2,8/ 1,62			
AG, A1G1, AG1, A1kG1, AkG1, ASG, AjP1, Ad, AdG, An,	2,55/ 1,48	3,05/ 1,77	3,55/ 2,06	
A1G2, AG2, Ak1G2, Ak1G2p, AkG2,	3,6/ 2,09	3,85/ 2,23	4,1/ 2,38	
E3, Nkm/p-m, Ns/p-m, E2, JvN2,	1,2/ 0,70			
D,	2,0/ 1,16	2,5/ 1,45	3,8/ 2,20	
DG1,	2,5/ 1,45	3,0/ 1,74	4,0/ 2,32	
DG2,	3,0/ 1,74	3,8/ 2,20	4,5/ 2,61	
APu, APt1, APz1, AjP2, APt2, APz2,	-	-	-	-
Pz1, Pz2, Nkdz,	-	-	-	-

Pt1, Pt2, Nkdt,	-	-	-	-
Pa1, Pa2, Nkda,	-	-	-	-
Nu, Rd, Rkm, Rm,	<0,5/0,29			
Nkm/s, Ns/s,				
Pagal LTDK-99				
PRk	<0,5/0,29			
PRb	0,5-1,5/0,58			
PRn	0,23/0,13			
KDc, KDz	<2,0/1,16			
RDK	7,12/4,13			
RDb	4,4/2,55			
RDN	3,4/1,97			
RDg	4,95/2,87			
IDk	6,4/3,71			
IDp	2,65-4,29/2,01			
IDe	3,49/2,02			
IDj				
IDg	9,22/5,35			
PLb	2,96/1,72			
PLn				
PLv				
PLd				
JIb	6,6-6,9/3,92			
JIn				
JIj				
JIg				
SDk	2,3/1,33			
SDr				
SDp				
SDe	1,45/0,84			
SDg	2,3/1,33			
JDp,	0,69/0,40			
JDf,	1,08-2,33/0,99			
JDg	5,83/3,38			
GLk	2,7/1,57	3,5/2,03	3,9/2,26	4,9/2,84
GLb				
GLv				
GLd				
PDz	26,4/15,31			
PDt	24,9/14,44			
PDa	24,4/14,15			
ADk	2,8/1,62	3,3/1,91	3,9/2,26	5,5/3,19
ADb				
ADn				
ADv, ADd				
ADy				
TDa				
TDi, TDM				

* Humusas, vid % / 1.724 = C_{org}, %

**TDV-96 dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai į LTDK-99 verčiami bendrąja tvarka vadovaujantis Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje pateikiama sąsaja.

SOL_CLAY(layer)	molio kiekis (%) <0.002 mm	Pagal Fere
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		Duomenū bazēje pateikiamos vidutinės reikšmės A,B,C horizontams.
SOL_SILT(layer)	dulkiū kiekis (%) 0.05 – 0.002 mm	Pagal Fere Duomenū bazēje pateikiamos vidutinės reikšmės A,B,C horizontams.
SOL_SAND(layer)	smēlio kiekis (%) – 2.0 – 0.05 mm	Pagal Fere Duomenū bazēje pateikiamos vidutinės reikšmės A,B,C horizontams.
SOL_ROCK(layer)	skeleto kiekis (%) > 2.0 mm	Pagal Fere Duomenū bazēje pateikiamos vidutinės reikšmės A,B,C horizontams.

Dirvožemio sluoksnio granulimetrinė sudėtis*.

Granulimet rinės sudėties pavadinimas	Granulimetrinės frakcijos pagal Fere trikampį							
	Skeletas >2mm		Smėlis (2-0,05mm),		Dulkės (0,05-0,002mm)		Molis (<0,002mm)	
	%	vid.	%	vid.	%	vid.	%	vid.
s	0-10	5,0	85-100	86,8	0-15	7,9	0-10	5,3
s1		0,0	70-85	73,5	0-30	14,0	10-15	12,5
ps	2	2,0	43-79	64,5	11-50	31,0	0-9	4,5
sp	0,5-30	13,0	52-85	69,5	0-39	17,0	9-20	13,5
sp2	0-5	2,5	45-80	60,75	0-28	13,5	20-35	25,75
p1	0,5-5	2,5	23-52	40,1	28-50	42,5	7-27	17,4
p2	5	2,85	20-45	31,8	15-53	34,4	27-40	33,8
dps	-	0,0	15-50	32,5	50-80	65,0	0-5	2,5
da	-	0,0	0-20	10,0	80-100	84,0	0-12	6,0
dp	0	0,0	10-45	27,0	50-80	63,0	5-15	10,0
dp1	-	0,0	0-35	17,0	50-88	65,0	10-27	18,0
dp2	-	0,0	0-20	10,0	40-73	56,5	27-40	33,5
sm	-	0,0	45-65	47,5	0-20	9,5	35-55	43,0
dm	-	0,0	0-20	10,0	40-60	45,0	40-60	45,0
m	-	0,0	0-45	19,5	0-40	16,5	40-100	64,0

*Išskaičiuota pagal granulimetrinės sudėties pavadinimo nustatymo grafinės raiškos Fere trikampį pateiktą [6] šaltinyje ir [8].

Dirvožemio molio, dulkių, smėlio ir skeleto kiekis yra skaičiuojamas atskirai A, B ir C horizontams, vadovaujantis jų granulimetrinės sudėties indeksu pateikiamu Dirv_DR10LT.

dps/dm, dps/dp, dps/dp1, ps/p1, ps/sp, s/dp, s/dp1, s/p1, s1/dp, s1/dp1, s1/p1, s1/sp, s1/sp2, dp/dm, dp/dp2, dp1/dm, dp1/dp2, dp2, dps/dp2, p1/m, p1/p2, p1/sp2, ps/m, ps/p2, ps/sm, ps/sp2, s/dm, s/dp2, s/m, s/p2, s1/dm, s1/dp2, s1/m, s1/p2, sp/m, sp/p2, sp/sm, sp/sp2,

Durpės granulimetrinė sudėtis imama pagal HWSD duomenų bazės Lietuvos teritorijos duomenis.

SOL_ALB(top layer)	dirvožemio albedo	Paviršiaus albedo skaičiuojamas žemės paviršiui atsižvelgiant į jo dirvodarines uolienas (neatsižvelgiant į daugianariškumą) Į duomenų bazę rašomos vidutinės reikšmės būdingos A horizontui.
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Dirvožemio Albedo pagal [20]

Dirvodarinės uolienos	Drėgnas uolienos albedo	Drėgnas uolienos vidutinis albedo
Smėlis (s, s1)	0.24	0.240
Priesmėlis (ps, dps)	0.10-0.19	0.145
Priemolis(sp, sp1, sp2, p1, p2, dp, dp1, dp2)	0.10-0.14	0.120
Molis (dm, m)	0.08	0.080
Durpė (d)	0.05 – 0.15	0.100

USLE_K(top layer)	dirvožemio nuardymo rodiklis	Pagal Wischmeier ir Smith (1978) metodiką pateikiamą SWAT metodikoje: Chapter 22, p. 306-310. Šiam rodikliui apskaičiuoti būtų panaudoti kiti SWAT modelio rodikliai: dirvožemio granulimetrinės sudėties struktūra – smėlio, dulkių bei molio dalelių kiekis; organinės anglies kiekis, dirvožemio hidraulinis laidumas. Taip pat skaičiavimams, nustatant dirvožemio susiklojimo struktūros pobūdį bei hidraulinio laidumo klasę būtų naudojamos, Chapter 22, p. 306-310 pateikiamomis metodinėmis lentelėmis. Gauti SWAT metodika duomenys bus lyginami su [39] šaltinio duomenimis.
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USLE_K koeficiento reikšmės useroil_Lithuania lentelėje yra pateikiamos apibendrinus 3 lentelės (3 lentelė) Lietuvos dirvožemio eroduojamumo koeficientų duomenis pagal granulimetrinę dirvožemio sudėtį. Useroil_Lithuania_agregat_svertinis ir useroil_Lithuania_agregat_BY_svertinis SWAT lentelėse šis koeficientas yra suvidurkintas skaičiuojant svertinį vidurkį pagal vyraujančią dirvožemių granulimetrinę sudėtį bei vadovaujantis dirvožemio tipų klasifikaciniais lygmenimis ir minimalaus modeliui taikomo vienatipių dirvožemių plotų (2500ha) sumos kriterijumi.

3 lentelė. Dirvožemio eroduojamumo koeficientai (K) pagrindiniams regionams Lietuvoje

Table 3. Values of soil erodibility factors (K) for the main regions of Lithuania

Regional Regions	Dirvožemio granulimetrinė sudėtis Soil texture	Eroduojamumo koeficientai Soil erodibility factors
Zemaičių aukštuma / Zemaitija Upland	Smėliai s ₁ /s / Sands	0,16
	Smėliai ps/s / Sands	0,25
	Priesmėliai ps/p-m / Sandy loams	0,37
	Smėlingi ir dulkiški lengvi priemoliai s.d*. p/p-m / Sandy and silty light loams	0,39
	Dulkiški vidutinio sunkumo priemoliai d. p ₁ /p ₁ -m / Silty medium loams	0,5
Baltijos aukštumų rytinė dalis / Eastern part of Baltic Uplands	Dulkiški sunkūs priemoliai d. p ₂ /p ₂ -m / Silty clay loams	0,46
	Smėliai s ₁ /s / Sands	0,05
	Smėliai ps/s / Sands	0,3
	Priesmėliai ps/p-m / Sandy loams	0,32
	Lengvi priemoliai p/p-m / Light loams	0,35
Baltijos aukštumų pietrytinė dalis / South-eastern part of Baltic Uplands	Vidutinio sunkumo priemoliai p ₁ /p ₁ -m / Medium loams	0,36
	Sunkūs priemoliai p ₂ /p ₂ -m / Clay loams	0,38
	Smėliai s s ₁ /s; ps/s / Sands	0,02
Vidurio Lietuva / Central Lithuania	Priesmėliai – lengvi priemoliai ps/p-m; p/p-m / Sandy loams – light loams	0,37
	Smėliai s s ₁ /s; ps/s / Sands	0,15
	Priesmėliai – lengvi priemoliai ps/p-m; p/p-m / Sandy loams – light loams	0,39
	Smėlingi lengvi priemoliai s. p/p-m / Sandy light loams	0,49
	Dulkiški lengvi priemoliai d. p/p-m / Silty light loams	0,53
	d. p ₁ ; p ₂ /p ₂ -m	0,59

* s. – smėlingi / sandy; d. – dulkiški / silty.

Table key: ž – gravel; s – sand; s₁ – loamy sand; ps – sandy loam; p – loam; p₁ – medium loam; p₂ – clay loam, m – clay.

SOL_EC(layer)	elektrinis laidumas (dS/m) modelyje nebus naudojami	Šis rodiklis rodo dirvožemių uždruskėjimą. Lietuvos teritorija yra drėgmės pertekliaus zonoje, todėl dirvožemiams nėra būdingas uždruskėjimas, o šis rodiklis nėra aktualus.
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SOL_CAL(layer)	karbonatų kiekis (%) (0-50%) modelyje nebus naudojami	Dirvožemio karbonatingumas priklauso nuo nuogulų, kuriose jis susiformavęs, genezės bei jų mažiaus [18], [24], [25], [26], [27]. Išsamiausi duomenys yra pateikiami geografiniuose bei geologiniuose šaltiniuose. Taip pat kai kurie duomenys randami ir dirvožemininkų šaltiniuose [8]. Naudotis tiek geografiniais, geologiniais, tiek dirvožemininkų šaltiniais yra nerekomenduotina, nes skiriasi karbonatingumo vertinimo metodikos, todėl duomenys yra sunkiai palyginami tarpusavyje. Kadangi geografiniai ir geologiniai duomenys yra išsamesni, nustatant dirvožemio karbonatų kiekį bei pateikiant Lietuvos mastu, rekomenduojama naudotis geologine ir geografine informacija.
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SOL_PH(layer)	dirvožemio pH	Dirvožemio pH yra atskirai vertinama miško augaviečių [14], [6] ir atskirai žemės ūkio teritorijų dirvožemiams [8], [2], [9].
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Dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai pagal LTKD-99	pH intervalai	Vidutinis pH
PRk/p-m,z	6,5-7,5	7,05
PRb/p-m	6-6,5	6,25
PRn/s	4,5-5,5	5,00
PRn/p	5-5,5	5,25
KDc, KDz, KDkz	6,5-7,5	7,00
RDK	6-7	6,50
RDb	6,5-6,9	6,70
Rdn, RDg	5,5-6	5,75
IDk	4,5-6	5,25
IDp	4,5-5,5	5,00
IDe	<4,5	4,30
IDj	<4,5	4,00
IDg	<=4,5	4,50
PLb	5-6	5,50
PLn	4,5-5	4,75
PLv	5-6	5,50
PLd	4,5-5	4,75
Jlb	4,5-6	5,25
Jln	4,5-5,5	5,00
Jlj	<4,5	4,00
Jlg	<=4,5	4,50
JDg, JDr, JDf	3,5-4,5	4,00
SDk	5,5-6	5,75
SDr	4,5-5,5	5,00
SDp	4,5-5,5	5,00
SDe	<4,5	4,30
SDg	<=4,5	4,50
JDp, JDf, JDg	3,5-4,5	4,00
GLk	5,5-6,5	6,00

Dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai pagal LTKD-99	pH intervalai	Vidutinis pH
GLb	5,5-6,0	5,75
GLn		5,50
GLv	4,5-5,0	4,75
GLd	3,5-4,5	4,00
PDz	4,0-4,5	4,25
PDt	3-4	3,50
PDa	3	3,00
ADk	7-7,5	7,25
ADb	6-6,5	6,25
ADn	5-6	5,50
ADv, ADd	5-5,5	5,25
ADy	5,5-6,5	5,75
TDa	5,5-6,5	5,75
TDi, TDm	6-7,5	6,25

*[8], [2], [9]

SOL_NO3(layer)	Pradinė NO3 koncentracija dirvožemyje (mg N/kg dirvožemio arba ppm)	<p>Azoto išteklius dirvožemyje sudaro organinis ir mineralinis azotas. Didžiąją dalį azoto išteklių dirvožemyje sudaro organinis azotas. Jo kiekiai, praktiškai, gali būti tapatinami su bendrojo azotu. Mineralinį azotą sudaro NH4 ir NO3 formos. Tik apie 1 % bendro azoto sudaro NO3.</p> <p>Lietuvos mastu, mineralinio azoto kiekiai yra pateikiami tik savivaldybių lygmenyje ir tik pagal mineralinio azoto kiekio grupes. Išsamių duomenų pagal dirvožemio tipologinius vienetus ar granulimetrinę jų sudėtį nėra. Tačiau, vadovaujantis aukščiau išsakytais nuostatomis galima naudoti organinio azoto dirvožemyje reikšmes joms taikant koeficientą 0,01.</p>
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SOL_ORGN(layer)	Pradinė organinio N koncentracija dirvožemyje (mg N/kg dirvožemio arba ppm)	N koncentracija dirvožemyje pagal pagrindines dirvožemio grupes ir granulimetrinę sudėtį pateiktas pagal [19]
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Organinio N kiekis.*

	Jv (IDj, PLb, PLn, PLv, PLd, JIb, JIn, JIj, SDk, SDr, SDp, SDe, Jdp, Jdf.)				JPv1(JIg, SDg, GLb, GLv, JDg)				VK (RDk, RDb, RDn, IDk, IDp, IDe)			VG1 (RDg, IDg, GLk, GLd)				Ak (ADk, ADb, ADn, ADv, ADd, ADy)		N2 (PRk, PRb, PRn)
	s	ps	p	m	s	ps	p	m	ps	p	m	s	ps	p	m	s	p	p
0-10	700	900	1000	1900	1400	2000	2600	3700	1200	1200	1800	1700	1700	2500	1800	1800	2400	800
11-20	600	900	900	1800	1200	1600	2200	2600	1100	1100	1800	1700	1300	2200	1700	1400	2100	700
20-30	500	400	500	1300	700	600	1400	1100	700	7000	900	700	400	700	1600	1000	2200	400
31-40	400	300	400	800	600	400	400	800	300	500		400	300	300	600	700	1500	
41-50		200			300	300	300		300	200	100		300	300	600		1100	
51-60	200	200	300		900	200	200	700			700		200	300	500	400		300
61-70	200	200	300	400	300	100	300	500			500	200	200	200	600		1900	
71-80	100		200		100	200	200	600	200	200	400		100	200	400			
81-90			100		300	300	200			200	400	100	100	300	500		1300	
91-100		100					200	500						200			300	
101-110	100						200											
A	600	700	800	1700	1100	1400	2100	2500	1000	1000	1500	1400	1100	1800	1700	1400	2200	750

B	225	225	300	600	440	240	280	650	300	350	400	400	266	300	566	550	1500	300
C	100	100	100		300	300	200	500		200	400	100	100	250	500		665	

*TDV-96 dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai į LTKD-99 verčiami bendrąja tvarka vadovaujantis Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje pateikiama sąsaja.

SOL_SOLP(layer)	Pradinis judriojo P kiekis dirvožemyje (mg N/kg dirvožemio arba ppm)	Duomenų bazėje bus pateikta sąsaja tarp TDV-96 ir LTKD-99 klasifikacijų, todėl, nors judriojo P koncentracija dirvožemyje, lentelėje yra pateikiama pagal TDV-96, tačiau SWAT modelio lentelėje ir duomenų bazėje ji bus konvertuojama į LTKD-99 tipologiją. Duomenys pateikti pagal [19].
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Pradinis judriojo P kiekis dirvožemyje (mg N/kg dirvožemio) [19]*

	Jv1 ps/p1 (IDg)	JPv1 p/p1 (Jlb, Jln)	Jv2 ps/p (IDj)	VGj1 ps/ps/p (IDk, IDp, IDe)	VGj1 p1/p1 (IDk, IDp, IDe)	VGi1 p1/p1/m (RDk, RDb, RDn, RDg)	VGi1 p/p1 (RDk, RDb, RDn, RDg)	Jv1 p/p (IDg, SDg)	JPv1 p/p1 (Jl, Jlg)
A	70	93	190	94	271	150	65	90	42
B	77,5	90,8	68,6	122	510,5	37,5	115,6	55	18,5
C	290	360		58,5	156,6	31	36,8		

*TDV-96 dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai į LTKD-99 verčiami bendrąja tvarka vadovaujantis Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje pateikiama sąsaja.

judriojo P kiekis mg/kg [43]

Horizontalai	Smėlingo priemolio rudžemis		Dulkiško priemolio rudžemis	
	Bendras P	Judrusis P	Bendras P	Judrusis P
A	1800	90	3000	108
B	1500	63,5	2600	114
C	1500	55,5	2250	98

SOL_ORGP (layer)	Pradinis organinio P kiekis dirvožemyje (mg N/kg dirvožemio arba ppm) Optional	Apibendrintos informacijos apie organinio P kiekio svyravimus vyraujančiuose Lietuvos dirvožemiuose nėra. Tačiau yra nustatyta, jog suminio P kiekis dirvožemyje priklauso nuo dirvožemio granulometrinės sudėties, jo pradinio kiekio dirvodarinėse uolienose, dūlėjimo proceso intensyvumo ir kt. dirvodaros veiksnių [43]. Nustatyta, jog moreninės kilmės smėlingame priemolyje suminio fosforo yra žymiai mažiau (0,18%) nei limnoglacialiniame dulkiškame priemolyje (0,30%) [43]. Šias tendencijas patvirtina ir užsienio autorių darbai [44] [45]. Jų darbuose taip pat yra nagrinėjamas suminio ir organinio fosforo tarpusavio santykis. Remiantis šiuo santykiu, perskaičiavus turimus bendrojo (suminio) fosforo kiekius vyraujantiems Lietuvos dirvožemio tipams, galėtume susidaryti daugiau mažiau apibendrinantį vaizdą apie Organinio fosforo kiekius Lietuvos dirvožemiuose.
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[44], [45] Užsienio šaltiniuose yra nagrinėjami suminio (bendrojo) P kiekio santykio su organiniu P priesmielio, dulkiško, dulkiško karbonatingo ir dulkiško sunkaus priemolio

dirvožemių pavydžiai. Šie pavydžiai neduoda visuminio ir išsamaus vaizdo apie šią sąsają, tačiau leidžia išvesti teorinę paralelę ir nustatyti santykį tarp jų išreikštą procentais. Šis santykis, teoriškai galėtų būti taikomas ir Lietuvoje.

Organinio ir suminio P santykis (%) [44], [45]

Nuogulų tipas	Organinio P vidutinė dalis suminiame P kiekyje
Priesmėlis	14,1
Dulkiškas Priemolis	33,7
Karbonatingas dulkiškas priemolis	37,7
Dulkiškas sunkus priemolis	43,9

Bendrojo P kiekis dirvožemyje (mg/kg dirvožemio) [19]*

	J ₁ ^v , JP ₁ ^v ps/s, s ₁ /s, s ₁ /s/p, ps/s/p (PLb, PLn, PLv, PLd, SDK, SDr, SDp, SDe, IDj, Jlb, Jln, Jlj, JDp, JDf, IDp, IDe, IDk, IDp, IDe)	J ₁ ^v , J ₂ ^v ps/p, p/p, p ₁ (IDj, Jlb, Jln, Jlj, JDp, JDf, IDp, IDe, IDk, IDp, IDe)	JP ₁ ^v p/p, p ₁ (Jlg, SDg, JDg)	VG ₁ ps/p, p/p (RDg, IDg, RDk, RDb, RDn, IDk)	VG ₁ p ₂ /p ₂ , m/m (RDg, IDg)	VG ₂ ^j p/p (GLk, GLd, GLb, GLv)	Aliuviniai A ₁ k ps/s, p/p (ADk, ADb, ADn, ADv, ADd, ADy)	Pelkiniai dirvožemiai (PDz, PDt, PDa)
A	1150	1050	1850	900	1800	1900	2450	1650
B	833	933	1133	825	1650	1050	1916	230
C	700	1250	1300	925	1800	1125	1750	160

*TDV-96 dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai į LTKD-99 verčiami bendrąja tvarka vadovaujantis Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje pateikiama sąsąja.

Organinio P kiekis dirvožemyje (mg/kg dirvožemio), remiantis[19]*

	Jv1 ps/p1 (PLb, PLn, PLv, PLd)	JPv1 p/p1 (JDg, Jlg)	Jv2 ps/p (Jlb, Jln, Jlj, JDp, JDf)	VGj1 ps/ps/p (IDp, IDe, IDj, IDg)	VGj1 p1/p1 (IDp, IDe, IDj, IDg)	VGi1 p1/p1/m (RDk, RDb, RDn, RDg, IDk)	VGi1 p/p1 (RDk, RDb, RDn, RDg, IDk)	Jv1 p/p (Jlb, Jln, Jlj)	Jv1g ps/p1 (JDg, Jlg)
A	9,87	31,34	26,79	13,25	65,85	65,85	24,50	30,33	18,89
B	11,40	30,60	68,6	17,20	98,38	16,46	50,74	18,53	23,48
C	97,73	121,32	23,12	22,05	30,18	13,60	16,15	-	-

*TDV-96 dirvožemio tipologiniai vienetai į LTKD-99 verčiami bendrąja tvarka vadovaujantis Dirv_DR10LT duomenų bazėje pateikiama sąsąja.

PPERCO_SUB	fosforo filtravimo koeficientas (10 m ³ /Mg)	fosforo filtravimo koeficientas (10 m ³ /Mg) kadangi šios reikšmės neturime ir nėra galimybės jos apskaičiuoti, pagal SWAT rekomendaciją, fosforo filtracijos koeficientui svyruojant nuo 10 iki 17,5, jo vietoje yra įrašoma 10.0
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Pesticide TITLE	Pesticido pavadinimas	Apibendrintos informacijos pagal vyraujančios dirvožemio tipologines grupes nepavyko rasti.
PESTNUM	Pesticido numeris iš pesticidų duomenų bazės	
PLTPST	pradinis pesticidų kiekis ant lapų (kg ai/ha)	
SOLPST	pradinis pesticidų kiekis dirvožemyje	
PSTENR	dirvožemio prisotinimo pesticidais laipsnis	

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Lietuvos dirvožemių parametru duomenų bazė SWAT modeliui

1 lentelė. user_soil_Lithuania.xls

Lentelėje pateikiami dirvožemio parametrai pagal SWAT modelio reikalavimus M 1:10 000 mastelio detalumu. Lentelėje pateikiama 3554 eilutės pagal trečio lygmens dirvožemio klasifikacinius vienetus bei jų fazes (ketvirtas klasifikacinis lygmuo) pagal granulimetrinę sudėtį.

2 lentelė. user_soil_Lithuania_agregat_svertinis.xls

Lentelėje pateikiami dirvožemio parametrai yra generalizuoti iki trečio lygmens dirvožemio tipologinių vienetų bei agreguoti pagal SWAT modelio reikalavimus iki tipologinių trečio lygmens vienetų užimančių nemažesnę kaip 2500ha Lietuvos teritorijos plotą.

3 lentelė. usersoil_Lithuania_agregat_BY_svertinis.xls

Lentelėje pateikiami dirvožemio parametrai (32 eilutės) yra agreguoti pagal Baltarusijos dirvožemių duomenų bazės detalumą iki antrojo klasifikacinio lygmens tipologinių vienetų atitinkančių Nemuno baseino teritorijos dirvožemių tipologinę įvairovę.

1-3 lentelės pateikiamos Galutinės ataskaitos 3a priede „Dirvožemių duomenys SWAT modeliui“ tik elektroniniame variante.

II. SWAT MODELIO KALIBRAVIMAS

Abstract

The report describes the calibration and validation of the renewed water quality modeling system of Lithuania.

Report is written in English, it contains 168 pages, 147 figures, 79 tables, and 18 references

1. Introduction

This is a revision of the 2nd interim report describing calibration and validation of the renewed SWAT modeling system used by the Environmental Protection Agency according to p.3.2 of the Terms of Reference (further ToR) of the project “*Renewal of a River Basin Districts Management Plans and Programmes of Measures*”, ID 141278.

The modeling system referred to is the one prepared (renewed) in PAIC (2014).

The report describes the calibration and validation of the modeling system in Chapter 2; the respective Sections of this Chapter include:

- Changes in the modelling system since PAIC (2014) in Section 2.1.
- Hydrological and water quality data used for calibration and validation in Section 2.2.
- Calibration and validation strategy in Section 2.3.
- Regionalisation and preliminary evaluation of the runoff regime is summarised in Section 2.4.
- Calibration and validation of the hydrological part of the model in Section 2.5.
- Calibration and validation of the water quality part of the model in Section 2.6.
- Calibration of the Belarus SWAT model in Section 2.7.

Chapter 3 contains a progress report on the preparation of the methodology (Section 3.1) and a tool (Section 3.2) for a spatial optimization of diffuse agricultural pollution reduction measures taking into consideration cost-effectiveness principle according to TOR 3.3.

2. Calibration and validation of renewed SWAT model (3.2)

2.1. Changes in data and methods

The SWAT modeling system was renewed with data and rebuilt in PAIC (2014). The attempts of calculation of the non-calibrated (default) reference situation revealed that additional changes in data and methods are necessary beside the renewal done in PAIC (2014).

2.1.1. SWAT version change

The incorrect calculation of potential evapotranspiration was revealed in SWAT2012 version rev 613. Therefore it was replaced by the most recent SWAT2012 version rev 627.

2.1.2. Management system using PHU

The **plant growth system** was introduced for correct implementation of winter crops, pastures and forests.

The following problems were discovered with data previously supplied for agricultural management praxis in PAIC (2014):

1. Initial biomass for forests was required.
2. The amount of PHU for winter crops to bring plant to maturity if growth started at the 1st of January is required besides the total plant heat unit (PHU) amount required for the plant growth from planting/sowing to harvest. This amount is needed for the first year of the model when winter crops are already planted.
3. In addition for pastures and forests the amount of PHU needed to reach maturity was required.
4. For other management practices (tillage, fertilization, manure application, mowing) the application time should be given as either fraction of base 0 heat units (HU) (if at the time of application crop is not planted) or as a fraction of PHU units (if at the time of application crop is planted). Initially PAIC (2014) all management operations were given as fraction of base 0 heat units.
5. In some regions plants didn't reach required PHU amount for harvest till the end of the year.

Table 1: Forest initial biomass, t/ha.

SWAT_ID	Biomass, t/ha
FRSD	275 137
FRSE	173 321
FRST	275 137
OAK	275 137
ORCD	259 641
PINE	173 321
POPL	231 216
WILL	231 216
RNGB	17 808

Initial biomass of forests (presented in Table 1) was calculated by a methodology described in FAO (1997). Data required for described calculations was acquired from FAO (2010).

Recalculation of application time for management practices was required and was done by following methodology:

1. Similarly as for initial calculations temperature measurements from meteorological stations of Lithuania was used. Only the data from stations with complete data (15 of 18 stations) was used.
2. PHU and base 0 HU amounts for each management practice for each plant were calculated as average amount of PHU or base 0 HU at all meteorological stations and calendar intervals corresponding to the specific plant and management operation. In cases when required this amount was converted to fraction of base 0 yearly HU or fraction of PHU required for plant growth.
3. Adjustment to PHU amount needed for plant growth was made in cases where plant didn't reach amount of PHU required for harvest in any station at any year. Such problem was observed for 6 crops and adjustments were made by calculating the maximum value with which plant finished growth in all of the meteorological stations.
4. For pastures and forests amount of PHU required for plant growth was calculated as average amount of PHU per year multiplied by coefficient of 0.94.

Following results were obtained:

1. In **Table 2** all the crops, their land use type and amount of PHU required for plant growth if crop is planted at the beginning of the year are provided. This PHU amount is required only for winter crops, pastures and forests.

Table 2: Crop identifiers and land use classes.

SWAT_ID	LUCLASS	PHUINITIAL
AGRC	Agricultural	
ALFA	Agricultural	
BARL	Agricultural	
BARR	Barren	
BROS	Pasture	1 125.05
BWHT	Agricultural	

SWAT_ID	LUCLASS	PHUINITIAL
CANA	Agricultural	1 073.37
CANP	Agricultural	
CELR	Agricultural	
CLVR	Pasture	2 575.57
CORN	Agricultural	
CRRT	Agricultural	
CSIL	Agricultural	
FRSD	Forest	817.57
FRSE	Forest	2 841.21
FRST	Forest	817.57
GRBN	Agricultural	
LMIX	Agricultural	
OAK	Forest	817.57
ORCD	Forest	1 295.31
PINE	Forest	2 841.21
POPL	Forest	817.57
RNGB	Forest	554.79
RYE	Agricultural	998.97
STRY	Agricultural	998.97
STTR	Agricultural	1 139.65
STWW	Agricultural	1 337.11
WBAR	Agricultural	932.27
WILL	Forest	817.57
WPAS	Pasture	2 841.21
WTRC	Agricultural	1 139.65
WWHT	Agricultural	1 084.76

2. For the agricultural land and pastures the management praxis was summarized in a separate table, (see examples of data in Tables 3, 4, 5). The name of this table is provided in variable *PLANTMGT_TABLE* of **settings.py** of the model preparation script. This table contains the following fields:

Table 3: Summer crop example.

SWAT_ID	OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
AGRC	1.5	T	0.12	4.00
AGRC	2.5	Phos	0.12	1.00
AGRC	3.5	Nitr	0.12	0.30
AGRC	4.5	Manure	0.12	0.65
AGRC	5.5	P	0.13	1 215.09
AGRC	6.5	Nitr	0.13	0.70
AGRC	7.5	H	1.10	
AGRC	8.5	T	0.01	3.00
AGRC	9.5	Manure	0.09	0.35

- i. SWAT_ID – crop SWAT ID;

- ii. OPNPK – variable that shows the order of management operations from 0 to infinity as a float number;
- iii. OPTYPE – operation type; the following operation types are possible:
 - P – planting, in field VALUE total amount of PHU is given;
 - H – harvest, nothing is required in field VALUE;
 - T – tillage, in field VALUE the type of tillage is given (possible values 1 to 4);
 - Nitr – application of mineral Nitrogen, in field VALUE fraction of total amount of mineral Nitrogen required for the plant is given;
 - Phos - application of mineral Phosphorus, in field VALUE fraction of total amount of mineral Phosphorus required for the plant is given;
 - Manure - application of manure, in field VALUE fraction of total amount of manure required for the plant is given;
 - Mowing – mowing, nothing is required in field VALUE.
- iv. HU – either fraction of base 0 HU or PHU;
- v. VALUE – values in this column depend on the operation performed.

Table 4: Winter crop example.

SWAT_ID	OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
STWW	1.5	Nitr	0.08	0.50
STWW	2.5	Nitr	0.29	0.25
STWW	3.5	Nitr	0.40	0.25
STWW	4.5	H	1.10	
STWW	5.5	T	0.15	3.00
STWW	6.5	Phos	0.15	1.00
STWW	7.5	Manure	0.15	1.00
STWW	8.5	P	0.15	1 441.74

Table 5: Pasture management.

SWAT_ID	OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
BROS	1.5	Manure	0.01	0.65
BROS	2.5	Mowing	0.33	
BROS	3.5	Manure	0.90	0.35
CLVR	1.5	Manure	0.06	0.65
CLVR	2.5	Mowing	0.38	
CLVR	3.5	Manure	0.81	0.35
WPAS	1	Manure	0.07	0.65
WPAS	1.5	Nitr	0.12	1.00
WPAS	2.5	Mowing	0.39	
WPAS	3.5	Manure	0.80	0.35

2.1.3. Changes of SWAT parameters

The list of changes in SWAT parameters and settings from PAIC (2014) were as follows:

1. Use of SWAT version REV627 requires setting the value of NDTARGR variable of .res file to 1.0 instead of 0.0 to correctly respond to the intended reservoir operations.
2. We solved the problems with winter crops not growing by rearranging the heat units of operations. The main difference from summer crops is the type of heat unit scheduling during the cold season. For summer crops the base zero HU are used and end of year is at the 1st of January. For winter crops the plant heat units are used, and there is no end of the year. Winter crops thus do not have the distinct "switch point" (1st of January) and production may drift from year to year. We solved this by careful balancing of PHU for winter crops, see Section 2.1.2.
3. We still do not have clear recipe how to handle the growth of trees. It seems that:
 - a. It is impossible to retain biomass of trees in the range of 100-200 tonnes/ha.
 - b. The biomass of trees have significant impact on the evaporation levels, e.g. evaporation from HRUs which have trees with biomass of 100 tonnes/ha is 20% less than HRUs with the same trees and 10 tonnes/ha. We would like to have a recipe what would be a reasonable initial biomass to use.
 - c. We are not quite sure what to put as potential heat units to bring plants to maturity for trees (PHU_PLT). We used plant based heat units for one year here multiplied by some coefficient close to unity (0.94).
 - d. A couple of crop.dat values seem strange for trees, as there is a default of 30% biomass loss at the start of dormancy for all tree types (including evergreen), which seems very high.
 - e. Also the parameter of min_LAI to which all trees change at the start of dormancy seems strange being 0.75 (both for deciduous and evergreen trees)
4. We are not quite sure what to put as potential heat units to bring plants to maturity for perennial pastures (PHU_PLT). We used plant based heat units for one year here multiplied by some coefficient close to unity (0.94). The initial calculations of the water quality indicate too high leakage of nutrients from the winter pastures. Therefore for winter pastures (WPAS) applied mineral fertilizer amount was reduced to 45% of the original amount.
5. There was some strange behaviour of SWAT with the default setting of dormancy parameter (DORM_HR). Default being 0 resulted in a dormancy period from Dec-16 to Dec-26). We put it to 3 hours, therefore dormancy of perennial plant now occur for a period of approx. end of October – end of February.
6. The initial calculations of the water quality modelling system indicated that the phosphate levels are systematically significantly overestimated (by up to 1700% more). We suspect that high phosphorus levels could be due to high SOL_LABP values. They are provided by soil expert, however, SWAT divides inorganic phosphorus into soluble, active and

stable parts, with active and stable parts being approx. 6 times larger than soluble parts. Typical SOL_LABP values are in the range 50 to 170 mg/kg in the upper soil layer while in the lower layers it can be up to 400 mg/kg. SWAT theoretical manual states “The concentration of solution phosphorus in all layers is initially set to 5 mg/kg soil. This concentration is representative of unmanaged land under native vegetation. A concentration of 25 mg/kg soil in the plow layer is considered representative of cropland”. The abundance of phosphorus also results in a SWAT CHECK message “unusually low phosphorus stress”. To solve this problem (solution was coordinated with the EPA) we assumed SOL_LABP and SOL_ORGP as calibration coefficients and not as the given data.

7. The lakes (and, generally, reservoirs) efficiently smoothens the hydrograph. However, the nutrient (nitrogen) seasonal cycle remains rather distinct. In nature this is because of the stratification of the lakes and reservoirs – the discharge comes from just the upper layer of the stratified water body while SWAT assumes homogeneous mixing. This effect can not be accounted for in SWAT model¹ therefore the lake depth was adjusted to 70% percent from the original depth to simulate the correct nutrient outflow.
8. During the calibration of the pilot basins two SWAT settings were changed from the default to improve the model performance:
 - a. for the calculation of evapotranspiration, IPET.bsn was set to 2 (Hargreav's method) instead of 1 (default as PET method).
 - b. IRTE.bsn was set from IPET=0 (the default value) as variable travel-time to value 1 which is Muskingum method.

2.2. Hydrological and water quality data

The calibration and validation requires a preparation of the set of hydrological and water quality observations (e.g. TOR 3.2.1.7, 3.2.1.8 etc). The data supplied by EPA were used, and preprocessed.

2.2.1. Hydrological data

Daily discharge data for 62 stations were provided. All of the data was preprocessed creating a single database containing all observations from 1997-2012. Afterwards stations that can be calibrated were identified (at least 6 years of data minimum 4 for calibration and 2 for validation). Stations with too few data or too downstream stations were excluded from calibration (these would be used only for validation).

¹ Personal communication with Ann Van Griensven

Figure 1. Discharge stations included in the observation database.

Coordinate correspondence with the name of the station was checked. Initial calculated versus observed PBIAS values of discharge were inspected for extremely large/small values allowing to identify the stations with possibly incorrect coordinates. Based on above mentioned criteria, correction of provided coordinates was made for several stations. The new station positions are shown in Figure 1.

Table 6 provides data about the number of observations, start and end date of the observations as well as the coordinates used in the modeling system, name of the watershed where a station is located (corresponds to a watershed in the system setup) and the station drainage area in the model.

Table 6: Discharge stations in the model. Use of colour codes: “yellow” - too few data, “blue” - too downstream, “green” - calibrated for the Belarus model and used as boundary conditions.

Station name	Nr. of obs.	Start date	End date	X	Y	Watershed name	Mode led area
Akmena-Danė-Kretinga	5477	01.01.97	31.12.12	334 090	6203 758	BalticSea_AkmenaDane	292
Klaipėdos kanalas-Lankupiai	1326	01.01.08	31.12.12	327 773	6160 041	BalticSea_KlaipedaChannel	131
Bartuva-Skuodas	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	344 113	6239 228	Bartuva_Bartuva	612
Svyla-Guntauninkai	3287	01.01.97	31.12.12	658 048	6121 074	Dauguva_Birveta	115
Dubysa-Lyduvėnai	5479	01.01.97	31.12.12	442 362	6151 161	Dubysa_Dubysa	1108
Kražantė-Pluskiai	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	418 309	6165 229	Dubysa_Dubysa	219
Jūra-Tauragė	5843	01.01.97	31.12.12	389 513	6127 032	Jura_Jura	1671
Jūra-Pajūris	318	20.01.12	31.12.12	376 512	6146 937	Jura_Jura	892
Akmena-Paakmenis	5843	01.01.97	31.12.12	395 588	6153 723	Jura_Jura	297
Šešuvis-Skirgailai	3988	01.01.97	31.12.12	395 477	6122 342	Jura_Sesuvis	1879
Platonis-Vaineikiai	1638	01.01.08	31.12.12	466 640	6237 650	Lielupe_MI_Block1	114
Sidarba-Šarkiai	1796	01.01.08	31.12.12	475 887	6239 823	Lielupe_MI_Block2	90
Yslykis-Kyburiai	5387	01.01.97	31.12.12	515 071	6227 710	Lielupe_MI_Block3	66
Merkys-Puvočiai	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	519 707	5996 584	Merkys_Merkys	4004
Skroblus-Dubininkas	1694	01.01.08	31.12.12	517 661	5989 113	Merkys_Merkys	60
Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	532 355	5998 040	Merkys_Pelesa	670
Šalčia-Valkininkai	1827	01.01.08	31.12.12	561 027	6021 747	Merkys_Salcia	774
Minija-Lankupiai	3288	01.01.04	31.12.12	334 708	6154 583	Minija_Minija_midstr	2604
Minija-Priekulė	70	27.01.97	13.11.02	334 350	6160 765	Minija_Minija_midstr	1902
Minija-Kartena	5842	01.01.97	31.12.12	343 391	6203 546	Minija_Minija_upstr	1222
Veivirzas-Mikuzai	280	07.02.12	12.11.12	344 313	6160 691	Minija_Veivirzas	335
Upita-Eidukai	5114	01.01.97	31.12.12	352 299	6166 513	Minija_Veivirzas	48
Daugyvenė-Rimšoniai	2498	01.03.06	31.12.12	495 897	6207 699	Musa_Daugyvene	503

Station name	Nr. of obs.	Start date	End date	X	Y	Watershed name	Mode led area
Kulpe-Siauliai	65	03.02.97	10.12.02	460 859	6205 001	Musa_Kulpe	136
Lėvuo-Bernatoniai	5114	01.01.97	31.12.12	518 488	6190 279	Musa_Levuo_dwnstr	570
Istras-Talackoniai	1461	01.01.97	31.12.00	522 253	6204 559	Musa_Levuo_dwnstr	109
Levuo-Kupiškis	3652	01.01.97	31.12.12	563 880	6194 132	Musa_Levuo_upstr	291
Mūša-Žilpamūšis	4263	01.05.01	31.12.12	526 758	6226 331	Musa_Musa_dwnstr	4395
Mūša-Ustukai	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	517 317	6215 309	Musa_Musa_Upstr	2240
Pyvesa-Žadeikiai	1430	01.01.08	31.12.12	530 625	6211 599	Musa_Pyvesa	462
Tatula-Trečionys	2629	07.01.97	31.12.12	534 348	6220 969	Musa_Tatula	429
Nemuno atš. Atmata-Rusnė	365	01.01.09	31.12.09	333 922	6133 482	Nemunas_Atmata	29869
Mituva-Žindaičiai	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	424 645	6116 296	Nemunas_Mituva	399
Nemunas-Smalininkai	5479	01.01.97	31.12.12	404 461	6103 920	Nemunas_Nemunas_midstr	81692
Nemunas-Kaunas	365	01.01.10	31.12.10	495 305	6083 647	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	46015
Nemunas-Nemajūnai	1794	01.01.08	31.12.12	504 055	6044 618	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	42536
Nemunas-Druskininkai	4398	14.01.97	31.12.12	494 740	5987 186	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	37259
Nemunas-Rusne	365	01.01.08	31.12.08	333 732	6131 908	Nemunas_Skirvyte	37336
Strėva-Semeliškės	5479	01.01.97	31.12.12	541 884	6063 914	Nemunas_Streva	205
Šyša-Šilute	2557	01.01.06	31.12.12	339 721	6136 756	Nemunas_Sysa	373
Verknė-Verbyliškės	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	512 798	6048 497	Nemunas_Verkne	678
Nemunėlis-Tabokinė	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	552 562	6252 188	Nemunelis_Nemunelis_dwnstr	2719
Nemunėlis-Kvetkai	1827	01.01.08	31.12.12	573 802	6221 648	Nemunelis_Nemunelis_dwnstr	765
Neris-Jonava	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	515 714	6101 689	Neris_Neris_dwnstr	24777
Neris-Vilnius	5479	01.01.97	31.12.12	577 343	6062 360	Neris_Neris_upstr	15180
Neris-Buivydžiai	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	610 086	6081 520	Neris_Neris_upstr	11036
Vilnia-Vilnius	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	586 514	6061 394	Neris_Vilnia	628

Station name	Nr. of obs.	Start date	End date	X	Y	Watershed name	Mode led area
Nevežis-Babtai	1827	01.01.08	31.12.12	486 394	6109 121	Nevezis_Nevezis_dwnstr	6342
Sanžilės kan.-Bernatoniai	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	516 158	6182 894	Nevezis_Nevezis_midstr	572
Nevėžis-Panevėžys	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	523 032	6174 015	Nevezis_Nevezis_upstr	1135
Nevėžis-Traupis	1827	01.01.08	31.12.12	538 923	6160 845	Nevezis_Nevezis_upstr	143
Šušvė-Josvainiai	4628	01.01.97	31.12.12	481 609	6129 424	Nevezis_Susve	1068
Šušvė-Šiaulėnai	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	464 159	6171 181	Nevezis_Susve	197
Šešupė-Kudirkos Naumiestis	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	434 928	6069 751	Sesupe_Sesupe_dwnstr	3287
Šešupė-Liubavas	1816	01.01.08	31.12.12	440 547	6028 140	Sesupe_Sesupe_upstr	325
Šventoji-Ukmergė	4749	01.01.97	31.12.12	548 490	6124 434	Shventoji_Shventoji_dwnstr	5354
Šventoji-Anykščiai	4749	01.01.97	31.12.12	565 284	6152 780	Shventoji_Shventoji_midstr	3568
Širvinta-Liukonys	5479	01.01.97	31.12.12	550 129	6100 452	Shventoji_Sirvinta	829
Venta-Leckava	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	391 466	6247 705	Venta_Venta_dwnstr	4049
Venta-Papilė	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	425 404	6224 036	Venta_Venta_upstr	1588
Aunuva-Aunuvėnai	5114	01.01.97	31.12.12	422 205	6198 014	Venta_Venta_upstr	90
Žeimena-Pabradė	5844	01.01.97	31.12.12	611 219	6091 892	Zeimena_Zeimena	2579

2.2.2. Water quality stations

Water quality data for more than 500 stations was provided. Data for 135 data rich stations (identified in the project *Development of methodics and modelling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania*) was pre-processed and a database containing all observations of needed parameters from 1997-2012 in these stations was created.

Figure 2. Water quality stations included in the observation database. Yellow colour indicates stations with less than 100 observation time sets.

Following parameters were included in the database:

- Flow (discharge of the river, m³/s)
- SS (concentration of suspended solids, mg/l)
- BOD7 (concentration of biological oxygen demand, mg/l)
- NH4 (concentration of ammonia, mg/l)
- NO2 (concentration of nitrites, mg/l)
- NO3 (concentration of nitrates, mg/l)

- Ntot (total concentration of nitrogen particles, mg/l)
- PO4 (concentration of phosphates, mg/l)
- Ptot (total concentration of phosphorus particles, mg/l)

Correction of provided coordinates was made for the stations whose positions didn't correspond with the observed data (PBIAS extremely off) and/or name of the station. The new station positions are shown in Figure 2.

Table 7 provides data about the number of observations, start and end date of the observations, name of the watershed it corresponds to in the system setup and the station drainage area in the model.

Table 7: Water quality stations included in the database.

Station name	Nr. of observations	Start date	End date	Watershed name	Modeled area
Akmena - Danė - aukščiau Klaipėdos	95	28.01.1997	13.12.2004	BalticSea_AkmenaDane	552
Akmena - Danė - ties Tūbausiais	156	28.01.1997	15.12.2009	BalticSea_AkmenaDane	181
Akmena - Danė - žiotyse	182	28.01.1997	13.02.2012	BalticSea_AkmenaDane	593
Karaliaus Vilhelmo kanalas - ties Dreverna	63	25.01.2005	02.08.2012	BalticSea_KlaipedaChannel	164
Šventoji - žiotyse	156	24.01.2000	13.11.2012	BalticSea_Sventoji	641
Bartuva - aukščiau Skuodo	192	28.01.1997	11.12.2012	Bartuva_Bartuva	252
Bartuva - žemiau Skuodo	193	28.01.1997	11.12.2012	Bartuva_Bartuva	619
Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje	191	21.01.1997	19.11.2012	Dauguva_Birveta	1087
Dysna - ties Kačergiške	96	24.01.2005	11.12.2012	Dauguva_Dysna	452
Laukesa - žemiau Zarasų	160	15.01.1997	10.07.2012	Dauguva_Laukesa	212
Kražantė - žemiau Kelmės	94	07.01.1997	09.11.2004	Dubysa_Dubysa	374
Kražantė - aukščiau Kelmės	102	07.01.1997	15.10.2007	Dubysa_Dubysa	279
Dubysa - ties Kaulakiais, ties keliu Nr.225	60	25.01.2005	09.12.2009	Dubysa_Dubysa	1284
Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus	192	15.01.1997	05.12.2012	Dubysa_Dubysa	2001
Jūra - aukščiau Tauragės	96	27.01.1997	15.12.2004	Jura_Jura	1671
Lokysta - žemiau Šilalės	96	27.01.1997	15.12.2004	Jura_Jura	131

Station name	Nr. of observations	Start date	End date	Watershed name	Modeled area
Jūra - žemiau Tauragės	97	27.01.1997	01.06.2005	Jura_Jura	3593
Akmėna - aukščiau Pagramančio	64	26.01.2005	01.10.2012	Jura_Jura	394
Jūra - ties Mociškiais	96	26.01.2005	10.12.2012	Jura_Jura	3935
Šaltuona - žemiau Raseinių	94	16.01.1997	14.12.2004	Jura_Sesuvis	272
Šešuvis - ties Taubučiais	60	25.01.2005	09.12.2009	Jura_Sesuvis	264
Šešuvis - ties Skirgailiais	110	27.01.1997	03.08.2010	Jura_Sesuvis	1878
Platonis - pasienyje	95	27.01.2005	06.12.2012	Lielupe_MI_Block1	135
Sidabra - žemiau Joniškio	95	06.01.1997	12.12.2004	Lielupe_MI_Block2	35
Sidabra - Latvijos pasienyje	190	06.01.1997	19.11.2012	Lielupe_MI_Block2	104
Merkys - aukščiau Varėnos	96	14.01.1997	08.12.2004	Merkys_Merkys	2583
Skroblus - žemiau Dubininkų	109	14.01.1997	04.12.2006	Merkys_Merkys	73
Merkys - žemiau Puvočių	192	14.01.1997	03.12.2012	Merkys_Merkys	4010
Ūla - Pelesa - ties Kašėtomis	64	24.01.2005	10.10.2012	Merkys_Pelesa	549
Šalčia - žemiau Šalčininkų	108	14.01.1997	07.12.2006	Merkys_Salcia	32
Minija - žemiau Priekulės	94	27.01.1997	15.12.2004	Minija_Minija_dwnstr	2485
Minija - ties Suvernais	96	25.01.2005	12.12.2012	Minija_Minija_dwnstr	2816
Minija - žemiau Gargždų	109	28.01.1997	20.07.2010	Minija_Minija_midstr	1669
Minija - žemiau Plungės	95	08.01.1997	13.12.2004	Minija_Minija_upstr	878
Minija - aukščiau Plungės	96	08.01.1997	18.07.2005	Minija_Minija_upstr	420
Salantas - ties Nasrėnais	36	24.01.2005	10.12.2007	Minija_Minija_upstr	261
Graumėna - ties Pakalniškiais	36	25.01.2005	11.12.2007	Minija_Veivirzas	52
Veiviržas - ties Veiviržėnais	159	28.01.1997	26.09.2012	Minija_Veivirzas	97
Daugyvenė - žiotyse	191	07.01.1997	06.12.2012	Musa_Daugyvene	503
Obelė - žemiau Radviliškio	95	07.01.1997	14.12.2004	Musa_Kruoja	6
Obelė - žiotyse	92	07.01.1997	14.12.2004	Musa_Kruoja	312
Kruoja - žiotyse	94	07.01.1997	14.12.2004	Musa_Kruoja	353
Kulpė - žemiau Šiaulių	95	06.01.1997	12.12.2004	Musa_Kulpe	129
Kulpė - žiotyse	94	03.02.1997	12.12.2004	Musa_Kulpe	219

Station name	Nr. of observations	Start date	End date	Watershed name	Modeled area
Lėvuo - aukščiau Pasvalio	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Musa_Levuo_dwnstr	947
Lėvuo - žiotyse	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Musa_Levuo_dwnstr	1035
Lėvuo - žemiau Kupiškio	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Musa_Levuo_upstr	484
Lėvuo - aukščiau Kupiškio	192	07.01.1997	19.12.2012	Musa_Levuo_upstr	289
Mūša - žemiau Saločių	192	07.01.1997	19.12.2012	Musa_Musa_dwnstr	4491
Mūša - aukščiau Kulpės	95	06.01.1997	12.12.2004	Musa_Musa_Upstr	603
Mūša - žemiau Kulpės	95	06.01.1997	12.12.2004	Musa_Musa_Upstr	319
Pyvesa - tarp Žadeikių ir Geivitonių	40	25.01.2005	04.10.2012	Musa_Pyvesa	455
Tatula - žemiau Biržų	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Musa_Tatula	270
Tatula - ties Trečionimis	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Musa_Tatula	454
Tatula - aukščiau Biržų	192	07.01.1997	19.12.2012	Musa_Tatula	182
Vilka - ties Gudais	96	26.01.2005	10.12.2012	Nemunas_Gege	177
Jiesia - ties Šilavotu	52	25.01.2005	02.10.2012	Nemunas_Jiesia	122
Nemunas - aukščiau Rusnės, aukščiau Leitės	149	24.03.1997	10.09.2012	Nemunas_Nemunas_dwnstr	74497
Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Zapyškiu	62	19.01.2000	07.12.2004	Nemunas_Nemunas_midstr	78058
Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Kulautuva	93	19.01.2000	06.04.2011	Nemunas_Nemunas_midstr	78051
Nemunas - žemiau Smalininkų	189	26.02.1997	05.12.2012	Nemunas_Nemunas_midstr	81692
Nemunas - ties Pagėgiais, ties keliu Nr. A12	84	18.01.2006	10.12.2012	Nemunas_Nemunas_midstr	92392
Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	73	09.01.1997	02.12.2002	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	42432
Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	73	14.01.1997	02.12.2002	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	37422
Nemunas - aukščiau Alytaus	96	09.01.1997	02.11.2004	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	42428
Nemunas - aukščiau Prienų	96	09.01.1997	02.11.2004	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	43314
Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	96	14.01.1997	02.11.2004	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	37422
Nemunas - aukščiau Kauno	100	15.01.1997	09.11.2004	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	44236
Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	108	09.01.1997	07.11.2006	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	42432

Station name	Nr. of observations	Start date	End date	Watershed name	Modeled area
Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	205	14.01.1997	05.11.2012	Nemunas_Nemunas_upstr	37248
Nemunas - Skirvytė aukščiau Rusnės	189	12.01.1998	14.11.2012	Nemunas_Skirvyte	37336
Strėva - ties Liutonimis	97	14.01.1997	10.11.2004	Nemunas_Streva	526
Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių	96	27.01.1997	20.12.2004	Nemunas_Streva	215
Šyša - aukščiau Šilutės	96	27.01.1997	14.12.2004	Nemunas_Sysa	349
Šyša - žemiau Šilutės	191	27.01.1997	12.12.2012	Nemunas_Sysa	374
Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Nemunelis_Nemunelis_dwnstr	3726
Nemunėlis - Tabokinė	95	25.01.2005	19.12.2012	Nemunelis_Nemunelis_dwnstr	2719
Laukupė - žemiau Rokiškio	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Nemunelis_Nemunelis_upstr	6
Lomena - žemiau Kaišiadorių	100	14.01.1997	13.07.2005	Neris_Lomena	63
Neris - žemiau Jonavos	62	14.01.1998	03.02.2003	Neris_Neris_dwnstr	24759
Neris - aukščiau Jonavos	96	07.01.1997	06.12.2004	Neris_Neris_dwnstr	17734
Neris - žemiau Jonavos	96	07.01.1997	06.12.2004	Neris_Neris_dwnstr	24807
Žiežmara - ties Paparčiais	64	26.01.2005	09.10.2012	Neris_Neris_dwnstr	56
Neris - aukščiau Kauno	193	07.01.1997	04.12.2012	Neris_Neris_dwnstr	25122
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	72	15.01.1997	09.12.2002	Neris_Neris_upstr	15271
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	72	15.01.1997	09.12.2002	Neris_Neris_upstr	15271
Neris - aukščiau Vilniaus	96	15.01.1997	13.12.2004	Neris_Neris_upstr	14469
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	108	15.01.1997	05.12.2005	Neris_Neris_upstr	15300
Neris - ties Buivydžiais	192	15.01.1997	01.10.2012	Neris_Neris_upstr	11036
Vilnia - aukščiau N.Vilnios	96	08.01.1997	13.12.2004	Neris_Vilnia	567
Vilnia - žiotyse	96	08.01.1997	13.12.2004	Neris_Vilnia	631
Kena - ties Rukainiais, ties keliu Nr.A3	64	27.01.2005	25.09.2012	Neris_Vilnia	55
Nevėžis - žemiau Kėdainių	100	09.01.1997	04.10.2004	Nevezis_Nevezis_dwnstr	4558
Nevėžis - aukščiau Raudondvario	194	09.01.1997	01.10.2012	Nevezis_Nevezis_dwnstr	6645
Nevėžis - aukščiau Kėdainių	101	09.01.1997	04.10.2004	Nevezis_Nevezis_midstr	3456
Nevėžis - žemiau Panevėžio	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Nevezis_Nevezis_midstr	1882

Station name	Nr. of observations	Start date	End date	Watershed name	Modeled area
Nevēžis - aukščiau Panevėžio	96	07.01.1997	07.12.2004	Nevezis_Nevezis_upstr	751
Juosta - žemiau Jackagalio	136	07.01.1997	24.09.2012	Nevezis_Nevezis_upstr	122
Šušvė - žiotyse	191	09.01.1997	03.12.2012	Nevezis_Susve	1128
Siesartis - žiotyse	48	09.01.2001	14.12.2004	Sesupe_Sesupe_dwnstr	201
Siesartis - žemiau Šakių	101	15.01.1997	20.10.2010	Sesupe_Sesupe_dwnstr	134
Šešupė - Kaliningrado srit. pasienyje	155	08.02.2000	12.11.2012	Sesupe_Sesupe_dwnstr	5505
Šešupė - aukščiau Marijampolės	96	15.01.1997	15.12.2004	Sesupe_Sesupe_upstr	1796
Šešupė - žemiau Marijampolės	96	15.01.1997	15.12.2004	Sesupe_Sesupe_upstr	1849
Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	101	15.01.1997	19.10.2011	Sesupe_Sesupe_upstr	491
Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	192	15.01.1997	19.12.2012	Sesupe_Sesupe_upstr	324
Rausvė - ties Nadrausve	96	18.01.2005	19.12.2012	Sesupe_Sesupe_upstr	183
Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio	96	15.01.1997	14.12.2004	Sesupe_Sirvinta	169
Širvinta - žiotyse	48	09.01.2001	14.12.2004	Sesupe_Sirvinta	312
Višakis - aukščiau Pilviškių (kelias 137)	44	18.01.2005	18.10.2011	Sesupe_Visakis	338
Šventoji - ties Bindzeliškiais, ties Pašilės žiotym	36	25.01.2005	19.12.2007	Shventoji_Shventoji_A	1409
Šventoji - aukščiau Ukmergės	96	09.01.1997	16.12.2004	Shventoji_Shventoji_dwnstr	5322
Šventoji - žemiau Ukmergės	96	09.01.1997	16.12.2004	Shventoji_Shventoji_dwnstr	5408
Šventoji - žiotyse	180	14.01.1998	04.12.2012	Shventoji_Shventoji_dwnstr	6849
Šventoji - žemiau Anykščių	108	07.01.1997	19.12.2006	Shventoji_Shventoji_midstr	3615
Šventoji - aukščiau Anykščių	156	07.01.1997	18.11.2009	Shventoji_Shventoji_midstr	3386
Šventoji - ties Sabaliūnais (žemiau Andrioniškio)	96	25.01.2005	20.11.2012	Shventoji_Shventoji_midstr	3301
Siesartis - žemiau Molėtų	97	14.01.1997	23.05.2005	Shventoji_Siesartis	131
Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų	156	09.01.1997	08.12.2009	Shventoji_Sirvinta	434
Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų	101	09.01.1997	26.09.2011	Shventoji_Sirvinta	489
Vyžuona - žemiau Utenos	102	22.01.1997	04.10.2010	Shventoji_Vyžuona	335
Ašva - pasienyje	96	26.01.2005	10.12.2012	Venta_Vadakstis	159

Station name	Nr. of observations	Start date	End date	Watershed name	Modeled area
Varduva - ties Grieže	96	26.01.2005	10.12.2012	Venta_Varduva	588
Venta - žemiau Mažeikių	191	08.01.1997	10.12.2012	Venta_Venta_dwnstr	4052
Venta - aukščiau Kuršėnų	95	08.01.1997	13.12.2004	Venta_Venta_upstr	885
Venta - žemiau Kuršėnų	95	08.01.1997	13.12.2004	Venta_Venta_upstr	963
Virvyčia - žemiau Pateklos	95	08.01.1997	13.12.2004	Venta_Virvyčia	911
Virvyčia - ties Janapole	60	26.01.2005	16.12.2009	Venta_Virvyčia	379
Žeimena - aukščiau Pabradės	96	22.01.1997	14.12.2004	Zeimena_Zeimena	2152
Žeimena - žemiau Švenčionėlių	102	22.01.1997	03.10.2007	Zeimena_Zeimena	1766
Žeimena - žemiau Pabradės	192	22.01.1997	04.12.2012	Zeimena_Zeimena	2623
Mera - Kūna - ties Pažeimene	72	24.01.2005	04.12.2012	Zeimena_Zeimena	190
Būka – aukščiau Balušo	105	21.01.1997	20.08.2007	Zeimena_Zeimena_upstr	155
Švogina-Žeimena - aukščiau Vaišniūnų	51	19.02.2001	08.10.2008	Zeimena_Zeimena_upstr	102
Žeimena - ties Kaltanėnais	192	22.01.1997	04.12.2012	Zeimena_Zeimena_upstr	764

Normalization of station areas to catchment areas was performed for all (hydrometric and water quality) stations. We took into account the difference between the catchment area of an observation station area and watershed area when comparing discharge measurements to observations. This is important to get the correct measures of calculation, especially for more upstream stations that are not located right at the outflowing nodes of the subbasins.

2.3. Calibration / validation strategy (3.2.1.3)

TOR 3.2.1. requests preparation of multi-site calibration strategy, which would enable to reach the best results for all calibration places, the compulsory elements of this strategy (including strategy for validation and finalization of model preparation) are listed throughout TOR 3.2.1-3.2.4.

2.3.1. Initial selection of example basins validated (3.2.1.1 of TOR)

Based on section 3.2.1.1 of TOR Lithuanian territory is divided into regions according to runoff formation hydrological conditions and pollution generation situation. Totally there are 13 hydrological regions. One basin should be selected as a representative case for each hydrological region for calibration and validation. Then the parametrization will be extrapolated to the catchments within the same region (refer to Chapter 2.4 Regionalization for more information).

Table 8: List of 13 selected basins in each hydrological region with the main hydrological station.

Hydrological region	Station Name (Main Station Hydrology)	Watershed Name
AI	Akmena-Danė-Kretinga	BalticSea_AkmenaDane
AII	Akmena-Paakmenis	Jura_Jura
BIII	Dubysa-Lyduvėnai	Dubysa_Dubysa
BIV	Tatula-Trečionys	Musa_Tatula
BV	Nevėžis-Panevėžys	Nevezis_Nevezis_upstr
BVI	Mituva-Žindaičiai	Nemunas_Mituva
BVII	Nemunėlis-Kvetkai	Nemunelis_Nemunelis_dwnstr
BVIII	Šešupe-Liubavas	Sesupe_Sesupe_upstr
BIX	Verknė-Verbyliškės	Nemunas_Verkne
CX	Širvinta-Liukonys	Shventoji_Sirvinta
CXI	Vilnia-Vilnius	Neris_Vilnia
CXII	Svyla-Guntauninkai	Dauguva_Birveta
CXIII	NO STATION	NO STATION

There should be considered that these basins are located in one specific dominant hydrological region and not interacted with trans-boundaries areas. But some of the setups during extrapolation fall into many regions. For instance, Dubysa falls into regions AII, BIII and BVI with dominant region being BIII. It means, that You will get different results while calibrating and that is perfectly normal, because extrapolation is taking into account regional differences in more detailed way. The relation of all stations to regions is summarised in Table 9.

Table 9: List of all stations used in this research with their corresponding dominant hydrologic region.

ID	STANAME	Region	Region dependent
19	Šyša - aukščiau Šilutės	AI	AI
20	Šyša - žemiau Šilutės	AI	AI
74	Akmena - Danė - ties Tūbausiais	AI	AI
76	Akmena - Danė - aukščiau Klaipėdos	AI	AI
77	Akmena - Danė - žiotyse	AI	AI
138	Šventoji - žiotyse	AI	AI
268	Vilka - ties Gudais	AI	AI
17	Minija - žemiau Priekulės	AI	AI,AII
266	Minija - ties Suvernais	AI	AI,AII
267	Karaliaus Vilhelmo kanalas - ties Dreverna	AI	AI,AII
127	Nemunas - Skirvytė aukščiau Rusnės	AI	AI,AII,BIII,BIV,BV,BVI,BVII,BVIII,CIX,CX,CXI,CXIII,TB
265	Jūra - ties Mociškiais	AI_AII	AI,AII,BIII,BVI
22	Jūra - žemiau Tauragės	AI_AII	AII,BIII,BVI
14	Minija - aukščiau Plungės	AII	AII
15	Minija - žemiau Plungės	AII	AII

ID	STANAME	Region	Region dependent
16	Mīnija - žemiau Gargždų	AII	AII
18	Veiviržas - ties Veiviržėnais	AII	AII
21	Jūra - aukščiau Tauragės	AII	AII
25	Lokysta - žemiau Šilalės	AII	AII
78	Bartuva - aukščiau Skuodo	AII	AII
79	Bartuva - žemiau Skuodo	AII	AII
269	Salantas - ties Nasrėnais	AII	AII
270	Graumena - ties Pakalniškiais	AII	AII
271	Akmėna - aukščiau Pagramančio	AII	AII
433	Virvyčia - ties Janapole	AII	AII
83	Virvyčia - žemiau Pateklos	AII	AII,BIII
23	Šėšuvis - ties Skirgailiais	AII	AII,BIII,BVI
34	Kražantė - aukščiau Kelmės	AII_BIII	AII,BIII
432	Ašva - pasienyje	BIII	BIII
35	Kražantė - žemiau Kelmės	BIII	AII,BIII
80	Venta - aukščiau Kuršėnų	BIII	AII,BIII
81	Venta - žemiau Kuršėnų	BIII	AII,BIII
82	Venta - žemiau Mažeikių	BIII	AII,BIII
217	Šėšuvis - ties Taubučiais	BIII_AII	AII,BIII
430	Varduva - ties Grieže	BIII_AII	AII,BIII
24	Šaltuona - žemiau Raseinių	BIII_AII	AII,BIII,BVI
84	Mūša - aukščiau Kulpės	BIV	BIV
86	Mūša - žemiau Kulpės	BIV	BIV
87	Sidabra - žemiau Joniškio	BIV	BIV
88	Sidabra - Latvijos pasienyje	BIV	BIV
99	Daugyvenė - žiotyse	BIV	BIV
100	Kruoja - žiotyse	BIV	BIV
101	Obelė - žemiau Radviliškio	BIV	BIV
102	Obelė - žiotyse	BIV	BIV
103	Kulpė - žemiau Šiaulių	BIV	BIV
104	Kulpė - žiotyse	BIV	BIV
431	Platonis - pasienyje	BIV	BIV
92	Tatula - aukščiau Biržų	BIV	BIV,BV
93	Tatula - žemiau Biržų	BIV	BIV,BV
94	Tatula - ties Trečionimis	BIV	BIV,BV
85	Mūša - žemiau Saločių	BIV	BIV,BV,BVII
97	Lėvuo - aukščiau Pasvalio	BIV	BIV,BV,BVII
98	Lėvuo - žiotyse	BIV	BIV,BV,BVII
360	Pyvesa - tarp Žadeikių ir Geivitonių	BIV_BV	BIV,BV
357	Nemunėlis - Tabokinė	BIV_BVII	BIV,BVII
36	Nevėžis - aukščiau Panevėžio	BV	BV
42	Juosta - žemiau Jackagalio	BV	BV
40	Nevėžis - aukščiau Raudondvario	BV	BIII,BIV,BV,BVII
37	Nevėžis - žemiau Panevėžio	BV	BV,BVII

ID	STANAME	Region	Region dependent
38	Nevėžis - aukščiau Kėdainių	BV	BV,BVII
39	Nevėžis - žemiau Kėdainių	BV	BV,BVII
49	Neris - žemiau Jonavos	BV	BV,BVII,CIX,CX,CXI,TB
50	Neris - aukščiau Kauno	BV	BV,BVII,CIX,CX,CXI,TB
130	Neris - žemiau Jonavos	BV	BV,BVII,CIX,CX,CXI,TB
48	Neris - aukščiau Jonavos	BV	BV,CIX,CX,CXI,TB
41	Šušvė - žiotyse	BV_BIII	BIII,BIV,BV
133	Šventoji - žiotyse	BV_CX	BVII,CX,CXI
30	Siesartis - žemiau Šakių	BVI	BVI
31	Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio	BVI	BVI
143	Siesartis - žiotyse	BVI	BVI
150	Jiesia - ties Šilavotu	BVI	BVI
402	Višakis - aukščiau Pilviškių (kelias 137)	BVI	BVI
11	Nemunas - žemiau Smalininkų	BVI	AII,BIII,BIV,BV,BVI,BVII,CIX,CX,CXI,CXIII,TB
135	Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Zapyškio	BVI	BIII,BIV,BV,BVI,BVII,CIX,CX,CXI,CXIII,TB
136	Nemunas – žemiau Kauno ties Kulautuva	BVI	BIII,BIV,BV,BVI,BVII,CIX,CX,CXI,CXIII,TB
142	Širvinta - žiotyse	BVI	BVI,BVIII
401	Rausvė - ties Nadrausve	BVI	BVI,BVIII
28	Šešupė - aukščiau Marijampolės	BVI	BVI,BVIII,CIX
29	Šešupė - žemiau Marijampolės	BVI	BVI,BVIII,CIX
137	Šešupė - Kaliningrado srit. pasienyje	BVI	BVI,BVIII,CIX
33	Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus	BVI_BIII	AII,BIII,BVI
7	Nemunas - aukščiau Prienų	BVI_CXI	BVI,CIX,CXI,CXIII,TB
8	Nemunas - aukščiau Kauno	BVI_CXI	BVI,CIX,CXI,CXIII,TB
89	Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio	BVII	BVII
91	Laukupė - žemiau Rokiškio	BVII	BVII
95	Lėvuo - aukščiau Kupiškio	BVII_BV	BV,BVII
96	Lėvuo - žemiau Kupiškio	BVII_BV	BV,BVII
52	Šventoji - aukščiau Anykščių	BVII_CX	BVII,CX
327	Šventoji - ties Sabaliūnais (žemiau Andrioniškio)	BVII_CX	BVII,CX
26	Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	BVIII_BVI	BVIII
27	Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	BVIII_BVI	BVIII
51	Lomena - žemiau Kaišiadorių	CIX	CIX
67	Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių	CIX	CIX
68	Strėva - ties Liutonimis	CIX	CIX
4	Nemunas - aukščiau Alytaus	CIX_CXI	CIX,CXI,CXIII,TB
5	Nemunas – žemiau Alytaus	CIX_CXI	CIX,CXI,CXIII,TB
6	Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	CIX_CXI	CIX,CXI,CXIII,TB
56	Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų	CX	CX
57	Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų	CX	CX

ID	STANAME	Region	Region dependent
59	Vyžuona - žemiau Utenos	CX	CX
106	Laukesa - žemiau Zarasų	CX	CX
53	Šventoji - žemiau Anykščių	CX	BVII,CX
54	Šventoji - aukščiau Ukmergės	CX	BVII,CX,CXI
55	Šventoji - žemiau Ukmergės	CX	BVII,CX,CXI
58	Siesartis - žemiau Molėtų	CX	CX,CXI
219	Žiežmara - ties Paparčiais	CX_BV	BV,CIX,CX
60	Vilnia - aukščiau N.Vilnios	CXI	CXI
61	Vilnia - žiotyse	CXI	CXI
62	Žeimena - ties Kaltanėnais	CXI	CXI
63	Žeimena - žemiau Švenčionėlių	CXI	CXI
64	Žeimena - aukščiau Pabradės	CXI	CXI
66	Būka – aukščiau Baluošo	CXI	CXI
71	Skroblus - žemiau Dubininkų	CXI	CXI
73	Šalčia - žemiau Šalčininkų	CXI	CXI
141	Švogina-Žeimena - aukščiau Vaišniūnų	CXI	CXI
151	Ūla - Pelesa - ties Kašėtomis	CXI	CXI
175	Mera - Kūna - ties Pažeimene	CXI	CXI
69	Merkys - aukščiau Varėnos	CXI	CIX,CXI,CXIII
70	Merkys - žemiau Puvočių	CXI	CIX,CXI,CXIII
1	Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	CXI	CIX,CXI,TB
2	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	CXI	CIX,CXI,TB
3	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	CXI	CIX,CXI,TB
65	Žeimena - žemiau Pabradės	CXI	CX,CXI
44	Neris - aukščiau Vilniaus	CXI	CX,CXI,TB
45	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	CXI	CX,CXI,TB
46	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	CXI	CX,CXI,TB
47	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	CXI	CX,CXI,TB
43	Neris - ties Buivydžiais	CXI	CXI,TB
105	Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje	CXII	CXII
325	Dysna - ties Kačergiške	CXII	CXII

2.3.2 Holistic multi-site calibration strategy (3.2.1.3 of TOR)

2.3.2.1 Bottom-up or top-down for calibration/validation/regionalization

Calibrations could be done by top-down or bottom-up approach. In a top-down approach, we start from the overall view and try to find rules/strategies that will be applied over the entire area, with the hope that these strategies lead to an overall improvement of the performance. In a bottom-up approach, small areas are intensively parameterized, and these parameters are then transferred to other areas, also with the hope that these transferred parameter sets lead to better parameterizations. As an example, the top down looks for strategies that affect the entire basin (e.g. all CN's are reduced by 15%). So in this study we emphasize on top-down strategy to calibrate the entire of four selected basins.

Then after a successful calibration and validation of pilot basins in each hydrological region we can extrapolate the parameters to the other catchments in the same hydrological category (bottom-up). Non-calibrating basins should be validated by using the extrapolated parameters of neighbor basins in the same hydrological category.

2.3.2.2 Multi variables or single variable strategy

Multi variable calibration and validation were implemented. The applied variables are river flow and in-stream NO₃ concentration, Total Nitrogen concentration, PO₄ concentration and P Total concentration in river to be calibrated simultaneously. Respectively, as it is common in calibration, one starts from upstream to downstream and flow, then nitrate, phosphorous and afterwards total N/total P.

2.3.2.3 Manual or automatic strategy for calibration

Automatic calibration methods will be tried by SWAT CUP 2012 5.1.6.2. After automatic calibration iteration we conduct manual calibration to improve the performance and recheck the water mass balance until reaching to the satisfactory results. Therefore for each catchment a multi-site combined automatic and manual calibration will be performed only for the flow (since we have continuous time series and this is ideal for the calibration)

But we conduct single-site manual calibration for the monthly times series of in-stream nitrate, total nitrogen, phosphate and total phosphorous. The model will be validated in each catchment for the rest of gauging stations.

2.3.2.4 Single-site or Multi-Site calibration and validation (water quantity)

For water quantity modelling we used multi site calibration and validation. So there were at least one or more stations which will be used at the same time for calibration and validation based on the agreement based on TOR: 1/3 beginning and 1/3 ending period representing as calibration and the 1/3 middle period representing as the validation. But there were some exemptions for some bigger catchments depending on data availability and the location of the flow station (e.g. if this is so upstream and/or with many transboundary or inlets from neighbor catchments), we may have one station for both calibration and validation of flow and another(others) for validation only will be used.

2.3.2.5 Single-site or Multi-Site calibration and validation (water quality)

For water quality we have used single site calibration (the station which is more data rich and more downstream and close to the output of the reach) and we validated the model with other measured points.

2.3.2.6 Number of HRUS and computation time

In order to reduce the computation time, we have decided to reduce the number of HRUs to avoid wasting time on long computation. By comparing simulation results between default model and the model with fewer HRUs, found out that there is no significant difference was observed. After calibrating and validating for reduced HRU model (Minimal HRU area 10 ha) then results will be compared with the results of default model (Minimal HRU area 5 ha based

on TOR requirements) to check whether the results are still satisfactory or not.

2.3.2.7 Using additional softwares for sensitivity analysis, calibration, validation and uncertainty analysis

SWAT-CHECK. SWAT error checker and mass balance checker will be performed by SWAT-CHECK 2012. This would be done for annual water yield components, phosphorous cycle components, nitrogen cycle components and crop growth cycle. SWAT Check reads model output from a SWAT project and performs many simple checks to identify potential model problems.

The intended purpose of this program is to identify model problems early in the modeling process. Hidden model problems often result in the need to recalibrate or regenerate a model, resulting in an avoidable waste of time. This program is designed to compare a variety of SWAT outputs to nominal ranges based on the judgment of model developers. A warning does not necessarily indicate a problem; the purpose is to bring attention to unusual predictions. This software also provides a visual representation of various model outputs to aid notice users.

Baseflow filtering tools. Baseflow filtering is a part of strategy for better calibration and parametrization of groundwater parameters and better analyze of global water yield results of the model. Two programs were investigated Subflow Filtering software by SWAT developers and WETSPRO Time Series analysis and subflow filtering program by KULeuven Hydraulics Lab.

The baseflow filter program SWAT estimates baseflow and groundwater recharge from streamflow records using the methodology outlined in Arnold&Allen (1999) and Arnold et al (1995).

WETSPRO is a tool in which a time series of total rainfall-runoff discharges can be splitted into its subflows (such as the overland flow, the subsurface flow or interflow, and the groundwater flow or baseflow) using a numerical digital filter technique. Its physical interpretation is based on the linear reservoir modelling concept, which will be described first. KU Leuven (2004), <http://www.kuleuven.be/hydr/pw/WETSPRO%20manual.pdf>.

Although both softwares were used in this research for initial investigation, but at the end, in order to improve and initialize the model, we recommended to update the value of Alpha_Bf to the updated parameter derived by Base flow filtering software “SWAT” rather than WETSPRO because Base flow filtering software “SWAT”, “SWAT CHECK” and “SWAT-CUP” are using the similar functioning.

SWAT-CUP for sensitivity analysis of water quality and quantity parameters and for multi-site automated calibration of flow. As it was mentioned. SWAT CUP was used as a comprehensive and useful tool for sensitivity analysis as well as for multi-site automated calibration of flow. SWAT-CUP is a public software for calibrating SWAT models. SWAT-CUP is a public domain program. The program links GLUE, ParaSol, SUFI2, MCMC, and

PSO procedures to SWAT. It enables sensitivity analysis, calibration, validation, and uncertainty analysis of a SWAT model. The overall program structure is shown in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: SWAT CUP general working algorithm.

2.3.2.8 Selection of mathematical method for automated calibration: PSO; advantages of selected method

Despite the large number of suggested techniques, only a few papers on comparison of different uncertainty analysis techniques are available. Yang et al. (2008) compared GLUE, parameter Solution (ParaSol), SUFI2 and MCMC methods in an application to a watershed in China with SWAT model and found that different methods converge to different solutions with more or less the same calibration and validation results.

Zhang et al (2009) also compared five global optimization algorithms including genetic algorithms, shuffled complex evolution, particle swarm optimization (PSO), differential evolution and artificial immune system and showed that particle swarm optimization (PSO) can obtain better parameter solutions than other algorithms given fewer number of model runs (less than 2000) PSO shares many similarities with evolutionary computation on techniques such as Genetic Algorithms (GA). The basic PSO algorithm consists of three steps: (i) generate the positions of particles (coordinate in the parameter space) and their velocities ('flying' direction and speed); (ii) update the velocity of each particle using the information from the best solution it has achieved so far and another solution with the best fitness value that has been obtained so far by all the particles in the population (global best); (iii) finally,

the new position of each particle is calculated by adding the updated velocity to the current position. Due to all these methods PSO method was used for global sensitivity analysis and automated calibration.

2.3.3. Practical plan for manual calibration

The final practical plan of calibration and validation consists of several steps:

1: Parameterization with change in original coefficients and initial condition: It consists of three different categories:

- a) Hydrological Parameterization with Impact on Flow, in stream N and in stream P.
- b) Calibration of Water Quality with Nitrogen Parameters with Impact on in stream N concentration. This can be nitrogen initial condition, denitrification rate coefficients and in-stream processes coefficients etc.
- c) Calibration of Water Quality with Phosphorous Parameters and Soil Erosion Parameters with Impact on in stream P concentration. This can be initial condition in the soil profile, soil erodibility and in-stream processes coefficients etc.

2: Parameterization with fertilizer input database: Adjusting of fertilizer database for three fertilizers used in the practices. Due to the last inquiry, experts' measurements can be almost +/-20 % changed. For all four catchments it has been adjusted as a unique and new fertilizer database.

3: Changing the calculation methods: In all pilot basins for the calculation of evapotranspiration, IPET.bsn was set to 2 (Hargreaves' method) instead of 1 (default as PET method) and IRTE.bsn was set from IPET=0 the default value as variable travel-time to value 1 which is Muskingum method.

The general strategy of calibration is outlined in Figure 4.

Figure 4: General scheme of calibration strategy.

2.3.4. Environmental models results evaluation (3.2.1.5 of TOR)

In hydrology and water quality models, the typical criteria used are the ‘Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) and R-squared. In this study NSE is our primary objective function for various variables (Eq.1). There are other criteria like RSE (Root Mean Squared Error), PBIAS (Percent Bias) and MSE that can be evaluated afterwards to evaluate the results of calibration and validation procedure.

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_{i,meas} - y_{i,sim})^2}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_{i,meas} - \bar{y}_{meas})^2} = 1 - \frac{RMS^2}{\text{var}(Y_{meas})} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

Table 10: Key residual criteria (Bennett et al., 2013).

ID	Name	Formula	Range	Ideal value	Notes
4.1	Residual plot	~	-	-	Plot residuals against the predictor variable(s), look for curvature or changes in magnitude as the predictor variable changes.
4.2	QQ plot	~	-	-	Plots the inverse distribution (quantile) function of residuals against normal distribution quantile function. Look for curvature and divergence away from the mean diagonal (Fig. 7).
4.3	Bias	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)$	$(-\infty, +\infty)$	0	Calculates the mean error. Result of zero does not necessarily indicate low error due to cancellation.
4.4	Mean Square Error (MSE)	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$	$(0, \infty)$	0	Calculates a mean error (in data units squared), which is not effected by cancellation. Squaring the data may cause bias towards large events.
4.5	Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$	$(0, \infty)$	0	MSE error (4.4) except result is returned in the same units as model, which is useful for interpretation.
4.6	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i - \hat{y}_i $	$(0, \infty)$	0	Similar to RMSE (4.5) except absolute value is used instead. This reduces the bias towards large events; however, it also produces a non-smooth operator when used in optimisation.
4.7	Absolute Maximum Error (AME)	$\max y_i - \hat{y}_i $	-	-	Records the maximum absolute error.

Following sample criteria for effective hydrological and water quality optimization are proposed. This is based on the calibration plan purposed by TOR to take into consideration recommendations made by Moriasi et al. (2007) and Bennet et al (2013), Tables 10-11.

Table 11: General performance ratings recommended statistics for a hydrological and water quality model based on research by Moriasi et al. (2007).

Performance Rating	RSR	NSE	PBIAS (%)		
			Streamflow	Sediment	N, P
Very good	$0.00 \leq RSR \leq 0.50$	$0.75 < NSE \leq 1.00$	$PBIAS < \pm 10$	$PBIAS < \pm 15$	$PBIAS < \pm 25$
Good	$0.50 < RSR \leq 0.60$	$0.65 < NSE \leq 0.75$	$\pm 10 \leq PBIAS < \pm 15$	$\pm 15 \leq PBIAS < \pm 30$	$\pm 25 \leq PBIAS < \pm 40$
Satisfactory	$0.60 < RSR \leq 0.70$	$0.50 < NSE \leq 0.65$	$\pm 15 \leq PBIAS < \pm 25$	$\pm 30 \leq PBIAS < \pm 55$	$\pm 40 \leq PBIAS < \pm 70$
Unsatisfactory	$RSR > 0.70$	$NSE \leq 0.50$	$PBIAS \geq \pm 25$	$PBIAS \geq \pm 55$	$PBIAS \geq \pm 70$

Finally, VUB and PAIC agreed (and co-ordinated with the Client) on the following criteria given in Tables 12-13 based on the information and experiences given above.

Table 12: Calibration, validation and parameter transfer targets for hydrological observations vs. model outputs.

Action	NSE threshold	PBIAS threshold
Calibration	NSE>0.5	PBIAS<20%
Validation	NSE>0.4	PBIAS<25%
Extrapolation (transfer)	NSE>0.3	PBIAS<30%

Water Quality: monthly average for all years which the results will be 12 values of concentration (mg/l) and these 12 values will compare with related observations, and R² (correlation of two arrays of observation and simulation for these 12 values) and PBIAS will be calculated.

Table 13: Calibration, validation and parameter transfer targets for water quality observations vs. model outputs.

Action	R ² threshold, N-NO ₃ , N-tot	PBIAS threshold, all parameters
Calibration	R ² >0.5	PBIAS<40%
Validation	R ² >0.4	PBIAS<70%
Extrapolation (transfer)	R ² >0.3	PBIAS<70%

Besides Hydrographs should be well predicted and the model must represent correct baseflow levels and peaks and recessions of water flow should be comparable to measurement data. Systematic deviations of modeled from measured hydrographs should be corrected during calibration.

2.4. Regionalization (3.2.1.1)

TOR (3.2.1.1) requests that the Lithuanian territory is divided into regions according to the runoff formation hydrological conditions and pollution generation conditions.

For this we analyze meteorological (Figure 5) and hydrological patterns over the Lithuanian territory comparing it to the proposed division (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Rainfall distributions over the Lithuanian territory.

After analyzing the initial calculations and observed data in the discharge stations we could identify three regions:

- **Central Lithuania.** The observed hydrographs in this region have distinct spring maximum and very low summer flows. Non-calibrated model overestimates the discharge in this region, mainly due to overestimation of summer flows. We think this is due to too low evaporation in summer. Other problems are (1) too early spring snow-melt peak and (2) overestimation of surface runoff. Typical modelled vs. observed hydrograph is shown in Figure 7, while typical averaged model year is depicted in Figure 8.

We did preliminary SWAT parameter assessment for this region and found that

- I. Snow melt peak position can be improved by changing snow related parameters as snowmelt/snowfall temperatures, snow melt factor and, especially snow pack temperature lag (TIMP).

Figure 6. Division of hydrological regions.

Figure 7. Typical calculated versus observed discharge in central Lithuania (station Levuo-Kupiskis as an example). green – calculated, red – observed.

- II. The way to lower the discharge is to increase soil available water capacity (AWC, Figure 12) and to lower a soil hydraulic conductivity (K, Figure 11). We estimated that for some cases increase of AWC by as much as 200% is necessary.
- III. The CN2 should also be lowered to ensure that calculated signal does not contain any significant surface runoff component.

Figure 8. Typical calculated (green) versus observed (red) seasonal cycle in central Lithuania. Notice that typical summer low flow discharge is 10 times lower than spring melt flow.

- **Western Lithuania.** The observed hydrographs in this region have smaller spring melt flood signal, but strong autumn rainfall signal appears. The precipitation in this region is higher (up to 1.5 times) than in central Lithuania. The calculated disbalance of water in this region is much smaller than in central Lithuania. NSE is also higher,

mainly because surface runoff signal are present in observations. Figures 9, 10 show a relatively good agreement of calculated/observed flow for Minija-Kartena station.

We do not clearly understand the difference in model behavior between central and western Lithuania. It could be that soil parameters are better represented in western Lithuania. It could be that rainfall amount (see Figure 5) is more correct in western Lithuania, etc. In Figures 11 and 12, SOL_AWC and SOL_K for the first soil layer are depicted. It should be noted that the surface run-off is also represented better so the changes of CN2 could be less significant than in the central region.

Figure 9. Calculated versus observed discharge in western Lithuania (station Minija-Kartena) (green – calculated, red – observed).

Figure 10. Typical calculated (green) versus observed (red) seasonal cycle in western Lithuania.

Figure 11. Soil saturated hydraulic conductivity (SOL_K) for the first soil layer. Notice lower conductivities in central Lithuania, which should lead to much lower discharges and larger evaporation.

Figure 12. Soil available water capacity (SOL_AWC) for the first soil layer. Notice higher AWC in central Lithuania, which should result in lower summer discharge and higher evaporation.

- **Southeastern Lithuania** (Merkys river basin, Žeimena river basin, partly Šventoji river basin.). Although at many stations average water balance is good, however, in this region NSE of calculated (by non-calibrated) versus modeled discharges are low. This is due to the baseflow that dominates the observed hydrograph. Figures 13-16 show calculated/observed hydrograph and seasonal cycle for Neris-Vilnia station and Žeimena-Pabrade station.

Figure 13. Calculated versus observed discharge in Neris-Vilnia station (green – calculated, red – observed).

Figure 14. Calculated (green) versus observed (red) seasonal cycle, station Neris-Vilnia.

Figure 15. Calculated versus observed discharge in Žeimena-Pabrade station (green – calculated, red – observed).

Figure 16. Calculated (green) versus observed (red) seasonal cycle, station Žeimena-Pabradė station.

2.5. Calibration and validation: hydrology

2.5.1. Introduction

The calibration (TOR 3.2.1.2-3.2.1.4) and validation (TOR 3.2.2.1-3.2.2.2) of hydrology was performed for the selected stations in each of the hydrological subregions of Lithuania (see Figures 6 and 17). The calibration and validation were performed by Vrije University Brussels (regions AII, BIII, BIV, CX) and “Center for processes analysis and research”, SIA (regions AI, BV, BVI, BVII, CIX, CXI, CXII), see Fig. 17. There are no hydrometric observation stations in region CXIII. The only hydrometric station in region BVIII (Šešupe-Liubavas) is dominated by transboundary water flow.

Figure 17: Hydrological regions of Lithuania. Green - PAIC regions, blue - VUB regions, red star - calibration stations chosen by PAIC.

The calibration targets were selected according to TOR 3.2.1.5 and coordinated with EPA (TOR 3.2.1.6).

The calibration and validation thresholds are summarised in Table 12 for daily values of discharge observations vs. model outputs.

Prior to calibration the sensitivity analysis (Section 2.5.2) and baseflow filtering (Section 2.5.3) was performed.

2.5.2. Sensitivity analysis for flow

In order to be fast, sensitivity analysis was done for two catchments. The top parameters (Table 14) in each case have been recognized as the most sensitive parameters for river flow. Regarding the other parameters, some of them were tried and they were not sensitive and were dropped out of further assessments and some other were not in the proper format to be capable for automatic calibration and were calibrated manually.

A sample result for sensitivity analysis by SWAT CUP is shown in Figure 18.

Table 14: Matrix of decision to recognize sensitive parameters.

Parameter	Rank Number			
	Jura 5 X 5	Jura 10 X 10	Jura 15 X 15	Sirvinta 8 X 8
SURLAG	17	16	16	17
GWQMN	13	17	7	16
CN2	16	3	17	15
SOL_BD	14	15	6	10
SMFMN	6	11	11	14
CANMAX	15	2	14	9
RECHARGE_DP	4	14	15	6
GW_DELAY	9	9	5	11
SMFMX	8	10	13	1
SOL_K	5	13	9	5
ESCO	7	8	4	13
TIMP	11	12	3	3
SMTMP	3	7	10	8
CH_N2	2	1	12	12
SFTMP	12	5	1	4
SOL_AWC	10	7	2	2
ALPHA BF	1	4	8	7

Figure 18: A sample result of sensitivity analysis for Jura with using PSO_SWAT CUP showing the sensitive parameters need to be changed for hydrological calibration.

2.5.3. Baseflow filtering results

A comparison between default and filter-derived values for ALPHA_BF for a test case has been illustrated located at six stations at four selected basins (average value) where continuous daily data points were available. The results of WETSPRO subflow filtering is

shown in Table 15. This Table contains the results of adjusted average ALPHA_BF and recession period for four selected basins by WETSPRO.

Table 15: Average results of baseflow filtering equivalent parameters derived from WETSPRO software.

	ALPHA_BF (1/day)	Recession time (days)
INITIAL SWAT (before calibration)	0.07	32.86
Subflow Filtering WETSPRO	0.18	13

A small difference is observed between the default value and the value derived by the subflow filtering. In order to improve and initialize the model, this would be better to update the value of Alpha_BF to the updated parameter derived by Base flow filtering software “WETSPRO”.

Next, the SWAT base flow filtering program has been used. In general, the fraction of water yield contributed by baseflow should be between the value of Baseflow Fr1 and Baseflow Fr2. If the baseflow in the watershed is not from aquifers recharged by a precipitation falling in the watershed, things get more complicated and this rule may not apply. The groundwater file variable, ALPHA_BF, can be set to the value calculated for Alpha Factor. Reference for SWAT base flow filtering software manual is given in:

http://swat.tamu.edu/media/70814/baseflow_inst_2006-06.pdf

A summary of calculations by SWAT base flow filtering program is given in Table 16.

Table 16: Baseflow results for some sample basins in all three representing hydrological regions. Application of SWAT baseflow filtering program.

	Hydrological Region B			Hydrological Region A			Hydrological Region C
	Dubysa		Tatula	Jura		Bartuva	Sirvinta
	Station ID 6	Station ID 10	Station ID 48	Station ID 3	Station ID 8	Station ID 5	Station ID 42
FR1	0.78	0.72	0.72	0.66	0.64	0.65	0.77
FR2	0.65	0.58	0.57	0.51	0.49	0.49	0.65
FR3	0.57	0.5	0.48	0.43	0.41	0.4	0.58
Alpha_Bf	0.037	0.049	0.066	0.067	0.065	0.063	0.037

2.5.4. Region AI

Hydrometric station Akmena-Dane-Kretinga was selected for calibration and validation in western hydrological region AI. The watershed of Akmena-Dane is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: BalticSea_AkmenaDane watershed, station Akmena-Danė-Kretinga was used for calibration.

Table 17: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

AI: Akmena-Danė-Kretinga	Period	NSE	PBIAS
Calibration	01.01.1997-31.12.2002; 02.01.2008-31.12.2012	0.51	11%
Validation	01.01.2003-01.01.2008	0.6	0%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets was reached for Akmena-Dane, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 17.

Table 18: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Akmena-Dane.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.052
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.127
V_GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V_GWQMN.gw	100	31.164
V_GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.050
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	0
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V_SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V_TIMP.bsn	1	0.800
V_SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.2
V_SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.150
V_SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.2
V_ESCO.hru	0.95	0.400
V_CANMX.hru	10	28.759
R_SOL_BD().sol	0	0.281

Figure 20: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 18.

Figure 21: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 22: SWAT Check screenshot for Akmena-Dane. Water balance components and warnings.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 20. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 21; it indicates very good representation of Akmena-Dane seasonal hydrograph.

The Water balance components for Akmena-Dane (full period) is shown in Figure 22 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10. No potential problems are identified by this software.

2.5.5. Region AII

Jūra catchment was chosen for calibration in region AII. Flow was calibrated at the location of station ID 3 (Table 19). Since Jura is a big catchment we used the upstream station ID 8 for validation and just to check the calibrated model.

Table 19: List of hydrological stations in Jura_Jura.

Hydrological region	Station Name (Hydrology)	Watershed Name
AII	Akmena_Pakmenis (reach 16) Station ID 3 Jura_Taruge (reach 26) Station ID 8	Jura_Jura

Duration of available data for stations in Jura_Jura catchment is 1997-2012.

Table 20: Assessment of calibration and validation for Jura_Jura watershed.

Jura Jura: Station 3 Akmena_Pakmenis, Reach16, Calibrating Station, Flow	
	Flow
NSE Cal (01.01.1997-31.12.2001; 01.09.2008-31.12.2012)	0.57
NSE Val (01.01.2002-31.12.2007)	0.68
PBIAS Cal	12%
PBIAS Val	16%
Jura Jura: Station 8 Jura_Taruge , Reach26, Validating Station, Flow	
	Flow
NSE Val 1997-2012	0.58
PBIAS Val	5%

Figure 23: Intermediate results of 95% prediction uncertainty bands quantification after flow autocalibration iterations for Jura_Jura.

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets was reached for Akmena_Pakmenis, and the validation threshold was also met for two stations (Table 20). Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The autocalibration results are shown in Figures 23-24. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the

calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 21.

Table 21: Calibrated hydrological parameters (R means relative change and V means replacing by a new value).

Hydrological Parameters with Impact on Flow, in stream N and in stream P	
r__CN2.mgt	-0.108
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.015
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.1
V__GWQMN.gw	30.0
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.634
V__SMTMP.bsn	1.284
V__TIMP.bsn	0.632
V__SMFX.bsn	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.623
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.05
V__RCHRD_DP.gw	0.05
V__ESCO.hru	0.3
V__CANMX.hru	6
r__SOL_AWC().sol	0.29
r__SOL_K().sol	0.25
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.05
V__REVAPMN.gw	30
r__SOL_BD().sol	0.35
V__LAT_TTIME.hru	0

Figure 24: Variation in objective function in 20 iterations for autocalibration of flow for Jura_Jura catchment.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 25. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 26; it indicates very good representation of Akmena_Pakmenis seasonal hydrograph.

Figure 25: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges for Akmena_Pakmenis for 1997-2012.

Figure 26: Model output seasonal plot – green, observations – red for Akmena_Pakmenis.

The Water balance components for Jura_Jura (full period) is shown in Fig. 27 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

Figure 27: SWAT Check screenshot for Jura_Jura. Water balance components and warnings.

Warnings indicated that:

1. Total water yield might be high and losses might be low but surface runoff ratio in comparison with groundwater flow and lateral flow can be relatively low.
2. The problem is considering a large portion of lateral flow but comparing to the amount of the water which is available in tile drainage flow, this is not significant. SWAT CHECK is not splitting and considering the tile flow separately. It is better to use output.std.
3. Checking ground water to total water yield ratio. Model indicates this value as: 0.5454 and the results of baseflow filtering (Table 22) by SWAT program which is fully compatible with SWAT and SWAT CUP algorithms, indicates that this fraction can vary between 0.41 and 0.64. Thus, the calibrated result is acceptable. We have used output.std information to calibrate a SWAT simulation mass balance.

Table 22: List of baseflow filtering results specifically for Jura_Jura using SWAT baseflow program.

	Jura	
	Station ID 3	Station ID 8
FR1	0.61	0.64
FR2	0.56	0.59
FR3	0.43	0.41
Alpha_Bf	0.067	0.065

2.5.6. Region BIII

Finally after completing automated and manual calibration, the flow variables were reached to the defined criteria for calibration and validation of flow for Dubysa watershed. There are two different stations (Table 23). Station ID 6 which is more downstream (tending to the middle stream) and the station ID 10 which is related to the upstream with more influence from the upstream part of the catchment. Since Dubysa is a big catchment we used this upstream station only to validate and check the calibrated model.

Table 23: Calibrated and validated watersheds and stations.

Hydrological region	Station Name (Hydrology)	Watershed Name
BIII	Dubysa_Lyubernai (reach 14) Krazantes_Pluskiiai (reach 3)	Dubysa_Dubysa

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

Table 24: List of calibration and validation results for Dubysa_Dubysa.

Dubysa Dubysa: Station 6, Reach14, Calibrating Station, Flow	
	Flow
NSE Cal: >0.5 (01.01.1997-31.12.2001;01.09.2008-31.12.2012)	0.58
NSE Val: >0.4 (01.01.2002-31.12.2007)	0.75
PBIAS Cal, <0.2	-1.32%
PBIAS Val, <0.25	4.12%
Dubysa Dubysa: Station 10, Reach3, Validating Station, Flow	
	Flow
NSE Val (01.01.1997-31.12.2012)	0.54
PBIAS Val	-19%

The calibration targets was reached for Dubysa_Lyubernai, and the validation threshold was also met for two stations, see Table 24. Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. Intermediate results of 95% prediction uncertainty bands quantification after flow autocalibration at station ID 6 are shown in Fig. 28 for Dubysa_Lyubernai for calibration period 1997-2001 and 2005-2009. They indicated that the model has been improved.

Figure 28: Intermediate results of 95% prediction uncertainty bands quantification after flow autocalibration. Station ID 6 for Dubysa_Lyuvėnai, calibration period 1997-2001 and 2005-2009.

Results changes in objective function after 20 iterations for initial automated calibration for flow for Dubysa_Lyuvėnai are shown in Figure 29.

The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 25.

Table 25: List of final hydrological parameters for Dubysa_Dubysa. R means relative change and V means replacing with a new value.

Hydrological Parameters with Impact on Flow, in stream N and in stream P	
r__CN2.mgt	-0.15
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.1
V__GW_DELAY.gw	1.2
V__GWQMN.gw	26.9
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.234
V__SMTMP.bsn	0.684
V__TIMP.bsn	0.632
V__SMFMN.bsn	2.623
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.05
V__RCHRD_DP.gw	0.06
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.23
V__ESCO.hru	0.7
V__CANMX.hru	5.5
r__SOL_AWC().sol	0.1
r__SOL_K().sol	0.1
r__SOL_BD().sol	0.2

Figure 29: Results changes in objective function after 20 iterations for initial automated calibration for flow for Dubysa_Lyuvėnai.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 30. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 31; it indicates very good representation of Dubysa_Lyuvėnai seasonal hydrograph.

The water balance components for Dubysa_Dubysa (full period) is shown in Fig. 32 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

A warning indicated that the surface runoff and surface runoff ratio may be too low. Checking ground water to total water yield ratio, model indicates this value as 0.51. The results of baseflow filtering by SWAT program which is fully compatible with SWAT and SWAT CUP algorithms indicated this fraction between 0.58 to 0.78 for Dubysa, see Table 26. The calibrated result seems to be acceptable. In general, the fraction of water yield contributed by baseflow should be between the value for Baseflow Fr1 and Baseflow Fr2. If the baseflow in your watershed is not from aquifers recharged by precipitation falling in the watershed, things get more complicated and this rule may not apply.

Figure 30: Time plot model output - green, observations – red for Dubysa_Lyuvėnai (for 1997-2012, just for 2011 there is no observation available).

Figure 31: Seasonal plot model output - green, observations - red for Dubysa_Lyuvernai.

Figure 32: SWAT Check screenshot for Dubysa_Dubysa. Water balance components and warnings.

Table 26: List of baseflow filtering results specifically for Dubysa_Dubysa using SWAT baseflow program.

	Dubysa	
	Station ID 6	Station ID 10
FR1	0.78	0.72
FR2	0.65	0.58
FR3	0.57	0.5
Alpha_Bf	0.037	0.049

2.5.7. Region BIV

Tatula-Trečionys station was chosen for calibration and validation in the hydrological region BIV, see Table 27.

Table 27: Calibrated watersheds and stations.

Hydrological region	Station Name (Hydrology)	Watershed Name
BIV	Tatula-Trečionys (reach 1)	Musa_Tatula

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets was reached for Tatula-Trečionys, and the validation threshold was also met for two stations, see Table 28. Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 29.

Table 28: Final results for Musa_Tatula.

2006-2012	Flow
NSE Cal, 2006-2007 and 2011-2012 , > 0.5	0.59
NSE Val, 2008-2010 , > 0.4	0.50
PBIAS Cal, < 20%	-10.12%
PBIAS Val, < 25%	1.2%

Table 29: List of final parameters for Musa_Tatula. R means relative change and V means replacing with a new value.

Hydrological Parameters with Impact on Flow, in stream N and in stream P	
r__CN2.mgt	-0.15
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.1
V__GWQMN.gw	35
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.634
V__SMTMP.bsn	0.884
V__TIMP.bsn	0.632
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.423
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.1
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.623
V__ESCO.hru	0.5
V__CANMX.hru	6
r__SOL_AWC().sol	0.25
r__SOL_K().sol	0.25
r__SOL_BD().sol	0.35

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 33. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 34. It indicates very good representation of Tatula-Trečionys seasonal hydrograph.

Figure 33: Time plot model output - green, observations – red for Tatula-Trečionys.
Observation period was shorter for this station (2006-2012).

Figure 34: Seasonal plot model output - green, observations – red for Tatula-Trečionys.

The Water balance components for Musa_Tatula basin (full period) are shown in Figure 35 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

Warnings indicated the problem considering a larger portion of lateral flow (a little bit larger than 1/3 of the total yield). However, comparing to the amount of the water which is available in tile drainage flow, this is not significant. SWAT CHECK is not splitting and considering the tile flow separately. It is better to use output.std.

Figure 35: SWAT Check screenshot for Musa_Tatula. Water balance components and warnings.

2.5.8. Region BV

Hydrometric station Nevėžis-Panevėžys was selected for calibration and validation in the central hydrological region BV. The watershed of upstream Nevėžis is shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36: Nevezis_Nevezis_upstr watershed, station Nevėžis-Panevėžys was used for hydrology calibration.

Table 30: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

BV: Nevėžis-Panevėžys	Period	NSE	PBIAS
Calibration	01.01.1997-02.05.2002; 02.09.2007-31.12.2012	0.63	-8%
Validation	03.05.2002-01.09.2007	0.67	-13%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets was reached for Nevėžis-Panevėžys, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 30.

Table 31: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Nevėžis-Panevėžys.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.1075
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.015
V_GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V_GWQMN.gw	100	30
V_GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.05
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V_SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V_TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
V_SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V_SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.05
V_SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V_ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V_CANMX.hru	15	20
R_SOL_AWC().sol	0	0.29
R_SOL_K().sol	0	0.25
R_SOL_BD().sol	0	0.35

Figure 37: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during

the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 31.

Figure 38: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 39: SWAT Check screenshot for Nevėžis-Panevėžys. Water balance components and warnings.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 37. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 38; it indicates a good representation of

Nevėžis-Panevėžys seasonal hydrograph; model slightly underestimates the snow-melt peak values.

The water balance components for Nevėžis-Panevėžys (full period) is shown in Fig. 39 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10. Three potential problems are identified by this software:

1. Groundwater ratio may be low
2. Lateral flow is greater than groundwater flow, may indicate a problem
3. Surface runoff may be too low

These warnings are characteristic for the central hydrological region (B) and do not reflect a problems in the model. Model correctly represents the situation in watershed with predominant low-permeable cambisoils (Figures 11-12). In this region the baseflow share in the river yield is low (warnings 1-2). In the same time a response to the rain events is not immediate due to rather flat terrain (warnings 2-3) and, generally lower precipitation (Figure 4).

2.5.9. Region BVI

Hydrometric station Mituva-Žindaičiai was selected for calibration and validation in the central hydrological region BVI. The watershed of Mituva is shown in Fig. 40.

Figure 40: Nemunas_Mituva watershed, station Mituva-Žindaičiai was used for calibration.

Figure 41: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Table 32: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

BVI: Mituva-Žindaičiai	Period	NSE	PBIAS
Calibration	01.01.1997-02.05.2002; 02.09.2007-31.12.2012	0.61	-14%
Validation	03.05.2002-01.09.2007	0.49	22%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets was reached for Mituva-Žindaičiai, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 32.

Table 33: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Mituva-Žindaičiai.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.236
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.075
V_GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V_GWQMN.gw	100	30
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634

	Initial	calibrated
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.850
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	6.803
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.400
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	6.803
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.315
V__CANMX.hru	10	7.000
R__SOL_AWC(..).sol	0	0.117
R__SOL_K(..).sol	0	0.394
R__SOL_BD(..).sol	0	0.396

Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 33.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 41. We noticed that the validation years were rather dry in this watershed in comparison with the calibration years. This resulted in less perfect PBIAS for the validation period, see Table 32.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 42; it indicates a very good representation of Mituva-Žindaičiai seasonal hydrograph.

The water balance components for Mituva-Žindaičiai (full period) is shown in Figure 43 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10. Two potential problems are identified by this software:

1. Surface runoff ratio may be low (< 0.2)
2. Lateral flow is greater than groundwater flow, may indicate a problem

These warnings are characteristic for the central hydrological region (B) and do not reflect a problems in the model. Model correctly represents the situation in watershed with predominant low-permeable cambisols (Figures 11-12). In this region the baseflow share in the river yield is low and lateral flow exceeds the groundwater flow (warning 2). The response to the rain events is not immediate due to rather flat terrain and, generally, the surface runoff is low (warning 1).

Figure 42: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 43: SWAT Check screenshot for Mituva-Žindaičiai. Water balance components and warnings.

2.5.10. Region BVII

Hydrometric station Nemunėlis-Kvetkai was selected for calibration and validation in the central hydrological region BVII. The watershed of downstream Nemunėlis is shown in Figure 44.

Figure 44: Nemunelis_Nemunelis_dwnstr watershed, station Nemunėlis-Kvetkai was used for calibration.

Table 44: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

BVII: Nemunėlis-Kvetkai	Period	NSE	PBIAS
Calibration	01.01.2008-31.08.2009; 03.05.2011-31.12.2012	0.69	7%
Validation	01.09.2009-02.05.2011	0.71	2%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation. Note that in hydrological region BVII the length of available data series for calibration and validation was only 5 years.

The calibration targets was reached for Nemunėlis-Kvetkai, and the validation threshold was

also met, see Table 44.

Table 45: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Nemunėlis-Kvetkai.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.076
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.026
V_GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V_GWQMN.gw	100	30
V_GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.05
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V_SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V_TIMP.bsn	1	0.842
V_SMFMN.bsn	4.5	2.455
V_SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.05
V_SMFMX.bsn	4.5	2.455
V_ESCO.hru	0.95	0.5
V_CANMX.hru	10	8.185
R_SOL_AWC(..).sol	0	0.29
R_SOL_K(..).sol	0	0.25
R_SOL_BD(..).sol	0	0.35

Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 45.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 45.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 46; it indicates a good representation of Nemunėlis-Kvetkai seasonal hydrograph with a slight overestimation of the summer low-flow.

The water balance components for Nemunėlis-Kvetkai (full period) is shown in Fig. 47 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10. Two potential problems are identified by this software:

1. Surface runoff ratio may be low (< 0.2)
2. Lateral flow is greater than groundwater flow, may indicate a problem

These warnings are characteristic for the central hydrological region (B) and do not reflect a problems in the model. Model correctly represents the situation in watershed with predominant low-permeable cambisols (Figures 11-12). In this region the baseflow share in the river yield is low and lateral flow exceeds the groundwater flow (warning 2). The response to the rain events is not immediate due to rather flat terrain and, generally, the surface runoff is low (warning 1).

Figure 45: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 46: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 47: SWAT Check screenshot for Nemunėlis-Kvetkai. Water balance components and warnings.

2.5.11. Region CIX

Hydrometric station Verknė-Verbyliškės was selected for calibration and validation in the southeastern hydrological region CIX. The watershed of Verknė is shown in Fig. 48.

Figure 48: Nemunas_Verkne watershed, station Verknė-Verbyliškės was used for calibration.

Table 36: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

CIX: Verknē-Verbylišķēs	Period	NSE	PBIAS
Calibration	01.01.1997-02.05.2002; 02.09.2007-31.12.2012	0.52	-14%
Validation	03.05.2002-01.09.2007	0.56	1%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation

The calibration targets was reached for Verknē-Verbylišķēs, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 36.

Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 37.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 49.

Table 37: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Verknē-Verbylišķēs.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.377
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.008
V_GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V_GWQMN.gw	100	0
V_GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.050
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	109.348
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V_SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V_TIMP.bsn	1	0.800
V_SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.2
V_SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.050
V_SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.2
V_ESCO.hru	0.95	0.400
V_CANMX.hru	10	10.824
R_SOL_AWC().sol	0	0.067
R_SOL_K().sol	0	0.188
R_SOL_BD().sol	0	-0.334

Figure 49: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 50; it indicates a good representation of Verknē-Verbyliškės seasonal hydrograph with an underestimation of the winter/spring discharges (note a negative PBIAS in Table 36).

Figure 50: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 51: SWAT Check screenshot for Verknė-Verbyliškės. Water balance components and warnings.

The water balance components for Verknė-Verbyliškės (full period) is shown in Fig. 51 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10. Two potential problems are identified by this software:

1. Surface runoff ratio may be low (< 0.2).
2. Surface runoff may be too low

These warnings are characteristic for the southeastern hydrological region (C) and do not reflect a problems in the model. Model correctly represents the situation in watershed with predominant relatively permeable luvisols (Figures 11-12). In this region the surface flow share in the river yield is low.

2.5.12. Region CX

Station Širvinta-Liukonys is used for calibration/validation in hydrological region CX, see Table 38.

Table 38: List of water quantity stations in Shevntoji_Sirvinta.

Hydrological region	Station Name (Hydrology)	Watershed Name
CX	Širvinta-Liukonys (reach 9) Station IS 42	Shventoji_Sirvinta

The time period of observations was split to 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration

and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets was reached for Širvinta-Liukonys, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 39. Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 40.

Table 39: List of final flow results for Shventoji_Sirvinta.

Širvinta - Liukonys: Station 42, Reach9, Calibration and Validation, Flow	
1999-2012	Flow
NSE Cal: 1999-2002 and 2009-2012, >0.5	0.58
NSE Val: 2003-2008, >0.4	0.74
PBIAS Cal, <0.2	-12%
PBIAS Val, <0.25	-0.5%

Table 40: List of final parameters for Shventoji_Sirvinta. R means relative change and V means replacing with a new value.

Hydrological Parameters with Impact on Flow, in stream N and in stream P	
r__CN2.mgt	-0.15
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.1
V__GWQMN.gw	30
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.634
V__SMTMP.bsn	1.284
V__TIMP.bsn	0.632
V__SMFMN.bsn	3.223
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.05
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.623
V__ESCO.hru	0.5
V__CANMX.hru	6
r__SOL_AWC().sol	0.29
r__SOL_K().sol	0.25
r__SOL_BD().sol	0.35

Figure 52: Time plot model output - green, observations – red for Širvinta-Liukonys watershed. Observation period was shorter for this station (1999-2012).

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 52. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 53; it indicates very good representation of Širvinta-Liukonys seasonal hydrograph.

Figure 53: Seasonal plot, model output - green, observations – red for Širvinta-Liukonys watershed (1999-2012).

The Water balance components for Shventoji_Širvinta (full period) are shown in Figure 54 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

Warnings indicated that:

1. The surface runoff and surface runoff ratio may be too low. Checking ground water to total water yield ratio model indicates this value as 0.587. The results of baseflow filtering by SWAT program which is fully compatible with SWAT and SWAT-CUP algorithms indicated this fraction can be between 0.25 and 0.77 for Sirvinta, see Table 41. The calibrated result seems to be acceptable and in the the range.
2. The problem considering a large protion of lateral flow comparing with the amount of the

water which is available in tile drainage flow is not significant. SWAT CHECK is not splitting and considering the tile flow separately. It is better to use output.std.

Table 41: List of baseflow filtering results for Širvita-Liukonys using SWAT baseflow program.

FR1	0.77
FR2	0.68
FR3	0.25
Alpha_Bf	0.037

Figure 54: Hydrological processes for Shventoji_Širvinta entire basin.

2.5.13. Region CXI

Hydrometric station Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos was selected for calibration and validation in the southeastern hydrological region CXI. The watershed of Ūla-Pelesa is shown in Fig. 55.

Figure 55: Merkys_Pelesa watershed, station Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos was used for calibration.

Table 42: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

CXI: Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos	Period	NSE	PBIAS
Calibration	01.01.1997-02.05.2002; 02.09.2007-31.12.2012	0.51	-9%
Validation	03.05.2002-01.09.2007	0.47	-1%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation

The calibration targets was reached for Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 42.

Table 43: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.400
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.03	0.120
V_GW_DELAY.gw	30	500
V_GWQMN.gw	100	30
v_RCHRG_DP.gw	0.35	0.050
V_GW_REVAP.gw	0.12	0.02
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.6
V_SMTMP.bsn	2	1.300
V_TIMP.bsn	0.1	0.6
V_SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.1
V_LAT_TTIME.hru	3	0
R_SOL_AWC().sol	0	-0.2
R_SOL_K().sol	0	0.2
R_SOL_BD().sol	0	-0.25

Figure 56: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial

parameter values are summarised in Table 43.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 56.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 57; it indicates a good representation of Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos seasonal hydrograph with a slight underestimation of the spring snow-melt discharges. The particularly spectacular is a high summer low-flow value (Figures 56-57) in a baseflow dominated watershed.

Figure 57: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The water balance components for Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos (full period) is shown in Figure 58 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10. Three potential problems are identified by this software:

1. Surface runoff ratio may be low (< 0.2).
2. Groundwater ratio may be high.
3. Surface runoff may be too low.

These warnings are characteristic for the southeastern hydrological region (C) and do not reflect a problems in the model. Model correctly represents the situation in watershed with predominant highly permeable arenosols (Figures 11-12). In the hydrological region CXI baseflow dominates in the river yield.

Figure 58: SWAT Check screenshot for Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos. Water balance components and warnings.

2.5.13. Region CXII

Hydrometric station Svyla-Guntauninkai was selected for calibration and validation in the southeastern hydrological region CXII. The watershed of Svyla is shown in Fig. 59.

Figure 59: Dauguva_Birveta watershed, station Svyla-Guntauninkai was used for calibration.

Table 44: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

CXII: Svyla-Guntauninkai	Period	NSE	PBIAS
Calibration	01.01.1997-31.12.1999; 02.01.2010-31.12.2012	0.69	-15%
Validation	01.01.2000-31.12.2000; 01.01.2008-01.01.2010	0.6	-14%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration and the middle part of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation. Note that there was a 7 year data gap for years 2001-2007 in the observations.

Table 45: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Svyla-Guntauninkai.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.309
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.125
V_GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V_GWQMN.gw	100	30
V_GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.031
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V_SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V_TIMP.bsn	1	0.796
V_SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.203
V_SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.156
V_SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.203
V_ESCO.hru	0.95	0.418
V_CANMX.hru	10	15.522
R_SOL_AWC(..).sol	0	-0.155
R_SOL_K(..).sol	0	0.012
R_SOL_BD(..).sol	0	0.423

Figure 60: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The calibration targets were reached for Svyla-Guntauninkai, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 44.

Model calibration was performed by combined usage of SWAT CUP (TOR 3.2.1.13) and manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 45.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 60.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 61; it indicates a reasonable representation of Svyla-Guntauninkai seasonal hydrograph with an underestimation of the spring snow-melt and winter discharges. See Table 44 for the respective negative PBIAS of water discharge.

Figure 61: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The water balance components for Svyla-Guntauninkai (full period) is shown in Fig. 62 according to analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10. Three potential problems are identified by this software:

1. Surface runoff ratio may be low (< 0.2).
2. Lateral flow is greater than groundwater flow, may indicate a problem
3. Surface runoff may be too low.

These warnings are characteristic for the hydrological regions (B and C) and do not reflect a problems in the model. Thus, observed match of the summer low-flow shows a correct representation of the baseflow component (warning 2). The absence of the immediate response to the rainfall event indicates that surface flow component is similar to hydrological region B.

Figure 62: SWAT Check screenshot for Svyla-Guntauninkai. Water balance components and warnings.

2.5.14. Transfer of coefficients

After the calibration and validation of the hydrological part of the model at selected stations the model parameters were transferred to the rest of the subbasins within the same hydrological region (Figures 6, 17) according to TOR 3.2.1.11. The parameters from hydrological regions BVI and CXI were transferred to the catchments of hydrological regions BVIII and CXIII, respectively.

The model validation was additionally performed in places where the model was not calibrated, i.e., where the parameters were transferred. The summary of this validation is given in Table 46 assessing the validation versus criteria set in Table 12 for the whole period of observations.

Table 46. Assessment of the optional validation of the model after the parameter transfer. Green – the results that correspond to the extrapolation criteria: NSE > 0.3, PBIAS < 30%.

ID	Station Name	NSE	PBIAS
2	Akmena-Danė-Kretinga	0.54	8%
3	Akmena-Paakmenis	0.56	-16%
4	Aunuva-Aunuvėnai	0.38	7%
5	Bartuva-Skuodas	0.54	-1%
6	Dubysa-Lyduvėnai	0.69	-3%
8	Jūra-Tauragė	0.50	-8%
9	Klaipėdos kanalas-Lankupiai	0.46	-20%

ID	Station Name	NSE	PBIAS
10	Kražantė-Pluskiai	0.68	9%
12	Lėvuo-Bernatoniai	0.64	-4%
13	Merkys-Puvočiai	0.54	-10%
14	Minija-Kartena	0.66	-8%
15	Minija-Lankupiai	0.68	5%
16	Minija-Priekulė	0.48	-9%
17	Mituva-Žindaičiai	0.60	-6%
18	Mūša-Ustukai	0.58	5%
19	Nemunas-Druskininkai	0.99	3%
20	Nemunas-Kaunas	0.71	9%
22	Nemunas-Nemajūnai	0.79	1%
24	Nemunas-Smalininkai	0.82	-1%
26	Nemunėlis-Tabokinė	0.48	5%
27	Nemuno atš. Atmata-Rusnė	0.73	1%
28	Neris-Buivydziai	1.00	1%
29	Neris-Jonava	0.81	3%
30	Neris-Vilnius	0.86	7%
31	Nevėžis-Panevėžys	0.65	-9%
32	Nevėžis-Traupis	0.44	-10%
33	Sanžilės kan.-Bernatoniai	0.62	-2%
35	Skroblus-Dubininkas	-52.64	-52%
37	Strėva-Semeliškės	-4.56	3%
38	Svyła-Guntauninkai	0.68	-15%
39	Šalčia-Valkininkai	-0.05	20%
40	Šešupė-Kudirkos Naumiestis	0.54	-4%
41	Šešusis-Skirgailai	0.60	11%
42	Širvinta-Liukonys	0.59	-3%
43	Šušvė-Josvainiai	0.63	-2%
44	Šušvė-Šiaulėnai	0.62	24%
45	Šventoji-Anykščiai	0.54	-15%
46	Šventoji-Ukmergė	0.67	-16%
47	Šyša-Šilute	0.42	1%
48	Tatula-Trečionys	0.62	-3%
49	Upita-Eidukai	0.39	-15%
50	Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos	0.49	-6%
51	Venta-Leckava	0.75	-1%
52	Venta-Papilė	0.65	-6%
54	Verknė-Verbyliškės	0.53	-9%
55	Vilnia-Vilnius	0.23	-3%
56	Yslykis-Kyburiai	0.53	6%
57	Žeimena-Pabradė	-0.69	8%
58	Nevežis-Babtai	0.58	-3%
59	Daugyvenė-Rimšoniai	0.52	6%
60	Levuo-Kupiškis	0.61	17%

ID	Station Name	NSE	PBIAS
61	Šešupe-Liubavas	-13.6 ²	77%
62	Mūša-Žilpamūšis	0.70	15%
63	Nemunėlis-Kvetkai	0.71	5%
64	Platonis-Vaineikiai	0.54	7%
65	Pyvesa-Žadeikiai	0.61	0%
66	Nemunas-Rusne	0.68	22%
67	Sidarba-Šarkiai	0.47	51% ³
68	Istras-Talackoniai	0.67	-16%
69	Kulpe-Siauliai	0.32	-10%
72	Veivirzas-Mikuzai	0.69	12%
73	Jūra-Pajuris	0.49	-12%

The validation targets are not met (or are met according to only one of criteria) in 7 stations. According to TOR 3.2.3.1. in places where the model was not calibrated, but where the required monitoring data are available and it is possible to significantly improve results of the model (after assessment of results of validation) the additional calibration and validation should be performed.

Therefore these 7 stations were analysed separately:

1. **Skroblus-Dubininkas** indicates both unsatisfactory NSE and model underestimation of the discharge (negative PBIAS). According to internet source http://lt.wikipedia.org/wiki/Skroblaus_versm%C4%97s the Skroblus catchment is a thermal spring area. The geothermal processes are not included in SWAT therefore the recalibration of Skroblus was rejected.
2. **Strėva-Semeliškės** of hydrological region CIX indicated an unsatisfactory NSE for daily values of discharge. The reason for this is an abundance of lakes in the catchment of Streva, see Figure 63. The recalibration of Streva was rejected because (a) the water balance for this catchment is correctly represented and (b) we do not know the method how to improve the SWAT performance in the lake-dominated watersheds.

² NSE=0.42 and PBIAS=-2% after recalibration.

³ NSE=0.51 and PBIAS=15% after correction of station's catchment area.

Figure 63: WMS Strēva-Semeliškės and its upstream catchments.

3. **Šalčia-Valkininkai** of hydrological region CXI indicated an unsatisfactory NSE for daily values of discharge. The location of Šalčia watershed is shown in Figure 64 while the comparison of monthly modeled and measured discharges – in Figure 65. The recalibration of Šalčia-Valkininkai was rejected because of the following reasoning (cumulative effect of all considerations):
 - a. The watershed has a transboundary part.
 - b. The observation period is relatively short – only 5 years.
 - c. The comparison of observations and model results indicates a good agreement for the first 2.5 years and worse agreement for the last 2.5 years.
 - d. The river is dominated by the baseflow (characteristic for hydrological region CXI). Under such circumstances the seasonal flow variation is weakly pronounced and achievement of good NSE is harder as in the rivers with distinct flow seasonality.

Figure 64: Location of Šalčia watershed.

Figure 65: Monthly time graph of modeled (green) and observed (red) discharges at Šalčia-Valtininkai.

4. **Vilnia-Vilnius** of hydrological region CXI indicated an unsatisfactory NSE for daily values of discharge. The comparison of monthly modeled and measured discharges at this station is shown in Figure 66. The recalibration of Vilnia-Vilnius was rejected

because of the following reasoning (cumulative effect of all considerations):

- a. The location of Rokantiškiu HE upstream the station may compromise the NSE based on daily values.
- b. The river is dominated by the baseflow (characteristic for hydrological region CXI). Under such circumstances the seasonal flow variation is weakly pronounced and achievement of good NSE is harder as in the rivers with distinct flow seasonality. Thus, visual inspection of Figure 66 indicates good agreement of observed and measured discharges.

Figure 66: Monthly time graph of modeled (green) and observed (red) discharges at Vilnia-Vilnius.

5. **Žeimena-Pabrade** is a downstream WMS of hydrological region CXI (minor parts in CX); comparison of modelled and observed discharges indicated an unsatisfactory NSE for daily values of discharge. The watershed of Žeimena and location of the station are shown in Figure 67, and the comparison of monthly modeled and measured discharges at this station is shown in Figure 68. The reason for this is an abundance of lakes in the watershed of Žeimena, especially in the upstream subbasins, see Figure 67. Comparison of model results with observations show that water balance and summer low flow is well represented in the model; also the peak flow values are only slightly overestimated – probably due to discharge smoothing in the lake system. However, lake system creates a delay in discharge signal (Figure 68) which is not fetched by the model. The recalibration of Žeimena was rejected because
 - a. The upper and lower discharge values and water balance for this catchment is

correctly represented.

- b. We do not know the method how to improve the SWAT performance in the lake-dominated watersheds – especially in the case of multiple lakes in a single subbasin.

Figure 67: WMS Žeimena-Pabrade and its upstream catchments.

6. **Sidarba-Šarkiai** of hydrological region BIV indicated high PBIAS of discharge. The situation was improved by manual calculation of the station catchment area.
7. **Šešupe-Liubava** of hydrological region BVIII; for this region a model parameter transfer from the hydrological region BVI obviously was not successful. Therefore the results at this station was improved by recalibration. The respective model parameters and parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 47.

Thus, after consideration of validation results at 7 stations we rejected recalibration in 5 of them, improved results without recalibration in one station and performed recalibration in hydrological region BVIII.

Figure 68: Monthly time graph of modeled (green) and observed (red) discharges at Žeimena-Pabrade.

Table 47: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for hydrological region BVIII.

	Initial	calibrated
R_CN2.mgt	0	-0.44
V_ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.07
V_GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	712
V_GWQMN.gw	100	184
V_REVAPMN.gw	125	109
V_IPET.bsn	1	2
V_SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.63
V_SMTMP.bsn	1	1.30
V_TIMP.bsn	1	0.92
V_SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.75
V_SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.05
V_SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.75
V_ESCO.hru	0.95	0.21
V_CANMX.hru	10	37.19
R_SOL_AWC(..).sol	0	-0.10
R_SOL_K(..).sol	0	-0.14
R_SOL_BD(..).sol	0	-0.35

2.6. Calibration and validation: water quality

2.6.1. Introduction and sensitivity analysis for nitrate load

The calibration (TOR 3.2.1.2-3.2.1.4) and validation (TOR 3.2.2.1-3.2.2.2) of water quality part of the model was performed for the selected stations in each of the hydrological subregions of Lithuania. The calibration and validation were performed by Vrije University Brussels (regions AII, BIII, BIV, CX) and “Center for processes analysis and research”, SIA (regions AI, BV, BVI, BVII, BVIII, CIX, CXI, CXII). There are no water quality monitoring stations in region CXIII.

Table 48: The sensitivity analysis for Musa Tatula for 100 iterations.

Rank	Parameter Name	Parameter	t-Stat	P-Value
27	v__ALPHA_BF.gw	Baseflow alpha factor (days).	0.07	0.94
26	r__GW_DELAY.gw	Groundwater delay (days).	-0.09	0.93
25	v__ESCO.hru	Soil evaporation compensation factor.	-0.14	0.89
24	r__SLSUBBSN.hru	Average slope length	-0.43	0.67
23	r__SOL_AWC().sol	Available water capacity of the soil layer	-0.69	0.50
22	r__SMTMP.bsn	Snow melt base temperature	-0.86	0.39
21	v__SURLAG.bsn	Surface runoff lag time	0.86	0.39
20	r__CDN.bsn	Denitrification exponential rate coefficient.	-0.92	0.36
19	r__SHALLST_N.gw	Concentration of nitrate in groundwater contribution to streamflow from subbasin (mg N/l).	-0.93	0.36
18	v__CANMX.hru	Maximum canopy storage	0.97	0.34
17	r__RSDCO.bsn	Residue decomposition coefficient	-1.09	0.28
16	r__SOL_BD().sol	Moist bulk density	-1.33	0.19
15	r__NPERCO.bsn	Nitrogen percolation coefficient	-1.33	0.19
14	r__RCHRГ_DP.gw	Deep aquifer percolation fraction	-1.59	0.12
13	r__BLAI{ }.crop.dat	Max leaf area index	-1.62	0.11
12	r__SOL_NO3().chm	Initial NO3 concentration in the soil layer.	-1.81	0.08
11	r__SOL_K().sol	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	1.85	0.07
10	r__CMN.bsn	Rate factor for humus mineralization of active organic nitrogen	-1.87	0.07
9	r__N_UPDIS.bsn	Nitrogen uptake distribution parameter	1.88	0.06
8	r__SMFMX.bsn	Maximum melt rate for snow during year	1.90	0.06
7	r__SOL_ORGN().chm	[mg/kg] Initial organic N concentration in the soil layer .	-2.04	0.04
6	r__RCN.bsn	Concentration of nitrate in precipitation (ppm)	-2.19	0.03
5	r__SDNCO.bsn	Denitrification threshold water content	-2.23	0.03
4	r__CN2.mgt	SCS runoff curve number	2.31	0.02
3	r__SOL_ALB().sol	Moist soil albedo	2.96	0.00
2	v__GWQMN.gw	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur (mm)	3.93	0.00
1	r__SOL_Z().sol	Depth from soil later to bottom of soil profile	5.48	0.00

The calibration targets were selected according to TOR 3.2.1.5 and coordinated with EPA (TOR 3.2.1.6). They were set for the concentrations of N-NO₃, N-tot, P-PO₄ and P-tot according to the TOR 3.2.1.12.

The calibration and validation thresholds are summarised in Table 13 for monthly values of the observations of nutrient concentrations vs. model outputs. The monthly averages for all years in respective calibration or validation period were calculated. These 12 values of modeled concentration (mg/l) and corresponding 12 values of observations were used for R² and PBIAS calculation.

The result of Table 48 illustrates the sensitivity analysis for Musa Tatula for 100 iterations. The water quality parameters in *.SWQ files were not included in this Table.

2.6.2. Region AI

The upstream water quality station “Akmena-Danė ties Tūbausiaiis” of Akmena-Danė watershed (Figure 69) was selected for the calibration and validation in western hydrological region AI.

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration (01.01.1997-31.12.2000; 01.01.2006-31.12.2009, 96 observations) and the middle part (01.01.2001-31.12.2005, 60 observations) of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets was reached for Akmena-Dane, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 49.

Table 49: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

Substance	Criteria	Calibration	Validation
N-NO ₃	PBIAS	3%	16%
N-NO ₃	R ²	0.89	0.91
NTOT	PBIAS	-3%	11%
NTOT	R ²	0.82	0.90
P-PO ₄	PBIAS	37%	-2%
PTOT	PBIAS	-29%	-23%

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 50.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figures 70-71. They indicate an excellent agreement between model results and observations.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, phosphate phosphorus concentrations and flux of phosphate phosphorus are shown in Figures 72-73. The model matches the observed concentration levels although there are some irregular fluctuations in observed seasonal phosphorus cycle. The agreement between modeled and observed phosphorus flux is good.

The nitrogen and phosphorus balance components for Akmena-Dane (full period) are shown in, respectively Figures 74-75 according to the analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

Figure 69: BalticSea_AkmenaDane watershed, station Akmena-Danė-ties Tūbausiai was used for calibration.

Table 50: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Akmena-Dane.

	default	calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.07
V__SDNCO.bsn	0.95	0.9
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
R__SOL_LABP.chm	0	-0.9
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	0	-0.5
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	0	1
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.04
V__RCHRG_DP.gw	0.05	0.08
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0.1
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.05
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	35	1
V__GWQMN.gw	100	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V__CANMX.hru	10	20
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.4
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.06
V__PSETLR1.res	0	7
V__PSETLR2.res	0	7
R__SOL_BD.sol	0	0.27
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0	0.29
R__SOL_K.sol	0	0.25
R__USLE_K.sol	0	-0.64
V__BC4.swq	0.35	0.05

The warning “Nitrate is being removed from the soil profile, the simulation ends with 92.4% less” is given for nitrogen cycle. However, we did not find a trend in the soil nitrogen content during the calculation period. Therefore we assumed this message as caused by either (1) an error in SWAT Check program or (2) a quick initial adjustment in the initial composition of nitrogen components in the soil profile during a warm-up period.

No potential problems were identified for the phosphorus cycle.

Figure 70: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen concentrations.

Figure 71: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen fluxes.

Figure 72: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus concentrations.

Figure 73: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus fluxes.

Figure 74: SWAT Check screenshot for Akmena-Dane. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 75: SWAT Check screenshot for Akmena-Dane. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.3. Region AII

Station ID 22 was used for calibration of water quality in Jūra watershed (Table 51) and all water quality variables were within the acceptable ranges (Table 51).

Table 51: Final results for Jura_Jura.

Jura Jura: Station 22, Reach 13, Calibrating Station, Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-16%	34%	-13%	14.83%
R2 Cal				0.63	0.67
Jura Jura: Station 25, Reach 2, Validating Station, Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		5%	39.7%	-2%	23.38%
R2 Validation				0.3	0.44
Jura Jura: Station 21, Reach5, Validating Station, Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-47%	39%	-32%	12.00%
R2 Validation				0.55	0.57
Jura Jura: Station 271, Reach18, Validating Station, Water Quality					
2005-2009	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-21%	25%	-106%	-23.94%
R2 Validation				0.18	0.08
Jura Jura: Station 265, Reach27, Validating Station, Water Quality					
2005-2012	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-57%	-13%	-55%	-13.17%
R2 Validation				0.43	0.47

Table 52: List of final parameters for Jura_Jura. R means relative change and V means replacing with a new value. PHOSKD based on Absolute defined range of parameters in SWAT CUP can vary between 100 and 200.

Nitrogen Parameters with Impact on in stream N concentration	
v__HLIFE_NGW.gw	1.0
v__CDN.bsn	0.01
V__SDNCO.bsn	0.9
r__SOL_ORGN().chm	1.5
Phosphorous Parameters or Erosion Parameters with Impact on in stream P concentration	
r__SOL_SOLP().chm	-0.9
r__SOL_ORGP().chm	-0.8
V__PHOSKD.bsn	200
r__USLE_K().sol	-0.9
V__BC4.swq	0.35

Regarding to validation of the in-stream water quality variables at the other gauging stations (Table 51), there are three gauging stations which are already validated except validation of R-squared (correlation of arrays) for nitrate which is only 0.1 lower the criteria in

problematic station ID 265 in the middle part of the catchment and station ID 271 which seems a relatively huge mass of Nitrogen has been added from the inlet located just before the station and caused this error. So this station is with an interaction from neighbor catchment and an inlet from other basins has high influence on this part of the catchment by modifying the inlet time series we can get more reasonable results. The PTotal and PO4 are already validated.

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 52.

The time plots of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figure 76. They indicate agreement between the model results and observations.

Figure 76: Time plot of NO₃-N output - green, observations – black for Jura_Jura watershed, Station ID 22 (calibration station) for 1997-2004.

In addition, the average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figure 77. They indicate an excellent agreement between the model results and observations.

The model matches the observed concentration levels although there are some irregular fluctuations (in the second month which might be due to bad initial condition in the first months) in observed seasonal nitrogen cycle. The agreement between modeled and observed flux is rather good.

Figure 77: Seasonal plot of NO₃-N output - green, observations – red for Jura_Jura watershed, Station ID 22 (calibration station) for 1997-2004.

The SWAT Check screenshots for N and P balance are shown in Figures 78-79.

The reason that more than 90% reduction in Nitrogen has been illustrated can be due to:

1. High amount of plant uptake
2. In comparison with initial model set-up before calibration there was reduction in soil initial condition and fertilizer input derived by soil and crop experts. This part of calibration in input data has led to a significant reduction in soil nitrogen comparing to the initial condition.

Figure 78: SWAT Check screenshot for Jura_Jura. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 79: SWAT Check screenshot for Jura_Jura. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.4. Region BIII

Water quality variables for Dubysa watershed were calibrated and validated successfully (Table 53). We have two different stations. Station ID 6 is more downstream (tending to the middle stream) and the station ID 10 is related to the upstream with more influence from the upstream part of the catchment. Since Dubysa is a big catchment the upstream station was only used to validate and check the calibrated model.

Table 53: List of final results for Dubysa_Dubysa.

Dubysa Dubysa: Station 33, Reach 29, Calibrating Station, Water Quality					
1997-2012	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-19%	39%	14%	38.53%
R2 Cal				0.61	0.64
Dubysa Dubysa: Station 34, Reach 4, Validating Station, Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-17%	32%	48%	58.21%
R2 Validation				0.68	0.73
Dubysa Dubysa: Station 35, Reach6, Validating Station, Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		1.6%	34%	46%	60.35%
R2 Validation				0.63	0.54
Dubysa Dubysa: Station 218, Reach23, Validating Station, Water Quality					
2005-2009	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-34%	45%	11%	47.52%
R2 Validation				0.50	0.57

With regards to the in-stream water quality variables, the gauging station at the outlet of the catchment with station ID 33 (Dubysa - aukščiau Serežiaus), was selected for calibration. The remaining three middle stream and upstream measurement points have been used to check for validation criteria for entire period of data availability. The full list of changed parameters has been shown in Table 54.

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 54.

Table 54: List of final parameters for Dubysa_Dubysa. R means relative change and V means replacing with a new value.

Nitrogen Parameters with Impact on in stream N concentration	
v__HLIFE_NGW.gw	0.01
v__CDN.bsn	0.01
r__SOL_ORGN().chm	2.0
Phosphorous Parameters or Erosion Parameters with Impact on in stream P concentration	
r__SOL_SOLP().chm	-0.95

r__SOL_ORGP().chm	-0.99
r__PHOSKD.bsn	-0.5
r__USLE_K().sol	-0.9

The time plots of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and phosphate phosphorous concentration are shown in Figure 80. They indicate an excellent agreement between model results and observations.

Figure 80. Time plot of NO₃-N (above) and PO₄-P (below) output - green, observations – black for Dubysa_Dubysya watershed, Station ID 33 (calibration station) for 1997-2012.

In addition, the average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figure 81. They indicate an excellent agreement between model results and observations.

The model matches the observed concentration levels although there are some few irregular fluctuations in observed nitrates (especially underestimation in dry and warm seasons in months 5, 6 and 7). But generally, the agreement between modeled and observed phosphorus flux is good. This small underestimation can be observed in time plot and seasonal plot for nitrate and can be due to overestimation in flow since the flux is already well calibrated.

Also there is overestimation in both flux and concentration in the second month which might be due to bad initial condition in the first months in observed seasonal nitrate nitrogen. The agreement between modeled and observed flux is rather good.

Figure 81: Seasonal plot of NO₃-N output - green, observations – red for Dubysa_Dubysa watershed, Station ID 33 (calibration station) for 1997-2012 (entire period).

SWAT Check screenshots for Dubysa_Dubysa are shown in Figures 82-83.

The reason that more than 80% reduction in Nitrogen and more than 100% reduction of Phosphorous has been illustrated can be due to:

1. High amount of plant uptake.
2. In comparison with initial model set-up before calibration there was reduction in soil initial condition and fertilizer input derived by soil and crop experts due to errors in initial measurements. This part of calibration in input data has led to a significant reduction in soil nitrogen comparing to the initial condition.

Figure 82: SWAT Check screenshot for Dubysa_Dubysa. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 83: SWAT Check screenshot for Dubysa_Dubysa. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.5. Region BIV

Regarding to water quality calibration in Tatula catchment results of calibration for nitrate and total N are very good but the PBIAS for TOTP and PO4 is already calibrated but are close to validation criteria. Basically this problem can be due to the impact of the point sources before the gauging stations (Table 55). This problem may be solved by adjusting the location of point sources and checking the quality of measured point source data. There is smoothly over 70% overestimation in the downstream station (station 94) and around 70% underestimation in the upstream part (station 92) so the reduction of underestimation in upstream lead to increase of overestimation in downstream and this structural problem cannot be solved.

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 56.

Table 55: Final results for Musa_Tatula.

Musa Tatula: Station 92, Reach 3, Calibration, Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		28%	23.95%	9.87%	31.2%
R2 (Arrays correlation) Entire Duration				0.67	0.72
Musa Tatula: Station 93, Reach8, Validation, Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		72.83%	57.68%	20.5%	37.6%
R2 (Arrays correlation) Entire Duration				0.64	0.42
Musa Tatula: Station 94, Reach 1, Validation, Water Quality					
1997-2012	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration		-41%	-74.85%	16.7%	20.7%
R2 (Arrays correlation) Entire Duration				0.62	0.62

Table 56: List of final parameters for Musa_Tatula. R means relative change and V means replacing with a new value.

Nitrogen Parameters with Impact on in stream N concentration	
v__HLIFE_NGW.gw	0.01
v__CDN.bsn	0.01
r__SOL_ORGN().chm	6.2
v__RS4.swq	0.001
Phosphorous Parameters or Erosion Parameters with Impact on in stream P concentration	
r__SOL_SOLP().chm	-0.99
r__SOL_ORGP().chm	-0.99
r__PHOSKD.bsn	-0.99
r__USLE_K().sol	-0.99
v__BC4.swq	0.01
v__RS5.swq	0.1
v__RS2.swq	0.001

Musa_Tatula watershed, Station ID 92 (calibration station) for 1997-2012 (entire period) is used for calibration of water quality variables. The time plots of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and phosphate phosphorous concentration are shown in Figure 84. They indicate an excellent agreement between model results and observations.

Figure 84: Time plot of NO₃-N and PO₄-P output - green, observations – black for Musa_Tatula watershed, Station ID 92 (calibration station) for 1997-2012.

In addition, the average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figure 85. They indicate an excellent agreement between model results and observations.

The agreement between modeled and observed flux is rather good. The model matches the observed concentration levels although there are some irregular fluctuations in observed nitrates (especially underestimation in dry and warm seasons). This can be more due to overestimation in flow regimes in months 5 and 6. But generally, the agreement between modeled and observed phosphorus flux is good.

The agreement between modeled and observed flux (Figure 85) is excellent.

Figure 85: Seasonal plot of NO₃-N concentration and flux output - green, observations – red for Musa_Tatula watershed, Station ID 92 (calibration station) for 1997-2012

The model matches the observed concentration levels although there are some irregular fluctuations (in the second month which might be due to bad initial condition in the first months) in observed seasonal phosphate P, see Figure 86.

SWAT Check screenshots for Musa_Tatula are shown in Figures 87-88.

Figure 86: Seasonal plot of PO4-P concentration output - green, observations – red for Musa_Tatula watershed, Station ID 92 (calibration station) for 1997-2012 (entire period).

Figure 87: SWAT Check screenshot for Musa_Tatula. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

The reason that more than 83% reduction in Nitrogen and more than 100% reduction of Phosphorous has been illustrated can be due to:

1. High amount of plant uptake.
2. In comparison with initial model set-up before calibration there was reduction in soil

initial condition and fertilizer input derived by soil and crop experts due to errors in initial measurements. This part of calibration in input data has led to a significant reduction in soil nitrogen comparing to the initial condition.

Figure 88: SWAT Check screenshot for Musa_Tatula. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.6. Region BV

The upstream water quality station “Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio” of Nevežis watershed (Figure 89) was selected for the calibration and validation in central hydrological region BV.

Figure 89: Nevežis_Nevežis watershed, station Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio was used for calibration.

Table 57: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

Substance	Criteria	Calibration	Validation
N-NO3	PBIAS	32%	60%
N-NO3	R ²	0.84	0.80
NTOT	PBIAS	13%	44%
NTOT	R ²	0.91	0.85
P-PO4	PBIAS	20%	7%
PTOT	PBIAS	28%	13%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration (01.01.1997-31.12.2000; 01.01.2005-31.12.2005; 01.01.2008-31.12.2009; 01.01.2012-31.12.2012, 87 observations) and the middle part (01.01.2001-31.12.2004, 47 observations) of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation. Note that there are data gaps in the observation data series for Years 2006-2007 and 2010-2011.

The calibration targets was reached for Juosta, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 57.

Table 58: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Juosta.

	default	calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.07
V__SDNCO.bsn	0.95	0.9
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
R__SOL_LABP.chm	9	-0.9
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	9	-0.5
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	9	2
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.015
V__RCHRG_DP.gw	0.09	0
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.05
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	40	1
V__GWQMN.gw	100	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V__CANMX.hru	15	20
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.108
V__PSETLR1.res	0	5
V__PSETLR2.res	0	5
R__SOL_BD.sol	0	0.35
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0	0.29
R__SOL_K.sol	0	0.25
R__USLE_K.sol	0	-0.58
V__BC4.swq	0.35	0.05

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 58. Beside that, incorrect reservoir parameters were identified for Catchment ID 925; they there replaces as in Table 59.

Table 59: Correction of reservoir parameters for Catchment ID: 925.

	default	calibrated
V_RES_ESA.res	33.57	0.33
V_RES_PSA.res	33.57	0.33
V_RES_EVOL.res	110.77	1.1
V_RES_PVOL.res	100.7	1
V_RES_VOL.res	100.7	1
V_RES_RR.res	0.58	0.0058

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figures 90-91 for the whole observation period. They indicate a satisfactory agreement between model results and observations. Model overestimates the winter nitrogen concentration; in the same time the summer minimum values are well represented in the model.

Figure 90: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen concentrations.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, phosphate phosphorus concentrations and flux of phosphate phosphorus are shown in Figures 92-93. The model matches the observed concentration levels and to some extent even represents the observed seasonal phosphorus cycle. The agreement between the modeled and observed phosphorus flux is rather good.

The nitrogen and phosphorus balance components for Juosta (full period) are shown in, respectively Figures 94-95 according to the analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

The warning “Nitrate is being removed from the soil profile, the simulation ends with 85.4% less” is given for nitrogen cycle. However, we did not find a trend in the soil nitrogen content during the calculation period. Therefore we assumed this message as caused by either (1) an error in SWAT Check program or (2) a quick initial adjustment in the initial composition of nitrogen components in the soil profile during a model warm-up period.

No potential problems were identified for the phosphorus cycle.

Figure 91: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen fluxes.

Figure 92: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus concentrations.

Figure 93: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus fluxes.

Figure 94: SWAT Check screenshot for Juosta. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 95: SWAT Check screenshot for Juosta. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.7. Region BVI

The water quality station “Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio” of Širvinta watershed (Figure 96) was selected for the calibration and validation in central hydrological region BVI. There are no other stations in this region which does not have significant impact from other hydrological regions.

Figure 96: *Sesupe_Sirvinta* watershed, station *Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio* was used for calibration.

Table 60: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

Substance	Criteria	Calibration	Validation
N-NO3	PBIAS	-5%	-11%
N-NO3	R ²	0.76	0.53
NTOT	PBIAS	21%	-3%
NTOT	R ²	0.46	0.37
P-PO4	PBIAS	-41%	13%
PTOT	PBIAS	-6%	30%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration (01.01.1998-31.12.1999; 01.01.2003-31.12.2004; 84 observations) and the middle part (01.01.2000-31.12.2002, 48 observations) of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation. Note that there are no data starting from 2005. Observation data of 1997 were neglected because the concentration levels in this year differed from the rest of the period – was essentially lower.

The calibration targets were not reached for Šeimenā (correlation for total nitrogen and PBIAS for phosphates), and the validation threshold was also not met (correlation for total nitrogen), see red numbers in Table 60. However, the difference between the targets and the result is rather small and we assume that further “improvement” of the quantitative targets for this station (located downstream a town) would lead to inadequate process representation.

Figure 97: P-PO4 amount from pointsource in Vilkaiviskis.

We suggest that the errors in point source data is the reason for impossibility to reach calibration targets:

1. Figure 97 shows the tree-times drop of point source loads from Vilkaiviskis in 2001-

2005 in comparison with 1998-2000. The model results corresponds to this drop while the in-stream P-PO₄ observations generally remains as high as in the beginning of the period, see Figure 98.

Figure 98: P-PO₄ concentration at Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio, red points – observations, green line – model.

Figure 99: Total nitrogen load from pointsource in Vilkaviškis.

2. Figure 99 shows that total nitrogen load varies more than 10 times between different years of the available observation period. The total nitrogen observations do not confirm such variations, see Figure 100.

Figure 100: *N*tot concentration at Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio, red points – observations, green line – model.

Figure 101: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen concentrations.

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 61.

The average seasonal cycle of nitrate nitrogen concentrations is shown in Figures 101 for the whole observation period. It indicates an excellent agreement between the model results and observations given the problems with calibration.

Table 61: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Šeimena.

	default	calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.05
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
V__PHOSKD.bsn	175	125
R__SOL_LABP.chm	0	-0.75
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	0	-0.45
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	0	3.5
V__RCHRG_DP.gw	0.05	0
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	30	1
V__GWQMN.gw	100	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V__CANMX.hru	10	7
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
V__DIS_STREAM.hru	35	37
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.2
V__PSETLR1.res	0	5
V__PSETLR2.res	0	5
V__NSETLR1.res	0	5
V__IRES1.res	0	6
V__IRES2.res	0	10
R__SOL_BD.sol	0	0.35
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0	0.29
R__SOL_K.sol	0	0.25
R__USLE_K.sol	0	-0.37
V__BC4.swq	0.35	0.07

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, phosphate phosphorus concentrations and flux of phosphate phosphorus are shown in Figures 102-103. The model rather well matches both

the observed concentration levels and seasonal cycle (Figure 102). The loads are overestimated (Figure 103) due to problems with point source data (see above Figs 97-98).

Figure 102: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus concentrations.

Figure 103: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus fluxes.

The nitrogen and phosphorus balance components for Šeimena (full period) are shown in, respectively Figures 104-105 according to the analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

The warning “Nitrate is being removed from the soil profile, the simulation ends with 82.7% less” is given for nitrogen cycle. However, we did not find a trend in the soil nitrogen content during the calculation period. Therefore we assumed this message as caused by either (1) an error in SWAT Check program or (2) a quick initial adjustment in the initial composition of nitrogen components in the soil profile during a model warm-up period.

No potential problems were identified for the phosphorus cycle.

Figure 104: SWAT Check screenshot for Šeimena. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 105: SWAT Check screenshot for Šeimena. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.8. Region BVII

The downstream water quality station “Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio” of Nemunėlis watershed (Figure 106) was selected for the calibration and validation in central hydrological region BVII. There are no upstream water quality stations suitable for calibration and validation in this region.

Figure 106: Nemunėlis_Nemunėlis watershed, station Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio was used for calibration.

Table 62: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

Substance	Criteria	Calibration	Validation
N-NO3	PBIAS	0%	0%
N-NO3	R ²	0.77	0.71
NTOT	PBIAS	14%	5%
NTOT	R ²	0.77	0.73
P-PO4	PBIAS	-39%	-46%
PTOT	PBIAS	-22%	-32%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration (01.01.1997-31.12.1998; 01.01.2002-31.12.2004, 60 observations) and the middle part (01.01.1999-31.12.2001, 36 observations) of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation. Note that there

are no data starting from 2005.

The calibration targets were reached for Nemunėlis, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 62. The overestimation of phosphorus may be associated with the unaccounted point sources for this downstream station.

Table 63: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Nemunėlis.

	default	calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.07
V__SDNCO.bsn	0.9	0.9
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
R__SOL_LABP.chm	0	-0.8
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	0	-0.5
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	0	3
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.015
V__RCHRG_DP.gw	0.05	0
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.05
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	50	1
V__GWQMN.gw	100	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V__CANMX.hru	10	20
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.108
V__PSETLR1.res	0	5
V__PSETLR2.res	0	5
V__NSETLR1.res	0	5
V__IRES1.res	0	6
V__IRES2.res	0	10
R__SOL_BD.sol	0	0.35
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0	0.29
R__SOL_K.sol	0	0.25
R__USLE_K.sol	0	-0.5

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 63.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figures 107-108 for the whole observation period. They indicate a very good agreement between the model results and observations both for concentrations and fluxes. Model underestimates the summer nitrogen concentration; this is explained by the unaccounted point sources.

Figure 107: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen concentrations.

Figure 108: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen fluxes.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, phosphate phosphorus concentrations and flux of phosphate phosphorus are shown in Figures 109-110. The model rather good matches the observed concentration levels which are significantly higher as in upstream WQ station (compare with Sections 2.6.2 and 2.6.5, for example). To some extent it even represents the observed seasonal phosphorus cycle. The agreement between the modeled and observed phosphorus flux is worse although it matches the calibration targets. One may consider that there are systematic unaccounted point sources in Nemunėlis watershed.

Figure 109: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus concentrations.

Figure 110: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus fluxes.

The nitrogen and phosphorus balance components for Nemunėlis (full period) are shown in, respectively Figures 111-112 according to the analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

The warning “Nitrate is being removed from the soil profile, the simulation ends with 88.4% less” is given for nitrogen cycle. However, we did not find a trend in the soil nitrogen content during the calculation period. Therefore we assumed this message as caused by either (1) an error in SWAT Check program or (2) a quick initial adjustment in the initial composition of nitrogen components in the soil profile during a model warm-up period. No potential problems were identified for the phosphorus cycle.

Figure 111: SWAT Check screenshot for Nemunėlis. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 112: SWAT Check screenshot for Nemunėlis. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.9. Region BVIII

Only 2 water quality stations were available in this region (Figure 113) and none of them are suited for calibration because they are either under string influence from other hydrological regions, located downstream towns and have transboundary component.

Figure 113: Illustration of water quality stations in BVIII region.

Due to this reason the coefficient transfer from BVI region was attempted, however the resulting validation results were not satisfactory, see red numbers in Table 64.

Table 64: Results of validation of water quality model of region BVIII with the parameters from BVI region (Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio).

ID	Station Name	NO3	NO3	NTOT	NTOT	PO4	PTOT
		PBIAS	R2	PBIAS	R2	PBIAS	PBIAS
26	Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	221%	0.60	110%	0.70	75%	35%
27	Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	101%	0.65	67%	0.86	40%	25%

According to TOR 3.2.3.1 the recalibration was performed for both Šešupė stations and the validation targets set in Section were met (Table 65). The parameter set acquired from manual calibration to improve results in BVIII is given in Table 66.

Table 65: Results of validation of water quality model of region BVIII after the recalibration.

ID	Station Name	NO3	NO3	NTOT	NTOT	PO4	PTOT
		PBIAS	R2	PBIAS	R2	PBIAS	PBIAS
26	Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	-23%	0.50	-57%	0.48	2%	-50%
27	Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	-51%	0.84	-63%	0.79	-32%	-53%

Table 66: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for hydrological region BVIII.

	default	calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.05
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
V__PHOSKD.bsn	175	200
R__SOL_LABP.chm	0	-0.9
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	0	-0.5
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	0	2
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	700
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	20	1
V__GWQMN.gw	100	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V__CANMX.hru	10	37
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.4
V__PSETLR1.res	0	5
V__PSETLR2.res	0	5
V__IRES1.res	0	6
V__IRES2.res	0	10
R__SOL_BD.sol	0	-0.334
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0	-0.1
R__SOL_K.sol	0	0.2
R__USLE_K.sol	0	-0.67
V__BC4.swq	0.35	0.05

2.6.10. Region CIX

The upstream water quality station “Strēva - žemiau Semeliškių” of Strēva watershed (Figure 114) was selected for the calibration and validation in south-eastern hydrological region CIX.

Figure 114: Nemunas_Streva watershed, station Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių was used for calibration.

Table 67: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

Substance	Criteria	Calibration	Validation
N-NO3	PBIAS	-2%	43%
N-NO3	R ²	0.51	0.40
NTOT	PBIAS	6%	12%
NTOT	R ²	0.68	0.58
P-PO4	PBIAS	-23%	-30%
PTOT	PBIAS	28%	38%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration (01.01.1997-31.12.1998; 01.01.2002-31.12.2004, 60 observations) and the middle part (01.01.1999-31.12.2001, 36 observations) of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation. Note that there are no data starting from 2005.

The calibration targets were reached for Strėva, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 67. There is an opposite bias of mineral and organic phosphorus which may be caused by a quality of point source data in Semeliški town.

Table 68: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Streva.

	default	calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.05
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
V__PHOSKD.bsn	175	100
R__SOL_LABP.chm	0	-0.75
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	0	-0.4
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	0	2.2
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.01
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0.1
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	25	1
V__GWQMN.gw	100	1
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V__CANMX.hru	10	10
V__LAT_TTIME.hru	0	0
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.154
V__PSETLR1.res	0	2
V__PSETLR2.res	0	2
V__NSETLR1.res	0	5
V__IRES1.res	0	6
V__IRES2.res	0	10
R__SOL_BD.sol	0	0
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0	0
R__SOL_K.sol	0	0.225
R__USLE_K.sol	0	-0.545
V__BC4.swq	0.35	0.05

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 68.

Besides this, calibration revealed data errors in one of the reservoirs (Catchment ID: 1223). The parameters were changed, see Table 69.

Table 69: Reservoir parameter changes for catchment ID 1223.

	default	calibrated
V_RES_ESA.res	61.71	0.61
V_RES_PSA.res	55.6	0.56
V_RES_EVOL.res	300.4	1.94
V_RES_PVOL.res	263.32	1.7
V_RES_VOL.res	263.32	1.7
V_RES_RR.res	2.15	0.0139

Figure 115: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen concentrations.

Figure 116: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen fluxes.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figures 115-116 for the whole observation period. They indicate a good agreement between the model results and observations both for concentrations and fluxes.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, phosphate phosphorus concentrations and flux of phosphate phosphorus are shown in Figures 117-118. The model well matches the observed concentration levels and its seasonal change. The agreement between the modeled and observed phosphate phosphorus flux is excellent.

Figure 117: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus concentrations.

Figure 118: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus fluxes.

The nitrogen and phosphorus balance components for Strēva (full period) are shown in,

respectively Figures 119-120 according to the analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

Figure 119: SWAT Check screenshot for Strēva. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 120: SWAT Check screenshot for Strēva. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

The warning “Nitrate is being removed from the soil profile, the simulation ends with 76.1% less” is given for nitrogen cycle. However, we did not find a trend in the soil nitrogen content during the calculation period. Therefore we assumed this message as caused by either (1) an error in SWAT Check program or (2) a quick initial adjustment in the initial composition of nitrogen components in the soil profile during a model warm-up period.

No potential problems were identified for the phosphorus cycle.

2.6.11. Region CX

Water quality variables were calibrated successfully for station Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų of hydrological region CX, see Table 70. We have two gauging stations for water quality: Station 57 which is a downstream station and the station 56 which is located more upstream with no impact from point source pollution. Since SWAT is recording the results at the outlet of corresponding reach, we decided to calibrate the model with the downstream station and check (validate) the model behavior on the model. The criteria are fulfilled in all calibration and validation stations, Table 70.

Table 70: List of final results for Shventoji_Sirvinta.

Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų: Station 57, Reach 7, Calibration , Water Quality					
1997-2004	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration <0.4		37%	14%	-0.3%	23.65%
R2 Entire Duration >0.5				0.8	0.94
Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų: Station 56, Reach 7, Validation, Water Quality					
1997-2009	Flow	PO4	TotP	NO3	TotN
PBIAS Entire Duration <0.7		-52%	-46%	-18%	12%
R2 Entire Duration >0.4				0.84	0.94

Table 71: List of final parameters for Shventoji_Sirvinta. R means relative change and V means replacing with a new value.

Hydrological Parameters with Impact on Flow, in stream N and in stream P	
r__CN2.mgt	-0.15
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.1
V__GWQMN.gw	30
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.634
V__SMTMP.bsn	1.284
V__TIMP.bsn	0.632
V__SMFMN.bsn	3.223
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.05
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.623
V__ESCO.hru	0.5
V__CANMX.hru	6
r__SOL_AWC().sol	0.29
r__SOL_K().sol	0.25
r__SOL_BD().sol	0.35

Nitrogen Parameters with Impact on in stream N concentration	
v__HLIFE_NGW.gw	1.0
v__CDN.bsn	0.01
r__SOL_ORGN().chm	1.8
Phosphorous Parameters or Erosion Parameters with Impact on in stream P concentration	
r__SOL_SOLP().chm	-0.9
r__SOL_ORGP().chm	-0.95
r__PHOSKD.bsn	-0.5
r__USLE_K().sol	-0.5

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 71.

The time plots of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux are shown in Figure 121. They indicate an excellent agreement between model results and observations.

Figure 121: Time plot of NO₃-N and PO₄-P output - green, observations – black for Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų Station ID 57 (calibration station) for 1997-2004.

The time series agreement between modeled and observed phosphorus flux and concentration is very good.

In addition, the average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figure 122. They indicate an excellent agreement between model results and observations.

The model matches the observed flux levels although there are some irregular fluctuations (only in the third and fourth months) in observed seasonal phosphate P, Figure 123. The agreement between modeled and observed flux is rather good.

Figure 122: Seasonal plot of NO₃-N concentration and flux output - green, observations - red for Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų, Station ID 57 (calibration station) for 1997-2004.

SWAT Check screenshot for Shventoji_Sirvinta are shown in Figures 124-125.

The reason that more than 80% reduction in Nitrogen has been illustrated can be due to:

1. High amount of plant uptake
2. In comparison with initial model set-up before calibration there was reduction in soil initial condition and fertilizer input derived by soil and crop experts. This part of calibration in input data has led to a significant reduction in soil nitrogen comparing to the initial condition.

Figure 123. Seasonal plot of PO₄-P flux output - green, observations – red for Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų, Station ID 57 (calibration station) for 1997-2004.

Figure 124: SWAT Check screenshot for Shventoji_Sirvinta. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 125: SWAT Check screenshot for Shventoji_Sirvinta. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.12. Region CXI

The upstream water quality station “Būka – aukščiau Baluošo” of upstream Žeimena watershed (Figure 126) was selected for the calibration and validation in south-eastern hydrological region CXI.

Figure 126: Zeimena_Zeimena_upstr watershed, station Būka – aukščiau Baluošo was used for calibration.

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration (01.01.1997-31.12.1999; 01.01.2003-31.12.2004, 60 observations) and the middle part (01.01.2000-31.12.2002, 36 observations) of data series – for validation. Such approach

ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation. Note that there are no data starting from 2005.

Figure 127: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen concentrations.

Figure 128: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen fluxes.

The calibration targets were reached for Būka, and the validation threshold was also met, see Table 72. There is an opposite bias of mineral and organic nitrogen which may be caused by a lake processes which are not resolved sufficiently in SWAT.

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 73.

Table 72: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

Substance	Criteria	Calibration	Validation
N-NO3	PBIAS	36%	24%
N-NO3	R ²	0.74	0.72
NTOT	PBIAS	-30%	-15%
NTOT	R ²	0.51	0.67
P-PO4	PBIAS	1%	0%
PTOT	PBIAS	-10%	-8%

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figures 127-128 for the whole observation period. They indicate a reasonable agreement between the model results and observations both for concentrations and fluxes. Model, in general, overestimates the seasonal variation of nitrogen which may be a common SWAT problem for the hydrological region CXI.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, phosphate phosphorus concentrations and flux of phosphate phosphorus are shown in Figures 129-130. The model well matches the observed concentration levels and its seasonal change. The agreement between the modeled and observed phosphorus flux is good except for observed fluctuation (July, October) which may be caused by unaccounted pollution sources.

Figure 129: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus concentrations.

The nitrogen and phosphorus balance components for Būka (full period) are shown in, respectively, Figures 131-132 according to the analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

The warning “Nitrate is being removed from the soil profile, the simulation ends with 70.3% less” is given for nitrogen cycle. However, we did not find a trend in the soil nitrogen content during the calculation period. Therefore we assumed this message as caused by either (1) an error in SWAT Check program or (2) a quick initial adjustment in the initial composition of nitrogen components in the soil profile during a model warm-up period.

No potential problems were identified for the phosphorus cycle.

Table 73: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Būka.

	default	calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.1
V__SDNCO.bsn	0.9	0.9
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	2	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	3	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	3	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	0.1	0.632
R__SOL_LABP.chm	0	-0.84
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	0	-0.4
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	0	2
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.03	0.12
V__RCHRG_DP.gw	0.35	0.05
V__GW_DELAY.gw	30	500
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.12	0.02
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	10	5
V__GWQMN.gw	100	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
R__GWSOLP.gw	0	-0.15
V__CANMX.hru	10	20
V__LAT_TTIME.hru	3	0
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
V__DIS_STREAM.hru	35	15
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.108
V__PSETLR1.res	0	5
V__PSETLR2.res	0	5
V__NSETLR1.res	0	15

V_IRES1.res	0	5
V_IRES2.res	0	10
R_SOL_BD.sol	0	-0.25
R_SOL_AWC.sol	0	-0.2
R_SOL_K.sol	0	0
R_USLE_K.sol	0	-0.33
V_BC4.swq	0.35	0.05

Figure 130: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus fluxes.

Figure 131: SWAT Check screenshot for Būka. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 132: SWAT Check screenshot for Būka. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.13. Region CXII

The downstream water quality station “Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje” of Birvėta watershed (Figure 133) was selected for the calibration and validation in the south eastern hydrological region CXII. There are no upstream water quality stations suitable for calibration and validation in this region.

Figure 133: Dauguva_Birveta watershed, station Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje was used for calibration.

Table 74: Quantitative results of calibration and validation.

Substance	Criteria	Calibration	Validation
N-NO3	PBIAS	31%	23%
N-NO3	R ²	0.74	0.83
NTOT	PBIAS	-24%	-29%
NTOT	R ²	0.75	0.53
P-PO4	PBIAS	-2%	-8%
PTOT	PBIAS	6%	24%

The time period of observations was split into 3 parts; first and last part was used for calibration (01.01.1997-31.12.2001; 01.01.2008-31.12.2012, 119 observations) and the middle part (01.01.2002-31.12.2007, 72 observations) of data series – for validation. Such approach ensures fulfillment of TOR 3.2.2.1, 3.2.2.2, 3.2.2.4 for the model validation.

The calibration targets were reached for Birvėta, and the validation thresholds were also met, see Table 74. The nitrogen PBIAS indicates simultaneous overestimation of nitrates and underestimation of organic nitrogen; this effect was not analysed deeper due to the calibration targets were met for all variables.

Model calibration was performed by manual calibration. The minimum required number of model parameters was changed during the calibration (TOR 3.2.1.9). These parameter changes from the PAIC (2014) initial parameter values are summarised in Table 75.

Table 75: Initial PAIC (2014) and calibrated parameters for Birvėta.

	Initial	Calibrated
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.32	0.05
V__SDNCO.bsn	0.9	0.9
V__CDN.bsn	0.02	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.5	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.5	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	1	0.632
R__SOL_LABP.chm	0	-0.83
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	0	-0.5
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	0	-0.3
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.07	0.015
V__RCHRG_DP.gw	0.05	0.05
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.3	0.1
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.02	0.05
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	25	1
V__GWQMN.gw	100	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	125	30
V__CANMX.hru	10	10
V__ESCO.hru	0.95	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	0	1
R__CN2.mgt1	0	-0.108
V__PSETLR1.res	0	5
V__PSETLR2.res	0	5
V__NSETLR1.res	0	5
V__NSETLR2.res	0	5
V__IRES1.res	0	6
V__IRES2.res	0	10
R__SOL_BD.sol	0	0.35
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0	0.29
R__SOL_K.sol	0	0.25
R__USLE_K.sol	0	-0.44
V__BC4.swq	0.35	0.15

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, nitrate nitrogen concentrations and flux of nitrate nitrogen are shown in Figures 134-135 for the whole observation period. They indicate

a satisfactory good agreement between the model results and observations both for concentrations and fluxes. The seasonal cycle is fetched well while the model slightly overestimates the overall nitrate concentrations.

Figure 134: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen concentrations.

Figure 135: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) nitrate nitrogen fluxes.

The average seasonal cycles of, respectively, phosphate phosphorus concentrations and flux of phosphate phosphorus are shown in Figures 136-137. The model well matches the observed concentration levels which are low in the watershed without important point sources. The spring phosphate loads are overestimated by the model.

Figure 136: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus concentrations.

Figure 137: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) phosphate phosphorus fluxes.

The nitrogen and phosphorus balance components for Birvėta (full period) are shown in, respectively Figures 138-139 according to the analysis by SWAT Check software required by TOR 3.2.1.10.

The warning “Nitrate is being removed from the soil profile, the simulation ends with 90.1% less” is given for nitrogen cycle. However, we did not find a trend in the soil nitrogen content during the calculation period. Therefore we assumed this message as caused by either (1) an error in SWAT Check program or (2) a quick initial adjustment in the initial composition of nitrogen components in the soil profile during a model warm-up period.

No potential problems were identified for the phosphorus cycle.

Figure 138: SWAT Check screenshot for Birvėta. Nitrogen balance components and warnings.

Figure 139: SWAT Check screenshot for Birvėta. Phosphorus balance components and warnings.

2.6.14. Transfer of coefficients

After the calibration and validation of the water quality part of the model at selected stations the model parameters were transferred to the rest of the subbasins within the same hydrological region (Figures 6, 17) according to TOR 3.2.1.11. The parameters from hydrological region CXI was transferred to the catchments of hydrological region CXIII.

The model validation was additionally performed in places where the model was not calibrated, i.e., where the parameters were transferred. The summary of this validation is given in Table 76 assessing the validation versus criteria set in Table 13 for the whole period of observations.

Table 76. Assessment of the optional validation of the model after the parameter transfer. Green – the results that correspond to the extrapolation criteria.

St.ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
1	Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	-0.01	0.97	-0.02	0.99	0.01	-0.03
2	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	0.00	0.96	-0.05	0.94	0.08	-0.09
3	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0.05	0.96	-0.09	0.95	0.03	-0.13
4	Nemunas - aukščiau Alytaus	0.03	0.97	-0.08	0.96	0.23	-0.09
5	Nemunas – žemiau Alytaus	-0.10	0.98	-0.18	0.98	0.10	-0.20
6	Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	-0.02	0.97	-0.12	0.94	0.14	-0.15
7	Nemunas - aukščiau Prienų	0.17	0.99	-0.06	0.99	0.36	-0.10
8	Nemunas - aukščiau Kauno	0.10	0.93	-0.18	0.79	-0.34	0.00
11	Nemunas - žemiau Smalininkų	0.09	0.91	-0.20	0.92	0.25	-0.15
13	Nemunas - aukščiau Rusnės, aukščiau Leitės	0.66	0.82	0.10	0.85	1.16	-0.06
14	Minija - aukščiau Plungės	0.12	0.84	-0.39	0.85	-0.46	-0.62
15	Minija - žemiau Plungės	0.10	0.92	-0.37	0.89	-0.39	-0.53
16	Minija - žemiau Gargždų	0.28	0.95	-0.16	0.90	-0.07	-0.49
17	Minija - žemiau Priekulės	0.42	0.97	-0.12	0.79	0.02	-0.46
18	Veiviržas - ties Veiviržėnais	0.65	0.79	0.01	0.74	-0.11	-0.43
19	Šyša - aukščiau Šilutės	-0.16	0.79	-0.22	0.85	-0.22	-0.35
20	Šyša - žemiau Šilutės	0.17	0.59	0.40	0.39	0.25	0.33
21	Jūra - aukščiau Tauragės	0.06	0.92	-0.28	0.74	0.35	-0.44
22	Jūra - žemiau Tauragės	-0.05	0.82	-0.32	0.74	0.11	-0.39
23	Šešuvis - ties Skirgailiais	-0.02	0.91	-0.26	0.87	-0.02	-0.55
24	Šaltuona - žemiau Raseinių	-0.35	0.85	-0.43	0.77	-0.49	-0.52
25	Lokysta - žemiau Šilalės	-0.19	0.70	-0.35	0.64	-0.15	-0.46
26	Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	-0.23	0.50	-0.57	0.48	0.02	-0.50
27	Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	-0.51	0.84	-0.63	0.79	-0.32	-0.53
28	Šešupė - aukščiau Marijampolės	-0.24	0.89	-0.11	0.91	0.11	0.21
29	Šešupė - žemiau Marijampolės	-0.37	0.83	-0.27	0.87	-0.50	-0.35
30	Siesartis - žemiau Šakių	0.03	0.77	-0.24	0.15	-0.87	-0.80
31	Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio	-0.08	0.69	0.09	0.49	-0.20	0.08
33	Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus	-0.18	0.92	-0.36	0.87	0.12	-0.33

St.ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
34	Kražantė - aukščiau Kelmės	-0.47	0.89	-0.59	0.87	0.19	-0.28
35	Kražantė - žemiau Kelmės	-0.47	0.90	-0.62	0.78	0.00	-0.31
36	Nevėžis - aukščiau Panevėžio	-0.06	0.90	-0.09	0.80	-0.59	-0.36
37	Nevėžis - žemiau Panevėžio	-0.25	0.54	-0.23	0.01	-0.47	-0.36
38	Nevėžis - aukščiau Kėdainių	-0.11	0.44	-0.06	0.66	0.09	0.07
39	Nevėžis - žemiau Kėdainių	-0.18	0.68	-0.11	0.71	-0.41	-0.33
40	Nevėžis - aukščiau Raudondvario	-0.10	0.94	-0.15	0.93	-0.34	-0.30
41	Šušvė - žiotyse	-0.32	0.92	-0.44	0.92	-0.13	-0.31
42	Juosta - žemiau Jackagalio	0.35	0.85	0.20	0.90	0.08	0.20
43	Neris - ties Buivydžiais	0.00	0.98	-0.03	0.96	0.05	-0.02
44	Neris - aukščiau Vilniaus	-0.11	0.98	-0.16	0.86	0.20	0.00
45	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.11	0.98	-0.14	0.88	0.20	0.08
46	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.12	0.95	-0.14	0.80	0.29	-0.02
47	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.13	0.97	-0.10	0.79	0.31	0.05
48	Neris - aukščiau Jonavos	-0.20	0.97	-0.26	0.91	0.48	0.05
49	Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0.09	0.97	-0.21	0.92	0.58	0.13
50	Neris - aukščiau Kauno	0.00	0.96	-0.26	0.81	0.69	0.05
51	Lomena - žemiau Kaišiadorių	-0.71	0.09	-0.61	0.26	-0.42	-0.44
52	Šventoji - aukščiau Anykščių	0.57	0.93	0.26	0.85	1.11	0.45
53	Šventoji - žemiau Anykščių	0.52	0.91	0.28	0.82	1.08	0.51
54	Šventoji - aukščiau Ukmergės	0.20	0.94	0.01	0.89	0.83	0.13
55	Šventoji - žemiau Ukmergės	0.16	0.94	0.00	0.89	0.54	0.06
56	Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų	0.03	0.89	-0.16	0.92	0.42	0.14
57	Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų	-0.11	0.91	-0.25	0.91	-0.36	-0.33
58	Siesartis - žemiau Molėtų	-0.42	0.74	-0.49	0.70	-0.36	-0.19
59	Vyžuona - žemiau Utenos	-0.22	0.72	-0.23	0.72	-0.44	-0.37
60	Vilnia - aukščiau N.Vilnios	-0.55	0.75	-0.26	0.72	-0.17	0.08
61	Vilnia - žiotyse	-0.56	0.74	-0.29	0.77	-0.22	0.06
62	Žeimena - ties Kaltanėnais	0.05	0.34	-0.05	0.40	-0.14	0.31
63	Žeimena - žemiau Švenčionėlių	-0.02	0.55	-0.14	0.47	0.01	0.08
64	Žeimena - aukščiau Pabradės	-0.09	0.53	-0.17	0.56	-0.01	-0.06
65	Žeimena - žemiau Pabradės	0.03	0.67	-0.05	0.60	0.39	0.17
66	Būka - aukščiau Baluoso	0.31	0.75	-0.25	0.76	0.09	0.01
67	Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių	0.11	0.54	0.08	0.85	-0.26	0.32
68	Strėva - ties Liutonimis	-0.40	0.28	-0.21	0.14	-0.31	0.36
69	Merkys - aukščiau Varėnos	-0.33	0.78	-0.17	0.71	0.44	0.09
70	Merkys - žemiau Puvočių	-0.39	0.75	-0.38	0.65	0.10	-0.08
71	Skroblus - žemiau Dubininkų	1.61	0.59	0.09	0.52	-0.62	-0.60
73	Šalčia - žemiau Šalčininkų	-0.69	0.18	-0.53	0.37	-0.63	-0.44
74	Akmena - Danė - ties Tūbaisiais	0.04	0.92	0.00	0.91	0.17	-0.27
76	Akmena - Danė - aukščiau Klaipėdos	-0.18	0.58	-0.11	0.20	-0.06	-0.06
77	Akmena - Danė - žiotyse	-0.06	0.75	-0.01	0.59	0.51	0.16
78	Bartuva - aukščiau Skuodo	0.61	0.80	0.19	0.80	0.59	-0.10

St.ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
79	Bartuva - žemiau Skuodo	0.45	0.87	0.02	0.81	-0.16	-0.30
80	Venta - aukščiau Kuršėnų	-0.23	0.90	-0.49	0.84	-0.18	-0.54
81	Venta - žemiau Kuršėnų	0.03	0.36	-0.14	0.00	2.00	1.01
82	Venta - žemiau Mažeikių	-0.13	0.93	-0.34	0.88	1.45	0.48
83	Virvyčia - žemiau Pateklos	-0.15	0.92	-0.45	0.88	-0.27	-0.40
84	Mūša - aukščiau Kulpės	-0.06	0.79	-0.31	0.86	-0.32	-0.51
85	Mūša - žemiau Kulpės	-0.33	0.51	0.05	0.06	-0.21	-0.17
86	Mūša - žemiau Saločių	-0.01	0.90	-0.14	0.91	-0.40	-0.28
87	Sidabra - žemiau Jonišio	0.11	0.87	-0.68	0.33	-0.98	-0.98
88	Sidabra - Latvijos pasienyje	-0.28	0.77	-0.37	0.22	-0.72	-0.69
89	Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio	-0.08	0.87	0.06	0.91	-0.42	-0.26
91	Laukupė - žemiau Rokiškio	-0.40	0.84	-0.15	0.66	-0.61	-0.38
92	Tatula - aukščiau Biržų	-0.32	0.94	-0.36	0.94	-0.20	0.08
93	Tatula - žemiau Biržų	-0.32	0.84	-0.39	0.63	-0.73	-0.53
94	Tatula - ties Trečionimis	-0.20	0.80	-0.19	0.77	0.34	0.87
95	Lėvuo - aukščiau Kupiškio	0.33	0.97	0.34	0.71	-0.30	0.05
96	Lėvuo - žemiau Kupiškio	-0.13	0.93	0.03	0.72	-0.48	-0.29
97	Lėvuo - aukščiau Pasvalio	0.07	0.90	-0.01	0.85	-0.54	-0.41
98	Lėvuo - žiotyse	-0.18	0.95	-0.22	0.84	-0.79	-0.75
99	Daugyvenė - žiotyse	0.33	0.84	-0.03	0.86	-0.12	-0.23
100	Kruoja - žiotyse	0.26	0.84	-0.01	0.86	-0.49	-0.51
101	Obelė - žemiau Radviliškio	0.83	0.40	-0.44	0.17	-0.53	-0.42
102	Obelė - žiotyse	-0.03	0.76	-0.31	0.91	-0.65	-0.65
103	Kulpė - žemiau Šiaulių	-0.01	0.68	-0.06	0.06	-0.46	-0.41
104	Kulpė - žiotyse	-0.42	0.34	0.06	0.14	-0.19	-0.14
105	Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje	0.15	0.81	-0.30	0.75	-0.17	-0.03
106	Laukesa - žemiau Zarasų	0.61	0.23	0.01	0.38	0.01	0.31
127	Nemunas - Skirvytė aukščiau Rusnės	0.30	0.90	-0.04	0.86	0.89	-0.08
133	Šventoji - žiotyse	0.21	0.94	-0.07	0.83	0.51	0.01
135	Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Zapyškui	-0.08	0.70	-0.28	0.68	-0.28	-0.10
136	Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Kulautuva	-0.38	0.88	-0.42	0.80	-0.16	-0.29
137	Šešupė - Kaliningrado srit. pasienyje	-0.32	0.54	-0.34	0.39	-0.55	-0.50
138	Šventoji - žiotyse	0.14	0.86	-0.07	0.86	0.04	-0.23
141	Švogina-Žeimena - aukščiau Vaišniūnų	-0.20	0.51	-0.34	0.41	0.56	0.34
142	Širvinta - žiotyse	-0.05	0.66	-0.04	0.51	-0.69	-0.60
143	Siesartis - žiotyse	-0.16	0.66	-0.10	0.51	-0.79	-0.71
150	Jiesia - ties Šilavotu	0.43	0.73	0.02	0.76	-0.18	-0.27
151	Ūla - Pelesa - ties Kašėtomis	-0.65	0.78	-0.60	0.35	-0.31	-0.23
175	Mera - Kūna - ties Pažeimene	-0.60	0.57	-0.48	0.20	0.98	0.17
176	Kena - ties Rukainiais, ties keliu Nr.A3	-0.38	0.72	0.14	0.66	0.66	1.99
217	Šešuvis - ties Taubučiais	-0.29	0.79	-0.53	0.85	-0.37	-0.61
218	Dubysa - ties Kaulakiais, ties keliu Nr.225	-0.25	0.82	-0.55	0.81	0.35	-0.43
219	Žiežmara - ties Paparčiais	-0.63	0.61	-0.65	0.54	-0.32	-0.40

St.ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
265	Jūra - ties Mociškiais	0.24	0.89	-0.08	0.87	0.45	-0.12
266	Minija - ties Suvernais	0.54	0.84	0.04	0.85	0.35	-0.22
267	Karaliaus Vilhelmo kanalas - ties Dreverna	0.28	0.86	-0.09	0.90	0.09	-0.23
268	Vilka - ties Gudais	-0.24	0.85	-0.19	0.85	-0.27	-0.10
269	Salantas - ties Nasrėnais	0.08	0.81	-0.16	0.75	-0.11	-0.22
270	Graumena - ties Pakalniškiais	0.83	0.57	-0.07	0.72	0.27	-0.30
271	Akmėna - aukščiau Pagramančio	0.42	0.69	-0.12	0.48	0.23	-0.24
325	Dysna - ties Kačergiške	0.10	0.53	-0.37	0.60	1.13	0.66
327	Šventoji - ties Sabaliūnais (žemiau Andrioniškio)	0.70	0.93	0.23	0.71	1.71	0.84
357	Nemunėlis - Tabokinė	0.45	0.63	0.23	0.82	-0.31	-0.19
359	Šventoji - ties Bindzeliškiais, ties Pašilės ziotym	0.56	0.25	0.23	0.00	0.21	0.34
360	Pyvesa - tarp Žadeikių ir Geivitonių	-0.04	0.96	-0.20	0.86	-0.43	-0.14
401	Rausvė - ties Nadrausve	-0.36	0.82	-0.29	0.68	-0.51	-0.40
402	Višakis - aukščiau Pilviškių (kelias 137)	0.73	0.93	0.11	0.69	1.38	0.48
430	Varduva - ties Grieže	0.30	0.73	-0.19	0.81	1.34	0.66
431	Platonis - pasienyje	-0.31	0.66	-0.43	0.64	0.31	-0.10
432	Ašva - pasienyje	-0.45	0.83	-0.57	0.79	0.64	-0.06
433	Virvyčia - ties Janapole	0.04	0.75	-0.51	0.62	-0.39	-0.56
612	Nemunas – ties Pagėgiais, ties keliu Nr. A12	0.35	0.81	0.09	0.78	0.71	0.00

There are 34 water quality stations for which the calibration criteria was not fulfilled. The complex systemic approach (as contrary to considering individual station) was used to improve the model performance according to TOR 3.2.3.1:

1. The in-stream water quality parameters were changed for Nemunas river (point 1a and 1c below) and several catchments in hydrological region BVII (point 1b).
 - a. Coefficient BC4.swq (Rate constant for mineralization of organic P to dissolved P in the reach at 20 °C, day⁻¹) and BC3.swq (Rate constant for hydrolysis of organic N to NH₄ in the reach at 20 °C, day⁻¹) were changed to value of 0.01 in basin of Nemunas. The list of catchments for this change is given in Table 77.

Table 77: List of Nemunas catchments where modification of point (1a) was performed.

Catchment ID										
1042	1040	637	1049	738	1051	1055	1062	1064	717	1060
1044	681	908	1047	794	1053	1057	994	867	1004	1045
1006	293	877	591	846	484	1058	853	50	1065	667

- b. In basin of Nemunelis BC4 was changed to value of 0.35. Such change was done in following catchments: 731, 605, 606, 608, 289, 1289, 784, 785, 365, 610.
 - c. For Nemunas downstream coefficient MUMAX (maximum specific algal growth rate at 20°C, day⁻¹) was changed to 100 (default is 2); this modification was applied for catchments 1065, 867, 50, 908.

- The coefficients in regions AII, BIII, BIV and CX were changed to improve extrapolation results, see summary in Table 78.

Figure 140: Definition of hydrological subregion BV1b.

Figure 141: Definition of hydrological subregion CX1b.

3. Because of differences in soil parameters within different parts of the same hydrological region we made two sub-regions:

Table 78: Recalibrated parameter values to improve the calibration after parameter transfer (calibration targets not affected). Green – default values. White – new values found in recalibration. Orange – changed back to default values during recalibration.

	AII	AIII	BIV	BVIb	CX	CXIb
V__SURLAG.bsn	0.05	0.15	0.05	0.1	0.05	0.1
V__CDN.bsn	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
V__SMTMP.bsn	1.284	1.284	1.284	1.284	1.284	1.284
V__SFTMP.bsn	0.634	0.634	0.634	0.634	0.634	0.634
V__SMFMX.bsn	4.623	4.623	4.623	4.623	4.623	4.623
V__SMFMN.bsn	4.623	4.623	4.623	4.623	4.623	4.623
V__TIMP.bsn	0.632	0.632	0.632	0.632	0.632	0.632
V__SDNCO.bsn	0.9	0.9	1	0.9	0.9	0.9
V__IRTE.bsn	0	0	0	0	0	0
V__PHOSKD.bsn	150	100	150	175	100	100
R__SOL_LABP.chm	-0.9	-0.9	-0.9	-0.83	-0.83	-0.83
R__SOL_ORGP.chm	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4
R__SOL_ORGN.chm	1.5	2.2	5.5	3	2	3
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.015	0.015	0.015	0.12	0.015	0.12
V__GW_DELAY.gw	0.1	0.1	0.1	500	0.1	500
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.02
V__HLIFE_NGW.gw	1	1	1	5	1	5
V__GWQMN.gw	30	30	30	30	30	30
V__REVAPMN.gw	30	30	30	30	30	30
R__GWSOLP.gw	0	0	0	-0.15	0	-0.15
V__RCHRG_DP.gw	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
V__CANMX.hru	20	10	10	10	20	10
V__ESCO.hru	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
V__ERORGP.hru	1	1	1	1	1	1
V__LAT_TTIME.hru	0	0	0	0	0	0
V__DIS_STREAM.hru	35	35	35	1	35	1
R__CN2.mgt1	-0.108	-0.108	-0.108	-0.108	-0.108	-0.26
V__PSETLR1.res	7	7	5	5	5	5
V__PSETLR2.res	7	7	5	5	5	5
V__NSETLR1.res	0	0	0	5	15	15
V__IRES1.res	6	6	6	5	6	5
V__IRES2.res	10	10	10	10	10	10
R__SOL_BD.sol	0.35	0.35	0.35	-0.25	0.35	-0.25
R__SOL_AWC.sol	0.29	0.29	0.29	-0.2	0.29	-0.2
R__SOL_K.sol	0.25	0.25	0.25	0	0.25	0.2
R__USLE_K.sol	-0.6	-0.7	-0.7	-0.3	-0.6	-0.34
V__BC4.swq	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
V__RS4.swq	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05

V_RS5.swq	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
V_RS2.swq	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05

- a. There is a spatially well-defined area of arenosols in the luvisol / cambisol dominated hydrological region BVI, see Figure 140. We defined a subregion BVib and find a different set of coefficients for it, see Table 78.
- b. Similarly, region CXI was split into region CXIa and CXIb, see Figure 141. The coefficients acquired from calibrating station Būka – aukščiau Baluošo were used for CXIa. Another set of coefficients was found for luvisol dominated subregion CXIb, see Table 78.

The summary of the validation after recalibration of the model is given in Table 79 assessing the validation versus criteria set in Table 13 for the whole period of observations.

Table 79. Assessment of the optional validation of the model after the recalibration and parameter transfer. Green – the results that correspond to the extrapolation criteria.

St ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
1	Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	-0.01	0.97	-0.02	0.99	-0.02	-0.03
2	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	0.00	0.96	-0.05	0.94	0.00	-0.09
3	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0.06	0.96	-0.09	0.95	-0.05	-0.13
4	Nemunas - aukščiau Alytaus	0.02	0.97	-0.09	0.96	0.08	-0.10
5	Nemunas – žemiau Alytaus	-0.12	0.98	-0.19	0.98	-0.03	-0.21
6	Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	-0.04	0.97	-0.13	0.94	0.00	-0.16
7	Nemunas - aukščiau Prienų	0.11	0.99	-0.07	0.99	0.12	-0.12
8	Nemunas - aukščiau Kauno	0.03	0.92	-0.19	0.79	-0.47	-0.02
11	Nemunas - žemiau Smalininkų	-0.02	0.90	-0.23	0.91	-0.13	-0.21
13	Nemunas - aukščiau Rusnės, aukščiau Leitės	0.47	0.83	0.07	0.84	0.48	-0.12
14	Minija - aukščiau Plungės	0.04	0.85	-0.30	0.88	-0.52	-0.55
15	Minija - žemiau Plungės	0.14	0.93	-0.20	0.81	-0.21	-0.32
16	Minija - žemiau Gargždų	0.25	0.92	0.04	0.90	-0.06	-0.33
17	Minija - žemiau Priekulės	0.40	0.94	0.03	0.77	0.10	-0.29
18	Veiviržas - ties Veiviržėnais	0.55	0.83	0.18	0.79	-0.30	-0.36
19	Šyša - aukščiau Šilutės	-0.16	0.79	-0.22	0.85	-0.22	-0.35
20	Šyša - žemiau Šilutės	0.17	0.61	0.39	0.38	0.22	0.32
21	Jūra - aukščiau Tauragės	-0.08	0.96	-0.20	0.72	0.06	-0.34
22	Jūra - žemiau Tauragės	-0.03	0.87	-0.16	0.78	0.02	-0.28
23	Šešuvis - ties Skirgailiais	0.15	0.94	-0.02	0.88	-0.17	-0.47
24	Šaltuona - žemiau Raseinių	-0.11	0.75	-0.11	0.54	-0.57	-0.51
25	Lokysta - žemiau Šilalės	-0.30	0.73	-0.24	0.70	-0.29	-0.33
26	Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	-0.23	0.50	-0.58	0.48	0.03	-0.50
27	Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	-0.52	0.84	-0.63	0.79	-0.31	-0.53
28	Šešupė - aukščiau Marijampolės	-0.25	0.90	-0.10	0.91	0.12	0.23
29	Šešupė - žemiau Marijampolės	-0.38	0.84	-0.27	0.87	-0.50	-0.34
30	Siesartis - žemiau Šakių	0.03	0.77	-0.23	0.13	-0.86	-0.79

St ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
31	Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio	-0.08	0.69	0.12	0.49	-0.18	0.11
33	Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus	0.00	0.91	-0.14	0.83	-0.16	-0.31
34	Kražantė - aukščiau Kelmės	-0.48	0.90	-0.52	0.84	-0.07	-0.22
35	Kražantė - žemiau Kelmės	-0.47	0.89	-0.53	0.63	-0.25	-0.25
36	Nevėžis - aukščiau Panevėžio	-0.08	0.90	-0.10	0.79	-0.60	-0.36
37	Nevėžis - žemiau Panevėžio	-0.26	0.54	-0.23	0.02	-0.47	-0.37
38	Nevėžis - aukščiau Kėdainių	-0.15	0.47	-0.09	0.67	0.04	0.04
39	Nevėžis - žemiau Kėdainių	-0.21	0.71	-0.14	0.73	-0.44	-0.35
40	Nevėžis - aukščiau Raudondvario	-0.16	0.92	-0.17	0.88	-0.42	-0.33
41	Šušvė - žiotyse	-0.23	0.89	-0.25	0.82	-0.15	-0.03
42	Juosta - žemiau Jackagalio	0.35	0.85	0.20	0.90	0.08	0.20
43	Neris - ties Buivydžiais	0.00	0.98	-0.03	0.96	0.05	-0.02
44	Neris - aukščiau Vilniaus	-0.12	0.98	-0.16	0.86	0.17	-0.02
45	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.10	0.98	-0.15	0.88	0.18	0.04
46	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.12	0.95	-0.15	0.80	0.27	-0.05
47	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.12	0.97	-0.11	0.78	0.29	0.02
48	Neris - aukščiau Jonavos	-0.20	0.96	-0.26	0.90	0.15	0.01
49	Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0.11	0.96	-0.23	0.93	0.17	0.05
50	Neris - aukščiau Kauno	-0.02	0.95	-0.27	0.80	0.24	-0.03
51	Lomena - žemiau Kaišiadorių	-0.71	0.09	-0.61	0.26	-0.42	-0.44
52	Šventoji - aukščiau Anykščių	0.32	0.85	0.07	0.78	0.10	0.10
53	Šventoji - žemiau Anykščių	0.28	0.85	0.09	0.81	0.07	0.12
54	Šventoji - aukščiau Ukmergės	0.06	0.91	-0.08	0.88	-0.06	-0.13
55	Šventoji - žemiau Ukmergės	0.03	0.90	-0.09	0.89	-0.21	-0.18
56	Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų	0.05	0.90	-0.10	0.94	0.11	0.02
57	Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų	-0.09	0.91	-0.20	0.91	-0.50	-0.40
58	Siesartis - žemiau Molėtų	-0.43	0.74	-0.44	0.68	-0.34	-0.17
59	Vyžuona - žemiau Utenos	-0.26	0.70	-0.24	0.72	-0.51	-0.39
60	Vilnia - aukščiau N.Vilnios	-0.33	0.80	-0.37	0.81	-0.28	-0.43
61	Vilnia - žiotyse	-0.35	0.78	-0.38	0.87	-0.32	-0.42
62	Žeimena - ties Kaltanėnais	0.03	0.35	-0.05	0.41	-0.21	0.26
63	Žeimena - žemiau Švenčionėlių	-0.07	0.55	-0.17	0.46	-0.10	-0.01
64	Žeimena - aukščiau Pabradės	-0.12	0.52	-0.19	0.55	-0.10	-0.13
65	Žeimena - žemiau Pabradės	-0.03	0.66	-0.09	0.60	0.23	0.06
66	Būka - aukščiau Baluoso	0.30	0.76	-0.26	0.77	0.05	-0.03
67	Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių	0.10	0.54	0.08	0.85	-0.28	0.31
68	Strėva - ties Liutonimis	-0.41	0.28	-0.22	0.14	-0.34	0.35
69	Merkys - aukščiau Varėnos	-0.20	0.76	-0.22	0.71	0.35	-0.10
70	Merkys - žemiau Puvočių	-0.24	0.75	-0.39	0.68	0.02	-0.24
71	Skroblus - žemiau Dubininkų	1.61	0.59	0.09	0.52	-0.62	-0.60
73	Šalčia - žemiau Šalčininkų	-0.51	0.18	-0.55	0.38	-0.60	-0.50
74	Akmena - Danė - ties Tūbaisiais	0.04	0.92	0.00	0.91	0.17	-0.27
76	Akmena - Danė - aukščiau Klaipėdos	-0.18	0.59	-0.11	0.21	-0.08	-0.07

St ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
77	Akmena - Danē - žiotyse	-0.06	0.76	-0.01	0.60	0.47	0.15
78	Bartuva - aukščiau Skuodo	0.49	0.88	0.44	0.71	-0.02	-0.16
79	Bartuva - žemiau Skuodo	0.36	0.90	0.25	0.77	-0.36	-0.25
80	Venta - aukščiau Kuršēnū	-0.17	0.90	-0.33	0.81	-0.46	-0.54
81	Venta - žemiau Kuršēnū	-0.08	0.82	-0.22	0.66	0.15	0.02
82	Venta - žemiau Mažeikiū	0.00	0.91	-0.17	0.85	0.49	0.19
83	Virvyčia - žemiau Pateklos	-0.16	0.93	-0.32	0.85	-0.27	-0.25
84	Mūša - aukščiau Kulpēs	-0.09	0.82	-0.08	0.73	-0.12	-0.15
85	Mūša - žemiau Kulpēs	-0.33	0.53	0.19	0.02	-0.16	-0.08
86	Mūša - žemiau Saločiū	0.04	0.89	0.07	0.77	-0.28	-0.08
87	Sidabra - žemiau Jonišķio	-0.07	0.88	-0.58	0.39	-0.98	-0.97
88	Sidabra - Latvijas pasienyje	-0.34	0.74	-0.28	0.07	-0.74	-0.70
89	Nemunēlis - žemiau Panemunio	-0.08	0.87	0.00	0.91	-0.43	-0.29
91	Laukupē - žemiau Rokišķio	-0.40	0.84	-0.18	0.63	-0.61	-0.39
92	Tatula - aukščiau Biržū	-0.32	0.96	-0.25	0.85	0.04	0.46
93	Tatula - žemiau Biržū	-0.34	0.86	-0.28	0.63	-0.68	-0.44
94	Tatula - ties Trečionimis	-0.22	0.83	0.00	0.75	0.72	1.46
95	Lēvuo - aukščiau Kupišķio	0.33	0.97	0.28	0.73	-0.61	-0.10
96	Lēvuo - žemiau Kupišķio	-0.13	0.93	-0.02	0.73	-0.53	-0.34
97	Lēvuo - aukščiau Pasvalio	0.05	0.89	0.04	0.80	-0.53	-0.37
98	Lēvuo - žiotyse	-0.23	0.95	-0.22	0.82	-0.81	-0.77
99	Daugyvenē - žiotyse	0.34	0.81	0.30	0.79	-0.06	-0.02
100	Kruoja - žiotyse	0.28	0.90	0.33	0.76	-0.43	-0.35
101	Obelē - žemiau Radvilišķio	0.78	0.44	-0.41	0.27	-0.49	-0.38
102	Obelē - žiotyse	-0.02	0.80	-0.07	0.79	-0.61	-0.54
103	Kulpē - žemiau Šiauliū	-0.01	0.62	-0.02	0.06	-0.49	-0.43
104	Kulpē - žiotyse	-0.43	0.33	0.16	0.00	-0.18	-0.11
105	Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje	0.15	0.82	-0.31	0.75	-0.20	-0.04
106	Laukesa - žemiau Zarasū	-0.09	0.49	-0.38	0.51	-0.28	-0.16
127	Nemunas - Skirvytē aukščiau Rusnēs	0.15	0.91	-0.07	0.85	0.29	-0.14
133	Šventoji - žiotyse	0.10	0.93	-0.13	0.80	-0.22	-0.22
135	Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Zapyšķiu	-0.14	0.72	-0.30	0.69	-0.49	-0.15
136	Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Kulautuva	-0.42	0.89	-0.43	0.81	-0.39	-0.34
137	Šešupē - Kaliningrado srit. pasienyje	-0.39	0.50	-0.37	0.34	-0.60	-0.50
138	Šventoji - žiotyse	0.14	0.86	-0.07	0.86	0.03	-0.23
141	Švogina-Žeimena - aukščiau Vaišniūnū	-0.20	0.51	-0.34	0.41	0.55	0.32
142	Širvinta - žiotyse	-0.06	0.66	-0.01	0.50	-0.67	-0.57
143	Siesartis - žiotyse	-0.16	0.66	-0.08	0.50	-0.78	-0.69
150	Jiesia - ties Šilavotu	0.43	0.73	0.04	0.76	-0.07	-0.19
151	Ūla - Pelesa - ties Kašėtomis	-0.45	0.75	-0.59	0.44	-0.34	-0.48
175	Mera - Kūna - ties Pažeimene	-0.60	0.57	-0.48	0.20	0.97	0.16
176	Kena - ties Rukainiais, ties keliu Nr.A3	0.00	0.74	0.02	0.65	0.64	0.65
217	Šešuvis - ties Taibučiais	0.01	0.80	-0.20	0.91	-0.22	-0.34

St ID	STATION NAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
218	Dubysa - ties Kaulakiais, ties keliu Nr.225	0.00	0.89	-0.31	0.95	-0.04	-0.42
219	Žiežmara - ties Paparčiais	-0.65	0.61	-0.65	0.53	-0.33	-0.41
265	Jūra - ties Mociškiais	0.25	0.88	0.06	0.84	0.25	-0.06
266	Minija - ties Suvernais	0.47	0.87	0.20	0.85	0.24	-0.10
267	Karaliaus Vilhelmo kanalas - ties Dreverna	0.25	0.85	0.00	0.89	0.06	-0.15
268	Vilka - ties Gudais	-0.24	0.85	-0.19	0.85	-0.27	-0.10
269	Salantas - ties Nasrėnais	0.00	0.83	0.07	0.51	-0.27	-0.09
270	Graumena - ties Pakalniškiais	0.64	0.58	-0.01	0.62	0.19	-0.20
271	Akmėna - aukščiau Pagramančio	0.19	0.79	-0.07	0.35	-0.12	-0.21
325	Dysna - ties Kačergiške	-0.27	0.45	-0.59	0.51	-0.27	0.02
327	Šventoji - ties Sabaliūnais (žemiau Andrioniškio)	0.43	0.83	0.04	0.65	0.27	0.36
357	Nemunėlis - Tabokinė	0.45	0.63	0.16	0.83	-0.38	-0.30
359	Šventoji - ties Bindzeliškiais, ties Pašilės ziotym	0.01	0.34	-0.16	0.10	-0.68	-0.25
360	Pyvesa - tarp Žadeikių ir Geivitonių	-0.08	0.97	-0.15	0.79	-0.37	-0.01
401	Rausvė - ties Nadrausve	-0.37	0.82	-0.27	0.67	-0.45	-0.33
402	Višakis - aukščiau Pilviškių (kelias 137)	-0.20	0.44	-0.36	0.27	0.56	0.09
430	Varduva - ties Grieže	0.26	0.66	-0.02	0.79	0.81	0.56
431	Platonis - pasienyje	-0.37	0.68	-0.17	0.86	0.54	0.47
432	Ašva - pasienyje	-0.20	0.81	-0.18	0.71	0.34	0.24
433	Virvyčia - ties Janapole	-0.11	0.79	-0.47	0.58	-0.69	-0.68
612	Nemunas – ties Pagėgiais, ties keliu Nr. A12	0.18	0.81	0.05	0.74	0.20	-0.06

There are still 20 water quality stations for which the validation criteria is not fulfilled. IN the same time the recalibration effort led to:

1. Additional 14 stations within the validation range.
2. Improvement of the overall values of the measured model performance.
3. Harmonisation of the coefficient sets between the hydrological regions.

The further improvement of the model results do not seem practical because the disagreement between the model results and observations for the 20 stations is most probably caused by either the inaccurate point source data or specific location of the sampling points relative to the outlets of the point sources. Let us illustrate the above with two water quality observation stations where validation targets were not met.

Pointsource loading amount is too low in comparison to the measured loads in the river, example – watershed Sesupe/Sesupe_dwnstr with focus on the Siesartis river, see Figure 142 where the location of WQ measurement stations is shown by green triangles and pointsources are shown with red squares. Problematic pointsource area is within Siesartis river (tributary of Sesupe), there is only one big pointsource – wastewater treatment facility (WWTF) of Šakiai town.

Concentrations of total phosphorus in effluent of WWTP Šakiai and measured in Siesartis river are compared in Figure 143. Note, that measured concentration in river can exceed

concentrations given in the WWTP discharge. The average water discharge in WWTP ($0.01 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) is 35 times smaller than the average measured discharge in Siesartis river ($0.35 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$). It means that this pointsource alone could not explain measured concentrations in the river, unless they are measured directly in the outflow of WWTP before mixing. As a result the model cannot match the observations, see Figure 144.

Figure 142: Location of WQ measurement stations (green triangles) and pointsources (red squares) within watershed Sesupe/Sesupe_dwnstr.

Figure 143: Concentrations of total phosphorus in effluent of WWTP Šakiai (blue) and observed in Siesartis river (red).

Figure 144: Modeled (green) versus observed (red dots) concentrations of Ptotal in “Siesartis, žemiau Šakių” water monitoring station.

Figure 145: Location of WQ measurement station “Varduva ties Grieže” and pointsource 91 “Mažeikiu nafta”/“Orlen Lietuva”.

Figure 146: Load of total phosphorus in g/day from pointsource 91.

Figure 147: Modelled (green) versus observed (red dots) P-PO4 concentration in WQ station "Varduva ties Grieže".

Pointsource load too high for particular periods, example of watershed Venta/Varduva. Location of WQ measurement station "Varduva ties Grieže" and major pointsource 91 "Mažeikiu nafta"/"Orlen Lietuva" is shown in Figure 145. The load of total phosphorus from pointsource 91 is shown in Figure 146 and it indicates a sharp decline in amount at the beginning of year 2008. The modelled and observed P-PO4 concentration in WQ station "Varduva ties Grieže" are shown in Figure 147. Note that level of measured concentrations is similar for the periods 2005-2007 and 2008-2012, while the modelled concentration reflects the changes in the pointsource load. Such a situation cannot be improved by calibration of the model.

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III. ENHANCEMENT OF SWAT MODEL

Abstract

The report describes the enhancement of the SWAT water quality model of Lithuania calibrated and validated in the previous stage of the project. The proposed enhancements achieves the systematical reduction of biases and provides a calibration of the SWAT water quality model for Belarus.

Report is written in English, it contains 42 pages, 46 figures, 11 tables, and 3 references.

1. Introduction

This is a supplement to the revision of the 3rd Interim report describing the enhancement of the performance of Lithuanian water quality model and providing of the feedback to conditional approval of the 3rd Interim report.

The calibration and validation of the renewed SWAT modeling system used by the Environmental Protection Agency according to p.3.2 of the Terms of Reference (further TOR) of the project “*Renewal of a River Basin Districts Management Plans and Programs of Measures*”, ID 141278 was performed in PAIC (2014b)

The modeling system referred to is the one prepared (renewed) in PAIC (2014a).

The enhancement of the model was performed via the country (or at least region) wide adjustment of the model parameters targeting the reduction of systematic negative biases of both water quantity and nutrient concentrations characteristic for the calibrated and validated modeling system delivered with PAIC (2014b).

Chapter 2 contains a description of considered alternative model settings. It continues the approach illustrated in Section 2.6.15.2 of PAIC (2014b).

Chapter 3 provides a performance metrics of considered alternatives of model parameter sets and recommendation for the use of the most appropriate alternative for the elaboration of river basin management plans.

The calibration and validation of the SWAT water quality modeling system for Belarus (TOR 3.2.4) started in PAIC (2014b) is finalized in the Chapter 4. For the convenience the full text of the Chapter 2.7 of PAIC (2014b) is included (renewed) in this report.

The methodics of validation and calibration for the water quality model of Lithuania considered calibration targets in terms of water discharge and concentrations of N_{tot}, N-NO₃, P_{tot}, P-PO₄ was elaborated and applied in PAIC (2014b); this formally differs from TOR 3.2.1.12 which requires calibration for “concentrations and loads”. The issue is considered in Chapter 5.

2. Alternative model parameter sets

Section 2.6.15.2 of PAIC (2014b) indicated that model of complexity, scale and resolution as that of water quality SWAT model of Lithuania may and should be improved continuously. Eight model alternatives were considered in PAIC (2014b) comparing their performance with the calibrated, validated and delivered model. It was shown that

1. The delivered model has systematic negative biases both in water quantity and the concentration of nutrients.
2. The integral model performance for different model settings was analysed showing that biases might be reduced – possibly at the cost of reaching model calibration and/or validation targets.

The further study was performed to improve the model performance and to reduce the biases. Following the path set in Section 2.6.15.2 of PAIC (2014b) we considered several alternatives outlying four most promising which are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Considered model alternatives.

No.	Alternative	Description
1	Delivered	Calibrated, validated model recalibrated after coefficient transfer. Delivered in PAIC (2014b).
2	Variante1	ESCO value for all region were changed to 0.7. Fertilization rate for nitrogen was put to 80% instead of 58% in PAIC(2014b) and for phosphorus to 100% instead of 80% in PAIC(2014b).
3	Variante2	ESCO value for all region were changed to 0.7. Fertilization rate for nitrogen was put to 80% instead of 58% in PAIC(2014b).
4	Variante3	Country wide parameter changes as in Variante1 . Additional changes (fine tuning) of regional soil parameters summarised in Table 2.
5	Variante3_fix	Variante3 with fixes of minor errors in plant management practice.

Table 2. Regional changes of model soil parameters for **Variante3**.

Parameter	Delivered	Variante3	Regions
R_SOL_LABP.chm	-0.9	-0.87	AI, AII, BIII, BIV, BV, BVIII
R_SOL_ORGP.chm	-0.5	-0.47	AI, AII, BIII, BIV, BV, BVIII
R_USLE_K.sol	-0.6	-0.55	AII
R_USLE_K.sol	-0.7	-0.6	BIII, BIV
R_USLE_K.sol	-0.67	-0.6	BVIII

3. Performance metrics of alternative model settings

The performance of different model settings (Delivered, Variante1, Variante2, Variante3) are illustrated in Figures 1-8. Model alternative Variante3_fix is not included in these Figures because it is rather similar to Variante3. The performance is shown as Box-plots of

- PBIAS and R2 for N-NO3 and Ntot.
- PBIAS for P-PO4 and Ptot.

- PBIAS and NSE for discharge.

The median PBIAS-es of discharge and nutrient concentrations for all considered alternatives are summarised in Table 3.

Table 2: PBIAS median values for considered alternatives.

	NO3	Ntot	PO4	Ptot	Q
Delivered	-0.076	-0.151	-0.155	-0.163	-0.069
Variant1	-0.017	-0.134	-0.144	-0.159	0.021
Variant2	-0.018	-0.134	-0.145	-0.165	0.021
Variant3	-0.017	-0.095	-0.121	-0.133	0.021
Variant3_fix	-0.009	-0.092	-0.122	-0.132	0.021

The overall effect of attempted changes is as follows:

1. The change of ESCO parameter efficiently eliminates the negative water quantity bias of the delivered model (all alternatives); it was shown also in PAIC (2014b).
2. The country wide increase of fertilisation reduces the negative biases for nutrient concentrations. It should be done for both N and P fertilisation, i.e. **Variant1** is preferable over **Variant2**.
3. The regional fine tuning of soil parameters (**Variant3**) allows for further decrease of median of PBIAS.
4. Fixing the errors in plant management practice (for minor crops) further improves the nitrogen performance of the model (**Variant3_fix**).

The improvement of the PBIAS of the model results have certain costs in terms of the meeting the model validation targets set in PAIC(2014b). The minor raise of outliers can be seen in boxplots. The percentage of the monitoring stations meeting the validation criteria for all considered alternatives is summarised in Table 4. We may conclude that the cost is one additional WQ station and one additional Q station out-of-validation range.

Figure 1: Boxplot of N-NO3 PBIAS for alternative model settings.

Figure 2: Boxplot of N-NO3 R2 for alternative model settings.

Figure 3: Boxplot of Ntot PBIAS for alternative model settings.

Figure 4: Boxplot of Ntot R2 for alternative model settings.

Figure 5: Boxplot of P-PO4 PBIAS for alternative model settings.

Figure 6: Boxplot of Ptot PBIAS for alternative model settings.

Figure 7: Boxplot of discharge PBIAS for alternative model settings.

Figure 8: Boxplot of discharge NSE for alternative model settings.

Table 4: Model performance comparison: percentage of stations meeting calibration / validation criteria.

	WQ	Q
Delivered	0.962	0.919
Variant1	0.960	0.911
Variant2	0.960	0.911
Variant3	0.958	0.911
Variant3_fix	0.960	0.911

The performance metrics of alternative model parameter set **Variant3_fix** is given in Tables 5 (water quality, compare with Table 77 of PAIC (2014b)) and 6 (water quantity, compare with Table 78 of PAIC (2014b)).

Table 5. Performance metrics of model alternative **Variant3_fix**. R2 and PBIAS for nutrient concentrations. Green – the results that correspond to the extrapolation criteria.

Station_ID	STANAME	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
1	Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	-0.01	0.97	-0.02	0.99	-0.02	-0.03
2	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0.01	0.96	-0.05	0.94	0.00	-0.09
3	Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0.06	0.96	-0.09	0.95	-0.05	-0.13
4	Nemunas - aukščiau Alytaus	0.02	0.97	-0.09	0.96	0.08	-0.11
5	Nemunas – žemiau Alytaus	-0.12	0.98	-0.19	0.98	-0.03	-0.22
6	Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	-0.04	0.97	-0.13	0.94	0.00	-0.17
7	Nemunas - aukščiau Prienų	0.12	0.99	-0.07	0.99	0.12	-0.13
8	Nemunas - aukščiau Kauno	0.04	0.92	-0.19	0.78	-0.47	-0.03
11	Nemunas - žemiau Smalininkų	0.03	0.94	-0.20	0.93	-0.14	-0.20
13	Nemunas - aukščiau Rusnės, aukščiau Leitės	0.56	0.89	0.13	0.88	0.47	-0.11
14	Minija - aukščiau Plungės	0.12	0.81	-0.23	0.90	-0.46	-0.45
15	Minija - žemiau Plungės	0.21	0.88	-0.14	0.84	-0.21	-0.28
16	Minija - žemiau Gargždų	0.34	0.88	0.12	0.89	-0.02	-0.26
17	Minija - žemiau Priekulės	0.49	0.92	0.11	0.76	0.15	-0.22
18	Veiviržas - ties Veiviržėnais	0.63	0.85	0.26	0.80	-0.20	-0.24
19	Šyša - aukščiau Šilutės	-0.05	0.75	-0.15	0.82	-0.18	-0.32
20	Šyša - žemiau Šilutės	0.24	0.77	0.39	0.30	0.17	0.26
21	Jūra - aukščiau Tauragės	-0.01	0.94	-0.13	0.72	0.17	-0.22
22	Jūra - žemiau Tauragės	0.05	0.84	-0.08	0.77	0.04	-0.23
23	Šešuvis - ties Skirgailiais	0.25	0.93	0.08	0.90	-0.12	-0.40
24	Šaltuona - žemiau Raseinių	-0.01	0.87	0.02	0.70	-0.59	-0.48
25	Lokysta - žemiau Šilalės	-0.23	0.68	-0.17	0.69	-0.22	-0.22
26	Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	-0.16	0.48	-0.54	0.44	-0.02	-0.51
27	Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	-0.48	0.83	-0.62	0.76	-0.37	-0.56
28	Šešupė - aukščiau Marijampolės	-0.17	0.91	-0.05	0.94	0.04	0.17
29	Šešupė - žemiau Marijampolės	-0.32	0.84	-0.23	0.90	-0.53	-0.38

Station_ID	STANAME	NO3 PRLAG	NO3 P3	NTOT PRLAG	NTOT P3	PO4 PRLAG	PTOT PRLAG
30	Siesartis - žemiau Šakių	0.15	0.87	-0.16	0.21	-0.87	-0.80
31	Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio	0.02	0.73	0.20	0.56	-0.25	0.04
33	Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus	0.10	0.94	-0.05	0.89	-0.08	-0.19
34	Kražantė - aukščiau Kelmės	-0.43	0.85	-0.47	0.86	-0.07	-0.13
35	Kražantė - žemiau Kelmės	-0.41	0.87	-0.48	0.65	-0.24	-0.14
36	Nevėžis - aukščiau Panevėžio	0.03	0.96	-0.02	0.90	-0.59	-0.33
37	Nevėžis - žemiau Panevėžio	-0.22	0.66	-0.25	0.00	-0.53	-0.43
38	Nevėžis - aukščiau Kėdainių	-0.11	0.72	-0.08	0.81	-0.08	-0.06
39	Nevėžis - žemiau Kėdainių	-0.15	0.85	-0.12	0.83	-0.50	-0.41
40	Nevėžis - aukščiau Raudondvario	-0.09	0.95	-0.12	0.95	-0.47	-0.35
41	Šušvė - žiotyse	-0.14	0.96	-0.15	0.92	0.04	0.26
42	Juosta - žemiau Jackagalio	0.48	0.84	0.30	0.91	0.23	0.39
43	Neris - ties Buivydžiais	0.00	0.98	-0.03	0.96	0.05	-0.02
44	Neris - aukščiau Vilniaus	-0.12	0.98	-0.16	0.85	0.16	-0.02
45	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.10	0.98	-0.15	0.88	0.17	0.03
46	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.12	0.95	-0.15	0.80	0.25	-0.06
47	Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0.12	0.97	-0.11	0.79	0.27	0.01
48	Neris - aukščiau Jonavos	-0.19	0.97	-0.26	0.91	0.13	0.00
49	Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0.08	0.97	-0.20	0.92	0.15	0.05
50	Neris - aukščiau Kauno	0.00	0.96	-0.25	0.82	0.22	-0.03
51	Lomena - žemiau Kaišiadorių	-0.73	0.18	-0.63	0.30	-0.47	-0.48
52	Šventoji - aukščiau Anykščių	0.40	0.87	0.16	0.81	0.10	0.17
53	Šventoji - žemiau Anykščių	0.36	0.87	0.19	0.83	0.07	0.19
54	Šventoji - aukščiau Ukmergės	0.14	0.91	-0.01	0.91	-0.06	-0.07
55	Šventoji - žemiau Ukmergės	0.11	0.91	-0.02	0.91	-0.21	-0.13
56	Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų	0.11	0.84	-0.03	0.94	0.12	0.11
57	Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų	-0.04	0.86	-0.14	0.93	-0.50	-0.35
58	Siesartis - žemiau Molėtų	-0.39	0.74	-0.40	0.72	-0.33	-0.12
59	Vyžuona - žemiau Utenos	-0.24	0.68	-0.19	0.74	-0.53	-0.38
60	Vilnia - aukščiau N.Vilnios	-0.32	0.80	-0.36	0.79	-0.29	-0.44
61	Vilnia - žiotyse	-0.34	0.78	-0.37	0.85	-0.33	-0.43
62	Žeimena - ties Kaltanėnais	0.05	0.38	-0.06	0.44	-0.21	0.22
63	Žeimena - žemiau Švenčionėlių	-0.04	0.56	-0.16	0.48	-0.12	-0.02
64	Žeimena - aukščiau Pabradės	-0.10	0.54	-0.18	0.57	-0.11	-0.14
65	Žeimena - žemiau Pabradės	-0.01	0.67	-0.08	0.61	0.21	0.05
66	Būka – aukščiau Baluošo	0.31	0.75	-0.26	0.77	0.06	-0.03
67	Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių	0.16	0.54	0.08	0.86	-0.27	0.28
68	Strėva - ties Liutonimis	-0.41	0.28	-0.16	0.16	-0.33	0.41
69	Merkys - aukščiau Varėnos	-0.15	0.75	-0.20	0.70	0.29	-0.13
70	Merkys - žemiau Puvočių	-0.21	0.73	-0.38	0.66	0.00	-0.25
71	Skroblus - žemiau Dubininkų	1.64	0.57	0.10	0.51	-0.63	-0.60
73	Šalčia - žemiau Šalčininkų	-0.44	0.19	-0.55	0.38	-0.63	-0.54

Station_ID	STANAME	NO3 PBLAC	NO3 P3	NTOT PBLAC	NTOT P3	PO4 PBLAC	PTOT PBLAC
74	Akmėna - Danė - ties Tūbausiais	0.14	0.93	0.05	0.93	0.27	-0.21
76	Akmėna - Danė - aukščiau Klaipėdos	-0.12	0.64	-0.08	0.31	-0.09	-0.07
77	Akmėna - Danė - žiotyse	0.01	0.78	0.02	0.65	0.47	0.16
78	Bartuva - aukščiau Skuodo	0.63	0.92	0.56	0.80	0.10	-0.01
79	Bartuva - žemiau Skuodo	0.49	0.87	0.36	0.82	-0.31	-0.14
80	Venta - aukščiau Kuršėnų	-0.08	0.90	-0.25	0.84	-0.38	-0.42
81	Venta - žemiau Kuršėnų	-0.01	0.85	-0.15	0.71	0.13	0.06
82	Venta - žemiau Mažeikių	0.08	0.91	-0.08	0.91	0.49	0.28
83	Virvyčia - žemiau Pateklos	-0.07	0.89	-0.24	0.89	-0.27	-0.20
84	Mūša - aukščiau Kulpės	0.01	0.89	0.08	0.81	-0.02	0.00
85	Mūša - žemiau Kulpės	-0.26	0.68	0.20	0.09	-0.25	-0.17
86	Mūša - žemiau Saločių	0.13	0.95	0.19	0.87	-0.33	-0.09
87	Sidabra - žemiau Jonišķio	0.09	0.89	-0.49	0.38	-0.98	-0.96
88	Sidabra - Latvijos pasienyje	-0.26	0.66	-0.22	0.09	-0.77	-0.72
89	Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio	-0.01	0.83	0.05	0.91	-0.49	-0.35
91	Laukupė - žemiau Rokiškio	-0.38	0.83	-0.18	0.63	-0.63	-0.43
92	Tatula - aukščiau Biržų	-0.23	0.95	-0.14	0.92	0.05	0.52
93	Tatula - žemiau Biržų	-0.25	0.84	-0.20	0.67	-0.72	-0.50
94	Tatula - ties Trečionimis	-0.11	0.83	0.13	0.80	0.51	1.23
95	Lėvuo - aukščiau Kupiškio	0.50	0.94	0.36	0.85	-0.56	-0.02
96	Lėvuo - žemiau Kupiškio	-0.01	0.95	0.06	0.81	-0.53	-0.32
97	Lėvuo - aukščiau Pasvalio	0.19	0.95	0.18	0.88	-0.52	-0.33
98	Lėvuo - žiotyse	-0.13	0.97	-0.14	0.88	-0.83	-0.79
99	Daugyvenė - žiotyse	0.49	0.85	0.51	0.90	-0.05	0.07
100	Kruoja - žiotyse	0.42	0.91	0.51	0.84	-0.42	-0.28
101	Obelė - žemiau Radviliškio	0.80	0.56	-0.43	0.23	-0.52	-0.41
102	Obelė - žiotyse	0.09	0.85	0.05	0.89	-0.60	-0.49
103	Kulpė - žemiau Šiaulių	0.06	0.75	-0.03	0.09	-0.52	-0.46
104	Kulpė - žiotyse	-0.37	0.52	0.15	0.03	-0.25	-0.17
105	Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje	0.24	0.74	-0.25	0.73	-0.14	0.07
106	Laukesa - žemiau Zarasų	-0.03	0.52	-0.31	0.53	-0.26	-0.10
127	Nemunas - Skirvytė aukščiau Rusnės	0.22	0.94	-0.02	0.88	0.28	-0.13
130	Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0.10	0.96	-0.31	0.78	0.43	0.04
133	Šventoji - žiotyse	0.17	0.91	-0.06	0.82	-0.20	-0.15
135	Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Zapyškium	-0.09	0.79	-0.27	0.73	-0.50	-0.15
136	Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Kulautuva	-0.40	0.93	-0.41	0.84	-0.39	-0.33
137	Šešupė - Kaliningrado srit. pasienyje	-0.32	0.64	-0.30	0.44	-0.60	-0.49
138	Šventoji - žiotyse	0.26	0.84	0.00	0.84	0.11	-0.17
141	Švogina-Žeimenė - aukščiau Vaišniūnų	-0.20	0.49	-0.35	0.39	0.51	0.29
142	Širvinta - žiotyse	0.09	0.74	0.14	0.59	-0.68	-0.56
143	Siesartis - žiotyse	-0.03	0.83	0.04	0.68	-0.79	-0.70
150	Jiesia - ties Šilavotu	0.49	0.65	0.09	0.75	-0.09	-0.17

Station_ID	STANAME	NO3 PBLAC	NO3 P3	NTOT PBLAC	NTOT P3	PO4 PBLAC	PTOT PBLAC
151	Ūla - Pelesa - ties Kašėtomis	-0.44	0.75	-0.59	0.41	-0.34	-0.48
175	Mera - Kūna - ties Pažeimene	-0.60	0.57	-0.48	0.20	0.91	0.13
176	Kena - ties Rukainiais, ties keliu Nr.A3	0.01	0.73	0.02	0.63	0.60	0.62
217	Šešuvis - ties Taubučiais	0.08	0.76	-0.13	0.88	-0.34	-0.41
218	Dubysa - ties Kaulakiais, ties keliu Nr.225	0.06	0.81	-0.24	0.92	0.04	-0.30
219	Žiežmara - ties Paparčiais	-0.62	0.56	-0.63	0.53	-0.35	-0.41
265	Jūra - ties Mociškiais	0.34	0.87	0.15	0.88	0.29	0.02
266	Minija - ties Suvernais	0.57	0.86	0.29	0.87	0.34	0.03
267	Karaliaus Vilhelmo kanalas - ties Dreverna	0.34	0.83	0.07	0.89	0.13	-0.06
268	Vilka - ties Gudais	-0.15	0.85	-0.12	0.86	-0.18	0.01
269	Salantas - ties Nasrėnais	0.12	0.80	0.20	0.54	-0.18	0.10
270	Graumena - ties Pakalniškiais	0.69	0.64	0.04	0.67	0.30	-0.09
271	Akmena - aukščiau Pagramančio	0.31	0.69	0.02	0.32	-0.07	-0.08
325	Dysna - ties Kačergiške	-0.20	0.44	-0.54	0.52	-0.20	0.17
327	Šventoji - ties Sabaliūnais (žemiau Andrioniškio)	0.49	0.86	0.13	0.67	0.30	0.49
357	Nemunėlis - Tabokinė	0.53	0.56	0.23	0.78	-0.39	-0.30
359	Šventoji - ties Bindzeliškiais,ties Pašilės ziotym	0.07	0.34	-0.04	0.08	-0.65	-0.07
360	Pyvesa - tarp Žadeikių ir Geivitonių	0.02	0.93	-0.04	0.84	-0.29	0.14
401	Rausvė - ties Nadrausve	-0.29	0.88	-0.20	0.76	-0.44	-0.30
402	Višakis - aukščiau Pilviškių (kelias 137)	-0.18	0.47	-0.35	0.27	0.50	0.06
430	Varduva - ties Grieže	0.34	0.59	0.05	0.81	0.80	0.67
431	Platonis - pasienyje	-0.31	0.59	-0.04	0.89	0.66	0.74
432	Ašva - pasienyje	-0.11	0.80	-0.03	0.71	0.56	0.64
433	Virvyčia - ties Janapole	-0.03	0.80	-0.41	0.58	-0.66	-0.60
612	Nemunas – ties Pagėgiais, ties keliu Nr. A12	0.25	0.87	0.10	0.79	0.20	-0.05

Table 6. Performance metrics of model alternative **Variant3_fix**. R2 and NSE for discharge. Green – the results that correspond to the extrapolation criteria.

Stat_ID	Station Name	VALID_NSE	VALID_PBIAS
2	Akmena-Danė-Kretinga	0.52	11%
3	Akmena-Paakmenis	0.62	-21%
4	Aunuva-Aunuvėnai	0.44	-2%
5	Bartuva-Skuodas	0.63	-3%
6	Dubysa-Lyduvėnai	0.59	-8%
8	Jūra-Tauragė	0.61	-10%
9	Klaipėdos kanalas-Lankupiai	0.48	-18%
10	Kražantė-Pluskiai	0.60	2%
12	Lėvuo-Bernatoniai	0.62	4%
13	Merkys-Puvočiai	0.33	-18%
14	Minija-Kartena	0.72	-8%
15	Minija-Lankupiai	0.58	6%
16	Minija-Priekulė	0.55	0%
17	Mituva-Žindaičiai	0.51	1%
18	Mūša-Ustukai	0.58	5%
19	Nemunas-Druskininkai	0.99	2%
20	Nemunas-Kaunas	0.67	11%
22	Nemunas-Nemajūnai	0.79	0%
24	Nemunas-Smalininkai	0.68	2%
26	Nemunėlis-Tabokinė	0.49	0%
27	Nemuno atš. Atmata-Rusnė	0.58	4%
28	Neris-Buivydžiai	1.00	1%
29	Neris-Jonava	0.37	7%
30	Neris-Vilnius	0.83	5%
31	Nevėžis-Panevėžys	0.64	5%
32	Nevėžis-Traupis	0.47	3%
33	Sanžilės kan.-Bernatoniai	0.62	6%
35	Skroblus-Dubininkas	-59.12	-50%
37	Strėva-Semeliškės	-9.27	10%
38	Svyła-Guntauninkai	0.59	-12%
39	Šalčia-Valkininkai	0.24	9%
40	Šešupė-Kudirkos Naumiestis	0.63	10%
41	Šešuvis-Skirgailai	0.61	8%
42	Širvinta-Liukonys	0.60	-1%
43	Šušvė-Josvainiai	0.67	-5%
44	Šušvė-Šiaulėnai	0.67	6%
45	Šventoji-Anykščiai	-0.63	0%
46	Šventoji-Ukmergė	-0.19	-2%
47	Šyša-Šilute	0.43	10%

Stat_ID	Station Name	VALID_NSE	VALID_PBIAS
48	Tatula-Trečionys	0.52	-1%
49	Upita-Eidukai	0.47	-18%
50	Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos	0.41	-17%
51	Venta-Leckava	0.67	4%
52	Venta-Papilė	0.67	-8%
54	Verknė-Verbyliškės	0.47	-2%
55	Vilnia-Vilnius	0.13	-10%
56	Yslykis-Kyburiai	0.59	-9%
57	Žeimena-Pabradė	-1.08	1%
58	Nevežis-Babtai	0.46	9%
59	Daugyvene-Rimšoniai	0.59	3%
60	Levuo-Kupiškis	0.61	22%
61	Šešupe-Liubavas	0.18	15%
62	Mūša-Žilpamūšis	0.66	20%
63	Nemunėlis-Kvetkai	0.67	2%
64	Platonis-Vaineikiai	0.52	2%
65	Pyvesa-Žadeikiai	0.57	8%
66	Nemunas-Rusne	0.51	26%
67	Sidabra-Šarkiai	0.47	33%
68	Istras-Talackoniai	0.57	-4%
69	Kulpe-Siauliai	-0.01	21%
72	Veivirzas-Mikuzai	0.70	7%
73	Jūra-Pajuris	0.48	-21%

We may conclude that the alternative model setup **Variant3_fix** has better performance related to the removal of the systematic negative biases characteristic for the calibrated model delivered with PAIC (2014b). This enhancement is achieved at the minimum cost of meeting the validation targets set in PAIC (2014b).

Therefore we recommend further usage of the alternative model setup **Variant3_fix** for further use in development of river basin management plans and deliver it electronically along with this document.

The enhanced model is used in model applications for PAIC (2015); it was delivered electronically in January 2015. The electronic deliverables are described in PAIC (2015) and delivered with the 4th Interim report.

4. Calibration of Belarus model

According to TOR 3.2.4.2 the calibration and validation for the territory of Belarus should assure compliance of overall water flow, Nt, Pt, NO₃-N, PO₄-P load and concentrations with the water monitoring data on the Neris and Nemunas rivers at the Belarusian-Lithuanian border. The model was calibrated and validated for 1997-2012 (TOR 3.2.4.3) only for the places where rivers inflow into Lithuanian territory (TOR 3.2.4.4).

Before the start of the calibration procedure it was noticed that Global Weather Data obtained from the SWAT homepage do not correspond with the observed values so before calibration a data bias correction was applied for the precipitation data of Belarus, see Section 4.1.

The calibration and validation targets are set in Section 4.2, the water quantity calibration and validation is presented in Section 4.3, and the water quality calibration and validation – in Section 4.4.

The calibrated and validated model of Belarus is delivered electronically with the revision of the 4th interim report in March, 2015. The electronic deliverables are described in PAIC (2015).

4.1. Belarus data bias correction

Contrary to meteorological data for Lithuania, where data was obtained from observations in 18 meteorological stations, meteorological data in Belarus in Nemunas basin was extracted from global meteorological database for the SWAT model, Global Weather Data for SWAT (TOR 3.1.15.3). When comparing precipitation data for locations (either meteorological stations or model grid points) close to the border between Lithuania and Belarus a significant difference in values could be observed (for example, observed average yearly precipitation in Vilnius meteorological station is 32% less than precipitation in nearest grid point of global meteorological database for the SWAT model). Therefore bias correction of the precipitation data was carried out.

Table 7: Bias correction coefficients for Vilnius.

Month	Precipitation Vilnius	Prec. Nearest Vilnius	Monthly Bias RATIO
1	1.4994	2.7244	0.5504
2	1.5035	2.8803	0.5220
3	1.4006	2.6381	0.5309
4	1.3555	2.2675	0.5978
5	2.0548	3.0635	0.6707
6	2.3839	3.2327	0.7374
7	2.9869	3.1689	0.9426
8	2.4886	2.9917	0.8318
9	1.9147	2.1606	0.8862
10	2.0017	2.8133	0.7115
11	1.5235	2.5476	0.5980
12	1.5338	2.5879	0.5927

Methodology for bias correction was as follows:

1. Closest grid points and corresponding data were extracted from the global meteorological database for the SWAT model for the three meteorological stations closest to border between Lithuania and Belarus – Vilnius, Varena, and Lazdijai. For each station set of Bias correction coefficients was calculated - coefficients were calculated for each month in the corresponding station as fraction of average daily precipitation for corresponding month between precipitation value at meteorological station and at grid point. In Table 7 the bias values for grid points close to Vilnius are given. In columns 'Precipitation Vilnius' and 'Prec. Nearest Vilnius' averaged daily values in millimeters are given.
2. Grid points of Belarus were split up in groups corresponding to the closest of the 3 meteorological stations (see Figure 9).
3. For precipitation values in each of the grid points bias correction coefficient corresponding to the closest of the three meteorological station and month of observation was applied. Corrected precipitation data for each grid point was acquired.
4. Corrected precipitation data was used to recalculate .wgn files.

Figure 9: Bias correction illustration for Belarus.

A. Calibration and validation targets for Belarus model

According to TOR 3.2.4.1 the calibration and validation targets for the Belarus water quality model should be different in comparison with the targets for Lithuanian water quality model set in PAIC (2014b). The calibration and validation targets should be lower given the low resolution and absence of data for the territory of Belarus, PAIC (2014a).

The data on agricultural practice, crops, fertilization, point sources and reservoirs are totally missing for Belarus.

The Belarus setup was calibrated on two calibration points, which correspond to the transboundary discharge and water quality measurement stations according to TOR 3.2.4.2 and 3.2.4.4:

1. Station Nemunas-Druskininkai is chosen for calibration of watershed Nemunas/Nemunas of Belarus setup.
2. Station Neris-Buividžiai is chosen for calibration of watershed Neris/Neris of Belarus setup.

Calibration and sensitivity analysis was performed by SWAT-CUP program using SUFI2 method in PAIC (2014b). Multiple rounds of auto calibration using discharge NSE as the objective function were performed in PAIC (2014b) targeting the “best possible” solution. An exercise indicated a possibility to reach good calibration results for water quantity while even the characteristic load and concentration levels for nutrients were not achieved due to poor quality of input data.

The calibration and validation targets were set (this Section) and the manual calibration was employed in this report to achieve the reasonable correspondence of nutrient loads and concentrations; sometimes at the cost of water quantity.

The targets for calibration and validation were chosen the same as targets for model performance in those Lithuanian setups for which the model parameters were transferred:

1. Nash-Sutcliff efficiency for daily discharges $NSE > 0.3$.
2. Absolute value of PBIAS for daily discharges $PBIAS < 0.7$.
3. Absolute values of PBIAS for monthly concentrations and loads of N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄ and P_{tot} $PBIAS < 0.7$.
4. Correlation coefficients for average monthly concentrations and loads of N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄ and P_{tot} $R^2 > 0.3$.

The absence of data on agricultural practice, crops, fertilization, point sources and reservoirs for Belarus does not allow to judge whether an attempt to reach these targets is based on the adequate process description.

The summary of the calibration results – the SWAT model parameters which are changed in comparison with PAIC (2014a) is given in Table 8.

Table 8: SWAT model parameters for Belarus setups.

Type of change	Parameter name	Parameter values for setups	
		Neris	Nemunas
Replaced by	V__CANMX.HRU	8.38	1
Replaced by	V__LAT_TTIME.HRU	0	0
Reduced (Increased) by	R__SOL_BD.SOL	0	0

Type of change	Parameter name	Parameter values for setups	
		Neris	Nemunas
Reduced (Increased) by	R__SOL_AWC.SOL	-0.1752	-0.3
Reduced (Increased) by	R__SOL_K.SOL	0	0
Reduced (Increased) by	R__CN2.MGT1	-0.18	-0.12
Replaced by	V__SURLAG.BSN	0.22	0.2
Replaced by	V__ALPHA_BF.GW	0.07	0.08
Replaced by	V__RCHRG_DP.GW	0.05	0.05
Replaced by	V__GW_DELAY.GW	700	700
Replaced by	V__GW_REVAP.GW	0.15	0.15
Replaced by	V__HLIFE_NGW.GW	3.8	4
Replaced by	V__GWQMN.GW	30	30
Replaced by	V__REVAPMN.GW	40	30
Replaced by	V__ESCO.HRU	0.95	0.95
Replaced by	V__SDNCO.BSN	0.9	0.7
Replaced by	V__CDN.BSN	0.01	0.05
Replaced by	V__SMTMP.BSN	1.284	1.284
Replaced by	V__SFTMP.BSN	0.634	0.634
Replaced by	V__SMFMX.BSN	4.623	4.623
Replaced by	V__SMFMN.BSN	4.623	4.623
Replaced by	V__TIMP.BSN	0.632	0.632
Replaced by	V__IRTE.BSN	0	0
Reduced (Increased) by	R__SOL_LABP.CHM	-0.85	-0.85
Reduced (Increased) by	R__SOL_ORGP.CHM	-0.4	-0.4
Replaced by	V__PHOSKD.BSN	175	175
Replaced by	V__ERORGP.HRU	1	1
Replaced by	V__EVRCH.BSN	1	1
Replaced by	V__PSETLR1.RES	15	15
Replaced by	V__PSETLR2.RES	0	5
Reduced (Increased) by	R__SOL_ORGN.CHM	2	2
Replaced by	V__USLE_P.MGT1	1	1
Reduced (Increased) by	R__USLE_K.SOL	-0.5	-0.34
Replaced by	V__ALPHA_BF_D.GW	0	0
Replaced by	V__NSETLR1.RES	15	30
Replaced by	V__NSETLR2.RES	0	0
Replaced by	V__DIS_STREAM.HRU	15	15
Replaced by	V__IRES1.RES	5	5
Replaced by	V__IRES2.RES	10	10
Reduced (Increased) by	R__GWSOLP.GW	-0.15	-0.15
Replaced by	V__SPCON.BSN	0.0001	0.0001
Replaced by	V__SPEXP.BSN	1	1
Replaced by	V__BC4.SWQ	0.05	0.05
Replaced by	V__IRES1.LWQ	4	4

B. Water quantity calibration for Belarus

TOR 3.2.4.3 requires calibration and validation for the time period 1997-2012. However, visual inspection of the observation data series at Nemunas – Druskininkai reveal that there exist a certain change of the water quantity and quality pattern. See Figure 9 for discharge and Figure 10 for N-NO3 time series. The change in data pattern occurs in 1-Jan-2005.

Figure 9: Calculated (green) and measured (red) discharge at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 10: Observed discharge (green) and observed N-NO3 concentrations (dots) at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

The calibration/validation for 1997-2012 at Druskininkai therefore is not technically possible. We selected the following time periods for the, respectively calibration and validation:

1. Nemunas-Druskininkai

- a. Calibration from 01-Jan-2005 to 01-Sep-2007 and from 03-May-2010 to 31-Dec-2012.
- b. Validation from 02-Sep-2007 to 02-May-2010.

2. Neris-Buivydziai

- a. Calibration from 01-Jan-1997 to 02-May-2002 and from 02-Sep-2007 to 31-Dec-2012.
- b. Validation from 03-May-2002 to 01-Sep-2007.

The calibration and validation results for water quantity are summarised in Table 9.

Table 9: Calibration and validation summary for water quantity of Belarus model.

Station Name	NSE	PBIAS	
Nemunas-Druskininkai	0.38	0.03	Calibration
Neris-Buivydziai	0.46	0.11	
Nemunas-Druskininkai	0.41	-0.01	Validation
Neris-Buivydziai	0.55	-0.03	

The time graphs of daily calculated discharges and measurements for, respectively, Nemunas-Druskininkai and Neris-Buivydziai are shown in Figures 11 and 13. The average seasonal cycle of monthly calculated and measured discharges for, respectively, Nemunas-Druskininkai and Neris-Buivydziai are shown in Figures 12 and 14.

Figure 11: Calculated (green) and measured (red) discharge at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

The calibration targets are met in both stations.

It is noticeable that modeled seasonal cycle of Nemunas has higher winter discharge and lower spring snow-melt maximum as observations. A possible reason for this is that global meteorological database for Belarus has positively biased winter temperature records

Figure 12: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharge at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 13: Calculated (green) and measured (red) discharge at Neris-Buivydziai station.

Figure 14: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharge at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

C. Water quality calibration for Belarus

The calibration and validation results for water quality of the Belarus model are summarised in Tables 10 and 11, respectively.

Table 10: Calibration summary for water quality of Belarus model.

STATION NAME	Concentrations						Loads					
	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	0.12	0.00	0.12	0.23	0.16	0.38	0.08	0.63	0.34	0.85	0.24	0.75
Neris - ties Buivydžiais	-0.04	0.15	-0.19	0.36	-0.06	0.07	0.09	0.48	0.00	0.74	0.13	-0.08

Table 11: Validation summary for water quality of Belarus model.

STATION NAME	Concentrations						Loads					
	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS	NO3 PBIAS	NO3 R2	NTOT PBIAS	NTOT R2	PO4 PBIAS	PTOT PBIAS
Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	-0.04	0.27	-0.30	0.53	-0.17	0.08	-0.08	0.87	-0.23	0.66	-0.22	0.23
Neris - ties Buivydžiais	-0.15	0.22	-0.35	0.20	-0.25	-0.54	-0.17	0.38	-0.28	0.45	-0.28	-0.44

The comparison of measured and observed concentrations and loads of water quality parameters (N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄, P_{tot}) is given in Figures 15-30 for Nemunas-Druskininkai and in Figures 31-46 for Neris-Buivydžiai:

- The time graphs of all measurements and daily calculated parameters.
- The average seasonal cycle of monthly calculated and measured parameters.

Figure 15: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of N-NO₃ at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 16: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-NO₃ concentration at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

The calibration and validation targets are reached for most (41 out of 48) parameters despite the absence of relevant input data for Belarus territory. Let us consider those cases where the targets are missed:

1. Seasonal cycle of nitrate concentrations in both Nemunas and Neris (R2 for N-NO3). The observed seasonal cycle of nitrates – high winter values is not reproduced well by the model. One of reasons might be the different agricultural practice in Belarus. However, the formal improvements (which are not backed by reliable changes in the input data) here would be at the cost of the seasonal cycle of the nitrate loads which is very well reproduced. One may notice also that observed cycles for nitrate concentration in Nemunas (Figure 15) is different for Years 2005-2009 vs. Years 2010-2012.

Figure 17: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of N-NO3 at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 18: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-NO3 load at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

2. The seasonal cycle of concentrations of total nitrogen in Nemunas. Figures 19-20

indicate an absence of well pronounced seasonal cycle in observations – as opposed to the situation with Neris (Figure 35). The most probable reason for this is a presence of a reservoir in Belarus which evens out the seasonal cycle; there is no such an input information in the model.

3. The PBIAS of total phosphorus load in Nemunas. Model overestimates the total phosphorus load; it also cannot reproduce the absence of seasonal cycle for TOT-P, see Figures 27-30 for TOT-P graphs. The most probable reason for this is a presence of a reservoir in Belarus which facilitates settling of organic phosphorus and evens out the seasonal cycle; there is no such an input information in the model.

Figure 19: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of N-TOT at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 20: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-TOT concentration at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 21: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of N-TOT at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 22: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-TOT load at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 23: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of P-PO4 at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 24: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-PO4 concentration at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 25: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of P-PO4 at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 26: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-PO4 load at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 27: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of P-TOT at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 28: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-TOT concentration at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 29: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of P-TOT at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 30: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-TOT load at Nemunas-Druskininkai station.

Figure 31: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of N-NO₃ at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 32: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-NO₃ concentration at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 33: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of N-NO₃ at Neris-Buivydziai station.

Figure 34: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-NO₃ load at Neris-Buivydziai station.

Figure 35: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of N-TOT at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 36: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-TOT concentration at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 37: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of N-TOT at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 38: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) N-TOT load at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 39: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of P-PO4 at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 40: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-PO4 concentration at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 41: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of P-PO4 at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 42: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-PO4 load at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 43: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) concentration of P-TOT at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 44: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-TOT concentration at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 45: Calculated (green) versus observed (dots) load of P-TOT at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Figure 46: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) P-TOT load at Neris-Buivydžiai station.

Summarising the calibration and validation we may conclude that reasonable agreements of the concentration levels as well as loads of substance is achieved for Belarus model.

However, it cannot be recommended to use the Belarus water quality model as a substitute of water quality and quantity observations for the boundary conditions of the Lithuanian water quality model. An additional information on the agricultural practice, crops, fertilization, - and, especially, point sources and reservoirs in the territory of Belarus is needed for further improvements beyond the scope of actual project.

5. Relation between model performance parameters

The calibration strategy for Lithuanian water quality model in PAIC (2014a) set quantitative targets for NSE and PBIAS values of water discharges and PBIAS and R2 values of concentrations of in-stream nutrients. Such an approach was agreed with EPA.

Nevertheless TOR 3.2.1.12 requires calibration for “loads and concentrations”. The performance criteria in respect the “loads” is not independent from the performance criteria in respect the “discharges and concentrations”; therefore if the criteria are set and met for “discharges and concentrations” then it virtually guarantees also the performance regarding “loads”. Let us illustrate the above by analysis of PBIAS criteria.

Let us define PBIAS of discharge (p_Q), concentration (p_c) and loads (p_L) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} p_Q &= \frac{\overline{Q_{obs}} - \overline{Q_{mod}}}{\overline{Q_{obs}}} \\ p_c &= \frac{\overline{c_{obs}} - \overline{c_{mod}}}{\overline{c_{obs}}} \\ p_L &= \frac{\overline{c_{obs}Q_{obs}} - \overline{c_{mod}Q_{mod}}}{\overline{c_{obs}Q_{obs}}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here Q is discharge, c is concentration; load is concentration times discharge; subscripts *obs* and *mod* denote observed and modeled values, respectively. Bar above values means averaging over time.

Correlation coefficient K between two time series (say, c and Q) is defined as:

$$K(c, Q) = \frac{\overline{cQ} - \overline{c}\overline{Q}}{\sigma_c \sigma_Q} \quad (2)$$

Here σ is the standard deviation of corresponding values.

Let's define coefficient of variation (CV) as

$$CV(c) = \frac{\sigma_c}{\overline{c}} \quad (3)$$

From the expression of correlation coefficient follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{c_{obs}Q_{obs}} &= K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})\sigma_{c_{obs}}\sigma_{Q_{obs}} + \overline{c_{obs}}\overline{Q_{obs}} \\ \overline{c_{mod}Q_{mod}} &= K(c_{mod}, Q_{mod})\sigma_{c_{mod}}\sigma_{Q_{mod}} + \overline{c_{mod}}\overline{Q_{mod}} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

After substitution of expression (4) into equation (1) for p_L :

$$p_L = \frac{K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})\sigma_{c_{obs}}\sigma_{Q_{obs}} - K(c_{mod}, Q_{mod})\sigma_{c_{mod}}\sigma_{Q_{mod}} + \overline{c_{obs}}\overline{Q_{obs}} - \overline{c_{mod}}\overline{Q_{mod}}}{K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})\sigma_{c_{obs}}\sigma_{Q_{obs}} + \overline{c_{obs}}\overline{Q_{obs}}}$$

Taking into account (3) and the fact that

$$\frac{\overline{c_{obs}Q_{obs}} - \overline{c_{mod}Q_{mod}}}{\overline{Q_{mod}}} = \overline{c_{obs}}(\overline{Q_{obs}} - \overline{Q_{mod}}) + \overline{Q_{obs}}(\overline{c_{obs}} - \overline{c_{mod}}) - (\overline{c_{obs}} - \overline{c_{mod}})(\overline{Q_{obs}} - \overline{Q_{mod}}) = \overline{c_{obs}Q_{obs}}(p_Q + p_c - p_Q p_c) \quad (5)$$

we obtain

$$p_L = \frac{CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs})(K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs}) - K(c_{mod}, Q_{mod})) + \frac{\sigma_{c_{mod}} \sigma_{Q_{mod}}}{\sigma_{c_{obs}} \sigma_{Q_{obs}}}(p_Q + p_c - p_Q p_c)}{K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs}) + 1} \quad (6)$$

Limits of expression (6) for p_L are as follows

1. In case there are no correlation between the concentration and discharge ($K=0$) p_L can be expressed as:

$$p_L^{(1)} = p_Q + p_c - p_Q p_c$$

and p_L can be evaluated as

$$|p_L^{(1)}| \leq |p_Q| + |p_c| + |p_Q p_c|$$

2. In case of perfect correlation between concentration and discharge (both modeled and observed, $K=1$) p_L can be expressed as:

$$p_L^{(2)} = \frac{(p_Q + p_c - p_Q p_c)}{K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs}) + 1} = \frac{p_L^{(1)}}{K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs}) + 1}$$

If $K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs}) > 0$ then, taking into account that $CV > 0$ p_L can be evaluated as:

$$|p_L^{(2)}| \leq |p_L^{(1)}|$$

3. If standard deviations of observed and modeled discharges and concentrations are the same then p_L can be expressed as:

$$p_L^{(3)} = \frac{CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs})(K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs}) - K(c_{mod}, Q_{mod})) + (p_Q + p_c - p_Q p_c)}{K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs}) + 1} = p_L^{(2)} + \frac{CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs})(K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs}) - K(c_{mod}, Q_{mod}))}{K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs})CV(c_{obs})CV(Q_{obs}) + 1}$$

In this case the evaluation of p_L is

$$|p_L^{(3)}| \leq |p_L^{(1)}| + |K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs}) - K(c_{mod}, Q_{mod})|$$

The evaluation of p_L from above in general case is:

$$|p_L| \leq |p_Q| + |p_c| + |p_Q p_c| + \left| K(c_{obs}, Q_{obs}) - K(c_{mod}, Q_{mod}) \frac{\sigma_{c_{mod}} \sigma_{Q_{mod}}}{\sigma_{c_{obs}} \sigma_{Q_{obs}}} \right|$$

Conclusions from the above analysis:

1. PBIAS of load depends on PBIAS of concentration and discharge, and also on the correlation between concentration and discharge.
2. If the correlation of concentration and discharge is similar both in observed data and modeled data, then the load PBIAS estimate could be obtained from PBIASes of concentration and discharge. In this case absolute value of PBIAS cannot be possibly larger than the sum of absolute values of PBIAS of concentration and discharge (for PBIASes less than 1.0).

References

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IV. OPTIMIZATION METHODOIC AND TOOL FOR AGRICULTURAL MEASURES WITHIN SWAT MODEL

Abstract

The report describes the development of (1) methodology for spatial optimization of water pollution reduction measures and (2) a tool for optimization of measures is also included in the report. The tool is developed for the implementation with the renewed water quality modeling system of Lithuania. The implementation of the agricultural measures in SWAT water quality modeling system is considered. Scenario calculations and optimization run is included in the report.

Report is written in English, it contains 146 pages, 32 figures, 120 tables, 9 references, and 1 Annex.

1. Introduction

This is the 4th Interim report describing the preparation of the methodology (Section 2) and a tool (Section 3) for a spatial optimization of diffuse agricultural pollution reduction measures taking into consideration cost-effectiveness principle.

The application of the tool will be based on the renewed and calibrated SWAT modeling system used by the Environmental Protection Agency within the project “*Renewal of a River Basin Districts Management Plans and Programs of Measures*”, ID 141278.

The tasks are performed according to pp.3.3.1-3.3.2 of the Terms of Reference (further TOR) of the abovementioned project.

The modeling system referred to is the one prepared (renewed) in PAIC (2014a), calibrated/validated in PAIC (2014b), and further enhanced in PAIC(2015).

Further Chapters of the report contain the implementation of various scenarios and running of different numerical exercises with the modeling system:

The baseline scenario is defined and implemented in Chapter 4.

The agricultural measures for usage with the optimization tool are defined and implemented in the SWAT modeling system in Chapter 5. Further, the run of the optimization tool is illustrated in Chapter 6.

The dedicated scenarios are defined, implemented and modeled in Chapter 7.

Chapter 8 contains description of the electronic deliverables which contains the software code, models and results of modeling associated with the current report.

Chapter 9 contains definition of supplementary agricultural measures and description of their implementation in the SWAT modeling system.

The definition of agricultural measures and scenarios throughout this report rely on references to particular crops and their management practices. Therefore the summary of all crops, their management and characteristics (“crop passports”) are provided in the Annex of the report.

2. Methodology for optimization of water pollution reduction measures (3.3.1)

This section contains a description of the development of the methodology for spatial optimization of water pollution reduction measures according to TOR 3.3.1.

The water quality in some area may not meet the criteria for the required water quality. For example, the concentrations of nitrates and phosphates could exceed the limits of the necessary water quality. Appropriate specific measures or actions, which correspond to Best Management Practices (BMPs), such as appropriate use of fertilizer, creation or modification of buffer strips, drainage management, etc., can significantly reduce the local pollution. This, however, leads to additional costs. The effect of the specific actions can be estimated by the SWAT model (TOR 3.3.1.2). Therefore, we get a multiobjective optimization problem (TOR 3.3), where we want to maximize the pollution reduction (TOR 3.3.1.4) by proper application of measures and simultaneously minimize the required costs of the measures (TOR 3.3.1.5).

2.1. Spatial optimization for reduction of agricultural pollution

As stated above, the purpose of the optimization is improvement of water body quality by proper placement of specific measures and minimization of costs and maximization of pollution reduction (PR) at sub-basin level. In the present setup of SWAT model PAIC (2014ab) area of Lithuania is divided into approximately 1200 sub-basins (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Division of sub-basins within Lithuania.

Number of HRU (hydrological response unit) n_{HRU} in each sub-basin is around 200. Each measure is applied on the HRU level as described in (Maringanti 2009, Panagopoulos

2013, and Arabi 2006). The list of possible measures should be prepared. The total number of possible measures (n_M) should be in the range 5 - 50; the total number of measures in (Maringanti 2009, Panagopoulos 2013, Arabi 2006) is 3 to 30. The list of measures should also include combined measures, i.e., two or more measures applied for the same HRU if a combination of them is possible. The list of measures should consider the results of Baltic Compass Project and the list should be agreed with agency (TOR 3.3.1.9). The measures are assumed to be discrete (Maringanti 2009, Panagopoulos 2013, Arabi 2006). It means that for each sub-basin there could be $n_M^{n_{HRU}}$ possible combinations for the measures. This by far exceeds the limits of direct optimization by running through all the possible variants directly. Henceforth, a heuristic approach should be used for the optimization. Genetic algorithm (GA) is very well suited for this task (TOR 3.3.1.3), where the measures are discrete (Maringanti 2009, Panagopoulos 2013, Arabi 2006). It mimics the process of evolution in nature. The efficiency of genetic minimization algorithm is well proven (Deb et al, 2002).

Figure 2. The optimization starts from upper sub-basins to the downstream sub-basins.

2.2. Hydrological and water quality data

The scheme of algorithm for the optimization of water pollution reduction measures is shown in Figures 3-4. This algorithm is realized in optimization tool described in Chapter 3. Algorithm is applied to baseline scenario, which must be calculated for all sub-basins, corresponding to the model state with implemented measures from previous river basin district management plan with implementation date up to 2021. The algorithm consists of following steps (TOR 3.3.1.13):

1. Select upstream sub-basin b with “bad” water body status according to expert criteria. According to (TOR 3.5.1.1.2-3) the primary criterion for the water quality is concentration of nitrates (NO_3). The water quality is measured by the annual average

concentration. The threshold annual average concentration is 2.3 mg/l of N-NO₃. Some of the sub-basins may already have good water quality. Thus, there is no need to apply additional costs for water quality that is better than required. However, there may be sub-basins with bad water quality which does not meet regulatory criteria. For these basins the optimization of measures and their costs should be carried out (ToR 3.3.1.13.1). The optimization process is started from upstream river basins (ToR 3.3.1.13.8, see also Figure 2), since the result of optimization can influence the water quality downstream. As a result water quality of some of the downstream river basins may become good by applying measures only to the upstream sub-basins.

Figure 3. Scheme of algorithm for the optimization of measures of water pollution reduction.

2. Run SWAT model for the sub-basin b for each measure m and create tables $cost_{m,HRU} = cost(m, HRU)$ and $PR_{m,HRU} = PR(m, HRU)$, here PR is “pollution reduction”. These tables contain a list of measures vs. a list of HRUs within the sub-basin. The use of tables will significantly improve the efficiency of algorithm, since we can run the optimization part without involving SWAT, which makes the calculations much faster.
3. Genetic optimization and extraction of Pareto border points (PBPs) (TOR 3.3.1.6) in $\frac{Cost_V}{PR_V}$ space, where $MHRU$ is set with all permutation of measures m and HRU .

$$\{ \min(\sum_{V \in MHRU} cost_{V_m, V_{HRU}}), \max(\sum_{V \in MHRU} PR_{V_m, V_{HRU}}) \}$$
Pareto border points are the points where it is not possible to increase the PR within sub-basin by not increasing the total cost for the sub-basin. Due to limited computational power, Pareto curve will be approximated by its discrete representation (PBPs), since we cannot run through all the possible combinations.
4. Take maximal possible PR $\max(PR)$ combination in sub-basin and run SWAT model for the corresponding set of measures. If all measures in this combination are equal and this combination was calculated before genetic optimization, take existing results.

It resembles the maximal possible reduction of pollution within sub-basin. If “good” water body status could not be achieved even with the maximal PR then go back to upstream sub-basin and repeat optimization process starting from point 2 (ToR 3.3.1.13.9). Of course, this sub-basin is already optimized and there exist concentrations C calculated by SWAT for the Pareto curve, so only proper concentration should be chosen. As maximum PR might not be desirable, since it will probable imply converting all agricultural lands to forest, some percentage of max PR criteria can be used in optimization algorithm instead of maximum PR.

5. If desired concentration C_{target} can be reached, run SWAT model for sub-basin b for 99 PBPs (TOR 3.3.1.13.6). Instead of using the concentration C_{target} , it can be multiplied by safety criteria (for example 0.95). This increases the chance for optimization of downstream water quality, if lower value in upstream basins is required. The results will provide overview what pollution reduction and what water quality can be achieved using the specified costs. Some of 100 PBPs may not have the desirable water quality, but, generally, the water quality will increase increasing the total cost for the sub-basin.
6. Select the best PBP. This is the point on Pareto curve which meets the criteria of water quality having minimal cost per PR (TOR 3.3.1.13.7).
7. Run SWAT model for all depended sub-basins (downstream) and receive new water body status. The optimization of upstream sub-basins may change influence the downstream sub-basins (see point 1).
8. Go to point 2. That is, the process continues to the rest of sub-basins downstream (TOR 3.3.1.13.10).

The measures should be given in the following table and should be expressed in annual costs and include investment, operation and maintenance as well as, if possible, opportunity costs (ToR 3.3.1.11):

#	Base BMP	Region of application	Cost, €/year/m ²	Descriptions	SWAT implementation
1					

Not all of the measures can be applied to all of the regions. Therefore, region of application should be specified, including soil, land use and slope combinations, if relevant. One of the most important quantities is the cost of the measure expressed in Euros per year and m². The last column in the table is SWAT implementation. Not all the measures can be implemented in the SWAT. Some of measures can be implemented by varying some parameters in the SWAT. Using the information above the measures will be implemented in optimization tool.

Basic measures can be combined into complicated ones according to experts to build a table (below):

# of measure	Basic BMP set
1	1,2,..

Not all the measures can be combined. Combined measures give a new measure for the genetic optimization. So, the number of measures increases rapidly increasing the set of the basic measures.

The points 2 and 3 of the optimization algorithm are described for the application of HRU level measures only. This reduces the enormous amount of simulations necessary for the finding of optimal combination of measures. If it is necessary to apply higher than HRU level measures (ToR 3.3.1.7) i.e. measures on SWAT catchment or riverbed level as extension of wetlands and arrangement of sedimentation pounds, a different strategy must be applied. Direct SWAT calculation of each combination of measures instead of doing summation within the cost-load reduction table is precise but absolutely non-useful due to enormous amount of computations. Instead, an approximated method is suggested. After the optimization of particular watershed without an accounting for higher level measures, some cases (e.g. points on Pareto curve) are recalculated in SWAT applying the watershed level measure. The result of this recalculation is a table with additional load reduction (or increase) depending on the load reduction (or cost). This result can be considered as additional line in the “cost”-“load reduction” table and the genetic optimization based on this new table must be carried out one more time. However, the functional dependence (and thus the precision) of the additional load reduction on the initial load reduction cannot be guaranteed and must be tested and checked for each particular case/measure.

Figure 4. Scheme of genetic optimization part.

2.3. Realization of genetic algorithm

A gene is an index of the combined BMPs. So the gene contains an integer number of the applied measure in corresponding HRU. Number 0 corresponds to the case when no measures are applied.

A chromosome is a set of genes – a set of HRUs with applied BMP at sub-basin (watershed) level. For example, a chromosome for sub-basin with 3 HRUs contains 3 genes i.e. it is array of 3 integer numbers.

Optimization is based on the multi-objective genetic algorithm (NSGA-II) (Kalyanmoy et al. 2002) and uses the cost and pollution reduction tables. The optimal parameters (size of population, recombination of fittest members, mutation rate) for the genetic algorithm are given, e.g., in (Maringanti et al. 2009).

The scheme of the genetic optimization part is shown in Figure 4. Starting from the initial population the points on Pareto boundary curve are calculated in each generation until the algorithm reaches convergence. There is an option to use preconditioning of initial population, which can decrease the effort of optimization considerably (see section 1.1.4 for details). The stop procedure is initiated if Pareto front doesn't improve the position during several generations of evolution (see Figure 5) or maximum of predefined generations is reached.

According to the ToR 3.3.1.13.4 an option of gradually reducing and, separately, gradually increasing the total amount of load reduction can be added to the standard algorithm. This is realized modifying the selection algorithm. The standard GA selection is used in every generation, as usual, with an exception of every $100+i*100$ generation and $50+i*100$ generation, where i is an integer number. For every $100+i*100$ generation, the selection is made only to choose the individuals with the lowest price disregarding what PR it has. For every $50+i*100$ generation, the selection is made only to choose the individuals with the highest PR disregarding what the price is. This measure is named “special selection” and could provide a better spread of Pareto optimum curve.

Figure 5. The evolutionary algorithm proceeds through a number of generations (epochs) N until the saturation, that is, until there is no significant change in population for M subsequent generations.

Additional very simple and efficient option to increase the spreading of Pareto curve is the addition of zero and maximum PR measures to the initial population (Figure 12). Typically, population is considerably larger than the prescribed size of final Pareto curve, therefore a reduction to 100 Pareto points is carried out by filtering of nearest points.

2.4. Preconditioning of initial population

The investigations of realized genetic algorithm in Section 2.5 below have revealed that the finding of points near the Pareto curve in whole cost range for the largest requested size of table in reasonable time is hardly possible (e.g. see Figure 10). Therefore, a method improving the initial random distribution was found and proposed as a possible option instead of random initial population.

Using the fact that the target functions are linear combination (sum) of values from relatively small input table with $n_{HRU} \cdot n_M$ elements, and large number of solutions arises by permutation of this table, a serial search through HRUs is possible.

The method for obtaining all combinations can be described as follows. The non-zero combinations are calculated for the first two HRUs assuming zero measures for all other HRUs, there are $n_M \cdot n_M$ combinations (notice that one measure is zero measure and we get also the “zero”-cost and “zero- PR case). After that these combinations are combined with the next HRU and n_M^3 combinations are obtained. The process is continued until the last HRU and a huge number of combinations $n_M^{n_{HRU}}$ is obtained.

For better understanding a small example with 5 HRUs and 5 measures (including “0”-measure) is demonstrated in Figure 6. The resulting table of all possible combinations has $5^5=625$ elements and can be easily analyzed.

Figure 6. Scheme of the method for serial obtaining of all combinations.

If 50 measures are used, then after first 7 HRUs the combinations require more space than any computer can store in RAM. The serial preconditioning method reduces the combinations to a reasonable number after addition of each new HRU. This is realized by selecting the “best” combinations only. Several selection algorithms/strategies can be applied in order to leave the most promising combinations – sorting by cost intervals, sorting by PR intervals and Pareto front selection. Finally all three methods can be combined. For example, for the small case shown in Figure 6, the matrix with 125 pairs, produced in step 2, is sorted and only 100 “best” pairs are provided to the next step for the combination with 4th HRU. This method will be called TG preconditioning.

Of course, there is no guarantee that using this method an optimum will be found because not all combinations are inspected. However, tests show very good performance of this method comparing to the genetic algorithm started from random initial conditions. Moreover, the use of genetic algorithm afterwards can improve the initial solution (see Section 2.5, Figure 11).

The detailed description of algorithm consists of definitions, main part, and permutation and selection algorithms.

Definitions

$V = (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_N)$ is solution vector, where $V_i = m_i \in [1, M]$ is measure number for i -th HRU.

M is count of measures, N is count of HRUs.

$V_{\max(\text{Cost})}$ is solution vector which leads to maximum cost.

$V_{\min(\text{Cost})}$ is solution vector which leads to minimum cost.

$V_{\max(\text{PR})}$ is solution vector which leads to maximum pollution reduction.

$\text{Cost}(V) = \sum_{i=1}^N \text{cost}_{V_i, i}$ is total cost for the solution vector V .

$\text{PR}(V) = \sum_{i=1}^N \text{pr}_{V_i, i}$ is total pollution reduction for the solution vector V .

$\text{cost}_{m, i}, \text{pr}_{v, i}$ is cost and pollution reduction for the i -th HRU and m -th measure.

Optimization goal is two-parameter optimization for

$$\left\{ \min_{V \in MHRU} \text{Cost}(V), \max_{V \in MHRU} \text{PR}(V) \right\}$$

where $MHRU$ is set with all permutation of measures m and HRU

$$V_{\max(\text{PR})_i} = \arg \left(\max_{m \in [1, M]} (\text{pr}_{m, i}) \right)$$

$$V_{\min(\text{Cost})_i} = \arg \left(\max_{m \in [1, M]} (\text{cost}_{m, i}) \right)$$

Interval $[\text{Cost}(V_{\min(\text{Cost})}), \text{Cost}(V_{\max(\text{PR})})]$ is a total cost interval where Pareto front is defined

Main part

The main algorithm performs the permutation of a list with the table row corresponding to the next HRU and selects an appropriate number of “best” list elements. At the beginning the list is empty and a typical maximum number of elements K in the list is equal to 100 – the number of required Pareto points at the end of optimization.

$L_0 = [(0,0, [],0,0)]$
 For i in $[1..N]$
 $L^* =$ Permutate L_{i-1} with table row i
 $L_i =$ Select elements from L^*

where list of records is

$L = [(C_{min}, C_{max}, V, C, R)_1, (C_{min}, C_{max}, V, C, R)_2, \dots, (C_{min}, C_{max}, V, C, R)_K]$

and K is count of records.

Permutation

In the case of selection method c , the row i is reduced by removing non Pareto front items ($cost_{m,i}, pr_{m,i}$). The point is not a Pareto point if there exists at least one point with less cost AND larger PR than that of this point.

List of records is combined with table ($cost_{m,i}, pr_{m,i}$) row i :

$C_{min,k-M+m}^* = C_{min,k} + cost_{m,i}$; $C_{max,k-M+m}^* = C_{max,k} + cost_{m,i}$;
 $C_{k-M+m}^* = C_k + cost_{m,i}$; $R_{k-M+m}^* = R_k + pr_{m,i}$; $V_{(k-M+m)} =$ append m to $V_{(k)}$ where
 $m \in [1, M]$.

$V_{(k)}$ stands for vector V taken from list element k , V_k is vector k -th vector element.

Selection

Three different methods are used for the selection of best K elements after the permutation with the next table row, i.e. with the next HRU.

a) cost interval selection

In the case if the length of the list L is less than K , selection is not applied.

Sort intervals by C_{max}

Create K new intervals (denoted by $*$) by grouping old intervals by C_{max} . Group G_i

$i = [1, K]$ includes all indexes j of list elements from interval

$$i = \left\lfloor K \frac{C_{max,j} - \min_{n \in [1, \text{length}(L)]} C_{min,n}}{\max_{n \in [1, \text{length}(L)]} C_{min,n} - \min_{n \in [1, \text{length}(L)]} C_{min,n}} \right\rfloor$$

New interval values are calculated as

$$C_{min,i}^* = \min_{n \in G_i} C_{min,n}; C_{max,i}^* = \max_{j \in G_i} C_{max,j};$$

$$PR_i^* = \max_{j \in G_i} PR_j, \text{ and corresponding } V_{(i)}^* = V_{(\arg(\max_{j \in G_i} PR_j))},$$

$$C_i^* = C_{\arg(\max_{j \in G_i} PR_j)}$$

b) pollution reduction interval selection

In case if the length of the list L is less than K , selection is not applied

Sort list elements by R

Create K new intervals (denoted by $*$) by grouping old intervals by R . Grope G_i

$i = [1, K]$ includes all indexes j of list elements from interval

$$i = \left\lfloor K \frac{R_j - \min_{n \in [1, \text{length}(L)]} R_n}{\max_{n \in [1, \text{length}(L)]} R_n - \min_{n \in [1, \text{length}(L)]} R_n} \right\rfloor$$

New values of list elements calculated as

$$C_i^* = \min_{j \in G_i} C_j; \text{ and corresponding } V_{(i)}^* = V_{(\arg(\min_{j \in G_i} C_j))}; R_i^* = R_{\arg(\min_{j \in G_i} C_j)}$$

C_{\min}, C_{\max} is not used

c) Pareto front selection

In case if the length of the list L is less than K , selection is not applied

At first, select only Pareto front records, i.e. delete all non Pareto elements. Variables C_{\min}, C_{\max} are not used for the selection. Instead of that all nearest items are removed until the length of the list L is not higher than K .

2.5. Examples of investigation of genetic optimization algorithm

The algorithm realized in optimization tool was tested during the development stage and some of the most important results are shown in this section and summarized at the end of the section. First, the used artificial input table of load reduction and the probability distribution in cost vs. PR plane is shown. After that the effect of most parameters used in genetic algorithm are investigated. From these results follows that for the expected sizes of tables the obtaining of a sufficiently good Pareto curve is hardly possible in reasonable time. Therefore additional preconditioning algorithms were developed and investigated. The effect of application of different selection algorithms on the spreading of Pareto curve is demonstrated as well.

2.5.1. Table of load reduction and costs

The algorithm was tested on tables with different sizes changing both n_{HRU} and n_M . The content of tables (pairs cost; PR) was artificially generated due to lack of real impact and costs of planned measures at this project stage. The formula for cost and PR for all demonstrated cases is the following:

$$PR = \frac{10 + HRUNR}{10} r_1 (1 - 2^{-20c}) + r_2$$

where r_1 and r_2 are uniform random numbers in range 0 to 1 and c is cost. The random distribution is uniform over the cost, but exponential over load reduction. Both values are positive in proposed artificial distribution, but algorithm will work also in the case of negative PR. One typical distribution is shown in Figure 7 where the cost is distributed between 0 and 100.

Figure 7. Initial random distribution of pollution reduction PR versus cost.

2.5.2. Definition of examples and quality criteria

In the following examples the table with 100 HRU and 10 measures is investigated if not stated otherwise. One of the measures is “zero” measure with zero cost and zero load reduction. In the figures the results are shown for every 300 generation if not stated otherwise. Most of the graphs contain also a nearly “ideal” Pareto curve which is obtained starting from preconditioned initial population. This curve, shown with blue dots, is not known for the genetic optimization algorithm which is started from random initial population and is shown in the same graph only for better sense of accuracy which can be achieved with different methods.

For the quantitative comparison between the simulations two parameters are introduced. **Dimensionless spreading of the front** a defined as

$$a = \frac{\max(\text{nitrogen reduction})}{\max(\text{nitrogen reduction})} - \frac{\min(\text{cost})}{\text{cost at maximal possible nitrogen reduction}},$$

and **dimensionless average effectivity**

$$b = \frac{\text{cost at maximal possible nitrogen reduction}}{\max(\text{nitrogen reduction})} \left(\frac{\text{nitrogen reduction}}{\text{cost}} \right).$$

The first parameter a varies from nearly 0 to 1, with 1 corresponding to very good spreading of the results i.e. good covering of the whole data range of Pareto curve. The

second parameter b is higher as it gets closer to the Pareto curve. Remember, that GA involves stochastic processes, so the parameters a and b may fluctuate during the optimization.

2.5.3. Probability distribution

In order to demonstrate that the finding of Pareto curve from initial random distribution is not an easy task the probability distribution in cost vs. PR plane is plotted. This is done by throwing large amount of randomly selected individuals on to this plane. Larger density of points corresponds to the position with larger probability.

Figure 8. Probability distribution in cost vs. PR plane for the case with $n_{HRU}=100$, $n_M=10$. Number of randomly selected points is $3 \cdot 10^4$ (a), $1 \cdot 10^6$ (b) and $2 \cdot 10^7$.

In Figure 8 the distribution for 100 HRU and 10 measures is shown. The Pareto front, calculated using other methods, is shown in the Figures with blue dots. As can be seen, the majority of random points are within a small cloud far away from the Pareto curve. The probability to match some desired point (e.g. specific point on Pareto front) is only $(10+1)^{-100}$ which is not possible just by random selection. If the numbers of HRU and measures are reduced to 16 and 4, respectively, the probability cloud spreads wider and comes closer to the Pareto front (Figure 9). In this case the probability to match a specific point is enormously larger: $6.6 \cdot 10^{-12}$.

Figure 9. Probability distribution in cost vs. PR plane for the case with $n_{HRU}=16$, $n_M=4$. Number of randomly selected points is $3 \cdot 10^4$ (a), $1 \cdot 10^6$ (b) and $2 \cdot 10^7$.

2.5.4. Preconditioning of initial population

The effect of preconditioning of initial population (Section 2.4) for genetic algorithm is shown based on population size $pop=300$ and the crossover and mutation probabilities as $Cr=Mu=0.5$ in VAROR variation algorithm, respectively. Individual mutation rate is $IMu=0.1$, i.e., every tenth HRU of the mutating individual gets mutated. The selection algorithm is NSGA2 in DEAP. The number of calculated generations is 3000 and each 30 generation is shown in next figures.

In Figure 10 the development of population is shown for random initial population and in Figure 11 for TG preconditioned population. The larger dots represent the initial distribution and smaller ones – the following generations. As can be seen from the plots, the initial guess of population i.e. the preconditioner is very important. It provides an excellent spreading of the Pareto front and requires just few generations to obtain nearly perfect Pareto front. For a random initial population, the spreading is much worse and the convergence requires a large amount of generations and is far away from the TG preconditioned results.

It can be seen in Figure 10, that the population convergences to the middle part of Pareto curve reasonably well, but the range does not spread to low total cost and maximal PR. As the zero cost measure is known and it is also trivial to find the combination of measures for maximum PR reduction, the initial distribution can be easily extended by these values.

Figure 10. Development of population during 3000 generations for random initial populations with size of $pop=300$.

To create such an initial population, the following is done: for $\frac{1}{4}$ of HRUs random measures are used, but for $\frac{3}{4}$ of the HRUs no measures are applied, i.e., the distribution will be closer to the point (0,0) in PR vs. cost axes. Additionally, few individuals (3 in this

example) with highest possible load reduction are included in the initial population. This preconditioning method is called RG preconditioning. The results are shown in Figure 12. The crossover part of genetic algorithm brings the population to the lower cost and higher PR parts of Pareto curve very fast, however, the middle part converges slower.

Figure 11. Development of population during 3000 generations for TG preconditioned initial population with size of pop=300.

Figure 12. Development of population during 3000 generations for RG preconditioned initial population with size of 300.

Based on the results above we endorse the TG preconditioning algorithm over the RG preconditioned and randomly selected initial population.

2.5.5. Role of crossover and mutation probabilities

The sum of crossover and mutation probabilities has to be lower or equal to value 1 for the given selection and variation algorithm VAROR in DEAP. The Cr is varied between 0.1 and 0.995, the sum of Cr and Mu is 1 in all cases but 0.8 in one case. The results for large population size $pop=1000$ and $IMu=0.1$ are summarized in Table 1 as values of spreading a and efficiency b . The development of population for 2 examples is shown in Figures 13 and 14.

The best convergence is achieved at the crossover probability 0.995-0.998 and mutation probability 0.002-0.005 if the number of generations is below 500. It is so, because using fast cross-over processes one can get close to Pareto front quickly.

Table 1. Influence of crossover and mutation probabilities for population size 1000. The columns represent different crossover probability (first number) and different mutation probability (second number). Rows represent number of generations. The elements in the cells are a and b values. The lower two rows represent the case with TG preconditioned initial population after 30 generations. Colored background means the best results.

	$C_r=0.995$ $M_u=0.005$	$C_r=0.95$ $M_u=0.05$	$C_r=0.9$ $M_u=0.1$	$C_r=0.8$ $M_u=0.2$	$C_r=0.7$ $M_u=0.3$	$C_r=0.6$ $M_u=0.4$	$C_r=0.5$ $M_u=0.5$	$C_r=0.4$ $M_u=0.6$	$C_r=0.2$ $M_u=0.8$	$C_r=0.1$ $M_u=0.9$	$C_r=0.6$ $M_u=0.2$
Time/gen	5.25 s	5.25 s	5.42 s	5.55 s	5.71 s	5.77 s		5.80 s	5.92 s	6.00 s	1.44 s
60	0.6598 1.935	0.6578 1.956	0.6144 1.935	0.6424 1.854	0.6097 1.766	0.6230 1.736	0.5418 1.647	0.5262 1.489	0.4611 1.318	0.4362 1.223	0.6054 1.783
180	0.7689 2.552	0.7353 2.413	0.6955 2.265	0.7448 2.298	0.7466 2.354	0.7517 2.410	0.7094 2.298	0.7090 2.209	0.6751 2.124	0.6216 1.742	0.7160 2.416
600	0.7808 2.426	0.7460 2.439	0.7155 2.298	0.7713 2.505	0.7762 2.455	0.7843 2.546	0.7345 2.501	0.7514 2.410	0.7362 2.578	0.7656 2.364	0.7790 2.407
1800	0.7826 2.402	0.7798 2.481	0.7586 2.353	0.7968 2.438	0.8187 2.502	0.8294 2.661	0.7911 2.549	0.7791 2.528	0.8021 2.533	0.7980 2.515	0.811 2.242
6000	0.7924 2.522	0.8156 2.538	0.8167 2.490	0.8524 2.629	0.8727 2.734	0.8809 2.722	0.8755 2.652	0.8665 2.588	0.8715 2.610	0.8596 2.650	0.8027 2.260
18000	0.8055 2.550	0.8611 2.628	0.8741 2.665	0.9035 2.855	0.9216 2.961	0.9382 2.927		0.9372 2.960	0.9302 2.753	0.9370 2.922	0.8445 2.291
Precond. Time/gen	5.57 s	5.65 s	5.71 s	5.65 s		5.59 s	5.64 s	5.58 s	6.24 s	6.34 s	2.72 s
30	0.9986 2.817	0.9986 2.824	0.9986 2.857	0.9986 2.754	0.9986 2.652	0.9986 2.710	0.9986 2.653	0.9986 2.480	0.9986 2.328	0.9986 2.436	0.9986 2.89

However, when reaching about 200 generations with low mutation probability, these simulations start to stagnate as the population cannot get to some principally new individuals beyond the existing ones without significant mutation. Thus, if the number of generations is above 500, the case with crossover probability $C_r=0.6$ and mutation probability $M_u=0.4$ are the best combination. It is because crossover processes are faster, but mutation processes change the long term behavior. For better spreading of the results (the first parameter a) even higher mutation probability is better. Calculation time per generation is weakly dependent on the crossover/mutation probabilities, but increases slightly with mutation probability. The situation will change if we will vary parameter IMu as will be shown next. The case with $C_r=0.6$ and $M_u=0.2$ (last column in Table 1) suggests that it is best to keep the sum C_r+M_u equal to 1.

As can be seen from the Table 1, the GA is still not converged after 18000 generations to cover full Pareto front. However, the situation is much better with TG preconditioning (last row in Table 1).

Figure 13. Development of population during 18000 generations for $Cr=0.995$ and $Mu=0.005$.

Next, the study is repeated for smaller population size $pop=300$ and lower individual mutation rate $IMu=0.1$, what yields to the considerable decrease of calculation time per generation. The results are summarized in Table 2. The results in the Table 2 suggest that for smaller population and lower IMu the mutation probability should be increased to $Mu=0.8$. Once again we see that it is best to keep the sum of crossover and mutation probabilities of 1, compare the column with $Cr=0.5$ and $Mu=0.4$.

The results for the best combination of parameters ($pop=300$, $IMu=0.01$, $Cr=0.2$; $Mu=0.8$) are shown in Figure 15. At these parameters good results (values of a and b) can be achieved also without preconditioning.

Figure 14. Development of population during 18000 generations for $Cr=0.6$ and $Mu=0.4$.

Table 2. Influence of crossover and mutation probabilities for population size 300 and $IMu=0.01$. The columns represent different crossover probability Cr and different mutation probability Mu . Rows represent calculation time on the same CPU. The elements in the cells are a and b values.

	$Cr=0.8$ $Mu=0.2$	$Cr=0.7$ $Mu=0.3$	$Cr=0.6$ $Mu=0.4$	$Cr=0.5$ $Mu=0.4$	$Cr=0.5$ $Mu=0.5$	$Cr=0.4$ $Mu=0.6$	$Cr=0.3$ $Mu=0.7$	$Cr=0.2$ $Mu=0.8$	$Cr=0.1$ $Mu=0.9$	$Cr=0.05$ $Mu=0.95$
Time/gen	0.475 s	0.462 s	0.419 s	0.341 s	0.415 s	0.399 s	0.373 s	0.348 s	0.341 s	0.327 s
1 min	126 gen: 0.6636 2.107	130 gen: 0.6960 2.229	143 gen: 0.6363 2.111	176 gen: 0.6618 2.220	145 gen: 0.6830 1.981	150 gen: 0.6888 2.085	161 gen: 0.6897 1.995	172 gen: 0.6761 2.193	176 gen: 0.6516 1.894	183 gen: 0.6639 1.830
5 min	632 gen: 0.8088 2.599	649 gen: 0.8334 2.681	716 gen: 0.8363 2.633	880 gen: 0.8717 2.764	723 gen: 0.8614 2.704	752 gen: 0.8766 2.886	804 gen: 0.9088 2.735	862 gen: 0.9075 2.850	880 gen: 0.9261 2.785	917 gen: 0.9174 2.606
20 min	2526 gen: 0.9400 3.041	2597 gen: 0.9719 3.411	2864 gen: 0.9760 3.357	3519 gen: 0.9599 2.892	2892 gen: 0.9855 3.427	3008 gen: 0.9842 3.340	3217 gen: 0.9890 3.379	3448 gen: 0.9917 3.540	3519 gen: 0.9938 3.440	3670 gen: 0.9921 3.253
1 h	7579 gen: 0.9870 3.347	7792 gen: 0.9957 3.595	8592 gen: 0.9987 3.554	10557 gen: 0.9634 2.464	8675 gen: 0.9972 3.453	9023 gen: 0.9998 3.702	9651 gen: 1.0000 3.735	10345 gen: 1.0000 3.676	10557 gen: 1.0000 4.050	11009 gen: 0.9998 3.456
2 h	15158 gen: 0.9970 3.498	15584 gen: 0.9993 3.581	17184 gen: 1.0000 0.3601		17349 gen: 0.9998 3.552					

Figure 15. Development of GA at optimized parameters: $Cr=0.2$; $Mu=0.8$; $IMu=0.01$; $pop=300$; NSGA2. Only the initial distribution (large green points) and final distribution after 6000 generations is showed on the cost vs. PR plot.

2.5.6. Role of individual mutation

DEAP algorithm has an additional parameter for mutations. If an individual is selected to mutation, then we can set the probability for each of the gene to mutate. The results are summarized in the Table 3. According to the results, the best convergence per computation time is achieved at individual mutation probability $IMu=0.01$ of an individual. Since we have 100 HRUs, it means that it is best to set the individual mutation probability to 1 divided by number of HRUs. Thus, approximately one gene of an individual will mutate per generation, if the individual is selected for the mutation. The computational time per generation slightly decreases decreasing the individual mutation probability since it invokes the random generator fewer times. Best spreading is achieved at very low individual mutation probability, but it is almost perfect also for individual mutation frequency ≤ 0.02 .

Table 3. Influence of individual mutation rate IMu at $Cr=0.2$, $Mu=0.8$ and $pop=300$.

	$IMu=0.003$	$IMu=0.005$	$IMu=0.007$	$IMu=0.01$	$IMu=0.02$
Time/gen	0.226 s	0.265 s	0.308 s	0.348 s	0.466 s
1 min	265 gen: 0.6816 2.131	226 gen: 0.6957 2.130	195 gen: 0.6775 2.198	172 gen: 0.6761 2.193	129 gen: 0.6491 1.884
5 min	1327 gen: 0.8758 2.517	1132 gen: 9.147 2.879	974 gen: 0.8985 2.778	862 gen: 0.9075 2.850	644 gen: 0.8668 2.596
20 min	5310 gen: 0.9809 3.171	4528 gen: 0.9928 3.452	3896 gen: 0.9953 3.471	3448 gen: 0.9917 3.540	2575 gen: 0.9832 3.431
1 h	15929 gen: 0.9999 3.631	13585 gen: 0.9999 3.645	11688 gen: 0.9999 3.664	10345 gen: 1.0000 3.676	7725 gen: 0.9993 3.610

2.5.7. Population size

The size of population in GA can be very important, as shown in Table 4. A small size of population does not converge well to the Pareto front. The required size of population can be estimated as a number of HRU multiplied by a number of measures. In our case it is in order of 1000. Then almost all measures per HRU are included in the population which suggests that there is proper variability that any combination of genes in chromosome could be reached even with a small number of mutations. It is important, because the crossover in GA do not create new genes (new measures of HRU), but for mutations there is low probability that better genes will be obtained during several generations.

However, an increase of population dramatically increases the calculation time. It increases more than proportionally to the increase of population size. Thus, we can get a higher number of generations with smaller population during the same calculation time. As a result, a small population gives very good spreading parameter a as the number of generations can reach very high number with good effect of mutation. The convergence of parameter b (representing the average ratio between the load reduction and cost) is best at population size of 300, if we have spent more than 20 minutes of calculation. There is no reason to take a larger population and considerably increase the calculation time per generation without any significant improvement of convergence per generation.

We can still compare the typical parameters of genetic optimization. Typically, the number measures studied in literature are relatively small (< 7), but we will need a higher number of measures up to 40. In the study of Maringanti (2009) the number of HRU is 443 and number of non-zero measures are 4. They found that population size 200 is good with idea that 400 is better, which well corresponds to our studies, i.e. 300. They used larger crossover rate of 0.9 instead of 0.2 in our case. For our VAROR part of the GA such crossover rate would mean the decrease in mutation rate which improves convergence for few generations (< 300) but deteriorates for higher number of generations. The mutation rate of 0.001 is a bit lower and corresponds well to our studies. For $n_{HRU}=443$ our optimal value would be ~ 0.002 . The number of required generations they found is 40000. Our estimations for the $n_{HRU}=443$ and $n_M=5$ would be ~ 15000 generations for population of 300, which converges faster than population of 200.

Table 4. Influence of population size at $Cr=0.2$, $Mu=0.8$ and $IMu=0.01$.

	pop=100	pop=200	pop=250	pop=300	pop=400
Time/gen	0.0835 s	0.201 s	0.268 s	0.348 s	0.547 s
1 min	719 gen: 0.8212 2.346	299 gen: 0.7416 2.262	224 gen: 0.7107 2.091	172 gen: 0.6761 2.193	110 gen: 0.6203 1.831
5 min	3593 gen: 0.9723 2.671	1493 gen: 0.9430 2.962	1119 gen: 0.9347 2.909	862 gen: 0.9075 2.850	548 gen: 0.8614 2.727
20 min	14371 gen: 0.9999 2.802	5970 gen: 0.9981 3.511	4478 gen: 0.9972 3.475	3448 gen: 0.9917 3.540	2194 gen: 0.9795 3.207
1 h		17910 gen: 1.0000 3.625	13433 gen: 1.0000 3.432	10345 gen: 1.0000 3.676	6581 gen: 0.9995 3.508

Arabi (2006) studied case where the number of HRU is 70 with just two non-zero measures applicable to 50 HRUs and other two measures to remaining HRUs. So, we can approximate it as $n_{HRU}=70$ and $n_M=2$. Our estimations give that with ~ 1000 generations it would be fully enough for high accuracy Pareto curve. They used up to 250 generations which is still sufficient. Since they have a very small system, they could use smaller population size with just 20-100 individuals.

2.5.8. Selection algorithm

Two selection algorithms are available in DEAP library - NSGA2 and SPEA2. Both algorithms are very similar in selection effectivity with slightly better result for the second, see Table 5. However, NSGA2 selection algorithm is around 10 times faster, especially for large populations, because of fast sorting introduced in NSGA2.

Table 5. Influence of selection algorithm at $IMu=0.1$, $pop=300$, $Cr=0.6$ and $Mu=0.4$. The rows represent computational time on the same CPU. The cell values represent number of generations for the respective computational time, and parameters a and b .

	NSGA2	SPEA2
Time/gen	0.304 s	4.43 s
1 min	197 gen: 0.6990;2.268	14 gen: 0.1993;0.9081
5 min	987 gen: 0.7304;2.434	68 gen: 0.5515;1.647
20 min	3947 gen: 0.8236;2.6495	271 gen: 0.7830;2.520
1 h	11842 gen: 0.8617;2.766	813 gen: 0.8444;2.507

2.5.9. Number of HRU

The larger the watershed, the more generations are required to find the Pareto front. Results, summarized in Table 6, suggest that the number of generations has to be proportional to the number of HRUs.

Figure 16. Development of population during 18000 generations for $n_{HRU}=500$, $pop=300$, $Cr=0.2$; $Mu=0.8$; $IMu=0.01$.

It can be seen also in Figure 16, that the Pareto curve is reached later for large number of HRU (compare to Figure 10). The table suggests also that the individual mutation rate has to be about 1 divided by HRU number: $1/n_{HRU}$. The population size has relatively weak dependence on HRU number, i.e., $pop=300$ is quite optimal. Just for very small n_{HRU} , the population can be slightly reduced for better performance. The computational time increases with n_{HRU} less than linearly, i.e., approximately as a square root from n_{HRU} .

Table 6. Columns represent HRU number, individual mutation rate and population size. Rows represent execution time on the same CPU. The cell values are respective number of generations, *a* and *b* values.

	nHRU=50 <i>IMu</i> =0.02 <i>pop</i> =300	nHRU=50 <i>IMu</i> =0.01 <i>pop</i> =300	nHRU=50 <i>IMu</i> =0.02 <i>pop</i> =200	nHRU=100 <i>IMu</i> =0.01 <i>pop</i> =300	nHRU=500 <i>IMu</i> =0.002 <i>pop</i> =400	nHRU=500 <i>IMu</i> =0.005 <i>pop</i> =300	nHRU=500 <i>IMu</i> =0.002 <i>pop</i> =300
Time/gen	0.181 s	0.139 s	0.0934 s	0.194 s	0.511 s	0.400 s	0.318 s
1 min	331 gen: 0.8924 2.487	431 gen: 0.8744 2.538	642 gen: 0.9648 2.895	309 gen: 0.7856 2.356	117 gen: 0.1344 1.091	150 gen: 0.2303 1.123	189 gen: 0.2213 1.210
5 min	1657 gen: 0.9931 2.996	2158 gen: 0.9942 3.006	3212 gen: 0.9988 3.206	1546 gen: 0.9597 3.010	587 gen: 0.5263 1.876	750 gen: 0.5826 1.933	943 gen: 0.5864 2.166
20 min	6630 gen: 1.0000 3.374	8633 gen: 0.9997 3.180	12848 gen: 1.0000 3.093	6186 gen: 0.9983 3.458	2348 gen: 0.7835 2.570	3000 gen: 0.8081 2.519	3774 gen: 0.8390 2.561
1 h					7045 gen: 0.9264 2.781	9000 gen: 0.9322 2.773	11321 gen: 0.9611 2.824
2h					14090 gen: 0.9768 2.973	18000 gen: 0.9775 2.879	22642 gen: 0.9922 2.862

2.5.10. Number of measures

The typical convergence depending on number of measures is given in Table 7.

Table 7. Columns represent count of measures and population size. Rows represent execution time on the same CPU. The cell values are respective number of generations, *a* and *b* values.

	nM=5 <i>pop</i> =200	nM=5 <i>pop</i> =300	nM=10 <i>pop</i> =300	nM=50 <i>pop</i> =400	nM=50 <i>pop</i> =300
Time/gen	0.102 s	0.194 s	0.194 s	0.349 s	0.214 s
1 min	588 gen: 0.9042 2.210	309 gen: 0.8193 2.088	309 gen: 0.7856 2.356	172 gen: 0.6217 2.276	280 gen: 0.6957 2.819
5 min	2941 gen: 0.9973 2.532	1546 gen: 0.9873 2.467	1546 gen: 0.9597 3.010	860 gen: 0.8385 3.791	1402 gen: 0.8777 4.072
20 min	11765 gen: 1.0000 2.603	6186 gen: 1.0000 2.749	6186 gen: 0.9983 3.458	3438 gen: 0.9588 4.422	5607 gen: 0.9661 4.615
1 h				10315 gen: 0.9919 4.800	16822 gen: 0.9954 4.824

The table suggests that population number can be kept the same around 300. The number of required generations increases slightly with increase of measure count with approximately the same execution time per generation. Note that the quantity b depends strongly on n_M and cannot be directly compared between cases with different n_M . The development of population for small n_M is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Development of population at $n_M=5$ (left) and $n_M=10$ (right) for population size of 300.

2.5.11. Special selection of individuals

This section investigates if special selections can improve the spreading of population. We will make the standard GA selection in every generation, as usual, with an exception of every $100+i*100$ generation and $50+i*100$ generation, where i is an integer number. For every $100+i*100$ generation, the selection is made only to choose the individuals with the lowest price disregarding what PR it has. For every $50+i*100$ generation, the selection is made only to choose the individuals with the highest PR disregarding what the price is. Other parameters are following: $n_{HRU}=100$, $n_M=10$, $pop=300$, $IMu=1/n_{HRU}$, $Cr=0.2$, $Mu=0.8$ according to optimal convergence studies above.

As can be seen from Figure 18, no one of these modifications improve the parameters a and b , since the selection only on the minimal cost throws away individuals with higher cost but also with high PR. On the other side, the selection only on high PR throws away individuals with lower PR but with low cost. The range parameter a is just at ~ 0.5 . Therefore, the range of PR becomes much more limited as for original selection, where the range parameter a is already saturated at 1. If use the only the special selection of minimal cost every $100+i*100$ generation, then the entire population moves to lower cost with fine Pareto here, but there is lack of individuals on the other side, and they are badly converged. The range parameter a is also just at ~ 0.5 . So this method cannot be recommended for improved spreading.

Figure 18. Distributions every 300 generations. a) special selections every $50+i*100$ generation (higher PR) and $100+i*100$ generation (lower cost). b) special selections every $50+i*100$ generation (higher cost) and $100+i*100$ generation (lower cost).

2.5.12. Conclusions on investigation of genetic optimization algorithm

- The optimal selection algorithm is NSGA2 in DEAP.
- The crossover probability $Cr=0.2$ and mutation probability $Mu=0.8$ are optimal in variation algorithm VAROR of DEAP.
- The optimal individual mutation rate is around $IMu=1/n_{HRU}$.
- The optimal population size is about $pop=300$.
- The number of generations for full Pareto front has to be about $5000 \frac{n_{HRU}}{100} \sqrt{\frac{nM}{10}}$.

- The number of generations can be dramatically reduced starting from preconditioned initial population. TG preconditioning requires less than thousand generations for the same precision. Even better result can be achieved using TG preconditioning.

Figure 18 (continued). Distributions every 300 generations. c) special selection every 100+i*100 generation (lower cost). d) the original selection.

3. Tool for optimization of water pollution reduction measures (3.3.2)

This section contains a description of the developed tool for optimization of water pollution reduction measures according to TOR 3.3.2. The optimization tool is designed to perform the optimization algorithm embedded in methodology (TOR 3.3.2.1).

The optimization tool is based on Python language, i.e. it is Python language scripts. Toolset includes several units which implements interaction with SWAT software and prepare output files. For genetic optimization the DEAP library is used (Fortin et al. 2012). Main optimization unit contain 4 functional blocks: selection of sub-basins, selection of measures, definition of output variables, optimization loop.

The tool includes 3 main executable scripts, one for optimization (**SpatialOptimization.py**), one for visualization and status information (**status.py**) and one for the extraction of SWAT setups from the calculation history (**prepare_optimal_setups.py**).

3.1. Upper level Python units

In this section the upper level Python units are described. These units containing the parameters and other input information are described in Section 3.2.1.

SpatialOptimization.py is executable unit. It performs all necessary initializations and performs the optimization loop. The optimization loop implements spatial optimization methodology (TOR 3.3.1)

status.py is executable unit. It prepares information about the status of calculation and tables for visualization (TOR 3.3.2.5 and 3.3.2.6).

prepare_optimal_setups.py is executable unit. This unit extracts the best solution from stored history for each watershed and prepares the SWAT setup (TOR 3.3.2.3).

Other units are not executable but contain upper level functionality and user parameters.

MeasuresSettings.py and **OptimizationSettings.py** contain all necessary options for optimization which control the optimization loop and also define the preferable output functionality.

SelectOptimisationRegion.py contains procedures for the selection of sub-basins and preparation of hierarchical tree of selected sub-basins. Procedures simplify the selection of a region for the genetic optimization.

ApplyMeasures.py contains a list of allowed measures and procedures for the selection of measures (TOR 3.3.2.4), it also provides the implementation of selected measure by updating the SWAT input data files (TOR 3.3.2.2).

SubBasinOptimisation.py implements the main optimization functions and runs SWAT model as well as extracts the calculation result in predefined folder (TOR 3.3.2.3).

CalcHistory.py prepares statistical values and stores the optimization history (TOR 3.3.2.6). Statistical values include the status of water body (annual average concentration of nitrates), the cost of the applied measure and the amount of reduction of nitrates load.

ParetoFrontier.py implements the calculation of Pareto curve by genetic algorithm method.

VisualizationOptParams.py contains the procedures for the representation of results in a GIS layer (TOR 3.3.2.5 and 3.3.2.6): tables for water body status, measures, cost and pollution reduction of the selected solution.

3.2. Main optimization blocks

The main executable script **SpatialOptimization.py** contains the following blocks:

- Update settings
- Read project
- Select optimization region
- Run optimization

3.2.1. Update settings

All settings are included in two files - **MeasuresSettings.py** and **OptimizationSettings.py**. The user should change the settings in these two files using a text editor.

MeasuresSettings.py

This file contains the definitions of all measures. The measures list requires following parameters for the definition of a new measure:

- **Cost** is the cost of measure, $\text{€}/(\text{m}^2\text{year})$. In case of composed measure the total cost is sum of joined measures costs.
- **JoinedMeasures** is a list of identifiers of basic measures in case of composed measure. This list is empty in the case of basic measure.
- **Name** is measure name. This field is for informative purpose only, the script uses ID for internal representation of the measure.
- **Description** is foreseen for the short description of measure. This field has only informative purpose.

Unit **ApplyMeasures.py** use measure settings for the construction of measure class and produce registry of all available measures (**MeasuresRegister**). List *SelectedMeasures*, defined in the unit **MeasuresSettings.py**, should contain only numbers of those measures, which will be currently used for the optimization. Default content of this list is all available measures.

OptimizationSettings.py

This file contains 3 logical blocks:

- Project settings
- Optimization settings
- SWAT output settings

Project settings point to the data necessary for the creation of project. SWAT output settings switch on the daily output and output the necessary substances for the water quality calculation. Project settings and SWAT output settings are described in the report PAIC (2014a).

Optimization settings block complete the settings by adding several new parameters. The listed values of parameters are the default values which will be used when not explicitly changed by user.

File structure:

- **LogFileName**="OptimizationLogFile.txt" is the name of log file (in setups folder)
- **HistFolder**="CALC_HISTORY" is the name of history folder (in watershed calculation folder)

Water Quality Criteria:

- WaterQualityCriteria=2.3
Maximum allowable yearly averaged nitrate concentration in the river in mg/l of N-NO₃
- QualitySafetyCriteria=0.98
The water quality criteria will be multiplied by safety criteria in order to increase the chance for optimization of downstream water quality, if lower value in upstream basins is set.

Precondition:

- PreconditionType="Estimate"
["RandomU", "RandomMM", "Estimate"] – the full list of possible options.

"RandomU" - all individuals created by chance selecting measure number with uniform probability distribution.

"RandomMM" - two individuals selected as $V_{min(Cost)}$ and $V_{max(PR)}$ (see 3.1.4), others 70% of individuals created by chance, 25 % of individuals created by combining $V_{min(Cost)}$ and random individual, 5% of individuals created by combining $V_{max(PR)}$ and random individual (RG preconditioning).

"Estimate" - Measure number selected by TG preconditioning (see 3.1.4)

- PreconditionMethodNr=-1
This parameter determines the selection method (see 3.1.4): 0 – method a, 1 – method b, 2 – method c, -1 – run TG precondition 3 times and use all 3 methods, total result integrates 3 particular results.
- PreconditionMaxMergeCount=[200,200,2500]
This prescribes the interval count (see 3.1.4) for selection method a, b and c, respectively.

Genetic algorithm settings (see DEAP 1.0.1 documentation):

- offspringCount=300
Count of offspring individuals (population size *pop*).
- mutpb=0.5
The probability of mutating an individual (*Mu*).
- cxpb=1.0-mutpb
The probability of mating two individuals (*Cr*).
- indpb=0.1
Independent probability for each attribute to be exchanged (*IMu*)
- ParetoPointCount=100
Resulting count of Pareto curve points
- SelectionFunction="NSGA2"
Genetic algorithm selection function

Genetic algorithm stop criteria:

- maxGenerationCount=100
The maximum number of generations
- OptimisationTolerance=1E-6
The optimisation is assumed as converged to the Pareto curve if optimization tolerance is less than OptimisationTolerance parameter. Optimization tolerance is a maximum difference between the relative areas below Pareto curves for last ToleranceMeasurmentStep generations. Relative area means the area below Pareto curves normalized by bounding rectangle area.
- ToleranceMeasurmentStep=10
Count of generations which are used for the calculations of tolerance. This is also the minimum possible number of generations used in the optimization.

Parallelization loop:

- ThreadCount=4
Count of parallel running threads. This parameter should be set smaller than the number of cores in computer used for optimization.
- MaxExecutionTimeForSWAT=600
The maximum execution time for one SWAT calculation in seconds.
If execution time is exceeded, “timed out” status will be returned and the optimization of watershed will be stopped.

3.2.2. Read project

Actual SWAT projects management’s system initialization. This procedure is described in PAIC (2014a).

3.2.3. Select optimization region

The optimization tool provides possibility to optimize at once all or any combination of watersheds in Lithuania. `catchments.TWatershed.Skip` is Boolean field containing information whether or not the watershed is selected for optimization. The “False” value means selection and “True” means that it will be skipped. This field can be set by python subroutine or can be initialized using GDB table. The unit **SelectOptimisationRegion.py** provides following user friendly functions for the selection of regions:

```
SelectAll(project)
select all watersheds;
SelectNone(project)
no one watershed will be selected;
SelectBy_f(project, function=lambda x,opt:True, options={ })
select watersheds by generic function which takes 2 parameters: watershed object and options;
SelectByName(project, WatershedsNamesList)
select watersheds which are in list WatershedsNamesList;
SelectByGDBid(project, GDBTablePath, WatershedIDFieldName)
select watersheds listed in the table;
SelectByGDBval(project, GDBTablePath, WatershedIDFieldName,
SelectionFieldName, SelectValue ="1")
select watersheds by comparing SelectionFieldName column data with the SelectValue value.
```

The parameters of selection procedures are:

- project is `catchments.TProject` object;
- GDBTablePath is the path to the GDB table;
- WatershedIDFieldName is the name of the GDB table column containing watershed’s identifiers;
- SelectionFieldName is the name of the column of GDB table containing the selection data;
- SelectValue is the value which indicates that the watershed is selected.

For example, `SelectOptimisationRegion.SelectByName (project, WatershedsNamesList = ["Venta\Venta_upstr72"])` selects only “Venta\Venta_upstr72” watershed for optimization.

3.2.4. Run optimization

Optimization can be started by running batch file **runOpt.bat** in folder `\Setup\Optimization\Script` (see chapter 3.4) or manually writing in command line:

> c:\Python26\ArcGIS10.0\python.exe **SpatialOptimization.py**

The blocks of **SpatialOptimization.py** described in 3.2.1-3.2.3 are executed first. The algorithm of last block is represented also using simplified pseudo code for better understanding. It is not foreseen that user should change any procedures or parameters in this block. Frequently used functions in block “Run optimization” are underlined.

The main optimization loop runs the optimization tasks for particular watershed in parallel on specified number of cores.

Optimization loop (selected watersheds)
Optimization task (one watershed)
Optimize watershed water quality

The optimization of particular watershed starts with calculation of baseline scenario. If necessary, zero measure solution is recalculated accounting for new best upstream solutions. If water quality with zero measure solution is “bad”, then the optimization of particular watershed is started (*Find best solution*).

Optimize watershed water quality:
Calculate baseline scenario
Recalculate baseline scenario taking into account best upstream solutions (zero measure solution)
Check water quality (nitrate concentration). If “bad water quality”:
Find best solution

If water quality is good, then the optimization of watershed is finished (best solution is current scenario), otherwise the optimization with selection of measures is started. Each measure selected in unit **MeasuresSettings.py** is applied to all HRU of watershed and corresponding SWAT calculation is performed. After the all scenarios are calculated, the table of cost/pollution is prepared. The maximum load reduction scenario is easily found in this table and corresponding concentration is calculated by SWAT. In case of sufficient water quality the Pareto curve is found using genetic optimization algorithm. After that the lowest cost “good” water quality solution is selected.

Find best solution:
For each measure from selected measure list:
Prepare scenario (apply measure to all watershed’s HRU)
Calculate watershed
Prepare cost/pollution reduction table
Prepare maximum pollution reduction scenario
Calculate watershed
Check if “good” water quality attainable. If “good” water quality attainable:
Calculate Pareto front by genetic optimization
For each scenario in Pareto front:
Calculate watershed
Select best Pareto solution (lowest cost “good” water quality solution)

Calculate watershed:
Check whether the scenario already exists in the history. If it does not exist:

Apply scenario
Calculate watershed by SWAT
Calculate water quality and HRU level load
Save results to history and assign new UUID to history record

Parallelization algorithm

Optimization loop (in file **calculation.py**) is a procedure for parallel computation of independent watersheds during the optimization. The scheme of parallel optimization is explained based on watershed connection shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Scheme of watershed identifiers and watershed connections

Let us assume that no one of watersheds is optimized. Each watershed is characterized by number of not optimized predecessors (upstream watershed) and successors (downstream watershed). In this case the fields NonOptPredCount and NonOptSuccCount have the following values:

washed ID	1	2	3	4
NonOptPredCount	0	0	1	3
NonOptSuccCount	2	1	1	0

Each watershed is associated with the calculation task. All tasks are stored in a sorted list. This list is sorted by "NonOptPredCount" and "NonOptSuccCount" simultaneously.

In presented case the processed watershed list is: [1, 2, 3, 4]. Tasks with "NonOptPredCount"=0 can be calculated simultaneously (in parallel). Just before the job will be started, it should be removed from the list. After the job is completed, its NonOptPredCount and NonOptSuccCount fields are recalculated and new tasks can be selected from the list for calculations. In such a way the longest river will be calculated at first.

3.3 Stored information

Information necessary for the preparation of visualization and restarting of optimization is stored on the hard drive. The watershed calculation folder contains history folder with 2 permanent items – file HISTORY.txt, file HRUCostLoadTable.zip and non-permanent items - calculation records (zip-files).

Summary history file (HISTORY.txt file is located in the history folder) contains 3 sections:

1. Common - contains references to universally unique identifier (UUID) to the following calculation records:
 - 1.1. “Baseline” is UUID to baseline scenario calculation (without optimization)
 - 1.2. “Best” is UUID of calculation
 - 1.3. “Optimal= True” - this field appears in case if watershed is optimized
 - 1.4. “Status” is status of calculation
2. Measures – contains list of calculation references (Measure ID, calculation UUID) which are necessary for the extraction of cost/pollution reduction table ($cost_{m,HRU}$, $PR_{m,HRU}$). Here one measure is applied to all HRU areas for calculation of concentration in SWAT.
3. Pareto – section contains `settings.ParetoPointCount` calculation references for Pareto curve
`HRUCostLoadTable.zip` is compressed file that contains the cost/pollution reduction table ($cost_{m,HRU}$, $PR_{m,HRU}$) and is located in the history folder.
The watershed calculation records are also stored in history folder. Each record is compressed zip archive file which contains:
 - watout.dat - SWAT output file;
 - upstream.txt – UUIDs of calculations of neighbor upstream watersheds;
 - NNO3.txt, Load.txt, LoadReduction.txt – each file contains single number - watershed NO₃ concentration, NO₃ load and load reduction, respectively.
 - HRU.txt - table of measures applied at HRU level and resulting pollution reduction (NO₃) and cost.
 - comments.txt - Comments in text form.

3.4 Folder structure

To perform an optimization task the necessary information and files should be distributed in predefined file structure of modeling system described in PAIC (2014a). New folder \Optimization is added in folder \Setup. Folder \Setup\Optimization is the main folder for performing of the optimization task. Executable python scripts and optimization settings are located in folder \Setup\Optimization\Script. The folder structure presented below is created by running the optimization script. Bold text items point to the directory name or compressed archive. Regular text items points to a file. UUID is universally unique identifier.

settings.setupsDir (default=\Watersheds)

settings.LogFileName (default=**OptimizationLogFile.txt**)

catchments.TWatershed.ProjectName() (for example: \Nemunus\Atmata484)

settings.defaultResSubDir (default=\SWAT)

settings.defaultCaseSubDir (default=\opt)

SWAT files

settings.HistFolder

(default=\CALC_HISTORY)

HISTORY.txt

HRUCostLoadTable.zip

HRUCostLoadTable.txt

Watershed calculation records (for example:
3c075011-9680-11e4-906d-50e54957755a.zip)

watout.dat

upstream.txt

HRU.txt

NNO3.txt
Load.txt

LoadReduction.txt

isBaseLine.txt

comments.txt

3.5. Preparation of output tables for visualization

The main executable script for visualization is **status.py**. The visualization part is independent from the calculation part. It can be run in parallel with calculation by running batch file **runStatus.bat** in \Setup\Optimization\Script folder or manually typing in command line: > **c:\Python26\ArcGIS10.0\python.exe status.py**. Optimization results – tables in form of text files - are placed in the Optimization/results subdirectory. The geodatabase is stored in \Setup\Optimization\Results\results.gdb folder.

Variables for the visualization at HRU level are the following: HRU ID, area [ha], NO₃ load [kg/ha/year], NO₃ load reduction [kg/ha/year], cost of the selected measure [€/ha/year], ID of the selected measure. All available HRU level output variables are listed in CalcHistory.historyHRUVars.

At watershed visualization level the following variables are prepared: status, watershed ID, NO₃ concentration [mg/l], NO₃ load [kg/year], NO₃ load reduction [kg/year]. All available output variables at watershed level are listed in CalcHistory.historyWatershedVars.

Summary tables contain optimization results on the watershed level. Baseline scenarios are depicted in tables “baseline_summary” in GDB format and BaselineSummary.txt in text format and best scenarios – in “best_summary” and “BestSummary.txt”. Table in GDB format “pareto_summary” and in text format “ParetoSummary.txt” contains all points of Pareto curve for catchments that are optimized. Fields in this table are the same as in previous tables, although in this table there are multiple records (each of them corresponding to one point of Pareto curve) with the same watershedID.

VisualizationOptParams.py unit contains procedures, which prepare the output of tables for visualization in GDB and tab delimited text files. The names of procedures and their corresponding returned results (tables) are listed below.

```
ExportSelectedMeasures(watershednamelist, txtFileName)  
return “measures table”
```

```
ExportHRUCatchmentWatershedTable(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName)  
return “hru id table”
```

Watershed level procedures:

```
ExportStatusFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName)  
return “status table”
```

```
ExportBaselineSummaryFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName,  
featureClass,  
historyVars)  
return “summary table”
```

ExportBestSummaryFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName,
historyVars) featureClass,
return "summary table"

ExportParetoSummaryFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName,
historyVars) featureClass,
return "summary table"

ExportZeroMeasureSummaryFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName,
historyVars) featureClass,
return "summary table"

HRU level procedures:

ExportBaselineHRUFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName,
historyVars) featureClass,
return "hru table"

ExportBestHRUFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName,
historyVars) featureClass,
return "hru table"

ExportMeasuresCalcHRUFromHistory(project, watershednamelist, txtFileName,
historyVars) featureClass,
return "hru m table"

Parameters of procedures are:

Project is **catchments.T**Project object

Watershednamelist is list of watershed project name

featureClass is path to the GDB table

txtFileName path to the file table

historyVars is list of selected variables HRU or watershed level

(CalcHistory.historyHRUVars, CalcHistory.historyWatershedVars)

Table type "measures table" ("measures" in GDB format and "Measures.txt" in text format) contains list of measures that are applied during the optimization. Fields of this table are the following:

id - integer identifier of the measure;

name - name of the measure;

Cost - cost of the measure in €/m²;

joined - field representing whether measure are combined from other measures.

Table type "hru id table" ("hru_catchment_id" and "HRUCatchmentID.txt") is the helper table that contains the relations of HRUs to the catchments. Fields of this table are the following:

HRU - integer identifier of HRU

Catchment - integer identifier of catchment

Watershed - integer identifier of watershed

ProjectName - name of SWAT project

It should be noticed that in optimization task the catchments are equal to watersheds, so their identifiers are equal.

Tables “status” and “status.txt” contains per watershed description of current status of optimization run.

Fields of table type “status table” are the following:

WatershedID - watershed identifier;

status - text field representing status. Meaning of values are:

"Good: optimization finished" - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment is below threshold value (2.3 mg/l) after optimization;

"Good: Improved by upstream" - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment is below threshold value (2.3 mg/l) due to optimized upstream catchments;

"best possible solution applied:" - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment is above threshold value (2.3 mg/l) after optimization, the lowest possible concentration value have been chosen, upstream catchment optimization could not improve the obtained result;

"upstream optimisation necessary" - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment is above threshold value (2.3 mg/l) after optimization, the lowest possible concentration value have been chosen, upstream catchment optimization could improve the obtained result ;

"There are NO applicable measures. Best possible solution applied" - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment is above threshold value (2.3 mg/l), but no optimization performed due to inavailability of HRUs targeted at optimization measures;

"good water quality" - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment is below threshold value (2.3 mg/l) without optimization;

"Good: Modifies by upstream" - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment is below threshold value (2.3 mg/l) without optimization, but modified due to upstream catchment optimization;

blank value - optimization not started;

all other values – number of step of the watershed optimization.

Table type “summary table” contains optimization results on the watershed level. The fields of this table are:

WatershedID - watershed identifier that could be joined to catchmentID field of catchment feature class;

CalcID - unique string calculation id that represents the best (optimized) results in this catchment;

Area - total area of HRUs in which measures are performed (m²);

Cost - total cost of applied measures (€);

NO₃Load - total amount of mineral nitrogen load from catchment (kg/year);

NO₃Reduction - difference between total mineral load from catchment in the optimized situation in comparison to baseline situation;

NO₃conc - arithmetic mean concentration of N-NO₃ in the river segment (mg/l).

Table “hru table” contains optimization results on HRU level. The fields of this table are the following:

HRU - integer identifier of HRU.

Measure - integer identifier of measure applied:

Area - area of HRU in ha;

Cost - cost of measure €/ha;

NO₃load - mineral N load in kg/ha/year;

NO₃reduction - reduction of mineral load in comparison to baseline situation (kg/ha/year).

Table type “hru m table” contains optimization results on HRU level. It combines many tables of type “hru table” together adding text string “m{measureID}_" before all column names for each measure.

Once the execution of visualization script is finished, the results can be studied in graphical form in ArcGIS software. For this purpose a mxd file is delivered, which loads all necessary data and links the tables in user friendly environment. The **status.mxd** file contains following layers:

- riverSegments - polyline feature class representing river stretches;
- catchments - polygon feature class representing catchments (watersheds);
- Optimization status - status of optimization per watershed;
- Optimized NO3 concentration - arithmetic mean NO3 concentration per watershed in optimized situation;
- Baseline NO3 concentration - arithmetic mean NO3 concentration per watershed in baseline situation;
- Concentrations - barcharts - concentrations in optimized and baseline situations depicted as bar charts;
- Cost - per watershed cost of optimization measures;
- Measures @ HRU - distribution of measures per HRU.

4. Baseline scenario

This document summarises the definition of the baseline scenario implemented on top of the the Lithuanian water quality model developed for Years 1997-2012.

The basis for the definition of the baseline scenario is the scope of measures prepared by the agricultural expert, see Table 7. Baseline scenario assumes 16 years of calculation by model PAIC (2015) with changed model configuration and/or input data. These changes in model configuration and/or input data are summarised in the following Sections of this Chapter.

Table 7. Set of agricultural measures defining the baseline scenario.

No	Measure	Implementation
1.1	Increase in livestock numbers	Predicted increase – 15 percent from the level of 2012. This will result in higher application of manure, but, considering optimal fertilization, amount of mineral fertilizers should decrease then.
1.2	Increasing area of arable land	Increase of arable land by 2-3 percent in the territories with non-utilized agricultural land
1.3	Changing structure of crop: greening	Areas of perennial grasses and pastures remain at the same level. In the farms with more than 15 ha of arable land 5% of arable land area has to be assigned for fallow or legumes.
1.4	Agri-environmental and climate measures of RDP: 1.4.1. Improving status of water bodies at risk (converting of arable land into perennial grasslands in the basins of water bodies at risk; no application of mineral fertilizers);	Implemented only in the basins of water bodies at risk. Total area of implementation: 8000 ha

No	Measure	Implementation
	1.4.2. Protection of water from pollution and soil erosion in arable land (establishment of additional buffer zones (5-10 m))	Implementation area – 10 000 ha (can applied on the entire territory of Lithuania)
	1.4.3. Protection of water and soil (legumes or perennial grasslands should cover 30 % of farm area in the basins of water bodies at risk and 20% in the remaining territories)	Implementation area – 52 300 ha (i.e. legumes or perennial grasslands will cover 20-30% of this area). Implementation – on the entire territory of Lithuania.
	1.4.4. Other agri-environmental measures: no application of mineral fertilizers.	Approx. 75 849 ha (additionally to the areas of above listed agri-environmental measures).
1.5	Support of organic farming	Area of organic farms (i.e. no application of mineral fertilizers) will increase by 25 000 ha (application – on the entire territory of Lithuania)
1.6	Other RDP measures: Reconstruction of drainage systems.	Increased leaching of nitrates. Area of implementation – 3 298 ha (on drained territories). Implementation of the measure should be considered on 0.5 percent of the drained land.

4.1. Point sources and water users

We assume that point source and water users' data of Year 2012 as prepared in PAIC (2014a) and modified by agricultural expert will be used for all 16 years of baseline calculations.

4.2. Increase in livestock numbers

The baseline measure 1.1 of Table 7 will be implemented by multiplying values of field *livestock_units* in *LIVESTOCK_TABLE* by 1.15, see PAIC (2014a).

4.3. Increase in area of arable land

The baseline measure 1.2 of Table 7 will be implemented as follows:

1. The arable land is assumed to be all land with „LU Class” equal to „Agricultural”.
2. The non-utilized agricultural land is assumed to be the territories with land use SWAT code „RNGB”.
3. The required increase of area of arable land is assumed 3%.
4. The following steps (5-8) are implemented for each subbasin.
5. The total areas of arable land in subbasin A_{al} and non-utilized agricultural land A_{nual} are calculated.
6. The increase of arable land area is set to $I_{al}=3\%*A_{al}$ if $A_{nual}>3\%*A_{al}$ or to $I_{al}=A_{nual}$ otherwise.
7. The area of non-utilized agricultural land is decreased by I_{al} .

8. The area of HRUs for each agricultural land use (crop x) is increased in the subbasin:

$$A_{x\text{-baseline}} = A_{x\text{-present}} * (A_{al} + I_{al}) / A_{al}$$

4.4. Greening

The baseline measure 1.3 of Table 7 will be implemented sequentially after implementation of measure 1.2 as follows:

1. The arable land is assumed to be all land with „LU Class” equal to „Agricultural”, including also area presently assigned for fallow or legumes.
2. The land presently assigned for fallow or legumes is assumed to be the territories with land use SWAT codes „GRBN, LUPN, PEAS, SOYB, VTCH, CLVR”.
3. The following steps (4-9) are implemented for each subbasin.
4. Ratio of area arable land in farms which have more than 15 ha of arable land (A_{al15}) to total area of arable land (A_{al}) is calculated: $f = A_{al15} / A_{al}$
5. The total of land presently assigned for fallow or legumes A_{fl} is calculated.
6. The decrease of arable land area is set to $D_{al} = (5\% - A_{fl} / A_{al}) * A_{al} * f$ if $A_{fl} < 5\% * A_{al}$ or to $D_{al} = 0$ otherwise.
7. The dominant slope/soil type for agricultural land in the subbasin is determined.
 - a. If there exist a HRU with the dominant slope/soil type and the land use SWAT code „CLVR” then its area is increased by D_{al} .
 - b. Otherwise a new HRU is introduced with the dominant slope/soil type and the land use SWAT code „CLVR” and its area is set to D_{al} .
8. The total area of arable land that is not assigned for legumes in subbasin A_{al_NL} is calculated.
9. The area of HRUs for each agricultural land use (crop x) that is not assigned for legumes is decreased in the subbasin:

$$A_{x\text{-baseline}} = A_{x\text{-present}} * (A_{al_NL} - D_{al}) / A_{al_NL}$$

4.5. Converting of arable land into nonfertilised grasslands

The baseline measure 1.4.1 of Table 7 will be implemented sequentially after implementation of measures 1.2 and 1.3 as follows:

1. The arable land is assumed to be all land with „LU Class” equal to „Agricultural”.
2. The area of the arable land in the water bodies at risk⁴ A_{alwbr} is calculated.
3. The conversion rate is calculated as $C_{al} = 8000 \text{ ha} / A_{alwbr}$.

⁴ List of water bodies at risk provided by agricultural expert as GIS layer.

4. The following steps (5-9) are implemented for each subbasin.
5. A new crop type with SWAT land use code „PGWF” is created. It corresponds to perennial grasslands without mineral fertilisation, and its „passport” is given in Table 8.

Table 8. Management practise and parameters for PGWF.

SWAT code		PGWF	
SWAT name		Winter Pasture	
LU class		Pasture	
IDC		6	
Base T		0	
Method		1	
N Demand		120	
P Demand		15.05	
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Manure	0.07	0.35
2	Mowing	0.39	
3	Manure	0.80	0.65

6. The dominant slope/soil type for agricultural land in the subbasin is determined.
7. Total area of arable land in subbasin A_{al} is calculated
8. A new HRU is introduced with the dominant slope/soil type and the land use SWAT code „PGWF” and its area is set to $C_{al} * A_{al}$.
9. The area of HRUs for each agricultural land use (crop x) is decreased in the subbasin

$$A_{x\text{-baseline}} = A_{x\text{-present}} * (1 - C_{al})$$

4.6. Establishment of additional buffer zones

The baseline measure 1.4.2 of Table 7 will be implemented by replacing of formula in Section 2.12 of PAIC (2014a) by $w = k_{bs} * (2 * A / p + 5)$. Effectively it increases the buffer zone width by 5 m elsewhere.

4.7. Increasing areas for legumes and perennial grasslands

The baseline measure 1.4.3 of Table 1 will be implemented sequentially after implementation of measures 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4.1 as follows:

1. The arable land is assumed to be all land with „LU Class” equal to „Agricultural”.
2. The areas of the arable land in the water bodies at risk A_{alwbr} and in the rest of Lithuania – outside the waterbodies at risk A_{alLT} are calculated.
3. The areas of the implementation of the measure will be calculated:

- a. $A_{I-wbr} = 52300 \text{ ha} * A_{alwbr} / (A_{alLT} + A_{alwbr})$ is the implementation area in the water bodies at risk
 - b. Implementation area in the rest of Lithuania is $A_{I-LT} = 52300 \text{ ha} - A_{I-wbr}$.
4. The conversion rates are calculated
 - a. In the water bodies at risk as $C_{al-wbr} = 30\% * A_{I-wbr} / A_{alwbr}$.
 - b. In the rest of Lithuania as $C_{al-LT} = 20\% * A_{I-LT} / A_{alLT}$.
 5. The following steps (6-8) are implemented for each subbasin.
 6. The total area of arable land in subbasin A_{al} is calculated.
 7. The dominant slope/soil type for agricultural land in the subbasin is determined.
 - a. If there exist a HRU with the dominant slope/soil type and the land use SWAT code „PEAS” then its area is increased by $C_{al-wbr} * A_{al}$ in the water bodies at risk or by $C_{al-LT} * A_{al}$ in the rest of Lithuania.
 - b. Otherwise a new HRU is introduced with the dominant slope/soil type and the land use SWAT code „PEAS” and its area is set to $C_{al-wbr} * A_{al}$ in the water bodies at risk or to $C_{al-LT} * A_{al}$ in the rest of Lithuania.
 10. The areas of HRUs for each agricultural land use (crop x) is decreased in subbasin
 - a. In the water bodies at risk as $A_{x-baseline} = A_{x-present} * (1 - C_{al-wbr})$
 - b. In the rest of Lithuania as $A_{x-baseline} = A_{x-present} * (1 - C_{al-LT})$.

4.8. Support of organic farming

The baseline measures 1.4.4 (no-use of mineral fertilisers) and 1.5 (support of organic farming) of Table 7 will be implemented simultaneously. They are implemented after implementation of measures 1.2, 1.3, 1.4.1 and 1.4.3 as follows:

1. The total area fertilized by mineral fertilizers in Lithuania A_F is calculated. It is calculated as total area of land with „LU Class” equal to „Agricultural” and land with landuse „WPAS”.
2. The fertilizer reduction rate is calculated as $C_F = (75849 \text{ ha} + 25000 \text{ ha}) / A_F$.
3. The application of mineral fertiliser (both P and N) is reduced by factor C_F for all applications included in the management practices.

4.9. Reconstruction of drainage system

The baseline measures 1.6 will be implemented as follows:

1. We assume that reconstruction of the drainage system on average reduces the TDRAIN and GDRAIN times by one third, i.e. from 24h to 16h, see PAIC (2014a).

2. Reconstruction of 0.5% of the drain fields thus results in changing the TDRAIN and GDRAIN values from 24.00 h to 23.96 h elsewhere.

5. Agricultural optimisation measures

This Chapter summarises the definition of the agricultural measures used for the optimization of the measures to achieve a better status of water quality in the water bodies of Lithuania.

The implementation of the optimization measures is intended on top of the baseline scenario (see definition Chapter 4) applying a methodics and a tool developed in Chapters 2-3.

The Sections of this Chapter sequentially provides the definition of the agriculturalal measures - “translation” form the ambiguous agricultural definition into deterministic definitions for the implementation in the SWAT modeling system.

The basis for the definition of the optimisation measures is the agricultural definition of these measures prepared by the agricultural expert. Agricultural definitions as discussed in project Consortium and agreed with EPA are given at the beginning of each of the subsequent Sections of this Chapter. They are followed by the deterministic definition of measures – i.e. description of their implementation in SWAT modeling system.

5.1. Catch crops

5.1.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. This measure involves planting of fast growing crop which can be grown simultaneously with, or between successive plantings of a main crop. Suitable catch-crops are oil radish, white or yellow mustard, oil rape, phacelia, clover etc. Catch crop has to be planted right after harvesting of the main crop (usually winter cereals) latest by the mid of August. Intensive growing requires at least 50 days. Catch crop has to be ploughed-in before land is frozen or before planting winter crop.

Further explanation. SWAT code for catch-crop: CANP. Application: in the fields of winter crop (i.e. after winter rye, winter wheat, winter barley, winter triticale). Planting and harvesting scheme will be provided after consulting an agronomist.

5.1.2. Implementation in SWAT

The “catch crop” measure may be used for the winter crops summarised in Table 9. Crop with SWAT ID CANP (Annual grasses) is used as catch crop. Catch crop is planted one day after harvest of the main crop and is removed (using SWAT operation ‘kill’) one day before the main crop is planted.

Table 9: Crops eligible for combining with catch crops.

RYE	Winter rye
WBAR	Winter barley
WTRC	Winter triticale
WWHT	Winter Wheat

The modification of the management practice for involved plants is summarised in Tables 10-13. The original practices and explanations see in the Annex 1. The modifications include:

- All tillage operations that would happen while the catch crop is planted are omitted from the management practice.
- Mineral N amount is reduced by 20% (reduction applied to all applications proportionally);
- Stubble breaking operation is removed.
- Deep ploughing (Tillage ID 109) is performed before planting instead of Soil loosening (Tillage ID 111).

Table 10: Management practise and parameters for RYE

SWAT code	RYE			
SWAT name	Rye			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	95			
P Demand	19.35			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.229	0.40	
2	Nitr	0.383	0.20	
3	Nitr	0.544	0.20	
4	H	1.100		
5	P	0.007	700.00	CANP
6	K	0.788		
7	T	0.005	2.00	
8	Phos	0.005	1.00	
9	Manure	0.005	1.00	
10	P	0.009	1 189.01	

Table 11: Management practise and parameters for WBAR

SWAT code	WBAR			
SWAT name	Winter Barley			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	155			
P Demand	18			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.200	0.40	
2	Nitr	0.467	0.20	
3	Nitr	0.601	0.20	
4	H	1.100		
5	P	0.006	700.00	CANP
6	K	0.810		
7	T	0.005	2.00	
8	Phos	0.005	1.00	
9	Manure	0.005	1.00	
10	P	0.010	1 163.80	

Table 12: Management practise and parameters for WTRC

SWAT code	WTRC			
SWAT name	Winter triticales			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	1			

N Demand		100		
P Demand		21.5		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.122	0.40	
2	Nitr	0.362	0.20	
3	Nitr	0.482	0.20	
4	H	1.100		
5	P	0.006	700.00	CANP
6	K	0.649		
7	T	0.004	2.00	
8	Phos	0.004	1.00	
9	Manure	0.004	1.00	
10	P	0.008	1 288.75	

Table 13: Management practise and parameters for WWHT

SWAT code		WWHT		
SWAT name		Winter Wheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		6		
Method		1		
N Demand		110		
P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.049	0.40	
2	Nitr	0.239	0.20	
3	Nitr	0.351	0.20	
4	H	1.100		

5	P	0.006	700.00	CANP
6	K	0.425		
7	T	0.004	2.00	
8	Phos	0.004	1.00	
9	Manure	0.004	1.00	
10	P	0.008	1 115.21	

5.2. Plant cover in winter

5.2.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. Straw-fields left in the field over the winter after harvest.

Further explanations. Application: for all declared cereal fields. Management: ploughing is allowed not earlier than 1st of March. Then spring crop is planted. No stubble breaking and ploughing after the harvest. No changes in fertilization practices.

5.2.2. Implementation in SWAT

The measure generally can be implemented for summer crops (see Table 14).

Table 14: Crops eligible for leaving plant cover throughout the winter. List of crops and the names of alternative crops created for this measure. CPNUM corresponds to new ID from crop database.

SWAT ID	Name	Alt_name	CPNUM
AGRC	Agricultural land	AGR1	152
BARL	Summer barley	BAR1	135
BWHT	Buckwheat	BWH1	136
CANP	Annual grasses	CAN1	137
CELR	Caraway	CEL1	138
CORN	Corn	COR1	139
CSIL	Corn for silage	CSI1	140
LUPN	Lupine	LUP1	141
OATS	Oats	OAT1	142
SCAN	Summer rape	SCA1	143
SOYB	Soy	SOY1	144
STBR	Summer barley (straw fields)	STB1	145
STCN	Summer rape (straw fields)	STC1	146
STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye	STR1	147
STWH	Summer wheat (straw fields)	STW1	148
SWHT	Summer wheat	SWH1	149
VTCH	Vetch	VTC1	150

The “plant cover” measure was implemented as the following (generalized) scheme for management practice:

- 1) Operation Harvest/Kill (SWAT ID 5) in autumn was replaced with operation Harvest only (SWAT ID 7).
- 2) Any tillage after harvest and in autumn was removed.
- 3) Kill operation (SWAT ID 8) was performed on 30th of March, i.e. shortly before planting of the crop;
- 4) If only the Soil loosening (Tillage SWAT ID 111) was done for original management practice in Spring, the it was replaced with the Autumn tillage type: either Deep ploughing (Tillage SWAT ID 109) or Ploughing (Tillage SWAT ID 1) for the corresponding plant.
- 5) Manure application was done in spring along with Tillage instead of splitting it up between autumn and spring.
- 6) 2 week delay in planting of crops BARL, OATS, SWHT, STBR was applied.

For this measure it was necessary to create an alternative crop for each of the crops used (Table 14). It was necessary, because

1. The original crop type often forced dormancy during winter. Dormancy is undesirable in model because it resets plant heat unit sum to 0 in winter making “Kill” operation evaluation in the plant heat units impossible in spring. Additionally crops with IDC 2 where changed to IDC 1 and all other involved crops where changed to IDC 4; see Annex for definitions of land cover / plant classification.
2. Logistics of SWAT requires that crop is planted (present) at the beginning of year. In regard to all other aspects an alternative crop is identical to original.

Management practice for each crop is provided in Tables 15 – 31. Two additional operations are used for management practice:

- HO – Harvest only operation;
- K – Kill operation.

Table 15: Management practise and parameters for AGRC

SWAT code		AGRC		
SWAT name		Agricultural Land-Close-grown		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		2		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
	1K			
	2T	0.115	4.00	
	3Phos	0.115	1.00	

4	Nitr	0.115	0.30	
5	Manure	0.115	1.00	
6	P	0.124	1 215.09	AGR1
7	Nitr	0.126	0.70	
8	HO	1.100		

Table 16. Management practise and parameters for BARL

SWAT code		BARL		
SWAT name		Spring Barley		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		1		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		17.2		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.080	2.00	
3	Phos	0.080	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.080	0.48	
5	Manure	0.080	1.00	
6	P	0.145	1 512.49	BAR1
7	Nitr	0.164	0.48	
8	Nitr	0.440	0.04	
9	HO	1.100		

Table 17. Management practise and parameters for BWHT.

SWAT code		BWHT		
SWAT name		Buckwheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		37		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.244	2.00	
3	Phos	0.244	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.244	1.00	
5	Manure	0.244	1.00	
6	P	0.256	930.00	BWH1
7	HO	1.100		

Table 18: Management practise and parameters for CANP.

SWAT code		CANP		
SWAT name		Spring Canola-Polish		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		19		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S

1	K			
2	T	0.065	2.00	
3	Cfert	0.065	1.00	
4	Manure	0.065	1.00	
5	P	0.073	859.20	CAN1
6	HO	1.100		

Table 19. Management practise and parameters for CELR.

SWAT code		CELR		
SWAT name		Celery		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		6		
Base T		2		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		17		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.244	2.00	
3	Phos	0.244	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.244	0.96	
5	Manure	0.244	1.00	
6	P	0.256	727.49	CEL1
7	Nitr	0.273	0.04	
8	HO	1.100		

Table 20. Management practise and parameters for CORN.

SWAT code	CORN			
SWAT name	Corn			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.158	2.00	
3	Phos	0.158	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.158	0.70	
5	Manure	0.158	1.00	
6	P	0.167	795.79	COR1
7	Nitr	0.104	0.30	
8	HO	1.200		

Table 21. Management practise and parameters for CSIL

SWAT code	CSIL			
SWAT name	Corn Silage			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	8			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			

OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.065	2.00	
3	Phos	0.065	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.065	0.70	
5	Manure	0.065	1.00	
6	P	0.073	742.87	CSII
7	Nitr	0.191	0.30	
8	HO	1.200		

Table 22. Management practise and parameters for LUPN.

SWAT code	LUPN			
SWAT name	Lupine			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	22			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.061	2.00	
3	Phos	0.061	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.061	0.40	
5	Manure	0.061	1.00	
6	P	0.069	1 243.35	LUP1
7	Nitr	0.146	0.60	
8	HO	1.200		

Table 23. Management practise and parameters for OATS.

SWAT code	OATS			
SWAT name	Oats			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	70			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.061	2.00	
3	Phos	0.061	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.061	0.50	
5	Manure	0.061	1.00	
6	P	0.124	1 714.46	OAT1
7	Nitr	0.104	0.50	
8	HO	1.100		

Table 24. Management practise and parameters for SCAN.

SWAT code	SCAN			
SWAT name	Summer rape			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	25.8			

OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.065	2.00	
3	Phos	0.065	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.065	0.50	
5	Manure	0.065	1.00	
6	P	0.073	1 861.56	SCA1
7	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
8	HO	1.100		

Table 25. Management practise and parameters for SOYB.

SWAT code	SOYB			
SWAT name	Soybean			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	1			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	29			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.208	2.00	
3	Phos	0.208	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.208	1.00	
5	Manure	0.208	1.00	
6	P	0.218	711.30	SOY1
7	HO	1.200		

Table 26. Management practise and parameters for STBR.

SWAT code	STBR			
SWAT name	Summer barley (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.080	3.00	
3	Phos	0.080	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.080	0.48	
5	Manure	0.080	1.00	
6	P	0.145	1 122.16	STB1
7	Nitr	0.148	0.48	
8	Nitr	0.421	0.04	
9	HO	1.100		

Table 27. Management practise and parameters for STCN.

SWAT code	STCN			
SWAT name	Summer rape (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	25.8			

OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.065	3.00	
3	Phos	0.065	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.065	0.50	
5	Manure	0.065	1.00	
6	P	0.073	1 381.23	STC1
7	Nitr	0.138	0.50	
8	HO	1.100		

Table 28. Management practise and parameters for STRC.

SWAT code	STRC			
SWAT name	Summer triticales+summer rye			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	5			
Method	2			
N Demand	75			
P Demand	28			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.061	3.00	
3	Phos	0.061	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.061	0.48	
5	Manure	0.061	1.00	
6	P	0.069	972.46	STR1
7	Nitr	0.178	0.48	
8	Nitr	0.464	0.04	

9HO	1.100		
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Table 29. Management practise and parameters for STWH.

SWAT code	STWH			
SWAT name	Summer wheat (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	95			
P Demand	15.05			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.061	3.00	
3	Phos	0.061	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.061	0.40	
5	Manure	0.061	1.00	
6	P	0.069	1 430.87	STW1
7	Nitr	0.138	0.50	
8	Nitr	0.625	0.10	
9	HO	1.100		

Table 30. Management practise and parameters for SWHT.

SWAT code	SWHT			
SWAT name	Spring Wheat			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			

Method		1		
N Demand		95		
P Demand		15.05		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.061	2.00	
3	Phos	0.061	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.061	0.40	
5	Manure	0.061	1.00	
6	P	0.124	1 935.47	SWH1
7	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
8	Nitr	0.625	0.10	
9	HO	1.100		

Table 31. Management practise and parameters for VTCH.

SWAT code		VTCH		
SWAT name		Vetch		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		2		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		22		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.044	2.00	
3	Phos	0.044	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.044	0.40	
5	Manure	0.044	1.00	
6	P	0.050	1 240.75	VTC1
7	Nitr	0.168	0.60	
8	HO	1.200		

5.3. Planting of winter crops

5.3.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. Winter catch-crop i.e. some type of catch-crop (winter rye, winter rape, winter vetch) left in the field over the winter after harvest.

Further explanations. SWAT code for catch crop: RYE. Application: all declared spring crop-fields. Management: cover crop is ploughed in spring and then spring crop is planted.

5.3.2. Implementation in SWAT

The “winter catch crop” is implemented similarly as “catch crops” measure in Section 5.1. The crops for which RYE can be planted and grown throughout the winter are summarised in Table 32.

Table 32. Crops eligible for combining with winter catch crop (rye).

AGRC	Agricultural land
BARL	Summer barley
BWHT	Buckwheat
CANP	Annual grasses
CELR	Caraway
CORN	Corn
CRRT	Vegetables
CSIL	Corn for silage
GRBN	Beans/ annual legumes
LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
LUPN	Lupine
OATS	Oats
PEAS	Peas
POTA	Potatoes
SCAN	Summer rape
SGBT	Sugar beet
SOYB	Soy
STBR	Summer barley (straw fields)
STCN	Summer rape (straw fields)
STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye
STWH	Summer wheat (straw fields)
SWHT	Summer wheat
VTCH	Vetch

The crop used as catchcrop is Winter rye (SWAT ID: RYE). To avoid dormancy issue (mentioned in Section 5.2.2) a crop RYE1 was introduced. This crop is identical in all parameters with original crop RYE except for IDC number which is changed from 5 to 4. The changes in management practice are as follows (generally):

- No tillage operations in autumn
- All manure is applied in spring (instead of part in spring, part in autumn)

- Spring tillage practice:
 - Planting delayed by ~2 weeks days;
 - Deep ploughing done ~2 weeks before planting;
 - Stubble breaking is done 2-3 weeks before deep ploughing.
- Spring fertilization:
 - Manure – between stubble breaking and deep ploughing;
 - Mineral fertilisation (both P and N) – together with deep ploughing;
- Mineral N amount reduced by 10% (proportionally in all applications).
- RYE Kill operation is performed on 30th of March for all crops.

The modified plant passports are summarised in Tables 33-55.

Table 33. Management practise and parameters for AGRC.

SWAT code		AGRC		
SWAT name		Agricultural Land-Close-grown		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		2		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.057	1.00	
3	Manure	0.091	1.00	
4	T	0.115	2.00	
5	Phos	0.115	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.115	0.27	
7	P	0.184	1 215.09	
8	Nitr	0.126	0.63	
9	H	1.100		
10	P	0.013	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 34. Management practise and parameters for BARL.

SWAT code	BARL			
SWAT name	Spring Barley			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.031	1.00	
3	Manure	0.057	1.00	
4	T	0.080	2.00	
5	Phos	0.080	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.080	0.43	
7	P	0.145	1 512.49	
8	Nitr	0.164	0.43	
9	Nitr	0.440	0.04	
10	H	1.100		
11	P	0.013	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 35. Management practise and parameters for BWHT.

SWAT code	BWHT			
SWAT name	Buckwheat			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	4			

Method		2		
N Demand		37		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.171	1.00	
3	Manure	0.213	1.00	
4	T	0.244	2.00	
5	Phos	0.244	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.244	0.90	
7	P	0.331	930.00	
8	H	1.100		
9	P	0.011	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 36 Management practise and parameters for CANP.

SWAT code		CANP		
SWAT name		Spring Canola-Polish		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		19		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.022	1.00	
3	Manure	0.044	1.00	
4	T	0.065	2.00	

5	Cfert	0.065	1.00	
6	P	0.128	859.20	
7	H	1.100		
8	P	0.013	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 37. Management practise and parameters for CELR.

SWAT code		CELR		
SWAT name		Celery		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		6		
Base T		2		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		17		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.171	1.00	
3	Manure	0.213	1.00	
4	T	0.244	2.00	
5	Phos	0.244	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.244	0.86	
7	P	0.331	727.49	
8	Nitr	0.273	0.04	
9	H	1.100		
10	P	0.013	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 38. Management practise and parameters for CORN.

SWAT code	CORN			
SWAT name	Corn			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.095	1.00	
3	Manure	0.132	1.00	
4	T	0.158	2.00	
5	Phos	0.158	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.158	0.63	
7	P	0.234	795.79	
8	Nitr	0.104	0.27	
9	H	1.200		
10	P	0.011	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 39. Management practise and parameters for CRRT.

SWAT code	CRRT			
SWAT name	Carrot			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	7			
Method	2			

N Demand		105		
P Demand		38		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.091	1.00	
3	Manure	0.128	1.00	
4	T	0.153	2.00	
5	Phos	0.153	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.153	0.90	
7	P	0.229	866.27	
8	H	1.100		
9	P	0.011	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 40. Management practise and parameters for CSIL.

SWAT code		CSIL		
SWAT name		Corn Silage		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		8		
Method		2		
N Demand		140		
P Demand		37		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.022	1.00	
3	Manure	0.044	1.00	
4	T	0.065	2.00	
5	Phos	0.065	1.00	

6	Nitr	0.065	0.63	
7	P	0.128	742.87	
8	Nitr	0.191	0.27	
9	H	1.200		
10	P	0.012	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 41. Management practise and parameters for GRBN.

SWAT code		GRBN		
SWAT name		Green Beans		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		1		
Base T		8		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		23		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.022	1.00	
3	Manure	0.044	1.00	
4	T	0.065	2.00	
5	Phos	0.065	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.065	0.36	
7	P	0.128	742.43	
8	Nitr	0.117	0.54	
9	H	1.200		
10	P	0.012	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 42. Management practise and parameters for LMIX.

SWAT code	LMIX			
SWAT name	Mix of legumes with other crops			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	21			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.022	1.00	
3	Manure	0.044	1.00	
4	T	0.065	2.00	
5	Phos	0.065	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.065	0.36	
7	P	0.128	1 263.59	
8	Nitr	0.151	0.54	
9	H	1.100		
10	P	0.011	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 43. Management practise and parameters for LUPN.

SWAT code	LUPN			
SWAT name	Lupine			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	4			
Method	2			

N Demand		40		
P Demand		22		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.020	1.00	
3	Manure	0.041	1.00	
4	T	0.061	2.00	
5	Phos	0.061	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.061	0.36	
7	P	0.124	1 243.35	
8	Nitr	0.146	0.54	
9	H	1.200		
10	P	0.010	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 44. Management practise and parameters for OATS.

SWAT code		OATS		
SWAT name		Oats		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		1		
N Demand		70		
P Demand		17.2		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.020	1.00	
3	Manure	0.041	1.00	
4	T	0.061	2.00	

5	Phos	0.061	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.061	0.45	
7	P	0.124	1 714.46	
8	Nitr	0.104	0.45	
9	H	1.100		
10	P	0.011	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 45. Management practise and parameters for PEAS.

SWAT code		PEAS		
SWAT name		Garden or Canning Peas		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		2		
Base T		5		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		23		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.022	1.00	
3	Manure	0.044	1.00	
4	T	0.065	2.00	
5	Phos	0.065	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.065	0.36	
7	P	0.128	958.05	
8	Nitr	0.159	0.54	
9	H	1.200		
10	P	0.012	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 46. Management practise and parameters for POTA.

SWAT code	POTA			
SWAT name	Potato			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	7			
Method	1			
N Demand	120			
P Demand	25.8			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.057	1.00	
3	Manure	0.091	1.00	
4	T	0.115	2.00	
5	Phos	0.115	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.115	0.90	
7	P	0.184	852.52	
8	H	1.100		
9	P	0.012	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 47. Management practise and parameters for SCAN.

SWAT code	SCAN			
SWAT name	Summer rape			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	90			

P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.022	1.00	
3	Manure	0.044	1.00	
4	T	0.065	2.00	
5	Phos	0.065	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.065	0.45	
7	P	0.128	1 861.56	
8	Nitr	0.154	0.45	
9	H	1.100		
10	P	0.010	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 48. Management practise and parameters for SGBT.

SWAT code		SGBT		
SWAT name		Sugarbeet		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		1		
N Demand		125		
P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.036	1.00	
3	Manure	0.065	1.00	
4	T	0.088	2.00	
5	Phos	0.088	1.00	

6	Nitr	0.088	0.54	
7	P	0.153	1 400.82	
8	Nitr	0.181	0.36	
9	H	1.100		
10	P	0.009	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 49. Management practise and parameters for SOYB.

SWAT code		SOYB		
SWAT name		Soybean		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		1		
Base T		7		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		29		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.141	1.00	
3	Manure	0.180	1.00	
4	T	0.208	2.00	
5	Phos	0.208	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.208	0.90	
7	P	0.294	711.30	
8	H	1.200		
9	P	0.011	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 50. Management practise and parameters for STBR.

SWAT code	STBR			
SWAT name	Summer barley (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.031	1.00	
3	Manure	0.057	1.00	
4	T	0.080	2.00	
5	Phos	0.080	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.080	0.43	
7	P	0.145	1 122.16	
8	Nitr	0.148	0.43	
9	Nitr	0.421	0.04	
10	H	1.100		
11	P	0.012	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 51. Management practise and parameters for STCN.

SWAT code	STCN			
SWAT name	Summer rape (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	4			

Method		2		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.022	1.00	
3	Manure	0.044	1.00	
4	T	0.065	2.00	
5	Phos	0.065	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.065	0.45	
7	P	0.128	1 381.23	
8	Nitr	0.138	0.45	
9	H	1.100		
10	P	0.010	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 52. Management practise and parameters for STRC.

SWAT code		STRC		
SWAT name		Summer triticales+summer rye		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		5		
Method		2		
N Demand		75		
P Demand		28		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.020	1.00	
3	Manure	0.041	1.00	

4	T	0.061	2.00	
5	Phos	0.061	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.061	0.43	
7	P	0.124	972.46	
8	Nitr	0.178	0.43	
9	Nitr	0.464	0.04	
10	H	1.100		
11	P	0.012	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 53. Management practise and parameters for STWH.

SWAT code		STWH		
SWAT name		Summer wheat (straw fields)		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		95		
P Demand		15.05		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.020	1.00	
3	Manure	0.041	1.00	
4	T	0.061	2.00	
5	Phos	0.061	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.061	0.36	
7	P	0.124	1 430.87	
8	Nitr	0.138	0.45	
9	Nitr	0.625	0.09	

10	H	1.100		
11	P	0.009	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 54. Management practise and parameters for SWHT.

SWAT code		SWHT		
SWAT name		Spring Wheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		1		
N Demand		95		
P Demand		15.05		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.020	1.00	
3	Manure	0.041	1.00	
4	T	0.061	2.00	
5	Phos	0.061	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.061	0.36	
7	P	0.124	1 935.47	
8	Nitr	0.154	0.45	
9	Nitr	0.625	0.09	
10	H	1.100		
11	P	0.009	1 189.01	RYE1

Table 55. Management practise and parameters for VTCH.

SWAT code	VTCH
SWAT name	Vetch

LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		2		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		22		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	K			
2	T	0.011	1.00	
3	Manure	0.029	1.00	
4	T	0.044	2.00	
5	Phos	0.044	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.044	0.36	
7	P	0.103	1 240.75	
8	Nitr	0.168	0.54	
9	H	1.200		
10	P	0.011	1 189.01	RYE1

5.4. Crop rotation

5.4.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. This measure involves changing of crop grown on the same field every year in the period of 4-5 years, for example:

- 1st year: mix of vetch and oat;
- 2nd year: winter wheat;
- 3rd year: clover;
- 4th year: winter rye;
- 5th year: summer barley.

Further explanations. Matrix of rotation may be prepared. Implementation of crop rotations should destroy existing agricultural proportions because implementation of crop rotations requires allocation of equal size fields for each crop in the rotation. I.e. if we have 4 crops in the rotation, area proportion has to be 25%-25%-25%-25%. There can be thousands of different crop rotations depending on the farm type and many other factors. So this measure is very difficult to define. Agricultural expert proposes that one rotation like WWHT-CLVR-RYE-BAR is modelled.

5.4.2. Implementation in SWAT

The optimization methodology described in Chapter 3 of this report assume the optimization measures applied on the HRU basis. Therefore the measure applied in a particular HRU should not affect the pollution loads from the other HRUs.

The crop rotation proposed by agricultural expert is: WWHT -> CANA -> BARL -> PEAS. The eligible crops are the four crops involved in the rotation as well as general agriculture land AGRC.

The following general approach to the management practice is applied:

- The following tillage practise is applied between crops:
 - Stubble breaking right after harvest.
 - Deep ploughing 2-3 weeks after stubble breaking.
 - Soil loosening just before new harvest.
- Manure is applied just as before (for original plants), resulting in years with 0 manure application (when winter crop CANA is harvested, but no other crop is planted) and with years with double manure application (when summer crop PEAS is grown and winter crop WWHT is planted right afte).
- Mineral N application amount is reduced by 20% for WWHT and BARL.
- Planting of CANA is done at the beginning of September (instead of beginning of August)

Management practices for rotation in HRUs are summarised in Table 56 (assuming PEAS as the 1st crop in rotation); it includes new operation: E – end of year.

Table 56. Management practise and parameters for rotation WWHT-CANA-BARL-PEAS.

SWAT code		AGRC		
SWAT name		Agricultural Land-Close-grown		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		2		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	1.00	
2	Phos	0.072	1.00	PEAS
3	Nitr	0.072	0.40	PEAS
4	Manure	0.072	0.35	
5	P	0.079	958.05	PEAS
6	Nitr	0.159	0.60	PEAS

SWAT code		AGRC		
7	H	1.200	0.00	
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	T	0.088	2.00	
10	Manure	0.088	0.65	
11	T	0.210	4.00	
12	Phos	0.210	1.00	WWHT
13	Manure	0.210	1.00	
14	P	0.214	1 018.11	WWHT
15	E			
16	Nitr	0.049	0.40	WWHT
17	Nitr	0.239	0.20	WWHT
18	Nitr	0.351	0.20	WWHT
19	H	1.100	0.00	
20	T	0.006	1.00	
21	T	0.079	2.00	
22	T	0.148	4.00	
23	Phos	0.148	1.00	CANA
24	Nitr	0.148	0.10	CANA
25	Manure	0.148	1.00	
26	P	0.153	1 560.08	CANA
27	E			
28	Nitr	0.314	0.60	CANA
29	Nitr	0.345	0.30	CANA
30	H	1.100	0.00	
31	T	0.007	1.00	
32	T	0.074	2.00	
33	E			

SWAT code		AGRC		
34	T	0.088	4.00	
35	Phos	0.088	1.00	BARL
36	Nitr	0.088	0.38	BARL
37	Manure	0.088	0.35	
38	P	0.094	1 512.49	BARL
39	Nitr	0.164	0.38	BARL
40	Nitr	0.440	0.03	BARL
41	H	1.100	0.00	
42	T	0.006	1.00	
43	T	0.087	2.00	
44	Manure	0.087	0.65	

5.5. Buffer zones

5.5.1. Agricultural definition

This measure involves extension of mandatory buffer zones by 5-10 m.

5.5.2. Implementation in SWAT

The optimization measure is implemented by replacing of formula in Section 2.12 of PAIC (2014a) by $w = k_{bs} * (2 * A / p + 5)$. Effectively it increases the buffer zone width by 5 m for particular HRU.

5.6. Reduced fertilization

5.6.1. Agricultural definition

Reduction of optimal fertilization rate by 10 percent should be considered. Application: for all declared and fertilized crops.

5.6.2. Implementation in SWAT

The use of mineral fertilizers and manure will be multiplied by 0.9. Measure is applicable for HRUs which are fertilized – agricultural land and pastures WPAS.

5.7. Limited fertilization in high-risk areas

5.7.1. Agricultural definition

Reduced fertilization on high-risk areas should be applied. Criteria for definition of high-risk areas should be discussed.

5.7.2. Implementation in SWAT

The use of mineral fertilizers and manure will be multiplied by 0.70. Measure is applicable for HRUs which (1) are fertilized – agricultural land and pastures WPAS and (2) belong to high risk areas. The GIS layer of high-risk areas is provided by agricultural expert.

5.8. No-plough technology

5.8.1. Agricultural definition

This measure comprises field tillage without deep ploughing. Shallow stubble braking is performed twice after the harvest, first time – at the depth of 5-7 cm, later (approx. after 2 weeks) – at the depth of 8-10 cm. Stubble braking is followed by the shallow land cultivation. Deep ploughing has to be performed every 3-4 years.

5.8.2. Implementation in SWAT

Management practice for each year should be the same in SWAT. Therefore the following changes in management practice were introduced:

- Stubble braking after harvest is performed as previously, deep ploughing after it is removed.
- Manure is applied with stubble breaking.

This measure is applicable for the crops summarized in Table 57. New management practice for the affected crops (crop passports) is given in Tables 59-75.

Table 58: List of crops eligible for no-plough technology.

BARL	Summer barley
BWHT	Buckwheat
CANP	Annual grasses
CELR	Caraway
CORN	Corn
CSIL	Corn for silage
LUPN	Lupine
OATS	Oats
SCAN	Summer rape
SOYB	Soy
SWHT	Summer wheat
VTCH	Vetch
CANA	Winter rape
RYE	Rye
WBAR	Winter barley

WTRC	Winter triticale
WWHT	Winter wheat

Table 59: Management practise and parameters for BARL

SWAT code	BARL			
SWAT name	Spring Barley			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.088	4.00	
2	Phos	0.088	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.088	0.48	
4	Manure	0.088	0.35	
5	P	0.094	1 512.49	
6	Nitr	0.164	0.48	
7	Nitr	0.440	0.04	
8	H	1.100	0.00	
9	T	0.006	1.00	
10	Manure	0.006	0.65	

Table 60: Management practise and parameters for BWHT.

SWAT code	BWHT
SWAT name	Buckwheat
LU class	Agricultural
IDC	4

Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		37		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.250	4.00	
2	Phos	0.250	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.250	1.00	
4	Manure	0.250	0.35	
5	P	0.259	930.00	
6	H	1.100	0.00	
7	T	0.006	1.00	
8	Manure	0.006	0.65	

Table 61: Management practise and parameters for CANP.

SWAT code		CANP		
SWAT name		Spring Canola-Polish		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		19		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	
2	Cfert	0.072	1.00	
3	Manure	0.072	0.35	
4	P	0.079	859.20	

5	H	1.100	0.00
6	T	0.006	1.00
7	Manure	0.006	0.65

Table 62: Management practise and parameters for CELR.

SWAT code		CELR		
SWAT name		Celery		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		6		
Base T		2		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		17		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.190	0.48	
2	T	0.250	4.00	
3	Phos	0.250	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.250	0.48	
5	Manure	0.250	0.35	
6	P	0.260	727.49	
7	Nitr	0.273	0.04	
8	H	1.100	0.00	
9	T	0.007	1.00	
10	Manure	0.007	0.65	

Table 63. Management practise and parameters for CORN.

SWAT code	CORN
SWAT name	Corn

LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		7		
Method		2		
N Demand		140		
P Demand		37		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.165	4.00	
2	Phos	0.165	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.165	0.70	
4	Manure	0.165	0.35	
5	P	0.170	795.79	
6	Nitr	0.104	0.30	
7	H	1.200	0.00	
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	Manure	0.006	0.65	

Table 64. Management practise and parameters for CSIL.

SWAT code		CSIL		
SWAT name		Corn Silage		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		8		
Method		2		
N Demand		140		
P Demand		37		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	

2	Phos	0.072	1.00
3	Nitr	0.072	0.70
4	Manure	0.072	0.35
5	P	0.079	742.87
6	Nitr	0.191	0.30
7	H	1.200	0.00
8	T	0.006	1.00
9	Manure	0.006	0.65

Table 65. Management practise and parameters for LUPN.

SWAT code		LUPN		
SWAT name		Lupine		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		2		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		22		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	4.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.40	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	1 243.35	
6	Nitr	0.146	0.60	
7	H	1.200	0.00	
8	T	0.005	1.00	
9	Manure	0.005	0.65	

Table 66. Management practise and parameters for OATS.

SWAT code	OATS			
SWAT name	Oats			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	70			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	4.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.50	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	1 714.46	
6	Nitr	0.104	0.50	
7	H	1.100	0.00	
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	Manure	0.006	0.65	

Table 67. Management practise and parameters for SCAN.

SWAT code	SCAN			
SWAT name	Summer rape			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	90			

P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	
2	Phos	0.072	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.072	0.50	
4	Manure	0.072	0.35	
5	P	0.079	1 861.56	
6	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
7	H	1.100	0.00	
8	T	0.005	1.00	
9	Manure	0.005	0.65	

Table 68. Management practise and parameters for SOYB.

SWAT code		SOYB		
SWAT name		Soybean		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		1		
Base T		7		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		29		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.215	4.00	
2	Phos	0.215	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.215	1.00	
4	Manure	0.215	0.35	
5	P	0.221	711.30	
6	H	1.200	0.00	

7	T	0.006	1.00
8	Manure	0.006	0.65

Table 69. Management practise and parameters for SWHT.

SWAT code		SWHT		
SWAT name		Spring Wheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		1		
N Demand		95		
P Demand		15.05		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	4.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.40	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	1 935.47	
6	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
7	Nitr	0.625	0.10	
8	H	1.100	0.00	
9	T	0.005	1.00	
10	Manure	0.005	0.65	

Table 70. Management practise and parameters for VTCH.

SWAT code		VTCH		
SWAT name		Vetch		
LU class		Agricultural		

IDC					2
Base T					4
Method					2
N Demand					40
P Demand					22
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S	
1	T	0.053	4.00		
2	Phos	0.053	1.00		
3	Nitr	0.053	0.40		
4	Manure	0.053	0.35		
5	P	0.057	1 240.75		
6	Nitr	0.168	0.60		
7	H	1.200	0.00		
8	T	0.005	1.00		
9	Manure	0.005	0.65		

Table 71. Management practise and parameters for CANA.

SWAT code					CANA
SWAT name					Spring Canola-Argentine
LU class					Agricultural
IDC					5
Base T					4
Method					2
N Demand					170
P Demand					27
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S	
1	Nitr	0.314	0.60		
2	Nitr	0.345	0.30		

3	H	1.100	0.00	
4	T	0.007	1.00	
5	Phos	0.063	1.00	
6	Nitr	0.063	0.10	
7	Manure	0.063	1.00	
8	T	0.063	4.00	
9	P	0.070	1 560.08	

Table 72. Management practise and parameters for RYE.

SWAT code		RYE		
SWAT name		Rye		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		1		
N Demand		95		
P Demand		19.35		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.229	0.50	
2	Nitr	0.383	0.25	
3	Nitr	0.544	0.25	
4	H	1.100	0.00	
5	T	0.007	1.00	
6	T	0.252	4.00	
7	Phos	0.252	1.00	
8	Manure	0.252	1.00	
9	P	0.259	1 189.01	

Table 73. Management practise and parameters for WBAR.

SWAT code	WBAR			
SWAT name	Winter Barley			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	155			
P Demand	18			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.200	0.50	
2	Nitr	0.467	0.25	
3	Nitr	0.601	0.25	
4	H	1.100	0.00	
5	T	0.006	1.00	
6	T	0.255	4.00	
7	Phos	0.255	1.00	
8	Manure	0.255	1.00	
9	P	0.265	1 163.80	

Table 74. Management practise and parameters for WTRC.

SWAT code	WTRC			
SWAT name	Winter triticales			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	1			

N Demand		100		
P Demand		21.5		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.122	0.50	
2	Nitr	0.362	0.25	
3	Nitr	0.482	0.25	
4	H	1.100	0.00	
5	T	0.006	1.00	
6	T	0.213	4.00	
7	Phos	0.213	1.00	
8	Manure	0.213	1.00	
9	P	0.218	1 288.75	

Table 75. Management practise and parameters for WWHT.

SWAT code		WWHT		
SWAT name		Winter Wheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		6		
Method		1		
N Demand		110		
P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.049	0.50	
2	Nitr	0.239	0.25	
3	Nitr	0.351	0.25	
4	H	1.100	0.00	
5	T	0.006	1.00	

6T	0.148	4.00	
7Phos	0.148	1.00	
8Manure	0.148	1.00	
9P	0.154	1 115.21	

5.9. Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing

5.9.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. Land is cultivated in spring instead of autumn cultivation. Measure is not applicable for medium to heavy soils.

Additional description. Application: all declared spring-crop fields. Not applied on heavy soils.

5.9.2. Implementation in SWAT

Land cultivation in autumn is replaced by land cultivation in spring – before the crop planting.

This measure is carried out for sandy soils only according to the division of the soils additionally provided by soil expert (Table 76).

This measure can be implemented for all summer crops except for those that had no autumn ploughing originally as there was nothing to change. See the list of eligible crops in Table 77. The changes in management practice involve:

- Any ploughing (ID 109 or ID 1) is done in spring 2 weeks before ploughing.
- All manure is applied with ploughing in spring.

The management practices for eligible crops are summarised in Tables 78-97.

Table 76. Classification of soils. Sandy (L) and medium to heavy (S) soils.

Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S
ADb-g4	L	GLn1	S	J1b2	S	RDg4-k2	S
ADb-g5	L	GLv-k	S	J1b2-e1	S	RDg8-k1	S
ADb-y	S	GLv-p	S	J1b2-e2	S	RDg8-k2	S
ADb2	L	GLv-s	L	J1g8-b	S	RDk1	S
ADd-p	L	IDg4-k	S	J1g8-n	S	RDk1-e1	S
ADk-g4	L	IDg4-n1	S	J1n-g0	S	RDk1-g0	S
ADk-g5	L	IDg4-p	S	J1n2	S	RDk2	S
ADk-p	L	IDg8-k	S	PDa2	L	RDk2-e1	S
ADk-s	L	IDg8-n1	S	PDa2-(n)	L	RDk2-g0	S
ADn-g4	L	IDg8-p	S	PDt1	L	SDg4-b	L
ADn-g5	L	IDk-g0	S	PDt2	L	SDg4-n	L
ADn1	L	IDk-p	S	PDt2-(n)	L	SDg8-b	L
ADv-p	L	IDk-p-e1	S	PDz1	L	SDg8-k	L
ADv-u	L	IDk-p-e2	S	PDz2	L	SDg8-n	L
GLb-y	S	IDp-n1	S	PDz2-(n)	L	SDk-p	L

GLb-s	L	IDp-n1-g0	S	PLb-g4	S	SDp-b	L
GLb2	S	IDp-t	S	PLb2	S	SDp-b-e2	L
GLd-p	S	IDp-t-e1	S	PLn-g4	L	SDp-b-g0	L
GLd-s	L	IDp-t-e2	S	PLn1	L	SDp-n	L
GLk-s	L	IDp-t-g0	S	PRb2	S	SDp-n-g0	L
GLk1	S	JDg8-t	S	PRk-p-(e3)	S		
GLk2	S	Jlb-g0	S	RDb2	S		

Table 77. Crop list eligible for substitution of autumn ploughing with spring ploughing.

AGRC	Agricultural land	LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
ALFA	Perennial legumes	LUPN	Lupine
BARL	Summer barley	OATS	Oats
BWHT	Buckwheat	PEAS	Peas
CANP	Annual grasses	POTA	Potatoes
CELR	Caraway	SCAN	Summer rape
CORN	Corn	SGBT	Sugar beet
CRRT	Vegetables	SOYB	Soy
CSIL	Corn for silage	SWHT	Summer wheat
GRBN	Beans/ annual legumes	VTCH	Vetch

Table 78. Management practise and parameters for AGRC.

SWAT code		AGRC		
SWAT name		Agricultural Land-Close-grown		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		2		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.076	3.00	
2	T	0.123	4.00	
3	Phos	0.123	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.123	0.30	
5	Manure	0.123	1.00	

6P	0.131	1 215.09	
7Nitr	0.126	0.70	
8H	1.100		

Table 79. Management practise and parameters for ALFA.

SWAT code	ALFA			
SWAT name	Alfalfa			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	3			
Base T	4			
Method	1			
N Demand	0			
P Demand	12.9			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.095	3.00	
2	T	0.144	4.00	
3	Phos	0.144	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.144	0.40	
5	Manure	0.144	1.00	
6	P	0.150	1 383.57	
7	Nitr	0.054	0.60	
8	H	1.000		

Table 80. Management practise and parameters for BARL.

SWAT code	BARL
SWAT name	Spring Barley
LU class	Agricultural
IDC	5

Base T		0		
Method		1		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		17.2		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.048	2.00	
2	T	0.088	4.00	
3	Phos	0.088	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.088	0.48	
5	Manure	0.088	1.00	
6	P	0.094	1 512.49	
7	Nitr	0.164	0.48	
8	Nitr	0.440	0.04	
9	H	1.100		
10	T	0.006	1.00	

Table 81. Management practise and parameters for BWHT.

SWAT code		BWHT		
SWAT name		Buckwheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		37		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.191	2.00	
2	T	0.250	4.00	

3	Phos	0.250	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.250	1.00	
5	Manure	0.250	1.00	
6	P	0.259	930.00	
7	H	1.100		
8	T	0.006	1.00	

Table 82. Management practise and parameters for CANP.

SWAT code		CANP		
SWAT name		Spring Canola-Polish		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		19		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.038	2.00	
2	T	0.072	4.00	
3	Cfert	0.072	1.00	
4	Manure	0.072	1.00	
5	P	0.079	859.20	
6	H	1.100		
7	T	0.006	1.00	

Table 83 Management practise and parameters for CELR.

SWAT code	CELR
SWAT name	Celery

LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	6			
Base T	2			
Method	2			
N Demand	60			
P Demand	17			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.191	2.00	
2	T	0.250	4.00	
3	Phos	0.250	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.250	0.96	
5	Manure	0.250	1.00	
6	P	0.260	727.49	
7	Nitr	0.273	0.04	
8	H	1.100		
9	T	0.007	1.00	

Table 84. Management practise and parameters for CORN.

SWAT code	CORN			
SWAT name	Corn			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.115	2.00	

2	T	0.165	4.00	
3	Phos	0.165	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.165	0.70	
5	Manure	0.165	1.00	
6	P	0.170	795.79	
7	Nitr	0.104	0.30	
8	H	1.200		
9	T	0.006	1.00	

Table 85. Management practise and parameters for CRRT.

SWAT code		CRRT		
SWAT name		Carrot		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		7		
Method		2		
N Demand		105		
P Demand		38		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.111	3.00	
2	Manure	0.111	1.00	
3	Phos	0.160	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.160	1.00	
5	P	0.168	866.27	
6	H	1.100		

Table 86. Management practise and parameters for CSIL.

SWAT code	CSIL			
SWAT name	Corn Silage			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	8			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.038	2.00	
2	T	0.072	4.00	
3	Phos	0.072	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.072	0.70	
5	Manure	0.072	1.00	
6	P	0.079	742.87	
7	Nitr	0.191	0.30	
8	H	1.200		
9	T	0.006	1.00	

Table 87. Management practise and parameters for GRBN.

SWAT code	GRBN			
SWAT name	Green Beans			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	1			
Base T	8			
Method	2			

N Demand		40		
P Demand		23		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.038	3.00	
2	Manure	0.038	1.00	
3	Phos	0.072	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.072	0.40	
5	P	0.079	742.43	
6	Nitr	0.117	0.60	
7	H	1.200		

Table 88. Management practise and parameters for LMIX.

SWAT code		LMIX		
SWAT name		Mix of legumes with other crops		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		2		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		21		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.038	3.00	
2	Manure	0.038	1.00	
3	Phos	0.072	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.072	0.40	
5	P	0.079	1 263.59	
6	Nitr	0.151	0.60	
7	H	1.100		

Table 89. Management practise and parameters for LUPN.

SWAT code	LUPN			
SWAT name	Lupine			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	22			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.035	2.00	
2	T	0.069	4.00	
3	Phos	0.069	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.069	0.40	
5	Manure	0.069	1.00	
6	P	0.076	1 243.35	
7	Nitr	0.146	0.60	
8	H	1.200		
9	T	0.005	1.00	

Table 90. Management practise and parameters for OATS.

SWAT code	OATS			
SWAT name	Oats			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	70			

P Demand		17.2		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.035	2.00	
2	T	0.069	4.00	
3	Phos	0.069	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.069	0.50	
5	Manure	0.069	1.00	
6	P	0.076	1 714.46	
7	Nitr	0.104	0.50	
8	H	1.100		
9	T	0.006	1.00	

Table 91. Management practise and parameters for PEAS.

SWAT code		PEAS		
SWAT name		Garden or Canning Peas		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		2		
Base T		5		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		23		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.038	3.00	
2	Manure	0.038	1.00	
3	Phos	0.072	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.072	0.40	
5	P	0.079	958.05	
6	Nitr	0.159	0.60	

7H	1.200		
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Table 92. Management practise and parameters for POTA.

SWAT code	POTA			
SWAT name	Potato			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	7			
Method	1			
N Demand	120			
P Demand	25.8			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.076	3.00	
2	Manure	0.076	1.00	
3	Phos	0.123	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.123	1.00	
5	P	0.130	852.52	
6	H	1.100		

Table 93. Management practise and parameters for SCAN.

SWAT code	SCAN			
SWAT name	Summer rape			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	25.8			

OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.038	2.00	
2	T	0.072	4.00	
3	Phos	0.072	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.072	0.50	
5	Manure	0.072	1.00	
6	P	0.079	1 861.56	
7	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
8	H	1.100		
9	T	0.005	1.00	

Table 94 Management practise and parameters for SGBT.

SWAT code	SGBT			
SWAT name	Sugarbeet			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	4			
Method	1			
N Demand	125			
P Demand	25.8			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.053	3.00	
2	Manure	0.053	1.00	
3	Phos	0.095	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.095	0.60	
5	P	0.103	1 400.82	
6	Nitr	0.181	0.40	
7	H	1.100		

Table 95. Management practise and parameters for SOYB.

SWAT code	SOYB			
SWAT name	Soybean			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	1			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	29			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.160	2.00	
2	T	0.215	4.00	
3	Phos	0.215	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.215	1.00	
5	Manure	0.215	1.00	
6	P	0.221	711.30	
7	H	1.200		
8	T	0.006	1.00	

Table 96. Management practise and parameters for SWHT.

SWAT code	SWHT			
SWAT name	Spring Wheat			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	95			
P Demand	15.05			

OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.035	2.00	
2	T	0.069	4.00	
3	Phos	0.069	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.069	0.40	
5	Manure	0.069	1.00	
6	P	0.076	1 935.47	
7	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
8	Nitr	0.625	0.10	
9	H	1.100		
10	T	0.005	1.00	

Table 97. Management practise and parameters for VTCH.

SWAT code	VTCH			
SWAT name	Vetch			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	22			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.026	2.00	
2	T	0.053	4.00	
3	Phos	0.053	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.053	0.40	
5	Manure	0.053	1.00	
6	P	0.057	1 240.75	

7	Nitr	0.168	0.60	
8	H	1.200		
9	T	0.005	1.00	

5.10. Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn

5.10.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. This is a method for sandy soils only..

Additional description. Ploughing has to be postponed to the end of October or beginning of November. Application: can be applied for all spring crops.

5.10.2. Implementation in SWAT

Deep Ploughing (Tillage SWAT ID: 109) and the associated manure application were postponed to late autumn - end of October or beginning of November.

This measure was carried out for sandy soils only, see Table 76. It is applicable to the crops summarized in Table 98.

To carry out this measure mean fraction of base 0 heat units required for management operation was calculated for the calendar interval 20.10-10.11. Crop management practice was updated accordingly, see Tables 99-110.

Table 98. List of crops eligible for sod-ploughing in late autumn.

BARL	Summer barley	LUPN	Lupine
BWHT	Buckwheat	OATS	Oats
CANP	Annual grasses	SCAN	Summer rape
CELR	Caraway	SOYB	Soy
CORN	Corn	SWHT	Summer wheat
CSIL	Corn for silage	VTCH	Vetch

Table 99. Management practise and parameters for BARL.

SWAT code	BARL
SWAT name	Spring Barley
LU class	Agricultural
IDC	5
Base T	0
Method	1
N Demand	90

P Demand		17.2		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.088	4.00	
2	Phos	0.088	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.088	0.48	
4	Manure	0.088	0.35	
5	P	0.094	1 512.49	
6	Nitr	0.164	0.48	
7	Nitr	0.440	0.04	
8	H	1.100	0.00	
9	T	0.006	1.00	
10	Manure	0.297	0.65	
11	T	0.297	2.00	

Table 100. Management practise and parameters for BWHT.

SWAT code		BWHT		
SWAT name		Buckwheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		37		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.250	4.00	
2	Phos	0.250	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.250	1.00	
4	Manure	0.250	0.35	

5	P	0.259	930.00	
6	H	1.100	0.00	
7	T	0.006	1.00	
8	Manure	0.249	0.65	
9	T	0.249	2.00	

Table 101. Management practise and parameters for CANP.

SWAT code		CANP		
SWAT name		Spring Canola-Polish		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		4		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		60		
P Demand		19		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	
2	Cfert	0.072	1.00	
3	Manure	0.072	0.35	
4	P	0.079	859.20	
5	H	1.100	0.00	
6	T	0.006	1.00	
7	Manure	0.445	0.65	
8	T	0.445	2.00	

Table 102. Management practise and parameters for CELR.

SWAT code	CELR
SWAT name	Celery

LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	6			
Base T	2			
Method	2			
N Demand	60			
P Demand	17			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.190	0.48	
2	T	0.250	4.00	
3	Phos	0.250	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.250	0.48	
5	Manure	0.250	0.35	
6	P	0.260	727.49	
7	Nitr	0.273	0.04	
8	H	1.100	0.00	
9	T	0.007	1.00	
10	Manure	0.392	0.65	
11	T	0.392	2.00	

Table 103. Management practise and parameters for CORN.

SWAT code	CORN
SWAT name	Corn
LU class	Agricultural
IDC	4
Base T	7
Method	2
N Demand	140
P Demand	37

OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.165	4.00	
2	Phos	0.165	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.165	0.70	
4	Manure	0.165	0.35	
5	P	0.170	795.79	
6	Nitr	0.104	0.30	
7	H	1.200	0.00	
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	Manure	0.261	0.65	
10	T	0.261	2.00	

Table 104. Management practise and parameters for CSIL.

SWAT code	CSIL			
SWAT name	Corn Silage			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	8			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	
2	Phos	0.072	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.072	0.70	
4	Manure	0.072	0.35	
5	P	0.079	742.87	
6	Nitr	0.191	0.30	

7	H	1.200	0.00	
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	Manure	0.267	0.65	
10	T	0.267	2.00	

Table 105. Management practise and parameters for LUPN.

SWAT code		LUPN		
SWAT name		Lupine		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		2		
Base T		4		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		22		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	4.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.40	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	1 243.35	
6	Nitr	0.146	0.60	
7	H	1.200	0.00	
8	T	0.005	1.00	
9	Manure	0.205	0.65	
10	T	0.205	2.00	

Table 106. Management practise and parameters for OATS.

SWAT code	OATS			
SWAT name	Oats			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	70			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	4.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.50	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	1 714.46	
6	Nitr	0.104	0.50	
7	H	1.100	0.00	
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	Manure	0.243	0.65	
10	T	0.243	2.00	

Table 107. Management practise and parameters for SCAN.

SWAT code	SCAN			
SWAT name	Summer rape			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	0			
Method	1			

N Demand		90		
P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	
2	Phos	0.072	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.072	0.50	
4	Manure	0.072	0.35	
5	P	0.079	1 861.56	
6	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
7	H	1.100	0.00	
8	T	0.005	1.00	
9	Manure	0.179	0.65	
10	T	0.179	2.00	

Table 108. Management practise and parameters for SOYB.

SWAT code		SOYB		
SWAT name		Soybean		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		1		
Base T		7		
Method		2		
N Demand		40		
P Demand		29		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.190	0.60	
2	T	0.215	4.00	
3	Phos	0.215	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.215	0.40	

5	Manure	0.215	0.35
6	P	0.221	711.30
7	H	1.200	0.00
8	T	0.006	1.00
9	Manure	0.346	0.65
10	T	0.346	2.00

Table 109. Management practise and parameters for SWHT.

SWAT code		SWHT		
SWAT name		Spring Wheat		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		1		
N Demand		95		
P Demand		15.05		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	4.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.40	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	1 935.47	
6	Nitr	0.154	0.50	
7	Nitr	0.625	0.10	
8	H	1.100	0.00	
9	T	0.005	1.00	
10	Manure	0.156	0.65	
11	T	0.156	2.00	

Table 110. Management practise and parameters for VTCH.

SWAT code	VTCH			
SWAT name	Vetch			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	22			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.053	4.00	
2	Phos	0.053	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.053	0.40	
4	Manure	0.053	0.35	
5	P	0.057	1 240.75	
6	Nitr	0.168	0.60	
7	H	1.200	0.00	
8	T	0.005	1.00	
9	Manure	0.221	0.65	
10	T	0.221	2.00	

5.11. Converting arable land into perennial grasslands

5.11.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. Changing from intensive agriculture to extensive grassland.

Additional description. SWAT code WPAS.

5.11.2. Implementation in SWAT

This measure is implementable in HRUs with any Agricultural land use type. These HRU were converted to perennial pastures (SWAT code WPAS) using the initial management practice for WPAS.

5.12. Converting arable land and grasslands to forests

5.12.1. Agricultural definition

Afforestation of arable land and/or grasslands.

5.12.2. Implementation in SWAT

This measure is implementable in HRUs with any Agricultural or Pasture land use type. These HRU were converted to mixed forests (SWAT code FRST).

5.13. Combined measures

Some of the measures defined in Sections 5.1-5.12 can be combined with other measures while some of them cannot. The combination of several measures is considered as additional (independent) measure in methodology developed in Chapter 2. The increase of number of measures increases the time required for running measure optimisation. Therefore a list of combination included in the optimisation was prepared by agricultural expert, see Table 111. *Table 111. List of combined pollution reduction measures for optimisation.*

#	Measure #1	Measure #2	Measure #3
1	Catch crops	Reduced fertilization	
2	Plant cover in winter	Buffer zones	
3	Plant cover in winter	Buffer zones	Limited fertilization in HRA
4	Plant cover in winter	Limited fertilization in HRA	
5	Winter crops	Reduced fertilization	
6	Crop rotation	Reduced fertilization	
7	Buffer zones	Crop rotation	
8	Buffer zones	Limited fertilization in HRA	
9	Buffer zones	Crop rotation	Limited fertilization in HRA
10	Reduced fertilization	No-plough technology	
11	Limited fertilization in HRA	Catch crops	
12	Limited fertilization in HRA	Catch crops	Buffer zones
13	No-plough technology	Limited fertilization in HRA	
14	Postponing ploughing	Buffer zones	
15	Postponing ploughing	Reduced fertilization	
16	Postponing ploughing	Buffer zones	Reduced fertilization
17	No-plough technology	Reduced fertilization	Buffer zones

5.14. Cost table

The annual mean costs for each of measures defined in Sections 5.1-5.12 was prepared by economic expert and expressed in EUR per m² per annum, see Table 112. The cost of combined measures (Section 5.13) was assumed to be equal to the sum of costs of involved measures.

Table 112. Annual cost of agricultural pollution reduction measures.

#	Name	Cost, Euro/m ²
1	Catch crops	0.0087
2	Plant cover in winter	0.0058
3	Planting of winter crops	0.0022
4	Crop rotation	0.0000
5	Buffer zones	0.0002
6	Reduced fertilization	0.0004
7	Limited fertilization on high risk areas	0.0001
8	Non-plough technology	-0.0051
9	Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing	0.0014
10	Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn	0.0006
11	Converting arable land into perennial grasslands	0.0248
12	Converting arable land and grasslands to forests	0.0175

6. Optimisation

The optimisation runs were performed according to the TOR 3.5.1. According to TOR 3.5.1.1 the spatial optimization of diffuse agricultural pollution reduction measures were performed taking into account the principle of cost-effectiveness as defined in Section 5.14. The spatial optimization of pollution reduction measures was carried out according to methodology described in Chapter 3 and by tool described in Chapter 4 (according to TOR 3.5.1.1.2) in all water basins where the water status did not meet the status of good condition due to agriculture pollution by nitrate concentrations as by base line scenario (according to TOR 3.5.1.1.1); namely, where the mean N-NO₃ instream concentration exceeded 2.3 mg/l. The optimization was performed only for the reduction of pollution by nitrates according to TOR 3.5.1.1.3.

Twelve pollution reduction measures defined in Sections 5.1-5.12 were included in the first optimisation run in Section 6.1. Additionally, 17 combined measures of Section 5.13 were added for the optimisation run in Section 6.2.

6.1. Basic pollution reduction measures

Twelve pollution reduction measures defined in Sections 5.1-5.12 were included in the first optimisation run in this Section.

Figure 20. In-stream concentration of nitrates (mg/l) for the baseline scenario.

The optimisation results are illustrated in the following Figures.

- The subbasins coloured by the in-stream N-NO₃ concentrations are shown in Figures 20-21 – for the baseline scenario, i.e. before the optimisation in Figure 20, and after the optimisation in Figure 21. The orange and red colors in Figure 20 correspond to the subbasins where optimisation is required (N-NO₃ concentration exceed 2.3 mg/l).

Figure 21. In-stream concentration of nitrates (mg/l) after optimisation run.

Figure 22. Optimisation status overview.

- The same colors in Figure 21 indicate the subbasins where the optimisation targets are not reached in terms of good water quality. It can be noticed that most of such places are downstream the towns with substantial pollution point sources.
- The optimisation overview is presented in Figure 22. The subbasins are coloured according to the optimisation results in this Figure; there are a total of 1237 subbasins:
 - The light blue are subbasins which were not optimised because of good water quality in baseline scenario (831 out of 1237 subbasins or 67%).
 - The darker blue are the [downstream] subbasins which were not optimised because of good water quality in baseline scenario, and which were further improved by optimisation of the upstream subbasins. 106 subbasins fall in this category; it is 8.6% of total.
 - The light green are subbasins for which the optimisation of pollution reduction measures were applied reaching the water quality targets via the optimum set of measures. 173 subbasins fall in this category; it is 14% of total or 57.5% of initially bad subbasins.
 - The darker green are the [downstream] subbasins which had bad water quality in baseline scenario; for these subbasins the water quality targets was achieved without optimisation measures via the improvement of the upstream subbasins. 18 subbasins fall in this category; it is 1.5% of total or 6% of initially bad subbasins.
 - The pink are subbasins where are no HRU for which the applicable measures of water pollution reduction are possible. 2 subbasins fall in this category; it is 0.2% of total or 0.7% of initially bad subbasins.
 - The red are subbasins for which the best combination of measures is applied but the outflowing water quality still does not reach the target values AND there is no upstream catchment to improve. The optimisation is finished for these subbasins reaching the optimums set of possible measures. 40 subbasins fall in this category; it is 3.2% of total or 13.3% of initially bad subbasins.
 - The purple are subbasins for which the best combination of measures is applied but the outflowing water quality still does not reach the target values AND there are upstream catchments to consider for reiterations according to optimisation methodics. The reiteration is not performed because the effect of point sources to the water quality is evident. 67 subbasins fall in this category; it is 5.5% of total or 22.6% of initially bad subbasins.
- The distribution of the total costs of the selected set of measures for each subbasin is shown in Figure 23. One may notice that “negative cost measures” are selected for the subbasins where the minor improvements of water quality was necessary. The costly measures are applied in subbasins where the reaching of water quality targets proved impossible including the subbasins downstream the major point sources.
- The example of Pareto curve (“Cost vs Load reduction”) as well as curve (“Cost vs Outflowing N-NO₃ concentration”) is shown in Figure 24. The set of measure with total financial income is selected as optimum here. Note, that baseline scenario situation (Zero load reduction at Zero cost) is well below the Pareto (Blue) line and, respectively, well above the red line (baseline concentration at Zero cost).
- The map of the distribution of the optimum measures on the HRU level is shown in Figure 25. 8 out of 12 measures are considered as optimum at least in some of the HRUs.

Figure 23. Total cost of optimum pollution measures (EUR).

Figure 24. Illustration of Pareto Curve for arbitrary catchment.

Figure 25. Distribution of the optimum measures on the HRU level.

6.2. Combined pollution reduction measures

Twelve pollution reduction measures defined in Sections 5.1-5.12 and 17 combined measures of Section 5.13 were included in the second optimisation run in this Section.

The optimisation results are illustrated in the following Figures.

- The subbasins coloured by the in-stream N-NO₃ concentrations are shown in Figures 20 and 26 – for the baseline scenario, i.e. before the optimisation in Figure 20, and after the optimisation in Figure 26. Comparison of Figures 21 and 26 show generally the same in-stream water quality pattern. Combined measures did not allow improvement of water quality downstream the pollution point sources and generally also in central northern area. The optimisation allow for improvement is several subbasins of southwestern Lithuania.
- The optimisation overview is presented in Figure 27. The subbasins are coloured according to the optimisation results in this Figure, see the description of colour scheme is Section 6.2. Comparing Figures 27 and 22 indicates minor differences which show that for the point-of view of improving water quality the use of single or combined measures makes a little difference. It also indicates that the optimisation tool produces rather robust and stable results. The summary of optimisation status is given also in Table 113. It can be seen that the in-stream water quality has changed a status to “good” for 7 catchments – all of them are the ones where upstream improvements are not longer necessary.
- The distribution of the total costs of the selected set of measures for each subbasin is shown in Figure 28. Comparison with Figure 23 shows that introduction of the combined pollution reduction measures decreases the overall expenses.

- The map of the distribution of the optimum measures on the HRU level is shown in Figure 29. 8 out of 12 single measures and 13 out of 17 combined measures are considered as optimum at least in some of the HRUs.

Figure 26. In-stream concentration of nitrates (mg/l) after optimisation run.

Figure 27. Optimisation status overview.

Table 113. Optimisation summary. Total number of subbasins 1237.

#	Optimisation status	1 st run (simple)	2 nd run (combined)
1	Good quality in baseline	831	831
1a	Further improved	106	106
3	Optimised reaching target	173	177
4	Target reached by upstream measures	18	21
5	No measures possible	2	2
6	Target not reached, upstream measures not possible	40	40
7	Target not reached, upstream measures possible	67	60

Figure 28. Total cost of optimum pollution measures (EUR).

Figure 29. Distribution of the optimum measures on the HRU level.

7. Scenario modelling

The scenarios modeling of selected structural changes in agriculture must be carried out according to TOR 3.5.2. Although TOR 3.5.2.1.1 suggests that at least two small basins (from 100 to 1000 km²) of regions with different hydrological characteristics where agriculture dominates must be selected for scenario modeling it is more logical to run scenario modeling for the whole territory of Lithuania and then focus on result analysis for particular catchments. Agricultural definitions of ambiguous scenarios prescribed by TOR are given at the beginning of each of the subsequent Sections of this Chapter as discussed in project Consortium and agreed with EPA. They are followed by the deterministic definition of scenarios – i.e. description of their implementation in SWAT modeling system.

7.1. Innovative farming

7.1.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. TOR 3.5.2.1.3 requests that the "innovative farming" scenario must evaluate effects of adapting recommendations of innovative farming rules on the water pollution. The document for innovative farming that ToR refers to (http://www.zum.lt/documents/PUTP_leidiny_2007.pdf) is old (2007) and in some cases contradicts to the current environmental requirements. However, some requirements perhaps could be modelled. These are:

1. Crop rotations to prevent soil erosion in hilly landscape:
 - Perennial grasslands should cover 35-40 % of the farm area when slope is less than 5°
 - Perennial grasslands should cover at least 50 % of the farm area when slope is less than 5-7°
 - Perennial grasslands should cover 65-80 % of the farm area when slope is less than 7-10°
 - Only perennial grasslands should be grown when slope 7-10°
2. Winter crop (including catch crop) should cover at least 50 % of the area in the farms having more than 15 ha of arable land.
3. Optimum use of fertilizers has to be considered (i.e. no over-fertilisation).
4. No fertilisation on frozen land (i.e. when land has been frozen for longer than 12 hours).
5. Postponing of ploughing to late autumn.
6. Catch crops (summer).
7. Winter catch crop.

Further explanation. The initial definitions are rather ambiguous and were further elaborated by agricultural expert and agreed with EPA:

1. Converting of arable land into grasslands (p.1) should not be considered because the rather flat basins should be selected according to TOR 3.5.2.1.1.
2. Winter crop (including winter catch crop, p.2) is realised automatically with the measures in pp.6-7.
3. Optimum use of fertilisers (p.3) is already considered in the calibrated and validated modelling system.

4. Fertilisation on frozen land (p.4) is an example of bad agricultural practice which is not included in the calibrated and validated model.
5. Postponing of ploughing to late autumn (p.5) contradicts the introduction of winter catch crop (p.7). Therefore it should be applied for specific crops CANP, CORN, CRRT, CSIL, GRBN, LMIX, LUPN, PEAS, POTA, SGBT, and VTCH.
6. The “innovative farming” scenario should be introduced on top of contemporary situation as opposed to baseline scenario.

7.1.2. Implementation in SWAT

The innovative farming scenario was define in the SWAT model as follows:

- Optimisation measure „Catch crops” was introduced elsewhere as described in Section 5.1.
- Optimisation measure „Planting of winter crops” was introduced elsewhere for crops AGRC, BARL, BWHT, CELR, OATS, SCAN, SOYB, STBR, STCN, STRC, STWH, and SWHT as described in Section 5.3.
- Optimisation measure „Postponing of sod ploughing to late autumn” was introduced similar to Section 5.10 but
 - for all soils (originally only for sandy);
 - for eligible plants CANP, CORN, CRRT, CSIL, GRBN, LMIX, LUPN, PEAS, POTA, SGBT, VTCH;
 - the new management practices were introduced for crops CRRT, GRBN, LMIX, PEAS, POTA and SGBT which were not considered in Section 5.10, see Tables 114-119.

Table 114. Management practise and parameters for CRRT.

SWAT code	CRRT			
SWAT name	Carrot			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	105			
P Demand	38			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Phos	0.160	1.00	
2	Nitr	0.160	1.00	
3	Manure	0.160	0.35	
4	P	0.168	866.27	
5	H	1.100		
6	T	0.237	3.00	
7	Manure	0.237	0.65	

Table 115. Management practise and parameters for GRBN.

SWAT code	GRBN		
SWAT name	Green Beans		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	1		
Base T	8		
Method	2		
N Demand	40		
P Demand	23		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Phos	0.072	1.00
2	Nitr	0.072	0.40
3	Manure	0.072	0.35
4	P	0.079	742.43
5	Nitr	0.117	0.60
6	H	1.200	
7	T	0.267	3.00
8	Manure	0.267	0.65

Table 116. Management practise and parameters for LMIX.

SWAT code	LMIX		
SWAT name	Mix of legumes with other crops		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	2		
Base T	4		
Method	2		
N Demand	40		
P Demand	21		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Phos	0.072	1.00
2	Nitr	0.072	0.40
3	Manure	0.072	0.35
4	P	0.079	1 263.59
5	Nitr	0.151	0.60
6	H	1.100	
7	T	0.243	3.00
8	Manure	0.243	0.65

Table 117. Management practise and parameters for PEAS.

SWAT code	PEAS
SWAT name	Garden or Canning Peas

LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	2		
Base T	5		
Method	2		
N Demand	40		
P Demand	23		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Phos	0.072	1.00
2	Nitr	0.072	0.40
3	Manure	0.072	0.35
4	P	0.079	958.05
5	Nitr	0.159	0.60
6	H	1.200	
7	T	0.303	3.00
8	Manure	0.303	0.65

Table 118. Management practise and parameters for POTA.

SWAT code	POTA		
SWAT name	Potato		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	7		
Method	1		
N Demand	120		
P Demand	25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Phos	0.123	1.00
2	Nitr	0.123	1.00
3	Manure	0.123	0.35
4	P	0.130	852.52
5	H	1.100	
6	T	0.273	3.00
7	Manure	0.273	0.65

Table 119. Management practise and parameters for SGBT.

SWAT code	SGBT		
SWAT name	Sugarbeet		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	4		
Base T	4		
Method	1		
N Demand	125		

P Demand		25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Phos	0.095	1.00	
2	Nitr	0.095	0.60	
3	Manure	0.095	0.35	
4	P	0.103	1 400.82	
5	Nitr	0.181	0.40	
6	H	1.100		
7	T	0.156	3.00	
8	Manure	0.156	0.65	

7.2. Optimal use of fertilisers

7.2.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. TOR 3.5.2.1.4 requests that the "the optimal use of fertilizers" scenario must evaluate the cost-optimal, use rates of fertilizers determined by agronomists. Optimal fertilization rates proposed by agronomists have been considered when estimating application of mineral fertilizers and setting up SWAT model in PAIC (2014a).

Further explanation. The fertilisation rates were corrected during the model calibration in PAIC (2014b). Optimal fertilization scenario should be modelled by removing fertilizer correction coefficients if it is expected that optimal use of fertilizers will increase the fertilization level.

7.2.2. Implementation in SWAT

The "the optimal use of fertilizers" scenario was defined in the SWAT model by applying the nitrate fertilization rates of PAIC (2014a).

7.3. Ecological farming

7.3.1. Agricultural definition

Initial definition. TOR 3.5.2.1.5 requests that the "ecological farming" scenario must evaluate the impact of the change of ecological farming on the water bodies. Similarly TOR 3.5.2.1.6 requests that "agriculture based on the principles of ecological agriculture" scenario must evaluate the impact of changes in agricultural farms for water bodies. The principles of ecological agriculture involve

1. Crop rotation.
2. Winter catch crop.
3. No application of mineral fertilizers (manure only). Minimum amount of N from manure - 70 kg/year. Maximum application of N – 170 kg/year.

Further explanation. 7-year crop rotation with modified fertilisation and management practices should be introduced.

Table 120. Management and fertilization practice for 7-year crop rotation of ecological farming.

OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S	MON	DAY
1	P	0.079	958.05	PEAS		
2	H	1.200				
3	T	0.006	3.00			
4	T	0.124	4.00			
5	P	0.129		RYE		
6	E					
7	H	1.100				
8	T	0.007	1.00			
9	Manure	0.097	90.00	FIXED		
10	T	0.097	2.00			
11	E					
12	T	0.088	4.00			
13	P	0.094	1 512.49	BARL		
14	H	1.100				
15	P	0.006	700.00	CANP		
16	K	0.772				
17	T	0.001	2.00			
18	E					
19	T	0.088	4.00			
20	P	0.094	1 512.49	BARL		
21	H	1.100				
22	T	0.006	1.00			
23	T	0.087	2.00			
24	E					
25	P			CLVR	4	5
26	Mowing				10	15
27	E					
28	Manure		80.00	FIXED	4	15
29	Mowing				6	30
30	Mowing				8	15
31	K				10	30
32	T	0.001	2.00			
33	E					
34	T	0.250	4.00			
35	P	0.259	930.00	BWHT		
36	H	1.100				
37	T	0.006	1.00			
38	T	0.079	2.00			

7.3.2. Implementation in SWAT

The "ecological farming" scenario was defined in the SWAT model by introducing the 7-year crop rotation on all arable land. The management practice which corresponds to this farming is summarised in Table 120. PEAS – RYE – BARL (with CANP catch crop) – BARL – CLVR – CLVR – BWHT.

Some differences to standard operations used in plant passports (see Annex) are introduced. These differences are:

- Clover management is carried out using calendar dates as mowing makes changes to accumulated PHU amounts that are too complicated to evaluate beforehand.
- Manure application is not based on livestock amount, but on the crop demands. These demands are as follows:
 - 90 kg/ha of nitrogen (sum of mineral and organic) for BARL, applied in autumn of the year before planting.
 - 80 kg/ha of nitrogen for CLVR, applied in spring of the second growth year.

8. Electronic deliverables

Electronic deliverables with the 4th Interim report consist of the updated SWAT water quality modeling system and the results of optimization. The principal structure of SWAT water quality modeling system is described in PAIC (2014a). It is electronically delivered as a data archive. Un-archiving of it creates a folder structure in **MAINPATH** (folders *Data*, *DataBY*, *lib*, *SETUP* and *SetupBY*, see the description in PAIC (2014a).

The water quality modeling system is generated automatically by executing the script *main.py* (or running *run10.bat* executable file) from folders *Setup/Scripts* and *SetupBY/Scripts* for Lithuania and Belarus setups, respectively. The calculation of all watersheds by SWAT is also performed automatically by the script. After running of the script the SWAT setup and results for each of the watersheds will be located under subdirectory *SWAT/results_v20150223*.

The baseline scenario and corresponding SWAT results could be obtained by running script *baseline.py* (or running *run_baseline.bat* executable file) from folder *Setup/Scripts*. After running of the script the SWAT setup and results for each of the watersheds will be located under subdirectory *SWAT/baseline*.

The optimization tool is included with SWAT water quality modeling system according to TOR 3.3.3.2. Principal library modules of optimization tool are included in *lib/py* subdirectory. List of modules with their description is provided in Section 3.1 of this report. The directory of *SETUP/Optimization* is the main folder of optimization tool. The structure of this folder is described in Section 3.4 of this report. Subdirectory *SETUP/Optimization/Script* contains main scripts and executables of the optimization tool. Running of the script *SpatialOptimization.py* (or executing *runOpt.bat* file) invokes the optimization tool.

Results of the optimization (i.e. the results obtained in Chapter 6) are provided as an archive of *SETUP/Optimization/Watersheds* folder *watersheds_optimization.zip*. This archive includes optimization history files for each of the catchments. Running of optimization script is not necessary for assessing and analysing of this [already performed] optimisation run. Un-archiving it in *SETUP/Optimization/Watersheds* folder allows running of script *status.py* (located under *SETUP/Optimization/Script*) which visualizes optimization results. The files generated by visualization script are located in subdirectory *SETUP/Optimization/Results*. The structure of files generated by visualization script is described in Section 3.5 of this report.

9. Supplementary agricultural measures

9.1. Scope of supplementary agricultural measures

This Chapter summarises the definition of the supplementary agricultural measures and their implementation in the SWAT modeling system.

The implementation of the supplementary measures is intended on top of the baseline scenario (see definition in Chapter 4).

There are 3 groups of the supplementary agricultural measures according to the list prepared by the agricultural expert:

1. Group 1 – “Obligatory national-scale measures”.
2. Group 2 – “Subsidized agronomic measures”.
3. Group 3 – “Engineering measures”.

The Sections 9.2-9.4 of this Chapter sequentially provides the definition of the supplementary agricultural measures for these three groups – “translation” from the sometimes ambiguous agricultural definition into deterministic definitions for the implementation in the SWAT modeling system.

Figure 30. Distribution of supplementary agricultural measures in SWAT model catchments.

The basis for the definition of the optimisation measures is the agricultural definition of these measures prepared by the agricultural expert. Agricultural definitions as discussed in project Consortium and agreed with EPA are given at the beginning of each of the subsequent Sections of this Chapter. They are followed by the deterministic definition of measures – i.e. description of their implementation in SWAT modeling system.

The supplementary agricultural measures of groups 2 and 3 are applied on the catchments of water bodies at risk which will not achieve good status after implementation of all obligatory measures. The areas of their application were prepared by agricultural expert, see Figure 30.

9.2. Obligatory national-scale measures

9.2.1. Agricultural definition

There are two obligatory national-scale measures referred further as 1a and 1b:

- a. Obligation to have fertilization plans for all farmers having more than 50 ha of arable land. This measure does not require implementation in SWAT modelling system.
- b. Obligation to cover at least 10 percent of farms arable land with catch-crops for all farms having more than 50 ha of arable land.

Agricultural expert suggested that the measure 1b should be interpreted as optimisation measure “Planting of winter catch crops”, see Section 5.3.

9.2.2. Implementation in SWAT

The implementation of measure 1b in SWAT modeling system was done as follows:

1. Total area of arable land in eligible catchment A_a was determined.
2. Supplementary measure 1b was implemented if applicable in catchment. Total area of HRUs that are eligible for optimization measure 5.3 was determined A_{53} .
3. Fraction $f_{53} = \min(1.0; 0.1 \cdot A_a / A_{53})$ of implementation of optimization measure 5.3 was calculated.
4. Each HRU eligible for optimisation measure 5.3 was duplicated; area of respective HRU is A_{HRU} .
5. Area of each new HRU was set to $f_{53} \cdot A_{HRU}$, and optimisation measure 5.3 was implemented.
6. Area of each existing HRU was reduced to $(1 - f_{53}) \cdot A_{HRU}$.

9.3. Subsidized agronomic measures

9.3.1. Agricultural definition

There are three subsidized agronomic measures referred further as 2a, 2b and 2c:

- a. Growing of catch-crops in the farms having less than 50 ha of arable land (target – 15 percent of farm area). Additional areas of catch-crops in the farms having more than 50 ha of arable land (target – 25 percent of farms area consisting of 10 percent obligatory measure 1b and additional 15 percent subsidized).
- b. Crop rotations with 20-30 percent of legumes or perennial grasses (target – rotations applied on 25 percent of total arable land).
- c. No tillage in 20 percent of arable land.

Agricultural expert suggested that

- a. The measure 2a should be interpreted as optimisation measure “Planting of winter catch crops”, see Section 5.3.
- b. The measure 2b should be interpreted as optimisation measure “Crop rotation”, see

Section 5.4.

- c. The measure 2c should be interpreted as optimisation measure “No-plough technology”, see Section 5.8.

9.3.2. Implementation in SWAT

The implementation of measure 2a in SWAT modeling system was done as follows:

1. Total area of arable land in eligible catchment A_a was determined.
2. Supplementary measure 2a was implemented if applicable in catchment. Total area of HRUs that are eligible for optimization measure 5.3 was determined A_{53} .
3. Fraction $f_{50ha} = A_{50ha} / A_a$ and area A_{50ha} of arable land in catchment belonging to farms having more than 50 ha of arable land were calculated.
4. Fraction $f_{53} = \min(1.0; (0.15 * (1 - f_{50ha}) + 0.25 * f_{50ha}) * A_a / A_{53})$ of implementation of optimization measure 5.3 was calculated.
5. Each HRU eligible for optimisation measure 5.3 was duplicated; area of respective HRU is A_{HRU} .
6. Area of each new HRU was set to $f_{53} * A_{HRU}$, and optimisation measure 5.3 was implemented.
7. Area of each existing HRU was reduced to $(1 - f_{53}) * A_{HRU}$.

The implementation of measure 2b in SWAT modeling system was done as follows:

1. Total area of arable land in eligible catchment A_a was determined.
2. Supplementary measure 2b was implemented if applicable in catchment. Total area of HRUs that are eligible for optimization measure 5.4 was determined A_{54} . The new HRUs created by implementation of measures 1b and 2a are not considered eligible for measure 2b.
3. Fraction $f_{54} = \min(1.0; 0.25 * A_a / A_{54})$ of implementation of optimization measure 5.4 was calculated.
4. Each HRU eligible for optimisation measure 5.4 was duplicated; area of respective HRU is A_{HRU} .
5. Area of each new HRU was set to $f_{54} * A_{HRU}$, and optimisation measure 5.4 was implemented.
6. Area of each existing HRU was reduced to $(1 - f_{54}) * A_{HRU}$.

9.4. Engineering measures

9.4.1. Agricultural definition

There are two engineering measures referred further as 3a and 3b:

- a. Reconstruction of drainage systems, i.e. construction of small retention ponds at the outlets of drainage pipes (approximately 1 are of pond per 15 ha of drained land). Agricultural expert provided the input data – areas of ponds in polygons.
- b. Construction of artificial wetlands. Wetland areas were estimated individually for each water body and provided by agricultural expert.

9.4.2. Implementation in SWAT

Both engineering measures are subbasin level measures.

The implementation of measure 3a in SWAT modeling system was done by adding additional pond area and volume in SWAT pond files .pnd as follows:

1. The fraction of additional pond area per catchment area was calculated. From this fraction it is possible to determine area of additional ponds (A_{ponds}) in each catchment.
2. Variables PND_PSA and PND_ESA (surface areas of ponds in subbasin) were increased by A_{ponds} .
3. Volumes of ponds were modified as follows:
 - a. PND_PVOL was increased by $2 * A_{\text{ponds}}$,
 - b. PND_EVOL was increased by $3 * A_{\text{ponds}}$.

The implementation of measure 3b in SWAT modeling system was done implemented by adding additional wetland area and volume in SWAT pond files .pnd as follows:

1. The fraction of additional wetland area per catchment area was calculated. From this fraction it is possible to determine area of additional wetlands (A_{wetl}) in each catchment.
2. Variables WET_NSA and WET_MXSA (surface areas of wetlands in subbasin) were increased by A_{wetl} .
3. Volumes of wetlands were modified as follows:
 - a. WET_NVOL was increased by $2 * A_{\text{wetl}}$,
 - b. WET_MXVOL was increased by $3 * A_{\text{wetl}}$.

9.5. Modeling results for supplementary measures

The modelling results for supplementary agricultural measures were electronically supplied as

MODELLING_SYSTEM/SWAT_2014/Results_20150609_scenario_supplementary/.

The results are illustrated in Figures 31-32 as the ratio of the in-stream concentrations of nitrate nitrogen (Figure 31) and phosphate phosphorus (Figure 32) between the supplementary measure scenario and baseline scenario.

Figure 31. Distribution of the ratio of the in-stream concentrations of nitrate nitrogen between the supplementary measure scenario and baseline scenario.

Figure 32. Distribution of the ratio of the in-stream concentrations of phosphate phosphorus between the supplementary measure scenario and baseline scenario.

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Annex 1. Management practice for crops in SWAT model

The annex contains a summary of management practice for all agricultural crops and pastures used with SWAT model, PAIC (2014a,b).

Explanation for information given in the crop Tables is as follows.

Crop description

LU class – land use class

IDC – Land cover/plant classification (taken from SWAT 2012 documentation, p.188)

1	Warm season annual legume
2	Cold season annual legume
3	Perennial legume
4	Warm season annual
5	Cold season annual
6	Perennial
7	Trees

Base T – Base temperature

Method – Required mineral fertilizer calculation method. Method 1 takes into account soil parameters, manure (livestock amount) and regional statistics for yield. Method 2 makes adjustment only based on manure.

N demand – Mineral Nitrogen demand for standard yield, kg/ha.

P demand – Mineral Phosphorus demand for standard yield, kg/ha.

Management description:

OPNPK – management operation order number

OPTYPE – operation type

- T – tillage operation;
- P – planting operation;
- H – harvest operation;
- HO – harvest only operation;
- K – kill operation (If HU amount is not shown in the passport, Kill operation is carried out on 30th of March);
- E – end of year operation;
- Phos – Mineral Phosphorus application;
- Nitr – Mineral Nitrogen application;
- Manure – Manure application;
- Mowing – Mowing, is applied only on pastures.
- Cfert – Continuous fertilization of Nitrogen, used only for WPAS and continued for 90 days

HU – fraction of HU or PHU units when operation is carried out. For operation done after planting till harvest fraction of PHU is used. For period when plant is not planted – fraction of yearly HU.

VALUE – depends on operation, see Table below.

Operation	Meaning of column VALUE
T	type of tillage (for example, ploughing or stubble breaking)
P	amount of PHU required for plant growth
H	-
HO	-
K	-
E	-
Phos	fraction of total required mineral Phosphorus amount to be applied
Nitr	fraction of total required mineral Nitrogen amount to be applied
Manure	fraction of total manure amount to be applied
Mowing	-
Cfert	fraction of total required mineral Nitrogen amount to be applied

VALUE_S – Provided only in specific cases. Depends on operation, see Table below:

Operation	Meaning of column VALUE
P	Planted plant
Phos	Shows for what plant should mineral P fertilizer be calculated.
Nitr	Shows for what plant should mineral N fertilizer be calculated.

Table 1: Management practise and parameters for AGRC

SWAT code		AGRC		
SWAT name		Agricultural Land-Close-grown		
LU class		Agricultural		
IDC		5		
Base T		0		
Method		2		
N Demand		90		
P Demand		15		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.123	4.00	
2	Phos	0.123	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.123	0.30	
4	Manure	0.123	0.35	
5	P	0.131	1 215.09	
6	Nitr	0.126	0.70	
7	H	1.100		
8	T	0.007	3.00	
9	Manure	0.094	0.65	

Table 2: Management practise and parameters for ALFA

SWAT code	ALFA		
SWAT name	Alfalfa		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	3		
Base T	4		
Method	1		
N Demand	0		
P Demand	12.9		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	T	0.144	4.00
2	Phos	0.144	1.00
3	Nitr	0.144	0.40
4	Manure	0.144	0.35
5	P	0.150	1 383.57
6	Nitr	0.054	0.60
7	H	1.000	
8	T	0.005	3.00
9	Manure	0.067	0.65

Table 3: Management practise and parameters for BARL

SWAT code	BARL		
SWAT name	Spring Barley		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	0		
Method	1		
N Demand	90		
P Demand	17.2		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	T	0.088	4.00
2	Phos	0.088	1.00
3	Nitr	0.088	0.48
4	Manure	0.088	0.35
5	P	0.094	1 512.49
6	Nitr	0.164	0.48
7	Nitr	0.440	0.04
8	H	1.100	
9	T	0.006	1.00
10	T	0.087	2.00
11	Manure	0.087	0.65

Table 4: Management practise and parameters for BWHT

SWAT code	BWHT			
SWAT name	Buckwheat			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	37			
P Demand	15			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.250	4.00	
2	Phos	0.250	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.250	1.00	
4	Manure	0.250	0.35	
5	P	0.259	930.00	
6	H	1.100		
7	T	0.006	1.00	
8	T	0.079	2.00	
9	Manure	0.079	0.65	

Table 5: Management practise and parameters for CANA

SWAT code	CANA			
SWAT name	Spring Canola-Argentine			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	170			
P Demand	27			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.314	0.60	
2	Nitr	0.345	0.30	
3	H	1.100		
4	T	0.007	1.00	
5	T	0.063	4.00	
6	Phos	0.063	1.00	
7	Nitr	0.063	0.10	
8	Manure	0.063	1.00	
9	T	0.069	2.00	
10	P	0.070	1 560.08	

Table 6: Management practise and parameters for CANP

SWAT code	CANP			
SWAT name	Spring Canola-Polish			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	60			
P Demand	19			
OPNPKO	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	
2	Cfert	0.072	1.00	
3	Manure	0.072	0.35	
4	P	0.079	859.20	
5	H	1.100		
6	T	0.006	1.00	
7	T	0.099	2.00	
8	Manure	0.099	0.65	

Table 7: Management practise and parameters for CELR

SWAT code	CELR			
SWAT name	Celery			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	6			
Base T	2			
Method	2			
N Demand	60			
P Demand	17			
OPNPKO	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.190	0.48	
2	T	0.250	4.00	
3	Phos	0.250	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.250	0.48	
5	Manure	0.250	0.35	
6	P	0.260	727.49	
7	Nitr	0.273	0.04	
8	H	1.100		
9	T	0.007	1.00	
10	T	0.095	2.00	
11	Manure	0.095	0.65	

Table 8: Management practise and parameters for CORN

SWAT code	CORN			
SWAT name	Corn			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.165	4.00	
2	Phos	0.165	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.165	0.70	
4	Manure	0.165	0.35	
5	P	0.170	795.79	
6	Nitr	0.104	0.30	
7	H	1.200		
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	T	0.081	2.00	
10	Manure	0.081	0.65	

Table 9: Management practise and parameters for CRRT

SWAT code	CRRT			
SWAT name	Carrot			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	105			
P Demand	38			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Phos	0.160	1.00	
2	Nitr	0.160	1.00	
3	Manure	0.160	0.35	
4	P	0.168	866.27	
5	H	1.100		
6	T	0.006	3.00	
7	Manure	0.077	0.65	

Table 10: Management practise and parameters for CSIL

SWAT code	CSIL			
SWAT name	Corn Silage			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	8			
Method	2			
N Demand	140			
P Demand	37			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	4.00	
2	Phos	0.072	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.072	0.70	
4	Manure	0.072	0.35	
5	P	0.079	742.87	
6	Nitr	0.191	0.30	
7	H	1.200		
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	T	0.082	2.00	
10	Manure	0.082	0.65	

Table 11: Management practise and parameters for GRBN

SWAT code	GRBN			
SWAT name	Green Beans			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	1			
Base T	8			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	23			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Phos	0.072	1.00	
2	Nitr	0.072	0.40	
3	Manure	0.072	0.35	
4	P	0.079	742.43	
5	Nitr	0.117	0.60	
6	H	1.200		
7	T	0.006	3.00	
8	Manure	0.091	0.65	

Table 12: Management practise and parameters for LMIX

SWAT code	LMIX		
SWAT name	Mix of legumes with other crops		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	2		
Base T	4		
Method	2		
N Demand	40		
P Demand	21		
OPNPKO	TYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Phos	0.072	1.00
2	Nitr	0.072	0.40
3	Manure	0.072	0.35
4	P	0.079	1 263.59
5	Nitr	0.151	0.60
6	H	1.100	
7	T	0.006	3.00
8	Manure	0.078	0.65

Table 13: Management practise and parameters for LUPN

SWAT code	LUPN		
SWAT name	Lupine		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	2		
Base T	4		
Method	2		
N Demand	40		
P Demand	22		
OPNPKO	TYPE	HU	VALUE
1	T	0.069	4.00
2	Phos	0.069	1.00
3	Nitr	0.069	0.40
4	Manure	0.069	0.35
5	P	0.076	1 243.35
6	Nitr	0.146	0.60
7	H	1.200	
8	T	0.005	1.00
9	T	0.072	2.00
10	Manure	0.072	0.65

Table 14: Management practise and parameters for OATS

SWAT code	OATS			
SWAT name	Oats			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	70			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	4.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.50	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	1 714.46	
6	Nitr	0.104	0.50	
7	H	1.100		
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	T	0.078	2.00	
10	Manure	0.078	0.65	

Table 15: Management practise and parameters for PEAS

SWAT code	PEAS			
SWAT name	Garden or Canning Peas			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	5			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	23			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Phos	0.072	1.00	
2	Nitr	0.072	0.40	
3	Manure	0.072	0.35	
4	P	0.079	958.05	
5	Nitr	0.159	0.60	
6	H	1.200		
7	T	0.006	3.00	
8	Manure	0.088	0.65	

Table 16: Management practise and parameters for POTA

SWAT code	POTA			
SWAT name	Potato			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	7			
Method	1			
N Demand	120			
P Demand	25.8			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Phos	0.123	1.00	
2	Nitr	0.123	1.00	
3	Manure	0.123	0.35	
4	P	0.130	852.52	
5	H	1.100		
6	T	0.006	3.00	
7	Manure	0.083	0.65	

Table 17: Management practise and parameters for RYE

SWAT code	RYE			
SWAT name	Rye			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	95			
P Demand	19.35			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.229	0.50	
2	Nitr	0.383	0.25	
3	Nitr	0.544	0.25	
4	H	1.100		
5	T	0.007	1.00	
6	T	0.097	2.00	
7	T	0.252	4.00	
8	Phos	0.252	1.00	
9	Manure	0.252	1.00	
10	P	0.259	1 189.01	

Table 18: Management practise and parameters for SCAN

SWAT code	SCAN		
SWAT name	Summer rape		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	4		
Base T	0		
Method	1		
N Demand	90		
P Demand	25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	T	0.072	4.00
2	Phos	0.072	1.00
3	Nitr	0.072	0.50
4	Manure	0.072	0.35
5	P	0.079	1 861.56
6	Nitr	0.154	0.50
7	H	1.100	
8	T	0.005	1.00
9	T	0.066	2.00
10	Manure	0.066	0.65

Table 19: Management practise and parameters for SGBT

SWAT code	SGBT		
SWAT name	Sugarbeet		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	4		
Base T	4		
Method	1		
N Demand	125		
P Demand	25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Phos	0.095	1.00
2	Nitr	0.095	0.60
3	Manure	0.095	0.35
4	P	0.103	1 400.82
5	Nitr	0.181	0.40
6	H	1.100	
7	T	0.005	3.00
8	Manure	0.062	0.65

Table 20: Management practise and parameters for SOYB

SWAT code	SOYB			
SWAT name	Soybean			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	1			
Base T	7			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	29			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.190	0.60	
2	T	0.215	4.00	
3	Phos	0.215	1.00	
4	Nitr	0.215	0.40	
5	Manure	0.215	0.35	
6	P	0.221	711.30	
7	H	1.200		
8	T	0.006	1.00	
9	T	0.092	2.00	
10	Manure	0.092	0.65	

Table 21: Management practise and parameters for SRYE

SWAT code	SRYE			
SWAT name	Summer Rye			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	5			
Method	1			
N Demand	95			
P Demand	19.35			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	3.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.48	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	972.46	
6	Nitr	0.178	0.48	
7	Nitr	0.464	0.04	
8	H	1.100		
9	Manure	0.092	0.65	

Table 22: Management practise and parameters for STBR

SWAT code	STBR			
SWAT name	Summer barley (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	17.2			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.088	3.00	
2	Phos	0.088	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.088	0.48	
4	Manure	0.088	0.35	
5	P	0.094	1 122.16	
6	Nitr	0.148	0.48	
7	Nitr	0.421	0.04	
8	H	1.100		
9	Manure	0.088	0.65	

Table 23: Management practise and parameters for STCN

SWAT code	STCN			
SWAT name	Summer rape (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	4			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	90			
P Demand	25.8			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.072	3.00	
2	Phos	0.072	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.072	0.50	
4	Manure	0.072	0.35	
5	P	0.079	1 381.23	
6	Nitr	0.138	0.50	
7	H	1.100		
8	Manure	0.067	0.65	

Table 24: Management practise and parameters for STRC

SWAT code	STRC			
SWAT name	Summer triticales+summer rye			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	5			
Method	2			
N Demand	75			
P Demand	28			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.069	3.00	
2	Phos	0.069	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.069	0.48	
4	Manure	0.069	0.35	
5	P	0.076	972.46	
6	Nitr	0.178	0.48	
7	Nitr	0.464	0.04	
8	H	1.100		
9	Manure	0.092	0.65	

Table 25: Management practise and parameters for STRY

SWAT code	STRY			
SWAT name	Rye (straw fields)			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	95			
P Demand	19.35			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.144	0.50	
2	Nitr	0.411	0.25	
3	Nitr	0.544	0.25	
4	H	1.100		
5	T	0.266	3.00	
6	Phos	0.266	1.00	
7	Manure	0.266	1.00	
8	P	0.275	1 162.13	

Table 26: Management practise and parameters for STTR

SWAT code	STTR		
SWAT name	Winter triticales (straw fields)		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	4		
Method	2		
N Demand	100		
P Demand	21.5		
OPNPKO	TYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Nitr	0.122	0.50
2	Nitr	0.362	0.25
3	Nitr	0.482	0.25
4	H	1.100	
5	T	0.213	3.00
6	Phos	0.213	1.00
7	Manure	0.213	1.00
8	P	0.218	1 288.75

Table 27: Management practise and parameters for STWH

SWAT code	STWH		
SWAT name	Summer wheat (straw fields)		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	4		
Method	2		
N Demand	95		
P Demand	15.05		
OPNPKO	TYPE	HU	VALUE
1	T	0.069	3.00
2	Phos	0.069	1.00
3	Nitr	0.069	0.40
4	Manure	0.069	0.35
5	P	0.076	1 430.87
6	Nitr	0.138	0.50
7	Nitr	0.625	0.10
8	H	1.100	
9	Manure	0.064	0.65

Table 28: Management practise and parameters for STWW

SWAT code	STWW		
SWAT name	Winter wheat (straw fields)		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	4		
Method	2		
N Demand	110		
P Demand	25.8		
OPNPKO	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Nitr	0.077	0.50
2	Nitr	0.291	0.25
3	Nitr	0.399	0.25
4	H	1.100	
5	T	0.148	3.00
6	Phos	0.148	1.00
7	Manure	0.148	1.00
8	P	0.154	1 441.74

Table 29: Management practise and parameters for SWHT

SWAT code	SWHT		
SWAT name	Spring Wheat		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	0		
Method	1		
N Demand	95		
P Demand	15.05		
OPNPKO	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	T	0.069	4.00
2	Phos	0.069	1.00
3	Nitr	0.069	0.40
4	Manure	0.069	0.35
5	P	0.076	1 935.47
6	Nitr	0.154	0.50
7	Nitr	0.625	0.10
8	H	1.100	
9	T	0.005	1.00
10	T	0.062	2.00
11	Manure	0.062	0.65

Table 30: Management practise and parameters for VTCH

SWAT code	VTCH			
SWAT name	Vetch			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	2			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	40			
P Demand	22			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	T	0.053	4.00	
2	Phos	0.053	1.00	
3	Nitr	0.053	0.40	
4	Manure	0.053	0.35	
5	P	0.057	1 240.75	
6	Nitr	0.168	0.60	
7	H	1.200		
8	T	0.005	1.00	
9	T	0.075	2.00	
10	Manure	0.075	0.65	

Table 31: Management practise and parameters for WBAR

SWAT code	WBAR			
SWAT name	Winter Barley			
LU class	Agricultural			
IDC	5			
Base T	4			
Method	2			
N Demand	155			
P Demand	18			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Nitr	0.200	0.50	
2	Nitr	0.467	0.25	
3	Nitr	0.601	0.25	
4	H	1.100		
5	T	0.006	1.00	
6	T	0.099	2.00	
7	T	0.255	4.00	
8	Phos	0.255	1.00	
9	Manure	0.255	1.00	
10	P	0.265	1 163.80	

Table 32: Management practise and parameters for WTRC

SWAT code	WTRC		
SWAT name	Winter triticales		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	4		
Method	1		
N Demand	100		
P Demand	21.5		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Nitr	0.122	0.50
2	Nitr	0.362	0.25
3	Nitr	0.482	0.25
4	H	1.100	
5	T	0.006	1.00
6	T	0.092	2.00
7	T	0.213	4.00
8	Phos	0.213	1.00
9	Manure	0.213	1.00
10	P	0.218	1 288.75

Table 33: Management practise and parameters for WWHT

SWAT code	WWHT		
SWAT name	Winter Wheat		
LU class	Agricultural		
IDC	5		
Base T	6		
Method	1		
N Demand	110		
P Demand	25.8		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE
1	Nitr	0.049	0.50
2	Nitr	0.239	0.25
3	Nitr	0.351	0.25
4	H	1.100	
5	T	0.006	1.00
6	T	0.079	2.00
7	T	0.148	4.00
8	Phos	0.148	1.00
9	Manure	0.148	1.00
10	P	0.154	1 115.21

Table 34: Management practise and parameters for BROS

SWAT code	BROS			
SWAT name	Smooth Bromegrass			
LU class	Pasture			
IDC	6			
Base T	8			
Method	2			
N Demand	0			
P Demand	0			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Manure	0.007	0.35	
2	Mowing	0.326		
3	Manure	0.899	0.65	

Table 35: Management practise and parameters for CLVR

SWAT code	CLVR			
SWAT name	Red Clover			
LU class	Pasture			
IDC	2			
Base T	1			
Method	2			
N Demand	0			
P Demand	0			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Manure	0.056	0.35	
2	Mowing	0.381		
3	Manure	0.812	0.65	

Table 36: Management practise and parameters for WPAS

SWAT code	WPAS			
SWAT name	Winter Pasture			
LU class	Pasture			
IDC	6			
Base T	0			
Method	1			
N Demand	120			
P Demand	15.05			
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Manure	0.069	0.35	
2	Cfert	0.120	0.45	
3	Mowing	0.389		

4	Manure	0.803	0.65
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Table 37: Management practise and parameters for PGWF

SWAT code		PGWF		
SWAT name		-		
LU class		Pasture		
IDC		-		
Base T		-		
Method		-		
N Demand		-		
P Demand		-		
OPNPK	OPTYPE	HU	VALUE	VALUE_S
1	Manure	0.069	0.35	
2	Mowing	0.389		
3	Manure	0.803	0.65	